

EUnet4DBP

European Network for Digital Building Permit

EUnet4DBP Publication Series

Digital Building Permit Conference 2024

18-19 April 2024

Barcelona COAC

PROCEEDINGS

Editors: Francesca Noardo & Judith Fauth

Open
Geospatial
Consortium

BDTA
BUILDING DIGITAL TWIN ASSOCIATION

EUBIM
TASK GROUP

isprs
Information from Imagery

EuroSDR

buildingSMART
International

Creating our futures
ECTP-CEU
European Council of Spatial Planners
Conseil européen des urbanistes

CEBC

**CONSORTIUM
OF EUROPEAN
BUILDING CONTROL**

EUnet4DBP Publication Series n.0

Doi: [10.5281/zenodo.12760551](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12760551)

<https://eu4dbp.net>

The present publication is shared with a CC BY license.

The present publication was peer-reviewed by EUnet4DBP members.

July 2024

Table of Contents

Abstract	5
Introduction: Building Permit Digitalisation and the DBP conference 2024	6
Digital Building Permit Conference 2024 Organizing Committee.....	16
Digital Building Permit Conference 2024 Scientific Committee	17
LEGISLATIVE SYSTEM Research Track	18
Building Permit Digitisation in Saudi Arabia	19
Requirements analysis and acceleration of approval procedures for federal highways in Germany	25
When DBP meets DBL – Conceptual alignment on process level.....	29
A theoretical approach for adopting smart contracts in granting building permits for individual houses in Vietnam	32
Aligning BIM, DBP, and Sustainability: Insights from a Venn Diagram Analysis	43
ORGANISATIONAL SYSTEM Research Track	48
Adaptability of digital permits for building-as-a-service asset	49
"STARTING WITH WHY": Shaping the future generation of planners by empowerment of necessary competences at universities to enable integral digital construction.....	53
A Call to Enhance the Digitalization of Building Permit Processing with Recognition-Primed Decision Making.....	56
Towards automated building lifecycle assessment calculation	61
A Maturity Model for Digital Building Permit: a path towards the digital transition	67
PROCEDURAL SYSTEM Research Track	72
BIM-based building permit process: Finland’s implementation path	73
Stakeholder attitudes and process readiness towards digital building permit processes in five European countries	80
Investigation and comparison of building permit processes in different sized municipalities at national level: the Italian case	86
Process Analysis and Comparative Evaluation of Building Permitting – PACE-BP	92
Analyzing Building Permit Processes Across Europe	95
Automated Regulatory Compliance: Insights from a Design Research	98
Building Permit Process Digitalization: A Municipal Implementation Process Map	102
A conceptual framework for managing the building permitting process in Brazilian municipalities	107
TECHNOLOGICAL SYSTEM Research Track	111
Geometry level of information needs for digital building permit regulations.....	112
Code compliance checking approach for elements implicitly contained in building models.....	122
ILS Space: applying and extracting a higher order spatial taxonomy from IFC building models.....	127
Design and development of a digital compliance workbench	132
IFC-Based Platform Prototype for Rule Editing and Code Compliance Check	135

Breaking the boundaries of Automated Code Checking through Semantic Enrichment and Graph Neural Networks	139
Formalization of building codes and regulations in knowledge graphs	143
Achieving Extensibility within a Standards-based Platform for the Digital Building Permit in Montevideo	148
Optimisation of the fire safety certificate process in the digital and model-based building permit procedure	154
Automatic verification of requirements in BIM models for building permit	157
Mapping the processes and developing the rule sets for automated compliance checking of health and safety regulations in UK’s infrastructure projects	163
DMN as a visual interface for building constraint creation	170
Building Standards Compliance for SMEs: A Case study of Scotland	176
Transformer-based Semantic Parsing of Building Regulations: Towards Supporting Regulators in Drafting Machine-Readable Rules	178
The IDS as a means of exchanging information requirements in public administrations: the use case of the digital building permit	183
Concept for Leveraging Road Digital Twins for Enhanced Planning and Building Permit Processes.....	189
Definition of BIM and 3DCitymodel information requirements for digital building permits	193
Advancing Automated Compliance Checking Through Visual Programming in the Context of Australian Building Codes.....	197
3D Cartographic Generalization of Indoor Spaces for Building Information Modelling	200
LEGISLATIVE SYSTEM Practice Papers.....	202
Checking 50yrs: Overview of Requirements on DBP from viewpoint of a public road authority.....	203
ORGANISATIONAL SYSTEM Practice Papers	204
Digitalizing the built environment – leading people through change with the power of experimental culture. Is a cultural revolution necessary for the digitalization of the built environment?.....	205
Digital Built Environment – Support public authorities in digitalising their building permit systems.....	207
PROCEDURAL SYSTEM Practice Papers	210
Designers as Catalysts for Change Towards Digital Building Permitting (DBP).....	211
BIM models and 3D City Model as part of the building permit in Finland	213
Methodology to analyse privacy in digital building permits: BPMN process taxonomy and simulations.....	215
TECHNOLOGICAL SYSTEM Practice Papers	229
An approach to GeoBIM using 3D City Database and BIMServer	230
ACABIM: Open Compliance Audit for New Zealand Regulations	232
Enhancing Smart Cities through Semantic Planning Law Data – The ACCORD-project and the Berlin TXL Use-Case	233

Checking of Urban Planning Regulations with GeoSPARQL and BIM SPARQL	235
Building Permit Management Data Space	236
CYPEURBAN and BIMserver.center: Lessons learned in the digitalization of the Building Permit	239
CHEK technology architecture: achieving interoperability for a modular approach	241
Enabling BIM in Building Permitting: The Critical Role of the Permitting Platform	243
AI-supported, automatic document checking for digital submission and processing of building applications in Germany	244
AI in compliance for the built environment	248
Use of Augmented Reality in the openBIM building authority process	249
COUNTRY-SPECIFIC EXPERIENCES	251
Germany’s Digital Building Application as a Trailblazing Guarantee for Accelerated Planning and Implementation of Nationwide Construction Projects	252
„One-for-All“ – experiences and perspectives of the digital building permit in Germany	254
Implementing a digital building permit system in Slovenia – current status and aspirations for the future	256
Developing automated building permitting in Finland	258
Building Permitting process in BRAZIL	260
LandLogic: Determining Applicable Law Agencies for Digital Building Permitting in Ontario, Canada	263
Information Model based Urban Planning prototype in Estonia	265
Transformative Journey: Dubai Municipality's BIM Adoption for Building Permitting and Regulatory Compliance	268
From paper to NOPaper: A 10-year journey of digital transformation for building permits in Vila Nova de Gaia	272
Concluding remarks: Main uptakes and lessons learnt	282

Abstract

The digitalisation of building permits gained a lot of momentum in the last years. 2024 sees several mature research items, initiatives and big projects on the topic, including available software and promoting governmental initiatives and policies. After three years from the first EUNet4DBP International workshop on Digital Building Permit, in 2021, finding itself at the moment in which several projects were at their early stages, including the European network for Digital Building Permit (EUNet4DBP), the Digital Building Permit conference 2024 was organised in Barcelona, to gather relevant efforts and contributions in an overview of the current status of progress towards building permit digitalisation, as well as an opportunity for active and interested stakeholders, researchers and developers to meet and exchange, envisaging cross-fertilisation for next projects and developments.

In this report, the conference is introduced, and all the abstracts submitted for presentations are published. Complementing this, online resources are available, such as the presentations slides, linked to the titles of the abstracts, and the recording of the conference, available in the EUNet4DBP YouTube channel and linked in this document.

Introduction: Building Permit Digitalisation and the DBP conference 2024

Francesca Noardo^a & Judith Fauth^b

^aOpen Geospatial Consortium / Belgium

^bCambridge University / UK

Digitalisation of building permits was detected as the critical knot to be solved, in order to pave the way towards massive digitalisation in the construction industry, and to enable the potential of automation and optimisation in the management of building and city data.

As mentioned by Michael Flickenschield (ECORYS, HLCF) “Next to BIM requirements in public procurement, digital building permits are key in enabling the digital transition of construction by starting digitalisation at the project's inception”.

The topic has been developing for a couple of years and now, in 2024, some mature solutions start to be available. Moreover, some important cross-border (e.g. European) projects as well as other local initiatives are currently running, as the European Union has acknowledged the relevance of the topic and its high potential as an input to related use cases, such as estate management and digital building logbook.

Therefore, the EUnet4DBP, together with several relevant organisations, organised the “Digital Building Permit Conference 2024”¹ to dive into the current status of research, developments and implementations, and to provide the opportunity for several digital building permit actors to meet and discuss.

Multidisciplinarity and inter-sectoral collaboration are key to solving the multifaceted and complex challenge of building permit digitalisation. Therefore, the conference was structured to host several different kinds of contributions and activities, from research to implementations, with a relevant part reserved for users and stakeholders, in order to investigate the challenges of the solutions' uptake.

The DBP conference 2024 was developed with close aims to the *New European Bauhaus*², whose festival of which it became a satellite event. The New European Bauhaus initiative is developing towards the goal of beauty, for places, practices and experiences to be:

- “
- **Enriching**, inspired by art and culture, responding to needs beyond functionality.
 - **Inclusive**, encouraging a dialogue across cultures, disciplines, genders and ages.
 - **Sustainable**, in harmony with nature, the environment, and our planet.
- ”

Enriching: the objectives of the conference

- Share progress all over Europe and the World

¹ <https://eu4dbp.net/dbpc24/>

² https://new-european-bauhaus.europa.eu/index_en

- Engage policy developers and regulators
- Show benefits and the value of building permit digitalisation through concrete examples
- Share solutions and components from several developers
- Encourage municipalities to bring their points of view and expertise
- Tackling the remaining outstanding problems and challenges
- Legal aspects discussion
- Share developments and experiences about data and technology for digital building permits

Inclusive: the participants to the conference

The conference was attended by approximately 150 participants, rather diverse from the point of view of their working sector and field of expertise (BIM, construction, geoinformation, law and regulations, computer science, urban planning and so on) and provenance Country, reaching way beyond Europe (Figures 1-3).

Fig. 1: Working sector of participants to the DBP conference 2024.

Fig. 2: Provenance map of participants to the DBP conference 2024.

One of the objectives of the conference was to engage with policy makers and building authorities, and it was achieved, with one fourth of attendants representing public or building permit authorities. In particular, representatives of 10 municipalities or local authorities participated, i.e.: Vila Nova de Gaia (Portugal), Madrid (Spain), Helsinki (Finland), Hamburg (Germany), Tallinn (Estonia), Area Metropolitana de Barcelona (Spain), Dubai (Arab Emirates), Bruxelles (Belgium), Rotterdam (The Netherlands), État of Geneva (Switzerland). In addition, national authorities of 10 countries attended the conference as well, i.e.: Slovenia, Switzerland, Germany, Croatia, Estonia, Cyprus, Slovak Republic, The Netherlands, Denmark, and Ukraine. Moreover, several researchers or companies working closely with building authorities to implement digital building permit day by day participated and contributed to the conference.

Nine countries' experiences (achievements, progress, lessons learnt) were presented in a dedicated session (Germany, Slovenia, Finland, Brazil, Ontario, Estonia, Dubai, Vila Nova de Gaia).

Fig. 3: Provenance of participants to the DBP conference 2024 per country.

Diversity in the conference, with the goal of allowing different audiences and expertise to meet and exchange, was also encouraged by the wide range of organisations supporting it. The *European Network for Digital Building Permit (EUnet4DBP)*³ was the main organiser and was already born and developed with the same approach, so, in turn gathering several researchers, professionals and public authorities around the topic of Digital Building Permit. *Open Geospatial Consortium (OGC)*⁴ is the standardisation organisation for geospatial information, and it's reaching out to the geomatics-related domain. Similarly, the *International Society for Photogrammetry and Remote Sensing (ISPRS)* covers geospatial data acquisition, processing and use science. It was mostly involved via its *Working Group IV/1, on Spatial Data Representation*

3 <https://eu4dbp.net>

4 <https://www.ogc.org>

and Interoperability⁵. The *European Association for Spatial Data Research (EuroSDR)* is mostly the association of European National Mapping and Cadastral Agencies, as well as related researchers, and was involved in the topic of digital building permit because it closely affects and in turn, can have ground-breaking consequences on the cadastral information management. EuroSDR⁶ promoted some specific projects on Digital building permit in the past⁷ and is active in the EUnet4dBP as well. *Building Digital Twin Association (BDTA)*⁸ was interested in how digital twins could be used for building permits and how privacy and ethics are included in the processes and workflows. As Digichcks partner they tried to contribute in those fields. Organisations related to BIMs and construction, i.e, *buildingSMART*⁹,

*EU-BIM Task group*¹⁰, the *European council of Spatial Planners (ECTP-CEU)*¹¹, *Consortium of European Building Control (CEBC)*¹² were also obviously interested and supporting the conference.

The topic is of interest at different levels in several countries, and treated with different approaches (e.g., top-down or bottom-up initiatives, starting from research or from implementation first and so on), as we learnt in the past four years of activity with the EUnet4DBP, and as shown in the several presentations at the conference. However, in 2022 three European HORIZON projects were funded to research on the topic and provide solutions at a European-wide level. The three projects, CHEK¹³, ACCORD¹⁴ and DigiChecks¹⁵ were actively involved in the conference organisation and their current results were presented.

Sustainable: our small steps towards climate and environment care

Since environmental sustainability is an urgent goal to be achieved by society, and this kind of events may have an impact on the production of CO₂ and other environmental-related negative factors, we took some measures intended to reduce emissions and negative environmental impact in general. Paper printing was limited at the very minimum, by managing all the advertisement materials and information provision online. No fliers nor gadgets were distributed at the event. The lanyards were rented by the conference venue as well, so that they could be recollected after the conference and reused. The dinner was almost entirely vegan, to reduce negative impact of meat consumption, besides adapting to the dietary needs of the participants more inclusively. Moreover, even if the event was planned entirely in presence, we allowed participants in countries outside Europe who made requests to present from a remote connection, so that they could avoid travelling.

Finally, to compensate, at least partly (i.e., 180.0 t CO₂), for the unavoidable emissions, we funded some projects through the programme and projects provided by Generalitat de Catalunya

5 <https://www2.isprs.org/commissions/comm4/wg1/>

6 <http://www.eurosd.net>

7 <https://3d.bk.tudelft.nl/projects/eurosd-geobim/>

8 <https://buildingdigitaltwin.org>

9 <https://www.buildingsmart.org/>

10 <https://eubim.eu/>

11 <https://ectp-ceu.eu/>

12 <https://cebc.eu/>

13 <https://chekdbp.eu>

14 <https://accordproject.eu>

15 <https://digichecks.eu>

– Secretaria d’Acció climàtica and Oficina Catalana del Canvi Climàtic¹⁶ through which some credits were bought to fund projects by the SendeCO2 programme¹⁷. The emissions were calculated with the online *myclimate*¹⁸ tool, supporting the calculation of emissions for events, among other categories, and adopting a methodology which can be customised according to the available data and use empirical values for uncertain values¹⁹. In future experiences, we will probably plan this calculation better, by requesting more accurate data to participants in the registration phase.

The DBP taxonomy and organisation of the programme

As a joint activity of a EUnet4DBP working group organised on purpose, a taxonomy on digital building permit systems was developed and published²⁰. It categorizes the digital building permit system into four subsystems: legislative, organizational, technological, and procedural, although recognizing that these subsystems often overlap. Despite this overlap, we assigned contributions to the four categories to organize the conference program. As a result, we had sessions for legislative, organizational, and procedural contributions, and multiple sessions for technological contributions, which appears to be the most investigated side of digital building permits. Figure 4 illustrates the primary focus areas of the contributions within these subsystems.

Fig.4: Taxonomy subsystems and contributions in percentage

Moreover, two types of abstracts were foreseen, to allow different kinds of organisations, having different sharing interests, to easily be part of the event. In fact, although only abstract submission was required, also in line with recent directives from some universities, willing to reduce the number of conference papers in favour of more valuable journal publications, we planned a *scientific track*, intended to share research and link relevant papers and resources; and a *practice track*, to allow practitioners and diverse stakeholders to present their initiatives, software companies to possibly show their solutions and less mature studies to be introduced even if at early stages of developments.

The review process worked differently for the two tracks. Scientific extended abstract underwent a peer-review process by at least two reviewers, who were members of the scientific committee (listed at the beginning of this publication). Reviewers evaluated the contributions by scoring and commenting, and authors had the opportunity to revise their abstracts in one iteration. The practice

¹⁶ <https://canviclimatic.gencat.cat/en/ambits/mitigacio/programa-voluntari-de-compensacio-de-gasos-amb-efecte-dhivernacle/index.html>

¹⁷ <https://www.sendeco2.com/es/>

¹⁸ <https://www.myclimate.org/en/>

¹⁹ <https://www.myclimate.org/en/information/about-myclimate/downloads/event-calculator/>

²⁰ <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2023.102312>

track abstracts were reviewed more shortly, to confirm that the contributions fit the scope of the conference.

We received approximately 70 submissions, which were beyond our expectations and a high number considering the planned two days of the conference. Since we wanted to allow everyone to present their contributions, unless really out of scope for the conference, this event became also an opportunity to experiment with a [tighter schedule for the presentations](#). We reserved 12 or 10 minutes, including questions and answers session, for the main contributions being presented as research or practice respectively. In addition, short pitches sessions were planned for the other presentations, selected according to reviewers advises or held by presenters who volunteered having a 3-minute slot. These had 3 minutes for their presentations, followed by 10 minutes of common questions and answers session. Such a dynamic schedule was rather appreciated by the audience, who attended rather continuously throughout the whole event. In addition, it gave the opportunity to provide a compact but comprehensive overview of current research, implementations, initiatives and solutions over the two days.

A special issue on "[Advances in digital building permits](#)" was planned contextually to the conference to give the opportunity to publish full papers about the presented studies, in the Journal of Building Research & Information. The guest editors of the special issue, who are part of the scientific committee, selected some contributions based on the extended abstract and the presentation, besides considering the recommendations from the reviewers.

[Programme of the conference](#)

The programme of the conference is here reported.

The presentations slides for keynotes and sponsor talks are linked to the titles in the text that follows, while for the abstracts presented, the slides are linked to the titles of the abstracts of each contribution in this book, whether available.

Keynotes of the DBP Conference 2024

Towards a more resilient, green and digital construction ecosystem - **Michael Flickenschild**, Senior Consultant, Ecorys, High Level Construction Forum

Digital building permits and procedures from a legal perspective - where does Switzerland stand? - **David Schwaninger**, Blum&Grob Attorneys at Law, Switzerland

Enriching building permit process from social science perspective - **Hannele Kerosuo**, Faculty of Education, University of Helsinki

ECTP and Built4People Partnership: perspectives on future digitalisation of Construction value chains – **Alain Zarli**, ECTP secretary General, B4P Management team

Development and process of the BIM building permit in the State of Geneva - **Ophélie Vincendon**, Etat de Genève, Switzerland

AI Thinks Your Building is Compliant! - **Robert Amor**, University of Auckland, New Zealand

Sponsor talks

CYPE - Beyond BIM and Digitalization in Construction Industry – **Pablo Gilabert**

BDTA - Stay ahead shaping the future of the Building Digital Twin Industry - **Eduard Loscos**

Future Insight - Why wait? Let's start with BIM-based permitting now! – **Jaan Saar**

Recording of the event

Videos of the recordings are published in the EUnet4DBP YouTube channel.

[Digital Building Permit conference 2024 – Day 1 18/04/2024 h.9:00-11:00](#)

[Digital Building Permit conference 2024 – Day 1 18/04/2024 h.11:30-12:50](#)

[Digital Building Permit conference 2024 – Day 1 18/04/2024 h.14:00-16:00](#)

[Digital Building Permit conference 2024 – Day 1 18/04/2024 h.16:30-18:20](#)

[Digital Building Permit conference 2024 – Day 2 19/04/2024 h.9:00-11:00](#)

[Digital Building Permit conference 2024 – Day 2 19/04/2024 h.11:30-13:05](#)

[Digital Building Permit conference 2024 – Day 2 19/04/2024 h.14:00-15:30](#)

[Digital Building Permit conference 2024 – Day 2 19/04/2024 h.16:00-17:00](#)

DAY 1 - 18th April 2024

8.30 - 9.00 Welcome and Registration

9.00 - 9.20 Opening by **Francesca Noardo** (Open Geospatial Consortium, Belgium) and **Judith Fauth** (University of Cambridge, United Kingdom)

Legislative System

9.20 - 9.40 Keynote | *Towards a more resilient, green and digital construction ecosystem*

Michael Flickenschild (Ecorys and EC High Level Construction Forum)

Chair | **Adrian Wildenauer** (University of Applied Sciences Bern, Switzerland)

9.40 - 10.00 Keynote | *Digital building permits and procedures from a legal perspective - where does Switzerland stand?*

David Schwaninger (Blum&Grob Attorneys at Law, Switzerland)

10.00 - 10.12 Research Paper (12') | *Building Permit Digitisation in Saudi Arabia*

Eyad Jalal (University College London, United Kingdom)

10.12 - 10.24 Research Paper (12') | *Requirements analysis and acceleration of approval procedures for federal highways in Germany*

Niklas Pauls (Schübler-Plan Digital GmbH, Germany)

10.24 - 10.36 Research Paper (12') | *When DBP meets DBL – Conceptual alignment on process level*

Pedro Méda (University of Porto, Portugal)

10.36 - 10.46 Research Paper (12') | *A Theoretical Approach For Adopting Smart Contracts In Granting Building Permits For Individual Houses In Vietnam*

Quan Nguyen (Hanoi University of Civil Engineering, Vietnam)

10.46 - 10.50 Presentation (10') | *Checking 50yrs: Overview of Requirements on DBP from viewpoint of a public road authority*

Odilo Schoch (FEDRO, Switzerland)

Technological System - 1

10.50 - 11.00 Sponsor talk (10') | *Beyond BIM and Digitalization in Construction Industry*

CYPE | Pablo Gilabert

11.00 - 11.30 Coffe Break

Chair | **Christian Schranz** (Technische Universität Wien, Austria)

11.30 - 11.42 Research Paper (12') | *Geometry level of information needs for digital building permit regulations*

Siham El Yamani (Delft University of Technology, Netherlands)

11.42 - 11.54 Research Paper (12') | *Code compliance checking approach for elements implicitly contained in building models*

Simon Fischer (Research Unit Digital Building Process, Technische Universität Wien, Austria)

11.54 - 12.06 Research Paper (12') | *Its Space*

Rolf Jonker (Gemeente Rotterdam, Netherlands)

12.06 - 12.18 Research Paper & Sponsor Talk (12') | *Design and development of a digital compliance workbench DBP format*

Nicholas Nisbet (AEC3 Ltd & University College London)

12.18 - 12.30 Research Paper (12') | *IFC-Based Platform Prototype for Rule Editing and Code Compliance Check*

Bruno Muniz (University of Minho, Portugal)

12.30 - 12.40 Presentation (10') | *An approach to GeoBIM using 3D City Database and BIMServer*

Bruno Rienzi (Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad de la Republica, Uruguay)

12.40 - 12.50 Presentation (10') | *ACABIM: Open Compliance Audit for New Zealand Regulations*

Robert Amor (University of Auckland, New Zealand)

13.00 - 14.00 Lunch

Organisational System

Chair | **Silvia Mastrolebo Ventura** (University of Brescia, Italy)

14.00 - 14.30 Keynote | *Enriching building permit process from social science perspective*

Hannele Kerosuo (University of Helsinki, Finland)

14.30 - 14.42 Research Paper (12') | *Adaptability Of Digital Permits For Building-As-A-Service Asset*

Adrian Wildenauer (University of Applied Sciences Bern, Switzerland)

14.42 - 14.54 Research Paper (12') | *Starting With Why: Shaping The Future Generation Of Planners By Empowerment Of Necessary Competences At Universities To Enable Integral Digital Construction*

Matias Penroz (University of Applied Sciences Bern, Switzerland)

- 14.54 - 15.06 Research Paper (12') | *Enhance the digitalization of Building Permit Processing with Recognition-Primed Decision Making*
Peter Nørkjær Gade (University College of Northern Denmark)
- 15.06 - 15.18 Research Paper (12') | *Towards automated building lifecycle assessment calculation*
Petr Hradil (Sova3D Oy Ltd., Finland)
- 15.18 - 15.30 Research Paper (12') | *A Maturity Model for Digital Building Permit: a path towards the digital transition*
Mariana Ataíde (Fraunhofer Italia Research)
- 15.30 - 15.40 Presentation (10') | *Digitalizing the built environment – leading people through change with the power of experimental culture. Is a cultural revolution necessary for the digitalization of the built environment?*
Tiina Talvitie (City of Helsinki, Finland)
- 15.40 - 15.50 Presentation (10') | *Digital Built Environment - Support public authorities in digitalising their building permit systems*
Miguel Pereira and Giulio Milanesi (PwC Luxembourg)
- 15.50 - 16.00 Presentation (10') | *e-Delivery report by CEBC*
Sasa Galonja (Consortium of European Building Control)
- 16.00 - 16.10 Sponsor talk (10') | Why wait? Let's start with BIM-based permitting now!
Future Insight | Jaan Saar
- 16.10 - 16.30 Coffe Break

Country-specific experiences

Chair | **Jaan Saar** (Future Insight, Netherlands)

- 16.30 - 16.40 Country specific (10') | *Germany's Digital Building Application as a Trailblazing Guarantee for Accelerated Planning and Implementation of Nationwide Construction Projects*
Christoph Vollmer and Eckhard Riege (Ministry of the Interior, Building and Digitalisation, Germany)
- 16.40 - 16.50 Country specific (10') | *"One-for-All" – experiences and perspectives of the digital building permit in Germany*
Ronny Weinkauff and Andreas Fiedler (Merseburg University of Applied Sciences, Germany)
- 16.50 - 17.00 Country specific (10') | *Implementing a digital building permit system in Slovenia – current status and aspirations for the future*
Jernej Tekavec (University of Ljubljana, Slovenia)
- 17.00 - 17.10 Country specific (10') | *Developing automated building permitting in Finland*
Antero Hirvensalo (Tampere University, Finland)
- 17.10 - 17.20 Country specific (10') | *Automatic Legislation/GIS/IFC Integration in Brazil*
Paulo Sergio Teixeira (Torch Engenharia, Brazil)
- 17.20 - 17.30 Country specific (10') | *LandLogic: Determining Applicable Law Agencies for Digital Building Permitting in Ontario, Canada*
Saeid Emamgholian (AECO Innovation Lab, Canada)
- 17.30 - 17.40 Country specific (10') | *Information Model based Urban Planning prototype in Estonia*
Christopher-Robin Raitviir (City of Tallinn, Estonia)
- 17.40 - 17.50 Country specific (10') | *Transformative Journey: Dubai Municipality's BIM Adoption for Building Permitting and Regulatory Compliance*
Nasser ALshaihani (Dubai Municipality)
- 17.50 - 18.00 Country specific (10') | *From paper to NOPaper: A 10-year journey of digital transformation for building permits in Vila Nova de Gaia*
Carla Pires (Gaiurb EM, Portugal)
- 18.00 - 18.20 Keynote | *ECTP and Built4People Partnership: perspectives on future digitalisation of Construction value chains*
Alain Zarti (European Construction Technology Platform, ECTP)

20.00 Dinner | HOTEL 1898, La Rambla 109 - 08002 Barcelona

DAY 2 - 19th April 2024

Procedural System

- 9.00 - 9.20 Keynote | *Development and process of the BIM building permit in the State of Geneva*
Ophélie Vincendon (Etat de Genève, Switzerland)
- Chair | **Judith Fauth** (University of Cambridge, United Kingdom)
- 9.20 - 9.32 Research Paper (12') | *BIM-based building permit process: Finland's implementation path*
Anna-Riitta Kallinen (ARK Consulting, Finland)
- 9.32 - 9.44 Research Paper (12') | *Stakeholder attitudes and process readiness towards digital building permit processes in five European countries*
Rita Lavikka (VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland)
- 9.44 - 9.56 Research Paper (12') | *Investigation And Comparison Of Building Permit Processes In Different Sized Municipalities At National Level: The Italian Case*
Kavita Raj (University of Brescia, Italy)
- 9.56 - 10.08 Research Paper (12') | *Process Analysis and Comparative Evaluation of Building Permitting – PACE-BP*
Tanya Bloch (Technion Israel Institute of Technology)
- 10.08 - 10.20 Research Paper (12') | *Analyzing Building Permit Processes Across Europe*
Peter Nørkjær Gade (University College of Northern Denmark)
- 10.20 - 10.32 Research Paper (12') | *Automated Regulatory Compliance: Insights from a Design Research*
Joao Soliman-Junior (University of Huddersfield, United Kingdom)
- 10.32 - 10.42 Presentation (10') | *Designers as Catalysts for Change Towards Digital Building Permitting (DBP)*
Borja Martinez (SIA.Architects, Luxembourg)
- 10.42 - 10.45 Short Pitch (3') | *Building Permit Process Digitalization : A Municipal Implementation Process Map*
Orjola Braholli (Fraunhofer Italia Research)
- 10.45 - 10.48 Short Pitch (3') | *Building Standards Compliance for SMEs: A Case study of Scotland*
Michael Tong (Glasgow Caledonian University, United Kingdom)
- 10.48 - 10.51 Short Pitch (3') | *A conceptual framework for managing the building permitting process in Brazilian municipalities*
Douglas Malheiro de Brito (Federal University of Bahia, Brazil)
- 10.51 - 11.00 Q&A (10')
- 11.00 - 11.30 Coffe Break

- Chair | **Harald Urban** (Technische Universität Wien, Austria)
- 11.30 - 11.33 Short Pitch (3') | *Transformer-based Semantic Parsing of Building Regulations: Towards Supporting Regulators in Drafting Machine-Readable Rules*
Robert Amor (University of Auckland, New Zealand)
- 11.33 - 11.36 Short Pitch (3') | *The IDS As A Means Of Exchanging Information Requirements In Public Administrations: The Use Case Of The Digital Building Permit*
Giancarlo de Marco (Fraunhofer Italia Research)
- 11.36 - 11.39 Short Pitch (3') | *A Concept for Leveraging Road Digital Twins for Enhanced Planning and Building Permit Processes*
Judith Fauth (University of Cambridge, United Kingdom)
- 11.39 - 11.42 Short Pitch (3') | *Aligning BIM, DBP, and Sustainability: Insights from a Venn Diagram Analysis*
Stefanie Brigitte Deac Kaiser (The Polytechnic University of Timisoara, Romania)
- 11.42 - 11.45 Short Pitch (3') | *Methodology to analyse privacy and IPR problems in digital building permits: BPMN processes taxonomy and simulations*
Pablo Vicente Legazpi (Building Digital Twin Association, Belgium)
- 11.45 - 11.48 Short Pitch (3') | *Definition Of BIM And 3DCitymodel Information Requirements For Digital Building Permits*
Sara Comai (University of Brescia, Italy)
- 11.48 - 11.50 Short Pitch (3') | *BIM models and 3D City Model as part of the building permit in Finland*
Petri Kokko (Sova3D Oy, Finland)
- 11.50 - 12.00 Q&A (10')

Technological System - 2

- Chair | **Rita Lavikka** (VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland)
- 12.00 - 12.10 Sponsor talk (10') | *Stay ahead shaping the future of the Building Digital Twin Industry*
BDTA - Eduard Loscos
- 12.10 - 12.22 Research Paper (12') | *Breaking the boundaries of Automated Code Checking through Semantic Enrichment and Graph Neural Networks*
Tanya Bloch (Technion Israel Institute of Technology)
- 12.22 - 12.34 Research Paper (12') | *Formalization of building codes and regulations in knowledge graphs*
Gonçal Costa (Ramon Llull University, Spain)
- 12.34 - 12.44 Research Paper (12') | *Achieving Extensibility within a Standards-based Platform for the Digital Building Permit in Montevideo*
Laura González (Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad de la Republica, Uruguay)
- 12.44 - 12.54 Presentation (10') | *Enhancing Smart Cities through Semantic Planning Law Data – The ACCORD-project and the Use-Case Berlin TXL*
Stefan Höffken (Tegel Projekt GmbH, Germany)
- 12.54 - 13.04 Presentation (10') | *Checking of Urban Planning Regulations with GeoSPARQL and BIM SPARQL*
Vladimir Alexiev (Ontotext AD, Bulgaria)
- 13.05 - 14.00 Lunch

Technological System - 3

- Chair | **Gonçal Costa** (Ramon Llull University, Spain)
- 14.00 - 14.30 Keynote | *AI thinks your building is compliant!*
Robert Amor (University of Auckland, New Zealand)
- 14.30 - 14.40 Presentation (10') | *Building Permits Management Data Space*
Francisco Javier Diez (Tekniker, Research and Technology Centre, Spain)
- 14.40 - 14.50 Presentation (10') | *CHEK technology architecture: achieving interoperability for a modular approach*
Ane Ferreira (CYPE, Spain)
- 14.50 - 15.00 Presentation & Sponsor Talk (10') | *Enabling BIM in Building Permitting: The Critical Role of the Permitting Platform*
Ilkka Mattila (Cloudpermit, Finland)
- 15.00 - 15.03 Short Pitch (3') | *AI-supported, automatic document checking for digital submission and processing of building applications in Germany*
Lisa Lenz (Building Information Cloud GLWG GmbH, Germany)
- 15.03 - 15.06 Short Pitch (3') | *AI Assisted compliance in the built environment*
Max van Riel (Struck, Netherlands)
- 15.06 - 15.09 Short Pitch (3') | *Advancing Automated Compliance Checking Through Visual Programming in the Context of Australian Building Codes*
Nikoo Mirhosseini (University of Melbourne, Australia)
- 15.09 - 15.12 Short Pitch (3') | *3D Cartographic Generalization of Indoor Spaces using Corpora of Geospatial Natural Language with Parsimony of Description*
Daniel Dos Santos (Military Institute of Engineering, Brazil)
- 15.12 - 15.22 Q&A (10')
- 15.30 - 16.00 Coffe Break

Technological System - 4

- Chair | **Eduard Loscos** (Building Digital Twin Association, Belgium)
- 16.00 - 16.12 Research Paper (12') | *Optimisation of the fire safety certificate process in the digital and model-based building permit procedure*
Janna Walter (THM - University of Applied Sciences, Germany)
- 16.12 - 16.24 Research Paper (12') | *Automatic verification of requirements in BIM models for building permit*
Filippo Chiappini (University of Brescia, Italy)
- 16.24 - 16.36 Research Paper (12') | *Mapping the processes and developing the rule sets for automated compliance checking of health and safety regulations*
Zijing Zhang (University College London, Aston University, Arcadis Consulting, United Kingdom)
- 16.36 - 16.48 Research Paper (12') | *DMN as a visual interface for building constraint creation*
Emma Nuyts (Ghent University, Belgium)
- 16.48 - 16.58 Presentation (10') | *Use of augmented reality in the openBIM building authority process*
Harald Urban (Technische Universität Wien, Austria)
- 17.00 Closing remarks

Digital Building Permit Conference 2024 Organizing Committee

Francesca Noardo (Chair)	Open Geospatial Consortium, BELGIUM
Angelo Ciribini	University of Brescia, ITALY
Anna-Riitta Kallinen	ARK Consulting, FINLAND
Christian Schranz	TU Wien, AUSTRIA
Eduard Loscos	Building Digital Twin Association, BELGIUM
Gonçal Costa	Ramon Llull University, SPAIN
Jaan Saar	MKM, ESTONIA
José Granja	ISISE, University of Minho, PORTUGAL
Judith Fauth	University of Cambridge, UK
Nicholas Nisbet	buildingSMART, UK
Pablo Vicente Legazpi	Building Digital Twin Association, BELGIUM
Rita Lavikka	VTT, FINLAND
Silvia Mastrolembro Ventura	University of Brescia, ITALY
Stefanie Kaiser	Politehnica University of Timisoara, ROMANIA
Tomi Henttinen	buildingSMART, FINLAND
<u>Support</u>	
Kavita Raj	University of Brescia, ITALY
Sara Comai	University of Brescia, ITALY

Digital Building Permit Conference 2024

Scientific Committee

Judith Fauth (Chair)	University of Cambridge, UK
Adrian Wildenauer	Bern University of Applied Sciences, SWITZERLAND
Ali Ismail	Dubai municipality, VAE
Angelo Ciribini	University of Brescia, ITALY
Antero Hirvensalo	University of Turku, FINLAND
Christian Schranz	TU Wien, AUSTRIA
Cornelius Preidel	University of Applied Sciences Munich, GERMANY
Dogus Guler	Istanbul Technical University, TURKEY
Edlira Vakaj	Birmingham City University, UK
Eduard Loscos	Building Digital Twin Association, BELGIUM
Eilif Hjelseth	NTNU, NORWAY
Elisabetta Colucci	Politecnico di Torino, ITALY
Filip Biljecki	National University of Singapore, SINGAPORE
Francesca Noardo	Open Geospatial Consortium, BELGIUM
Francisco Javier Díez	Tekniker, SPAIN
Gonçal Costa	Ramon Llull University, SPAIN
Harald Urban	TU Wien, AUSTRIA
Jaan Saar	MKM, ESTONIA
Jantien Stoter	TU Delft, NETHERLANDS
Jernej Tekavec	University of Ljubljana, SLOVENIA
Joao Soliman Junior	University of Huddersfield, UK
Joaquin Diaz	Technische Hochschule Mittelhessen – University of Applied Sciences, GERMANY
José Granja	ISISE, University of Minho, PORTUGAL
Markus König	Ruhr University Bochum, GERMANY
Massimiliano Pepe	University “G. D’Annunzio” of Chieti-Pescara, ITALY
Miguel Azenha	ISISE, University of Minho, PORTUGAL
Nicholas Nisbet	buildingSMART, UK
Orjola Braholli	Fraunhofer Italia, ITALY
Pablo Vicente Legazpi	Building Digital Twin Association, BELGIUM
Pawel Bogulaski	Wroclaw University of Environmental and Life Sciences, POLAND
Pedro Meda Magalhães	Porto University, PORTUGAL
Peter Nørkjær Gade	UCN – University College of Northern Denmark, DENMARK
Piotr Zaborowski	Open Geospatial Consortium, POLAND
Ricardo Mateus	Universidade Lusófona, PORTUGAL
Rita Lavikka	VTT, FINLAND
Robert Amor	University of Auckland, NEW ZEALAND
Ronny Weinkauff	Merseburg University of Applied Sciences, GERMANY
Ruben Verstraeten	Ghent University, BELGIUM
Saeid Emamgholian	AECO Innovation Lab, CANADA
Silvia Mastrolembro	University of Brescia, ITALY
Ventura	
Tanya Bloch	Technion – Israel Institute of Technology, ISRAEL
Tomi Henttinen	buildingSMART, FINLAND
Zijing Zhang	UCL, UK

LEGISLATIVE SYSTEM

Research Track

The abstracts in this section were peer reviewed.

Building Permit Digitisation in Saudi Arabia

Eyad Jalal^a, Claire Ellul^a, Ben Clifford^b

^aDepartment of Civil, Environmental and Geomatic Engineering, University College London / UK

^bBartlett School of Planning, University College London / UK

General Statement

In recent years, efforts to digitise the building permit processes and regulations have increased at different levels. Countries and municipalities have put strategies in place to use and adopt the benefit of technology to manage data and design cities sustainably [1], [2], [3].

A building permit is an official document the responsible authority must grant before the construction phase begins [4]. Designing a new building should consider several aspects: the design quality and the geographical relationship of the new building to its context. For a permit to be issued, the proposed building must comply with the related building regulations. Currently, they are written in the form of (text), read, and interpreted by people [5].

However, studies [2], [6], [7], [8] found that issuing a building permit encounters issues including:

- 1) The processes are time-consuming and costly.
- 2) Regulations are open to interpretation.
- 3) Assessment is subject to human error.
- 4) Lack of transparency in the application assessment.
- 5) Lack of use of technology in the assessment processes.

Problem Statement

Digitally enabled (semi-automated) building permit application processing could help overcome these issues [9], [10], [11] and investigations have been carried out in various countries [7], [12], [13], [14], [15], [16]. However, to date, very little work has been done in the context of Saudi Arabia.

Context – Saudi Arabia

Saudi Arabia is the biggest nation in the Middle East and the fourteenth largest globally. Saudi cities are witnessing dramatic urban growth due to growing populations [17], [18]. [19] Saudi Arabia is one of the most urbanised countries worldwide, with an approximate population of 30 million, with 84% residing in cities in 2021 [19], predicted to rise to [20]39.1 million by 2025 [20]. Consequently, this will result in increases in housing demand [21], restrictions on green infrastructure, carbon emissions, and traffic restrictions and congestion [22].

Research Questions

The Saudi planning system provides an opportunity to extend and further validate approaches to digital building permits, both in terms of the rapid urbanisation of the country and in terms of the challenges that may be presented by the use of the Arabic language (and hence character set/alphabet) to encode regulations. The desert climate also means that the regulations may have a different focus than those traditionally encountered in existing case studies (which are mostly based in Northern Europe).

This paper takes preliminary steps towards exploring these issues, providing initial answers to two questions:

- To what extent does Saudi Arabia adopt similar approaches and face similar challenges to other countries in the context of digital building permits?
- What is the potential to apply existing approaches towards the digitisation of building permit regulations in Saudi Arabia?

Methods

A two-step approach was taken to answer these questions.

Step 1: A literature review (of both academic literature and grey literature as well as official government publications in English and Arabic) was conducted to identify and document the processes used in obtaining building permits in Saudi Arabia and any existing research on this topic. The resulting planning and permits workflows and issues are then compared to those already documented for other countries.

Step 2: Digitally encoded and parse-able building permits are a pre-requisite of any digital permit system to automate or semi-automate regulations checks. However, to date, most countries create their regulations in PDF format (although digital processes may be used to create the PDFs initially). To frame further research, a review of existing approaches to planning regulations encoding from PDF to digital format was conducted to identify any specific challenges that will be faced if these are applied in a different cultural/linguistic context.

Preliminary Results

Step 1a: The Saudi Building Permit Process

Saudi municipalities use a basic e-system (Baldy) for issuing building permits [23]. Issuing the building permit starts when the applicant assignees and discusses the design preferences with a certified engineering office. Then, the engineering office starts preparing the drawings following the applicant’s requirements and building regulations and uploads the required documents to Baldy in PDF format. Next, the municipality conducts an administrative review to ensure the application includes the required documents and a manual content review to ensure the proposed design complies with building and planning regulations. Lastly, the municipality makes the decision, and the applicant is notified in Baldy [17], [23]. As shown in Figure 1, the process of obtaining a building permit in Saudi Arabia is closely similar to that of other countries.

Fig. 1: Comparison of building permit workflow. Adopted from [8]

Step 1b: Existing Challenges for Saudi Building Permits

[17] Saudi cities face issues associated with the regulations and policies in the building permit cycle and among decision-makers and notifying the applicant of the states of the building permit, which is lengthy and fragmented [17]. Moreover, the study found that Saudi municipalities need to adopt new technology for issuing permits and enhancing city management performance. Further, the study found that many engineering offices have improved their capabilities and use of digital models to ensure that proposals comply with the municipalities' regulations, such as the building height, prior to submitting a building permit application. However, checking processes are taking significant time and effort and results can be inaccurate (ibid). A study by [24] found that the time required to issue a building permit for an apartment building is one to six months, and for a villa is about four months. This is due to the fact that:

- The submitted drawings often do not comply with the regulations.
- The regulations are subject to interpretation by officials.
- The processes are not transparent for both officials and consultant construction firms.

These issues were confirmed by the Ministry of Municipal and Rural Affairs (MOMRA) report, which revealed that about 75% of public construction projects are delayed and need to meet the planned time [25].

Step 2: Applying Existing Approaches to Digitising the Saudi Planning Regulations

To develop an automated compliance checking system, it is essential to digitise the building regulations, where the regulation must be translated from natural human language into computer language [14], [26]. Digitising the related building regulations is one of the most challenging tasks in digitising the building permit process [14], [27], [28]. In this context, [29], [30] developed a mark-up method, namely Requirement, Applicability, Selection and Exception (RASE), which aims to transform the regulations text into a computable form. This method has been used in different contexts. For example, [15] modified the RASE method to interpret the Turkish zoning regulations in the English language. Another project is the CHEK project, which applies the RASE method in four municipalities in Italy, Portugal, and Czechia [14].

Saudi planning regulations are provided in Arabic as text in PDF format. Some regulation documents include images and tables to illustrate specific cases, such as building height and percentage, as shown in Figure 2. In some cases – e.g. Jeddah City – all the regulations are conveniently contained in one document [31].

Fig. 2: Rear parcel building percentage and building height rule. Adapted from [31]

The RASE method was applied to a selected planning rule (building percentage and building height) of Jeddah's municipality. Preliminary results show the general applicability of the RASE method in the Arabic language. However, careful consideration of sentence structure and vocabulary is needed, as certain words can alter the meaning of the rule, resulting in different interpretations. Considering the following sentence from [31]:

“القطع الخلفية: تأخذ نظام المنطقة الخلفية في الاستخدام أما الارتفاع فيكون كما يلي:”

Once applying the RASE method, this sentence can be interpreted as a Requirement (Rear Parcel: take the rear area system in use, **and** the height is as follows), or as an Exception (Rear Parcel: take the rear area system in use, **but** the height is as follows). Here, the word “أما” can be translated into English as (AND) or (BUT).

Conclusion and Future Work

Our review shows that the construction sector in Saudi Arabia is performing poorly in terms of service provision (time and cost) [32], and the planning and permits sector faces similar challenges to those encountered elsewhere. Additionally, planning and permit workflows are, in fact, relatively similar to those adopted in other countries. Regulations are – as in many other countries – provided in PDF documents, however, in Arabic. This means that existing approaches, such as RASE, are applicable in the Saudi context.

More broadly, implementing new practices and advancements in the construction industry is important but requires altering the regulations and reducing or eliminating obstacles. In addition, digitising the building permit process in the Saudi Arabian context is rarely discussed. Further work will involve a more in-depth review of benefits, processes, and regulations, including a more in-depth study of the applicability of RASE to the planning regulations and an investigation of the impacts of GeoBIM-based automated compliance checking on the building permit process.

References

- [1] F. Noardo et al., “Unveiling the actual progress of Digital Building Permit: Getting awareness through a critical state of the art review,” *Build Environ*, vol. 213, p. 108854, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1016/J.BUILDENV.2022.108854.
- [2] F. Rehmann, F. Cudok, R. Streblov, J. Fauth, G. Malacarne, and C. Marcher, “Digitalisation of the

- building permit process - a case study in Italy,” *IOP Conf Ser Earth Environ Sci*, vol. 1101, no. 5, p. 052008, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/1101/5/052008.
- [3] EuroSDR, “Workshop Report European Spatial Data Research I EUnet4DBP International workshop on Digital Building Permit DIGITAL BUILDING PERMIT: A STATE OF PLAY,” 2021.
- [4] K. Ullah, E. Witt, and I. Lill, “The BIM-Based Building Permit Process: Factors Affecting Adoption,” *Buildings*, vol. 12, no. 1, 2022, doi: 10.3390/buildings12010045.
- [5] D. M. Brito, D. B. Costa, and E. A. M. Ferreira, “Code Checking using BIM for Digital Building Permit: a case study in a Brazilian municipality,” *IOP Conf Ser Earth Environ Sci*, vol. 1101, no. 2, p. 022049, Nov. 2022, doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/1101/2/022049.
- [6] F. Noardo, T. Wu, K. Arroyo Otori, T. Krijnen, and J. Stoter, “IFC models for semi-automating common planning checks for building permits,” *Autom Constr*, vol. 134, p. 104097, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1016/J.AUTCON.2021.104097.
- [7] N. Hobeika et al., “Geobim Information to Check Digital Building Permit Regulations,” *ISPAR*, vol. 43B4, no. B4-2022, pp. 529–535, May 2022, doi: 10.5194/ISPRS-ARCHIVES-XLIII-B4-2022-529-2022.
- [8] F. Noardo et al., “Opportunities and challenges for GeoBIM in Europe: developing a building permits use-case to raise awareness and examine technical interoperability challenges,” <https://doi.org/10.1080/14498596.2019.1627253>, vol. 65, no. 2, pp. 209–233, May 2019, doi: 10.1080/14498596.2019.1627253.
- [9] C. Ellul, F. Noardo, L. Harrie, and J. Stoter, “THE EUROS DR GEOBIM PROJECT-DEVELOPING CASE STUDIES FOR THE USE OF GEOBIM IN PRACTICE,” 2020, doi: 10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIV-4-W1-2020-33-2020.
- [10] K. Ullah, E. Witt, I. Lill, N. Banaitienė, and M. Statulevičius, “Readiness assessment for BIM-based building permit processes using Fuzzy-COPRAS,” *jest.vgtu.lt*, 2022, doi: 10.3846/jcem.2022.17274.
- [11] H. Lee, J. K. Lee, S. Park, and I. Kim, “Translating building legislation into a computer-executable format for evaluating building permit requirements,” *Autom Constr*, vol. 71, pp. 49–61, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.1016/J.AUTCON.2016.04.008.
- [12] T. Beach, “D-COM: Digital COMpliance : Digitisation of Requirements, Regulations and Compliance Checking Processes in the Built Environment - Final Report,” 2019, doi: 10.17863/CAM.40451.
- [13] I. Kim, J. Choi, E. Teo, H. S.-J. of C. Engineering, and undefined 2020, “Development of K-BIM e-Submission prototypical system for the openBIM-based building permit framework,” *journals.vilniustech.lt*, 2020, doi: 10.3846/jcem.2020.13756.
- [14] S. Mastrolembro Ventura et al., “Change toolkit for digital building permit Deliverable number D2.1 Deliverable name Regulations interpretation and needs identification for CHEK DBP Authors and contributors Author Organisation E-mail Quality control Author Organisation Role Date Document history Release Description Date Author,” 2023.
- [15] Y. Demir Altıntaş and M. E. Ilal, “Loose coupling of GIS and BIM data models for automated compliance checking against zoning codes,” *Autom Constr*, vol. 128, p. 103743, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1016/J.AUTCON.2021.103743.
- [16] P. O. Olsson, J. Axelsson, M. Hooper, and L. Harrie, “Automation of Building Permission by Integration of BIM and Geospatial Data,” *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information* 2018, Vol. 7, Page 307, vol. 7, no. 8, p. 307, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.3390/IJGI7080307.
- [17] O. Aljobaly, M. Maatouk, and E. Qurnfulah, “Developing Buildings Permits Systems Platforms (BPSP) for driving change to introduce GeoBIM potentials, challenges, and opportunities,” *Journal of Applied Geospatial Information*, vol. 6, no. 2, pp. 711–721, Dec. 2022, doi: 10.30871/JAGI.V6I2.4698.
- [18] A. Alqahtany, “Affordable housing in Saudi Arabia’s vision 2030: new developments and new challenges,” *International Journal of Housing Markets and Analysis*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 243–256, Feb.

- 2021, doi: 10.1108/IJHMA-04-2020-0035/FULL/PDF.
- [19] The World Bank, “Population, total - Saudi Arabia | Data.” Accessed: May 02, 2023. [Online]. Available: https://data.worldbank.org/indicator/SP.POP.TOTL?end=2021&locations=SA&most_recent_value_desc=false&start=1960
- [20] General Authority for Statistics, “General Authority for Statistics, Population and Vital Statistics,” General Authority for Statistics. Accessed: May 05, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://www.stats.gov.sa/en/indicators/1>
- [21] R. M. Doheim, A. A. Farag, and S. Badawi, “Smart city vision and practices across the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia—a review,” *Smart Cities: Issues and Challenges Mapping Political, Social and Economic Risks and Threats*, pp. 309–332, Jan. 2019, doi: 10.1016/B978-0-12-816639-0.00017-X.
- [22] M. Aljoufie and A. Tiwari, “Exploring Housing and Transportation Affordability in Jeddah,” <https://doi.org/10.1080/10511482.2020.1815070>, 2020, doi: 10.1080/10511482.2020.1815070.
- [23] Ministry of Municipal and Rural Affairs, “Building Permit.” Accessed: Jun. 04, 2023. [Online]. Available: https://www.my.gov.sa/wps/portal/snp/servicesDirectory/servicedetails/s9057!/ut/p/z0/04_Sj9C Pykssy0xPLMnMz0vMAfljo8zivQIsTAwdDQz9LQwNzQwCnS0tXPwMvYwN3A30g1Pz9L30o_ArAppi VOTr7JuuH1WQWJKhm5mXlq8fUWxpYGquX5DtHg4AUafoaw!!/
- [24] M. Helmi, “The ability of the local planning authority to implement zoning regulations: a case study of Jeddah, Saudi Arabia,” 2015, Accessed: May 04, 2023. [Online]. Available: <http://theses.ncl.ac.uk/jspui/handle/10443/2872>
- [25] M. A. Al-Hammadi and W. Tian, “Challenges and Barriers of Building Information Modeling Adoption in the Saudi Arabian Construction Industry,” *The Open Construction & Building Technology Journal*, vol. 14, no. 1, pp. 98–110, Jul. 2020, doi: 10.2174/1874836802014010098.
- [26] R. J. G. Mateus et al., “Improving Regulations for Automated Design Checking Through Decision Analysis Good Practices: A Conceptual Application to the Construction Sector,” pp. 160–169, 2024, doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-38241-3_19.
- [27] K.-Y. Kim, “Improving Regulations for Automated Design Checking Through Decision Analysis Good Practices: A Conceptual Application to the Construction Sector,” *Flexible Automation and Intelligent Manufacturing: The Human-Data-Technology Nexus Proceedings of FAIM 2022*, June 19–23, 2022, Detroit, Michigan, USA /, pp. 160–169, 2024, doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-38241-3_19.
- [28] Y. S. Huang, S. G. Shih, and K. H. Yen, “An integrated GIS, BIM and facilities infrastructure information platform designed for city management,” <https://doi.org/10.1080/02533839.2021.1897481>, vol. 44, no. 4, pp. 293–304, 2021, doi: 10.1080/02533839.2021.1897481.
- [29] N. Nisbet, L. Ma, and G. Aksenova., “Presentations of rase knowledge mark-up,” Jul. 2022. doi: 10.35490/EC3.2022.162.
- [30] E. Hjelseth and N. Nisbet, “CAPTURING NORMATIVE CONSTRAINTS BY USE OF THE SEMANTIC MARK-UP RASE METHODOLOGY,” pp. 26–28, 2011.
- [31] Jeddah Municipality, “المخطط المحلي لمحافظة جدة أنظمة وضوابط البناء.”
- [32] S. Alhumayn, E. Chinyio, I. N.-W. T. on T. Built, and undefined 2017, “The barriers and strategies of implementing BIM in Saudi Arabia,” witpress.com, 2017, doi: 10.2495/BIM170061.

Requirements analysis and acceleration of approval procedures for federal highways in Germany

Niklas Pauls^a, Marlena Block^b, Tanja Jakovljevic^a, Florian Köllner^c,
Andreas Bach^a, Markus König^b

^aSchübler-Plan Digital GmbH, Düsseldorf, Germany

^bComputing in Engineering, Ruhr-University Bochum, Bochum, Germany

^cFederal Trunk Road Authority, Leipzig, Germany

The research project "BeGeBIM" was initiated in June 2023 for the purpose of investigating the effectiveness of the BIM method in acceleration of the approval procedures in Germany. The project aims to establish the essential requirements and solutions for a digital, model-driven approval process in the construction of road infrastructure. The project partners aim to outline requirements for BIM models, analyze traditional approval processes within existing legal regulations, and develop and evaluate digital verification routines for possible implementation in a model-based approval process. [1]

The contribution centres on the results of the initial phase of the project. The objective was to analyze the current as-is processes of the approval procedure and identify (sub)processes whose improvement could accelerate the entire approval process.

Ensuring a resilient transport infrastructure is an important task for the public sector. The current need for expansion and renovation results from the increasing wear and tear on highways and bridges due to the sharp rise in traffic volumes. Cumbersome and lengthy construction approval procedures lead to a considerable amount of time being spent, meaning that these procedures need to be accelerated in the interests of the national economy. Recognising the intrinsic link between efficient transportation networks and economic prosperity, expediting the approval processes becomes paramount. Acceleration not only addresses the immediate challenges of infrastructure degradation but also serves as a catalyst for economic growth. Streamlining these procedures demands a strategic approach that balances speed with the maintenance of rigorous standards, ensuring the sustained safety and environmental integrity of the infrastructure.

The early adoption of an end-to-end digital process chain appears to be a practicable solution. Implementing a comprehensive digital process can accelerate decision-making, enhance transparency, reduce administrative bottlenecks, and minimize the margin for error. The Building Information Modeling (BIM) method is founded on the principle that all information is stored and transmitted in a three-dimensional model throughout the planning, construction, and operation of a building or a construction. Nowadays, numerous construction projects are being executed as BIM projects. Presently, there is a media discontinuity when submitting planning documents to the approval authority, as two-dimensional plans must be submitted for approval. This requires additional work from the planners to create the plans. The use of models in the approval process is expected to lead to more consistent data exchange and simplify the process of checking for approvability. Countries in which the BIM-based approval process has already been introduced are Singapore, Norway, Estonia, Finland and the Netherlands [2]. It has already been shown that a lot of information in an approval process can be objectified and quantified and is therefore suitable for integration into a BIM-based workflow [3]. In building construction, the successful use of BIM in the approval process has already been evaluated and it has been shown that a partially automated inspection using digital models is possible with the help of comprehensive checking rule definitions [4].

The objective of the initial phase of the research project was to analyse the current as-is processes of the approval procedure. To begin with, it was necessary to document the current approval procedure in detail to understand the specific tasks and dependencies. Formal process maps help to visualise and comprehend the connections between individual specialist departments and the submitted documents involved in an approval process. The current approval process was captured with the special knowledge of experts from the Federal Trunk Road Authority and formalized using Business Process Model and Notation 2.0 (BPMN). BPMN 2.0 has emerged as the standard for business process diagrams. It is designed for stakeholders involved in designing, managing, and implementing business processes. These principles are detailed in a publicly accessible specification.[5]

Fig. 1: Overview of the approval process including the relation to the preliminary examination as a sample process for the second level

In Germany, the planning of buildings is typically divided into the five phases “Basic evaluation”, “Preliminary planning”, “Design planning”, “Building permission application” and “Detailed design” (cf. fig. 1). During this planning period, the approval process for federal infrastructure projects takes place and consists of three main phases, as outlined in the guidelines for the "Planning procedure and the uniform design of planning documents in road construction" [6]. These phases are “Preliminary examination”, “Preliminary draft” and “Draft declaration”. To ensure clarity and manage complexity, the process map was modelled with four levels of detail. The first level represents the overall process of the successive phases. The second level models the processes of each phase, with a focus on clearly outlining communication processes between the project owner and the approval authority. The third level concentrates on procedures and processes within one of the reviewing organisations. For instance, the review process from the assignment of approval documents to the aggregated review result. The fourth level, which is the most detailed, illustrates specific workflows of the inspectors, such as the inspection of technical equipment. The level structure is depicted in figure 2.

Fig. 2: Hierarchy of the individual process modelling levels

The potential for process improvement was identified through two methods. Firstly, an evaluation scheme was developed that prioritises individual processes consistently. With respect to the project objectives, an assessment was carried out in the categories "suitability for use of the BIM method", "dependencies", "legal framework" and "demonstrator capability & transfer". High-priority processes include, for example, reviewing the content of the approval documents. This example can now be used to explain the second way of identifying potential for improvement. Process maps were used to identify uniform process sequences suitable for automation due to their repetitive nature. In the content review process, the communication channels, access to authorization documents, and aggregation of results are identical. The approval procedure involves checking various documents, such as the project location and overview, plans for immission control measures, and plans for drainage measures, rather than just technical equipment.

The next step of the research project will be to formulate target processes based on the as-is analysis of the approval procedure processes and prioritisation. These processes should address potential issues through the consolidation of process flows, digitalisation, and automation. One possible solution is to create a federated model at the beginning of the approval process. This model should cover all the information requirements of the individual inspections in the same way as the approval documents. Defining the information requirements (LOIN) for different specialised models is necessary as it provides the basis for a federated model. Subsequent steps in the development process can facilitate the creation of checking rules and routines that can be applied to the authorisation models. These semi-automated checking rules can significantly speed up the checking process, reduce human error, and ensure the quality of the planning.

A semi-automated approval procedure undoubtedly offers advantages such as efficiency gains and process acceleration. However, the question remains as to whether it is merely a short-term measure or whether it will be sustainable in its current form in the long term. In principle, it is crucial to identify potential challenges and risks, especially in the evaluation phase, to ensure that it meets the needs of all stakeholders and complies with legal requirements. In answering this question, it is important to consider not only the current state of technology, but also the progress made, particularly in the areas of Natural Language Processing (NLP) to seamlessly

convert standards and guidelines into machine-readable formats and artificial intelligence (AI) to achieve a higher level of automation.

Although legal framework conditions currently prevent an end-to-end digital process in Germany, demonstrating the feasibility of such a procedure and partially automating process steps will make the potential transparent and remove hurdles to an accelerated digital authorisation procedure in the long term. To optimize the process, select the highest priority and most automation and acceleration potential processes. The aim is to develop target processes, create necessary specifications for digital foundations, use technical systems for implementation, and carry out an exemplary implementation. Accompanying measures, such as measuring throughput times, are intended to evaluate the efficiency increase resulting from process digitization.

References

- [1] BMDV, *Beschleunigung von Genehmigungsprozessen im Straßenbau durch digitale Modelle: BeGeBIM*. [Online]. Available: <https://bmdv.bund.de/SharedDocs/DE/Artikel/DG/mfund-projekte/begebim.html> (accessed: Mar. 6 2024).
- [2] M. Terzić, I. Peško, M. S. Pejić, V. Mučenski, and D. Stanojević, "Experiences of countries with the adoption of the BIM-based permit process," in *Proceedings: Creative Construction Conference 2023, CCC 2023, Keszthely, Lake Balaton, 20-23 July 2023*, Keszthely, Hungary, 2023, pp. 286–292. Accessed: Mar. 7 2024. [Online]. Available: <https://repozitorium.omikk.bme.hu/server/api/core/bitstreams/4d17c821-8722-41f2-a035-0e80c38cedab/content>
- [3] D. Piazza, M. Röck, G. Malacarne, A. Passer, C. Marcher, and D. T. Matt, "BIM for public authorities: Basic research for the standardized implementation of BIM in the building permit process," *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.*, vol. 323, no. 1, p. 12102, 2019, doi: 10.1088/1755-1315/323/1/012102.
- [4] M. König, A. Vonthron, T. Drathler, M. Drathler, and N. Hoffmann, "Bericht zur Ersten BIM-basierten Baugenehmigung in Nordrhein-Westfalen,"
- [5] OMG BPMN 2.0, *Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN), Version 2.0*. [Online]. Available: <http://www.omg.org/spec/BPMN/2.0>
- [6] BMVBS, "Richtlinien zum Planungsprozess und für die einheitliche Gestaltung von Entwurfsunterlagen im Straßenbau," 2012.

When DBP meets DBL – Conceptual alignment on process level

Pedro Mêda^a, Judith Fauth^b, Hipólito Sousa^a, Christian Schranz^c, Harald Urban^c

^aCONSTRUCT-GEQUALTEC / University of Porto – Faculty of Engineering, Porto, Portugal

^bUniversity of Cambridge, Cambridge, UK

^cTU Wien, Wien, Austria

The digitalisation of the building permitting (DBP) process is suffering a significant push, with several researchers actively working and supported by the European Commission's (EC) ambition of setting a common framework for it.

Similarly, following several European Union (EU) studies, a common framework of requirements to ensure data traceability at the building level and throughout the built entity life cycle is also being proposed and trialled. This information container, which can collect data and set links to different databases, is defined as the Digital Building Logbook (DBL) [1] [2].

As a starting point, both initiatives have existing processes that can vary substantially from country to country or even from public authority to public authority in the same region. Notwithstanding, the processes they aim to improve, expand, or replace are critical, either for compliance checking against regulations, establishing and verifying performance or environmental indicators, obtaining a license for building use, and recording changes from interventions or other events, among different possible examples. Additionally, some aspects are common. DBP and DBL share the same scope: the building and its life cycle and similar flaws are identified by many researchers, where data loss and the absence of traceability are among the ones raising more concerns [3].

Given the investment to better understand and establish guidelines at the EU level supporting the digitalisation and standardisation of building permits and building logbooks, and given the common aspects shared by both, it is the authors' intuition that is key to seeking potential links, merging partially the systems architecture and identify the requirements and inherent data that should be shared, if applicable.

Although several studies are investigating the processes, the data and the requirements surrounding each concept, few studies exist focusing on understanding if both concepts overlap and, facing a positive answer, how they overlap or complement each other.

The present study aims to answer the following questions:

- Are DBP and DBL related concepts?
- If yes, how should they relate at the process level?

Based on the intuition of the relationship between DBP and DBL, the CIFE horseshoe methodology was established as the framework [4]. Action research and its system model constitute the core method, where the preparation, the realisation of a workshop and the iterations with experts support all methodological steps, as presented in “Fig 1” [5]. Insights from surveys were used for the iteration process. The discussion period was used for spreading ideas and focusing on specific aspects, leading to issues clustering, and enabling the main findings and contributions.

Fig. 3: Methodological approach based on CIFE horseshoe (simplified) and Action research.

The findings lead to the overall perception that DBP and DBL are related concepts, overlapping in processes and data, meaning that technological links or similar or, at least, compatible reference architectures should be adopted.

„Fig 2“ illustrates the connections on a process level considering the built entity lifecycle. The DBL layer is based on Méda, 2022 [6], while the DBP level is based on a digital building permit taxonomy based on Fauth, 2024 [7]. The interconnections between the two layers are shown. In addition, and based on current practices and law, milestones are fixed stages within the process.

Fig. 4: Process level connections between DBP and DBL.

Additionally, thoughts were shared about the linking concerns to other databases containing relevant data, and that must be kept as the source of that data. The maturity of these databases and the fact that they are not being fully established for the construction sector raise compatibility issues and the question of how the boundary conditions should be defined. From a technological viewpoint, tools and standards exist to support information exchanges. However,

most of them are limited in scope to the construction sector. Other initiatives can also bring valuable contributions to the DBP and DBL developments, such as the INSPIRE Directive, Digital Product Passports, Asset Management systems, and smart buildings management systems [8] [9]. Likewise, opportunities and challenges arise from these possibilities.

The study delivers insights and guidance for ongoing developments by clarifying the potential relationships between DBP and DBL. Additionally, this contribution is significant at the strategic level as EU grey literature should assume this as a starting point for actions, guiding principles and implementation roadmaps. Although the findings are relevant to all construction sector stakeholders, these are more meaningful to researchers and strategists working on twin transitions in construction. In these, governments and public authorities are included. It is also essential to highlight the importance of the outcomes to the relevant stakeholders engaged in aspects surrounding Digital Twins and Asset management systems, among other topics where much experience already exists and where relevant contributions can be built based on it.

This work also provides insights into how DBP and DBL dependencies can work and to which extent one can be part of the other. Although some conclusions are presented in this respect and mainly focusing on the process's perspective, the study identifies several issues to be worked out in future research, namely in what relates to the relevant data to be exchanged attached to each process.

References

- [1] M. Gómez-Gil, A. Espinosa-Fernández, and B. López-Mesa, "Review and Analysis of Models for a European Digital Building Logbook," *energies*, vol. 15, p. 24, 2022, doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/en15061994>.
- [2] M. Malinovec Puček, A. Khoja, E. Bazzan, and P. Gyuris, "A Data Structure for Digital Building Logbooks: Achieving Energy Efficiency, Sustainability, and Smartness in Buildings across the EU," *Buildings*, vol. 13, no. 4, 2023, doi: [10.3390/buildings13041082](https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13041082).
- [3] I. Papadaki et al., "Transition pathway for Construction," Brussels, 2023. [Online]. Available: <https://ec.europa.eu/docsroom/documents/53854>
- [4] J. Kunz and M. Fischer, "CIFE Research Questions and Methods," Stanford, 2007.
- [5] M. Christie, "Using action research to improve teaching," no. January, 1992.
- [6] P. Mêda, D. Calvetti, D. Kifokeris, and M. Kassem, "A Process-Based Framework for Digital Building Logbooks," in *2022 European Conference on Computing in Construction*, 2022, p. 8. doi: [10.35490/EC3.2022.183](https://doi.org/10.35490/EC3.2022.183).
- [7] J. Fauth et al., "Taxonomy for building permit system - organizing knowledge for building permit digitalization," *Adv. Eng. Informatics*, vol. 59, no. May 2023, p. 21, 2024, doi: [10.1016/j.aei.2023.102312](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2023.102312).
- [8] M. Gómez-Gil, M. M. Sesana, G. Salvalai, A. Espinosa-Fernández, and B. López-Mesa, "The Digital Building Logbook as a gateway linked to existing national data sources: The cases of Spain and Italy," *J. Build. Eng.*, vol. 63, no. August 2022, 2022, doi: [10.1016/j.jobbe.2022.105461](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2022.105461).
- [9] C. V. Bellos, K. Petroutsatou, and L. Anthopoulos, "Electronic Building Permission System: The Case of Greece," *Procedia Eng.*, vol. 123, pp. 50–58, 2015, doi: [10.1016/j.proeng.2015.10.056](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.proeng.2015.10.056).

A theoretical approach for adopting smart contracts in granting building permits for individual houses in Vietnam

Quan T. Nguyen^a

^aHanoi University of Civil Engineering, quannt@huce.edu.vn

Vietnam has been going under its urbanisation since its economic reform in 1986, but the urbanisation rate has increased significantly for about 15 years. This urbanisation has led to the booming in housing development in the country, both for housing in projects and individual houses. According to the current regulations, for most of the cases of individual houses, the house owners must apply for a building permit from district-level government before they can start the construction work [1]. Statistical figures show that the number of permits issued for individual houses accounts for more than 90% of the number of Building Permits issued by provinces. The Building Permit process is often subjective, long and complicated, then error-prone [2]. Civil servants in charge of processing the building permit applications keep claiming to be overloaded. This practice leads to less efficient use of public assets and low level of quality in public service provision. Digitalisation has been proved to be a solution for facilitating the building permit issuance [2]. BIM model and web application can be used for reviewing the building permit applications. However, the building permit can only be granted if all the conditions are met, while the conditions are very subjective which leads to a lot of different cases to be reviewed. Previous publications have stated that smart contracts can be applied to granting building permits [3, 4].

According to Nick Szabo [5], a smart contract is “a computerized transaction protocol that executes the terms of a contract. The general objectives of smart-contract design are to satisfy common contractual conditions (such as payment terms, liens, confidentiality, and even enforcement), minimise exceptions both malicious and accidental, and minimise the need for trusted intermediaries.” In other words, smart contracts are “an agreement among multiple parties written at least in part in computer code” [5]. Smart contracts are following “if/then” logical statement written on the blockchain. When the predefined conditions are met and verified, a computer network executes the functions. Apparently, the conditions in granting building permits can be converted into codes then smart contracts can be used for the issuance of building permits. Parties engaged in the smart contract must agree on the terms that govern the transactions, the methods by which data and transactions are recorded on the blockchain, the investigation of any exceptions, and the creation of a dispute resolution mechanism. In building permit issuance, different agencies need to agree on the conditions to grant the permit, similar to the way the users approve a transaction in blockchain.

A typical smart contract process is presented in Figure 1. Parties must first decide when to work together and decide on the goals for each party in order to construct a smart contract. Any potential exchange of value, such as products or services, may fall under this category. They then need to specify the requirements that must be fulfilled for an exchange to take place. These could be set off by the individuals involved, by outside circumstances, or by particular benchmarks. After this, programmatic writing of all the specifications and contract terms is done utilizing computer logic and code. After that, the smart contract may be added to the blockchain, where it will automatically run when certain criteria are met [6].

Fig. 1: A typical smart contract process [6]

Literature shows that smart contracts have been applied to automate different kinds of processes in the built environment. Table 1 summarizes selected applications.

Tab. 1: Selected applications of smart contracts in the built environment

No	Smart contract application	Sources
1	Automatic verification of the compliance of the digital deliverables provided by Exchange Information Requirements	[7]
2	Automated Code Compliance Checking for Building Envelope Design	[8]
3	Improving supply chains, supply chain management	[6, 9]
4	Automatically recording and calculating reimbursed costs, profits, and cost savings for each member of a construction project	[10]
5	Automatic payment in the construction industry	[11-13]
6	Eliminating or reducing payment issues in construction contracts	[14]

According to the current regulations, a typical process for granting Building Permit for individual houses can be divided into 5 steps (Figure 2). The timeframe for granting a Building Permit for new construction is presented in Table 2.

Fig.2: Building Permit business processes for individual houses

Tab. 2: Building Permit: key timeframes for an application for new construction

Activities	Duration
Request for additional document (if any)	Within 7 working days after receiving the application. Applicant to have maximum 2 times to submit required additional documents
Checking the first supplemented documents	Local government agency is given 5 working days for checking the first supplemented documents
Refusal notification (if applicable)	If supplemented documents still do not satisfy, a refusal notification needs to be sent out within 3 working days
Building Permit decision	Since the time the application is complete with required documents, a decision must be sent out within 15 days; an extension may be applicable in special cases but not more than 10 days
Comments/feedback from consulted government agencies	Government agencies being consulted must respond within 12 days, if not, they are considered to agree with the application

Source: [15]

The documents to be submitted for applying for a building permit are summarised in Table 3.

Tab.3: Building permit for individual houses: application documents

No	Building Permit Application Documents	Remarks
1	A letter of application for a Building Permit	Original/scanned copy
2	A copy of one of the proofs of land use rights as prescribed by the land law	Certified/electronic copy
3	Construction design drawings: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Work plan on the land plot, enclosed with the work location diagram • Floor plan, elevations and sections of the work • Footing plan and sections enclosed with connection diagram of infrastructure outside the work including water supply and drainage, power supply 	Original/electronic copy
4	Additional documents (if any): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • fire safety design appraisal certificates • copy of design practice certificates of designers, design reviewers • construction design review report on safety issues • adjacent works safety assurance commitment 	Original/ Certified/ electronic copy

Source: [16]

The conditions for granting a building permit can be grouped into: Validity of the application documents, Conformity of the application documents and Timeframes in the business processes. A general if/then framework for application of smart contracts can be developed based on these conditions (Figure 3).

Fig.3: General if/then conditions for using in the smart contracts

Selected checkpoints then need to be taken into account, according to the current regulations

[16]:

- if the house is in the list of construction permission waiver or not;
- houses with 7+ storeys and having another function may need a certificate for firefighting and prevention.
- houses with 7+ storeys and/or with from 2 basements require a qualified design review consultant
- if there is any adjacent building, a letter of commitment for securing the safety of the adjacent buildings is needed.
- houses with basement(s), GFA of greater than 250m2 or having from than 3 floors or having a height of at least 12m need to hire qualified people or organization to design

A theoretical framework for application of smart contracts in granting building permits for individual houses in Vietnam is then developed (Figure 4, 5, 6, 8, 9).

Fig.4: General Framework for Application of Smart Contracts

Fig.5: Application Validity Check

Smart Contract 1: Application Validity Check

BEGIN

IF the house type is in the list of Building Permit exemption

 Issue Refusal Letter

 Return the Application Documents

ELSE

 IF each application document is correct in type

 IF the number of document types is enough in quantity

 Issue Application Receipt Form

 Handover to Department in charge

 Set time for processing at 15 days

 CREATE Smart Contract 2

 END IF

 ELSE

 Issue Refusal Letter

 Provide Guidance

 Return the Application Documents

 END IF

END IF

TERMINATE Smart Contract 1

END

Fig.6: Document Check and Site Inspection

Fig.7: Agencies to be consulted for building permits

BEGIN

IF there are documents missing, improper or untrue to reality

 Issue Additional Document Request (once only) with timeframe

 IF additional documents submitted within the timeframe AND are satisfied

 Reset the processing time to 0

 ELSE

 Issue Refusal Letter

 Return the Application

 END IF

END IF

IF there is a need of consulting other government authorities

 CREATE Smart Contract 3

ELSE

 CREATE Smart Contract 4

END IF

TERMINATE Smart Contract 2

END

Fig. 8: Related Government Authorities Consultation

Smart Contract 3: Related Government Authorities Consultation

```

BEGIN
IF Related Government Authorities respond in writing within 12 days
    CREATE Smart Contract 4
ELSE
    Set the information requested from Related Government Authorities as conforming
    CREATE Smart Contract 4
END IF
TERMINATE Smart Contract 3
END
    
```


Fig.9: Final Decision

Smart Contract 4: Final Decision

```

BEGIN
IF processing time is within 15 days
    IF application documents are all valid
        Issue Building Permit
        Publish Building Permit on local government’s website
    END IF
TERMINATE Smart Contract 4
END
    
```

```
ELSE
    IF extra days are needed for processing the application
        Inform Applicant
        Report to higher management level
    ELSE
        Issue Building Permit automatically
        TERMINATE Smart Contract 4
    END IF
END IF
END
```

The proposed solution can bring in a number of benefits, such as: (i) reducing the duration for processing and exchanging correspondences among related government authorities, then increasing the state management efficiency, (ii) enhancing the level of professionalism of related authorities which leads to higher productivity and quality of public services, (iii) facilitating the building permit automation and enhancing the accuracy, (iv) the decision making process is digitally recorded for future use and decision, and (v) providing applicants a means for easy track the building permit process, then improving the process transparency.

The limitation of this study is that it only proposed a conceptual framework for the application of smart contracts to building permits for individual houses. Future works will need to deal with the programming, and also to address a wider approach for integrating all types of building permits, not only for individual houses but also for building projects in general for a better total efficiency of public assets.

References

- [1]. Law No 62/2020/QH14 amendments to Construction Law, Vietnam National Assembly, Editor. 2020.
- [2]. Fauth, J., G. Malacarne, and C. Marcher. Digitalisation of the building permit process-a case study in Italy. in IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science. 2022. IOP Publishing.
- [3]. Nawari, N.O. and S. Ravindran, *Blockchain and the built environment: Potentials and limitations*. Journal of Building Engineering, 2019. 25: p. 100832.
- [4]. Mora, H., et al. Management city model based on blockchain and smart contracts technology. in Research & Innovation Forum 2019: Technology, Innovation, Education, and their Social Impact 1. 2019. Springer.
- [5]. Vigliotti, M.G., What do we mean by smart contracts? open challenges in smart contracts. Frontiers in Blockchain, 2021. 3: p. 553671.
- [6]. Law, A., Smart contracts and their application in supply chain management. 2017, Massachusetts Institute of Technology.
- [7]. Li, J., et al. A proposed approach integrating DLT, BIM, IOT and smart contracts: Demonstration using a simulated installation task. in International Conference on Smart Infrastructure and Construction 2019 (ICSIC) Driving data-informed decision-making. 2019. ICE Publishing.
- [8]. Tan, X., A. Hammad, and P. Fazio, *Automated code compliance checking for building envelope design*. Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering, 2010. 24(2): p. 203-211.

- [9]. Dolgui, A., et al., *Blockchain-oriented dynamic modelling of smart contract design and execution in the supply chain*. International Journal of Production Research, 2020. 58(7): p. 2184-2199.
- [10]. Elghaish, F., S. Abrishami, and M.R. Hosseini, *Integrated project delivery with blockchain: An automated financial system*. Automation in construction, 2020. 114: p. 103182.
- [11]. Di Giuda, G.M., P.E. Giana, and G. Pattini, The shortening and the automation of payments: The potentiality of smart contract in the AECO sector, in Proceedings of International Structural Engineering and Construction. 2020, ISEC Press. p. 1-6.
- [12]. Chong, H.-Y. and A. Diamantopoulos, *Integrating advanced technologies to uphold security of payment: Data flow diagram*. Automation in construction, 2020. 114: p. 103158.
- [13]. Hamledari, H. and M. Fischer, Construction payment automation using blockchain-enabled smart contracts and robotic reality capture technologies. Automation in Construction, 2021. 132: p. 103926.
- [14]. Ahmadiheykhsarmast, S. and R. Sonmez. Smart contracts in construction industry. in 5th International Project and Construction Management Conference (IPCMC2018). 2018. North Cyprus.
- [15]. The National Assembly (Vietnam), The Construction Law, No 50/2014/QH13 dated 18th June 2014, in 50/2014/QH13. 2014: Vietnam.
- [16]. Government of Vietnam, Decree 15/2021/ND-CP detailing on management of construction investment projects. 2021: Online.

Aligning BIM, DBP, and Sustainability: Insights from a Venn Diagram Analysis

Stefanie-Brigitte Deac-Kaiser^a, Judith Fauth^b, Nicolae-Andrei Crişan^a

^a Politehnica University of Timisoara, Department Steel Structures and Structural Mechanics, Traian Lalescu 11, Timisoara, Romania

^b Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, UK

Introduction

The construction industry's significant impact on resource depletion, waste generation, and energy consumption, with buildings projected to emit a substantial amount of carbon dioxide by 2030 [1], underscores the urgency of adopting sustainable practices. In the United States, buildings consume a significant amount of energy resources, contributing to 40% of global CO₂ emissions [2] mainly from building operations, such as heating, cooling, lighting, and electrical appliance usage [3]. Recognizing these challenges, the United Nations introduced 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) in 2015, with Goal 11 focusing on creating inclusive, safe, resilient, and sustainable cities and human settlements [4].

Amidst this backdrop, digital building permits (DBP) emerge as a transformative solution, replacing traditional paper-based methods with an efficient online system, allowing automated code compliance check streamlining the building permitting process. By leveraging technology, DBP ensures design proposals meet regulations while digitizing processes to enhance transparency, predictability, and accuracy. Moreover, the shift towards digital permits brings sustainability benefits like reduced CO₂ emissions and paper usage, alongside cost savings and streamlined workflows [5].

In response to the growing demand for efficient, sustainable buildings, designers are exploring methods to minimize environmental impact and energy usage [3]. Collaborative BIM platforms like Autodesk Revit play a pivotal role in this endeavor, contributing to Building Sustainable Assessment (BSA) methods [6]. These platforms enable the comprehensive assessment of sustainable criteria, with emphasis on environmental performance monitoring and data collection.

Despite these advancements, a notable research gap persists in understanding the interconnectedness of sustainability, DBP, and BIM. While individual studies have explored these domains separately, there remains limited research addressing their collective impact. Thus, a comprehensive literature review is necessary to identify overlaps and connections between sustainability, DBP, and BIM, paving the way for proposing integrated solutions. This study aims to fill this gap by examining the relationship between these concepts and addressing key research questions surrounding their intersection.

Research Approach

The methodological framework that guided this research started with identifying the commencement of the three concepts of sustainability, DBP, and BIM, through literature review, and proceeded to the utilization of a Venn diagram to identify the common ground. A Venn diagram stands for a graphical representation of logical sets, represented as circles or closed curves enclosed within a rectangle [7]. The shared elements among the sets are visually conveyed through the intersections of the circles, which represent the interconnection between the sets [7]. Through Venn diagrams relations of different subjects, inclusion and the operations of union, intersection and complementation can be represented [8]. Evaluating the suitability of these

representations is crucial for ensuring that the related concepts are comprehended and effectively applied in relevant fields, such as Architecture, Engineering, Construction, Owner Operator (AECOO) [5].

Findings

The relationship between the aspects of sustainability, DBP and BIM, can be shown graphically by the Venn Diagram (Figure 1) composed of the three overlapping circles, with each circle representing a distinct concept, whereas the intersections showcase the specific shared characteristics based on literature review. The size of each circle and its extent with the other two can be adjusted to represent the perceived significance of each aspect in relation to the others and the extent to which these dimensions are interconnected by sharing common elements [5]. The circles in Venn diagram are arranged symmetrically around the central area, where all three circles meet, designating the integration of the nominally achievement [5]. Transitioning to the individual circles of our Venn diagram (Figure 1), the blue circle represents BIM concepts, the red circle represents DBP, and the green circle stands for sustainability. Initially, each concept was identified independently, followed by the identification of their overlaps.

The study started with specifying the key characteristics of each individual concept through the literature review. Starting with sustainability, where long term environmental considerations in the building industry are most specific. They are supported by green building standards and certifications, such as LEED (Leadership in Energy and Environmental Design) or BREEAM (Building Research Establishment Environmental Assessment Method). While building regulations have progressed towards incorporating sustainable requirements, there remains a scarcity of green building standards and certifications beyond air tightness test certificates and EPCs (Energy Performance Certificates). Furthermore, DBP is uniquely characterized by its ability to automate code compliance checks, streamlining the permitting process. Illustrating the dynamics of BIM, that already functions as a collaborative efficiency in the digitalization of building permitting processes, its potential can surpass conventional boundaries. Through the utilization of BIM and openBIM, it enables the integration of multiple types of information related to the building project, as well as the parametric modeling techniques.

The overlap between the green and red circles in the Venn diagram highlights the integration of BIM enabled DBP, streamlining information flow during project development. Successful projects require comprehensive permit data, including design details. Integration of BIM enabled DBP makes possible the coordination among stakeholders. This integration enhances accuracy and tasks like energy optimization and automated code compliance checks, improving collaborative efficiency among stakeholders. Countries like Singapore, Estonia, Finland, and Norway are already adopting BIM-enabled DBP processes, with Singapore's "CORENET e-Submission system" leading electronic permit processing since 2015 [9], [10]. In Finland, over 60% of municipalities use "Lupapiste" for digital permit interactions, building on the success of the "KIRA-digi" project, which demonstrated the viability of accessing permit data directly from BIM models [9], [11], [12].

In the overlap between the red and blue circles representing DBP and sustainability, common elements crucial for urban development include energy efficient standards, green building certification requirements, as well as provisions for renewable energy systems. These aspects play a pivotal role in promoting environmentally and resourceful building practices. Ikram et al. (2021) conducted a study to identify how certain sustainability standards align with specific Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), providing valuable insights for various stakeholders [13]. With knowledge from these studies, stakeholders can work towards harmonizing sustainable regulations within the building permit system, by promoting environmentally responsible and resource-efficient building practices. This involves integrating new green

building certification requirements and exploring provisions for renewable energy systems, ultimately fostering sustainable construction practices.

Fig.1: Venn Diagram: Sustainable Building Synergy: BIM & DBP Intersection

The interrelation of both blue and green circles, BIM with sustainability practices, drives advancements in low-carbon building design optimization. Zhao et al. (2022) propose a methodology leveraging BIM and enhanced genetic algorithm to optimize energy efficiency and daylighting performance. By incorporating building data into BIM models, this approach enables efficient simulation, optimization, and informed decision-making towards sustainability goals [14]. Additionally, Carvalho et al. (2020) investigate the effectiveness of integrating BIM into SBTool, comparing its alignment with LEED and BREEAM standards. They focus on identifying which BSA methods benefit most from BIM and highlight energy and material-related criteria as particularly significant [15]. The study reveals that BIM, especially with Autodesk Revit, can assess energy and material aspects effectively [15]. Furthermore, digital tools for low-carbon technologies and carbon emission reduction can seamlessly integrate into BIM workflows. Assessing the environmental impact of construction materials during the design phase enables

optimization of building processes [16], including efficient logistics and just-in-time delivery strategies to minimize unnecessary material storage. Continuous monitoring, preventive maintenance, and proactive asset management further enhance sustainability efforts [16]. The sustainable application of BIM holds promises in advancing Smart Cities and urban development through the introduction of innovative software and low-carbon technologies.

Discussion

The Venn Diagram reveals the interconnectedness of BIM, DBP, and sustainability, emphasizing the need to consider them together for practical applications and policy development. Integrating sustainability into BIM-enabled DBP's offers a transformative opportunity for urban development, enhancing the built environment's quality through sustainable design and construction practices. By streamlining compliance with sustainability standards, DBP, workflows facilitate effective collaboration among stakeholders to achieve sustainability goals while meeting regulatory requirements. Additionally, BIM technology enables comprehensive environmental impact assessment, informing sustainable decision-making in DBP processes. While our study provides valuable insights, limitations exist due to the complexity of the concepts and study constraints. The study aimed to get a broad overview of the connection of the concepts on high granularity level. Due to time constraints, it lacks detailed investigations. By overcoming these limitations, future studies can enhance our understanding of sustainability, BIM, and DBPs, driving more effective and sustainable urban development practices.

Conclusion

In conclusion, our study highlights the interconnectedness of sustainability, BIM, and DBP, underscoring the significance of their integration for advancing sustainable urban development. Through the analysis of the Venn Diagram, we have demonstrated how BIM-enabled DBPs hold the potential to drive low-carbon building design optimization and ensure managed sustainable development. The integration of low carbon technologies and life cycle assessment tools into BIM workflows enhances environmental consciousness and promotes energy-efficient practices in urban development projects. Despite certain limitations, our study lays the groundwork for future research endeavors aimed at exploring the potential of sustainable DBPs and addressing the insufficient exploitation of building energy forms. By overcoming these challenges, we can pave the way for more effective and sustainable urban development practices in the future. Our study emphasizes the importance of considering BIM, DBP and sustainability together to drive a change in the built environment, while contributing to more resilient, inclusive, and sustainable cities. Future research is exploring the transformative potential of an energy-centric approach to sustainable DBPs, addressing the underutilization of building energy forms. The case studies of Denmark, Germany, and Romania are analyzed and seek the integration of sustainability principles into BIM-enabled processes.

References

- [1] Z. Sriyolja, N. Harwin and K. Yahya, "Barriers to Implement Building Information Modeling (BIM) in Construction Industry: A Critical Review," in IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, The 20th Sustainable, Environment and Architecture, Indonesia, 2021.
- [2] R. Howard and B.-C. Björk, "Building information modelling – Experts' views on standardisation and industry deployment," *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, vol. 22, no. 2, pp. 271-280, 2008.
- [3] J. K. W. Wong and J. Zhou, "Enhancing environmental sustainability over building life cycles through green BIM: A review," *Automation in Construction*, vol. 57, pp. 156-165, 2015.
- [4] U. Nations, "The Sustainable Development Goals Report," United Nations publication issued by the Department of Economic and Social Affairs, New York, NY, 10017, United States of America, 2021.

- [5] S. M. K. Carter, "Diagrammatic Representations of Sustainability – a Review and Synthesis," in Proceedings 28th Annual ARCOM Conference, Edinburgh, 2012.
- [6] J. P. Carvalho, L. Bragança and R. Mateus, "Sustainable building design: Analysing the feasibility of BIM platforms to support practical building sustainability assessment," *Computers in Industry*, vol. 127, 2021.
- [7] B. Grünbaum, "Venn Diagrams and Independent Families of Sets," *Mathematics Magazine*, vol. 48, no. 1, pp. 12-23, 1975.
- [8] M. E. Baron, "A Note on the Historical Development of Logic Diagrams: Leibniz, Euler and Venn," *The Mathematical Gazette*, vol. 53, no. 384, 2016.
- [9] M. Terzić, I. Pesko, M. Senjak, V. Mučenski and D. Stanojević, "EXPERIENCES OF COUNTRIES WITH THE ADOPTION OF THE BIM-BASED PERMIT PROCESS," in *Creative Construction e-Conference 2023*, 2023.
- [10] S. Government, "CORENET Government," [Online]. Available: [https://www.corenet.gov.sg/general/building-information-modeling-\(bim\)-esubmission.aspx](https://www.corenet.gov.sg/general/building-information-modeling-(bim)-esubmission.aspx). [Accessed 10 11 2023].
- [11] E. C. S. Observatory, "Building Information Modelling in the EU construction sector," *Trend Paper Series*, 2019.
- [12] "KIRA-digi," [Online]. Available: <https://www.kiradigi.fi/en/front-page.html>. [Accessed 23 10 2023].
- [13] M. Ikram, Q. Zhang, R. Sroufe and M. Ferasso, "Contribution of certification bodies and sustainability standards to sustainable development goals: An integrated grey systems approach," *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, vol. 28, pp. 326-345, 2021.
- [14] L. Zhao, W. Zhang and W. Wang, "BIM-Based Multi-Objective Optimization of Low-Carbon and Energy-Saving Buildings," *Sustainability*, vol. 14, no. 20, 2022.
- [15] J. P. Carvalho, L. Bragança and R. Mateus, "A Systematic Review of the Role of BIM in Building Sustainability Assessment Methods," *Applied Sciences*, vol. 10, no. 13, 2020.
- [16] L. Lima, E. Trindade, L. Alencar, M. Alencar and L. Silva, "Sustainability in the construction industry: A systematic review of the literature," *Journal of Cleaner Production*, vol. 289, 2021.

ORGANISATIONAL SYSTEM Research Track

The abstracts in this section were peer reviewed.

Adaptability of digital permits for building-as-a-service asset

Adrian Wildenauer^a, Matias Penroz^a, Alex Mbabu^b

^a Institute for Digital Construction and Wood Industry, Bern University of Applied Science, Biel/Bienne, Switzerland

^b University of Salford, School of Science, Engineering and Environment, Manchester, United Kingdom

Achieving the Sustainable Development Goals is a critical factor that is being pushed by supranational organisations, like the United Nations (UN). These 17 UN goals specify how the climate targets can be achieved with targeted, interlinked measures. The construction and property industry plays a key role in this. Novel approaches will be needed to fulfil these global goals and make the potential savings possible on a larger scale. The use of Building Information Modelling (BIM) is a first step towards making the construction industry more digital. Still, it will not be sufficient to generate tangible added value if it is not used comprehensively over the life cycle [1] in terms of a data supply tool and supplier of information for the facility management.

One of these approaches to further develop BIM and extend the use of data over the life cycle in line with the SDGs is Building-as-a-Service, in which buildings and their use are rethought. Building-as-a-Service is a new concept to fulfil the sustainability development goals (SDG) of the United Nations (UN) [2] and other political institutions. It involves using information management and technology to construct buildings in such a way that they are able to offer adaptive services themselves over their life cycle. Therefore, it is not about the type of services provided in a building, but about services provided by the building [3]. It is important to understand that the way buildings have been planned and constructed up to now has always been subject to a specific purpose [4]. Thus, a school building was built to provide education; an office building to offer commercial services etc. Following this approach, buildings were always designed for one use typology, which led to vacancies during economic crises or overcrowding during economic peaks, which in turn had to be compensated for at great expense: either with monetary losses in the event of under-occupancy or with costs for conversion measures and technical installations if more people were to carry out their respective activities in the same space [5]. Moreover, facilities are always intended for a specific use for which the relevant supervisory authorities have authorised them. However, this rigid approach often fails to account the dynamic nature of urban environments and societal needs. For instance, in cities with a significant float population, buildings may remain unutilised for extended periods when seasonal workers leave, or remote working affects dramatically the daily basis of companies. Similarly in smaller communities, valuable spaces like schools remain idle during summer months. Such examples underscore the limitations of traditional building permits that are automatically revoked if there is a change in usage. This inflexibility means that built facilities are afforded the luxury of only being used for a specific purpose and risk losing their operating license if used for another one, even when general building requirements like room occupation rate, average temperature, and fire protection requirements remain compliant within a certain range. Due to increasingly limited resources and a growing number of cost-saving programmes at national, European and international levels, it is necessary to plan, build and operate resource-efficiently [6]. Resource efficiency can only mean that buildings and their utilisation must become more flexible and smart(er) [7].

In this context, more flexible means that a building must be adaptable in its use regardless of the planned life cycle: it must be built more connected, digital and eco-social [8]. For a typical school, for example, classrooms could be used as meeting rooms or workspaces during holidays, without having to restrict operations for security reasons. The fundamental question of security and

accessibility of the respective buildings and legal handling must be worked out and contractually agreed.

This would allow temporarily vacant buildings to be used for a specific purpose without imposing any underlying restrictions. To achieve this, several, preferable maintenance-low or -free sensors are needed in the respective rooms to monitor occupancy and report back if a room is empty for a certain period of time. Coupled with sensors for light, climate and window opening, various optimisation measures can be implemented at room and building level, which can be coupled with their respective digital twins for a continuous remote monitoring.

It requires a new thinking of building licences, which are usually strict [9]. To overcome this burden, it requires coordinated information management, smart applications supported by sensors, actuators [10;11] and the flexible organisation and structuring of buildings in terms of modularity [12].

However, transitioning to this new paradigm poses challenges, especially when considering the traditionally rigid nature of building permits. It is therefore proposed that authorisations for the construction of buildings no longer depend on the purpose for which the building was designed in the planning, but rather on the range of services a building could potentially fulfil over its lifespan. This means that buildings are no longer linked to a specific purpose, but the flexibility of the building is assessed and permitted. This can be achieved by using digital tools and methods to analyse the potential of a building at the start of the official approval process. Digital test criteria can be used to analyse which sensors and actuators are required to enable the building to perform additional functions.

The concept of Building-as-a-Service (BaaS) can be exemplified through the multifunctional use of the school building. Firstly, we can investigate additional functionalities the building could provide, such as the utilisation of the sports hall outside school hours or the transformation of classrooms into co-working spaces during holidays. Secondly, the identification of necessary technical aids to offer these services is essential, including access and billing systems, along with sensors for lighting, heating, and other utilities. Thirdly, how high a possible utilisation of the building would be. In this way, after initial costs for the equipment, the operating costs can be reduced during the utilisation and a higher occupancy rate can be generated.

To further enhance this model, integrating a digital system that couples services into primary, secondary, and tertiary structure within the building's architecture is crucial. Such a system allows for a more accurate and efficient allocation of services, closely aligning them with the building's various functional layers. This digital categorisation facilitates an easier and more precise analysis and simulation of different usage scenarios. Consequently, it makes the technical and constructive aspects of adaptability significantly more manageable. Consequently, it enables buildings to transcend their physical adaptability and achieve a functional versatility that covers a broader spectrum of needs and scenarios. This maximises both their utility and efficiency.

In the field of digital building permits, adopting a BaaS approach revolutionises the permit issuance process. Permits would no longer be constrained to a building's original intended purpose but instead, be based on its ability to adapt to various service roles over its lifespan. This shift towards a service-oriented, flexible permitting process is in sync with the evolving dynamics of urban spaces and societal needs. Implementing purpose-independent permit processes requires a departure from conventional design and planning paradigms. This evolution compels architects, developers, and property owners to embrace innovative building typologies that accommodate a broader range of user requirements through a building's lifecycle. Concurrently, regulatory frameworks must evolve to assess buildings based on the diversity of services they can offer rather than their originally intended purposes. This approach requires a re-evaluation of

current zoning laws, building codes, and urban development policies to support a more versatile and resilient urban fabric. At the same time, it encourages sustainable development by optimising existing structures for multiple uses, thus reducing the need for new construction, and contributing to resource conservation.

In conclusion, integrating the BaaS model with specific service categories with a digital building permit system represents a significant advancement in urban planning and development. With the BaaS approach briefly presented here, greater flexibility and usability is possible than before, which must be legally and permit-related clarified. It acknowledges and harnesses the potential of buildings as adaptable, multi-functional assets within our communities. This approach not only aligns with modern sustainability goals but also ensures that our built environment remains responsive and relevant to the ever-changing fabric of urban life.

References

- [1] Patacas, J., Dawood, N., & Kassem, M. (2020). BIM for facilities management: A framework and a common data environment using open standards. *Automation in Construction*, 120, 103366. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103366>
- [2] United Nations. (2015). *The 17 Goals: Sustainable Development Goals*. United Nations (UN). <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>
- [3] Wildenauer, A. A., Mbabu, A., Underwood, J., & Basl, J. (2022). Building-as-a-Service: Theoretical Foundations and Conceptual Framework. *Buildings*, 12(10), 1594. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12101594>
- [4] Litau, O. (2015). *Nachhaltiges Facility Management im Wohnungsbau: Lebenszyklus - Zertifizierungssysteme - Marktchangen*. Springer Vieweg.
- [5] Braun, H. P. (Ed.). (2013). *Facility Management: Erfolg in der Immobilienbewirtschaftung* (6. Aufl.). Springer Vieweg.
- [6] Adler, D., Wargan, P., & Prakash, S. (2019). *The Green New Deal for Europe: Blueprint for Europe's Just Transition* [Edition II]. <https://report.gndforeurope.com/cms/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/Blueprint-for-Europes-Just-Transition-2nd-Ed.pdf>
- [7] Kornyshova, E., Deneckère, R., Sadouki, K., Gressier-Soudan, E., & Brinkkemper, S. (2022). Smart Life: Review of the Contemporary Smart Applications. In R. Guizzardi, J. Ralyté, & X. Franch (Eds.), *Lecture Notes in Business Information Processing. Research Challenges in Information Science* (Vol. 446, pp. 302–318). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-05760-1_18
- [8] Gremmel-Simon, H., & E-Nova, I. K. (2017). *Zukunft der Gebäude? Vernetzt - digital - ökosozial : e-nova*, international conference 22. und 23. November 2018, Band 21. Science.Research.Pannonia
- [9] Noardo, F., Guler, D., Fauth, J., Malacarne, G., Mastrolembu Ventura, S., Azenha, M., Olsson, P.-O., & Senger, L. (2022). Unveiling the actual progress of Digital Building Permit: Getting awareness through a critical state of the art review. *Building and Environment*, 213, 108854. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.108854>
- [10] Mekki, K., Derigent, W., Rondeau, É., & Thomas, A. (2017). Data Lifecycle Management in Smart Building using Wireless Sensors Networks. *IFAC-PapersOnLine*, 50(1), 12944–12949. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ifacol.2017.08.1796>
- [11] Wildenauer, A. A. (2023). *Intelligent Data Structuring for Facility Management as Basis for Smart Applications* (67921) [PhD]. University of Economics and Business, Prague. https://vskp.vse.cz/english/87690_intelligent-data-structuring-for-facility-management-as-basis-for-smart-applications?author=Wildenauer&page=1
<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.32150.22083>
- [12] Flyvbjerg, B. (2021). *Make Megaprojects More Modular: Spotlight Series - Better Project*

Management. <https://hbr.org/2021/11/make-megaprojects-more-modular>

"STARTING WITH WHY": Shaping the future generation of planners by empowerment of necessary competences at universities to enable integral digital construction

Adrian Wildenauer^a, Katharina Lindenberg^a, Matias Penroz^a

^a *Institute for Digital Construction and Wood Industry, Bern University of Applied Science, Biel/Bienne, Switzerland*

The practical utilisation of theoretical knowledge and the development of the associated competencies is one of the indispensable tasks of practice-oriented universities in Switzerland. In a world of “data overload”, it is even more important to implement the basics of information materialisation. In this context, the competence of information materialisation is the ability to research in a targeted manner, to make a meaningful selection of information and to grasp the deeper meaning/relevance of information [1]. The use of Building Information Modelling (BIM) is seen as an enabler that can improve productivity of a construction project [2], but it leads to a considerable amount of data and information which needs to be handled and used for making the right decisions for the project. This approach must be learnt anew, especially with regard to the sustainability goals of national and international government initiatives, such as the European Green Deal or the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG).

The principles of the United Nations SDG are summarised in 17 goals that governments and government-related organisations shall implement to achieve the goals of sustainable stewardship of the planet (United Nations [UN], [3]). However, governments are not independent entities but rather individual organisations that are composed of individuals with individual competencies. In order to enable this information materialisation in the context of the SDGs, additional competencies are required, which are referred to in this context as "Inner Development Goals" (IDG). These are rarely taught by universities and, thus must be acquired independently by students. These IDG consist of “a framework of 23 specific inner qualities, abilities and skills, grouped in 5 dimensions, whose cultivation can help to build a sustainable future for people and planet and address adaptive challenges” based on the SDG. “The framework was developed by a team of thought leaders, experts and international researchers following extensive outreach consultation” [4].

The relevance of these competencies becomes particularly evident in the context of digital building permits, a critical period in the construction sector’s ability to address housing crises and contribute to the SDGs. The construction industry, a significant player in the realisation of sustainable living environments, faces a persistent challenge: the slow and often cumbersome process of obtaining building permits. This bottleneck not only delays construction projects but also discourages investment in housing from both private and public sector undermining efforts to resolve housing shortages and contribute to SDG goals like sustainable cities and communities (SDG11). Digital building permits, while a step towards streamlining this process, introduce new complexities that demand a workforce equipped with both technical know-how and a deep understanding of sustainable development principles. The IDGs, in this case, are not just educational tools but vital instruments for bridging the gap between the ambitious targets set by the SDGs and the practical realities of the construction sector.

Progressive universities no longer emphasise the mere transfer of knowledge, but also the empathic and social skills needed to work purposefully. The focus is no longer on theoretical knowledge alone [5], but on specific application across all project phases, including permits, which are often seen as a "black box" in the construction process; especially when it comes to

digital approvals and the new competences that are required from both sides: the approving persons and the submitting companies [6]. These competencies include dealing with complexity and its responding awareness, the associated critical thinking and dealing with communication in a digital context based on a long-term orientation and visioning while providing with comprehensive understanding of more technical skills to assess data overload and redundancy in complex processes.

This educational gap highlights the need for a revised pedagogical approach, particularly in fields such as digital construction and planning. The introduction of this framework into the educational system, especially in applied science universities, is a transformative step towards creating a workforce that is not only skilled in their respective fields but also conscious of their role in achieving the broader SDG objectives.

The Bern University of Applied Sciences (BFH), one of Switzerland's largest universities of applied sciences, employs a comprehensive methodology to enhance construction education by integrating targeted training in competencies essential for digital workflows within the construction value chain. This initiative aims to align participant's existing skills with the digital process requirements through holistic development processes and methods for ordering, producing, structuring, and validating data across the planning and execution phases of construction projects. Utilising Simon Sinek's Golden Circle theory [7], which emphasises understanding the "why" behind actions, the program fosters motivation and deeper comprehension among students, enabling them to develop not only inter- and transdisciplinary technical skills through real-case scenarios but also personal competencies in a self-driven environment. Furthermore, integrating Inner Development Goals (IDG) with Building Information Modeling (BIM) and integral planning methods marks a significant evolution in higher education, extending the learning scope beyond conventional technical training. This approach equips students with the technical proficiencies required for digital construction processes, alongside critical thinking, and social skills necessary to navigate the complexities of today's construction industry. Through this methodology, BFH aims to teach and implement competencies that surpass the individual's occupational profile, promoting a comprehensive understanding and application of these skills in real-world contexts.

Emphasising IDGs in conjunction with BIM indicates BFH's dedication to instilling a deep understanding and a purpose-driven mindset in students. This methodology aligns with international sustainability efforts, including the European Green Deal and the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals. These initiatives place students' education in the larger context of global environmental stewardship. By incorporating these aspirations into its curriculum, BFH prepares learners not just as competent professionals but as insightful, compassionate contributors to sustainable development.

This educational model, inspired by Sinek's Golden Circle, shifts the focus from simple knowledge transfer to a deeper exploration of the motivations behind design and construction processes. This shift is crucial at a time of significant digital advances, offering both opportunities and challenges. The curriculum's attention to issues ranging from digital building permits to all the necessary digital workflows prepares students to deal in depth with the complex and ethical aspects of their future fields. In this context, it is also necessary to start with the why: education is necessary to be able to provide the correct information in projects - but also in everyday personal life - in the ever-faster pace of digital change.

In conclusion, BFH's approach emerges as an innovative educational model apt for the digital era. Knowledge-based design should also be mentioned in this context, as the aim here is to be able to make correct and valid decisions based on all available information. It aims to cultivate a new group of construction professionals who are not only technically adept but also morally

aware and ready to make valuable contributions towards a sustainable future. This pioneering approach serves as a benchmark for educational institutions, underscoring the need for teaching strategies that adapt to the dynamic demands of our contemporary world.

References

- [1] Hartmann, W., & Hundertpfund, A. (2015). *Digitale Kompetenz: Was die Schule dazu beitragen kann* (1. Auflage, http://deposit.d-nb.de/cgi-bin/dokserv?id=5262015&prov=M&dok_var=1&dok_ext=htm). hep verlag.
- [2] Kim, K. P., Mostafa, S., & Park, K. S. (2022). Integrated BIM Education in Construction Project Management Program. In L. Tomei & F. G. Giuseffi (Eds.), *Advances in Educational Technologies and Instructional Design. Enhancing Teaching and Learning With Socratic Educational Strategies* (pp. 134–152). IGI Global. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-5225-8452-0.CH008>
- [3] United Nations. (2015). *The 17 Goals: Sustainable Development Goals*. United Nations (UN). <https://sdgs.un.org/goals>
- [4] Jurisic, N., Molund, T., Hjalmar Akerblad, J., Bakker, M., & et. al. (2023). *Orienting inner development in organisations: White Paper #1*. <https://www.innerdevelopmentgoals.org/resources>
- [5] Harty, C. (2008). Implementing innovation in construction: contexts, relative boundedness and actor-network theory. *Construction Management and Economics*, 26(10), 1029–1041. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01446190802298413>
- [6] Ullah, K., Raitviir, C., Lill, I., & Witt, E. (2020). BIM ADOPTION IN THE AEC/FM INDUSTRY – THE CASE FOR ISSUING BUILDING PERMITS. *International Journal of Strategic Property Management*, 24(6), 400–413. <https://doi.org/10.3846/ijspm.2020.13676>
- [7] Sinek, S. (2011). *Start With Why: How great leaders inspire everyone to take action*. Portfolio Penguin.

[A Call to Enhance the Digitalization of Building Permit Processing with Recognition-Primed Decision Making](#)

Peter Nørkjær Gade ^a

^a *Technology & Business, University College of Northern Denmark*

In the construction industry, the process of obtaining building permits is a cornerstone of ensuring safe, legal, and efficient use of land and resources. Building permits serve as a crucial checkpoint, aligning architectural designs with established building codes and urban planning principles. However, the journey to securing a building permit is often fraught with complexities and delays, posing significant challenges for designers and stakeholders alike [1,2]. As we convene at this conference, dedicated to unraveling the intricacies of building permit processes, it becomes imperative to address the underlying decision-making mechanisms that govern these processes. One of the less explored terrains in this field is the decision-making aspect of building permit processing. The issuance or denial of permits hinges on a series of decisions made by various authorities, often under constraints of time, information, and regulatory pressure. Designers, striving to create structures that are both innovative and compliant, frequently encounter roadblocks due to opaque or inefficient decision-making processes. This not only stifles architectural creativity but also can lead to a prolonged permit approval process, escalating costs, and potential legal entanglements [3].

The field of decision-making psychology offers valuable insights into how decisions are made in complex, uncertain environments. Central to this field is the Recognition-Primed Decision (RPD) model [4], which explains how experienced decision-makers use their knowledge and intuition to rapidly identify viable solutions in challenging situations. The RPD model suggests that effective decision-making, especially in high-stake and time-sensitive scenarios, relies more on the recognition of patterns and cues from experience than on methodical, analytical processing, see Fig 1. This perspective could be particularly enlightening in the context of building permit processing, a domain where decisions are made under varying degrees of uncertainty and pressure.

Fig. 1: A simplified representation of the RPD model, adapted from Klein 2009 [5]

The RPD model, as outlined by Klein [6], provides a comprehensive framework for understanding decision-making in naturalistic settings. The RPD model emphasizes the integration of three critical elements: perception of the situation, knowledge about the situation, and knowledge about potential actions. At the heart of this model lies the concept of pattern recognition, which is pivotal in decision-making processes. This model posits that human expertise is key to recognizing patterns within the available information for a specific situation, thereby facilitating accurate situational diagnosis. Expert pattern recognition is crucial; without it, the decision-making process is compromised, characterized by poor diagnosis, weak linkage between situation and action, and an inability to identify appropriate actions.

A situation is influenced by several factors: the goals of the decision maker, the identification of critical cues, expectations regarding the evolution of the situation, and typical actions pertinent to such scenarios. Situational patterns are composed of relevant cues that are interconnected through conditional, causal, or temporal relationships, reflecting goals, constraints, and expectations. These patterns form an integral part of the planner's knowledge base and are essential to their expertise. Within the RPD framework, planners utilize these patterns to pinpoint critical system states and simplify the system's complexity to a manageable number of cues. This simplification enables the recognition of prototypical situations. Consequently, non-algorithmic decision-making in planning and permitting processes hinges on a pattern matching process. In this process, current information is juxtaposed with stored patterns in the planner's knowledge base, facilitating the immediate retrieval of a potential course of action. A decision is then reached when the preferred course of action is confirmed through mental simulation, namely the cognitive anticipation of the potential consequences of a decision.

Applying the RPD model to the realm of building permit decision-making presents a promising avenue for improvement. The model's emphasis on experience-based recognition and intuitive judgment can streamline decision-making processes, reducing delays and increasing efficiency. For designers, an understanding of how permit authorities make decisions can guide the creation of designs that better align with legal and regulatory expectations, reducing the likelihood of permit denial. For instance, consider a scenario where a building authority is evaluating a complex design proposal. Utilizing the RPD model, the decision-maker can rapidly assess the design based on accumulated experience and recognized patterns, leading to a quicker and more informed decision. This approach contrasts sharply with a purely analytical model that might require extensive time and resources, often leading to bottlenecks in the permit approval process.

The RPD model's integration into building permit decision-making can serve as a catalyst for more responsive and adaptive processes, benefiting both the authorities and the designers. The RPD model is based on the idea that experienced professionals can make rapid, yet effective decisions by recognizing patterns that they have encountered before. In the context of building permits, this means that officials can draw on their past experiences with similar cases to make quicker and more informed decisions. The RPD model does not disregard analytical thinking but integrates it with intuitive judgment [7]. This hybrid approach is particularly beneficial in the building permit process, where decisions often involve both interpreting technical details and considering broader urban planning principles. Moreover, it can assist in improving consistency and reducing bias by formalizing the intuitive decision-making process through the RPD model, decision-makers can become more aware of their thought processes. This awareness can help in identifying and mitigating problematic biases, leading to more consistent and fair decisions.

Implementing RPD in training programs for officials involved in building permit processing can cultivate a more structured approach to decision-making. Moreover, by aligning decision-making practices with the intuitive and experience-based principles of the RPD model, there is potential to foster a more collaborative environment. Designers could receive more immediate and

context-relevant feedback, allowing for iterative improvements in design that comply with legal standards without compromising creative integrity. This synergy between psychological insight and practical application could redefine the dynamics of building permit processing, setting a new standard for efficiency and effectiveness. Despite its potential, the application of decision-making psychology, particularly the RPD model, in the context of building permit processing remains markedly underexplored. Current research predominantly focuses on the technical, bureaucratic, and regulatory aspects of the process, with less attention paid to the cognitive and psychological mechanisms underpinning decision-making. This gap signifies a critical missed opportunity for innovation and improvement in this field.

This abstract opens dialogue to accomplish several key objectives. Firstly, it aims to elucidate the decision-making processes involved in building permit approval, grounded in the principles of psychological decision-making theories like the RPD model. Secondly, it endeavors to explore how these insights can be applied to enhance the efficiency of permit processing and the compliance of designs with building laws. Finally, it intends to open a dialogue for further interdisciplinary research, combining psychological theories with urban planning, architectural practices, and also new technological perspectives. The integration of rule checking systems in building permit processes, aligned with the RPD model, represents a significant advancement. Rule checking, an automated process that verifies compliance with established codes and regulations, can be effectively combined with the experiential and intuitive decision-making approach of the RPD model.

In practice, this means leveraging automated systems to scrutinize building permit applications against a comprehensive database of zoning laws, safety regulations, and urban planning guidelines. This method facilitates a potential to rapid identification of compliance issues and potential red flags, enabling decision-makers to focus their attention on areas that require nuanced judgment and expertise. By marrying the efficiency of rule checking with the seasoned intuition emphasized by the RPD model, the building permit process can potentially become more streamlined, accurate, and consistent, thereby reducing the problematic subjectivity and variability often associated with these decisions.

Moreover, the application of Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning technologies to enhance decision-making in building permit processing aligns with the principles of the RPD model. AI and ML algorithms, particularly those specializing in pattern recognition, can be trained on extensive historical data pertaining to building permit decisions. Such systems can identify complex patterns and anomalies that might not be immediately apparent to human reviewers, thus complementing the rule-checking process. This capability is particularly beneficial in the context of the RPD model, which values the use of experience and intuition in decision-making. By providing decision-makers with AI-driven insights, which mirror the depth and nuance of experiential intuition, the decision-making process can become more efficient and informed.

This integration of technology with cognitive principles can potentially enhance the ability of officials to make balanced, well-informed decisions that are both compliant with regulations and sympathetic to the practicalities of urban development using technology and assist in developing better technology. The synergistic application of AI-driven pattern recognition and rule checking within the framework of the RPD model offers a new paradigm in building permit decision-making. This approach not only streamlines the process of checking compliance with building codes and regulations but also adds a layer of sophisticated analytical capability, enhancing the decision-makers' ability to handle complex and ambiguous cases. The incorporation of these technological solutions within the RPD framework allows for a more adaptive, responsive, and accurate decision-making process. Decision-makers are equipped to rapidly identify key issues and make informed decisions based on a combination of rule-based compliance checks and nuanced understanding derived from pattern recognition and past experiences. This integration

signifies a move towards a more advanced, efficient, and reliable building permit process, where decisions are grounded in a robust blend of empirical data, technological innovation, and cognitive expertise.

An integral component of this exploration is the Level of Information Need (LoIN), which plays a pivotal role in the seamless integration of Building Information Modelling (BIM) and Geographic Information Systems (GIS) within the building permit process. Defined by standards such as EN ISO 19650 and BS EN 17412-1, LoIN specifies the detail and precision of data required at different stages of the construction process, ensuring decision-makers have access to essential information. LoIN can enhance the evaluation of complex designs and their compliance with urban planning constraints, thereby streamlining decision-making in building permit approvals. Distinguishing this paper from existing literature, we provide a nuanced analysis of building permit decision-making through the RPD model, emphasizing the innovative integration of LoIN within a BIM-GIS environment. Unlike previous research focusing primarily on the bureaucratic and regulatory facets of permit processing, our interdisciplinary approach sheds light on the cognitive and psychological aspects underpinning decision-making, offering fresh insights into optimizing building permit processes.

Furthermore, our methodology includes a comprehensive examination of how building permit requirements are identified whether through manual interpretation of bylaws or the involvement of governmental bodies and automated tools. This clarification enhances understanding of the research approach, highlighting the potential for technology to improve the accuracy and efficiency of identifying compliance requirements. Lastly, our discussion extends to the significance of semantic requirements in the context of BIM-models. While geometric requirements are often emphasized, recognizing, and identifying semantic requirements—relating to the meaning and context of building elements and spaces—is critical. Addressing both semantic and geometrical requirements can lead to more comprehensive and automated review processes, facilitating a deeper understanding of design proposals and enhancing the efficiency of building permit processes.

Lastly, this is a call to all interested parties in opening a novel field of research within the domain of digital enhanced decision-making, not only in the domain of building permits but in general, as it constitutes an under researched field with much potential to improve how users of technology in the construction industry implement existing technologies, but also improve how we think about the users and their practices when we develop solutions that are meant for improvement. Currently, research is underway, in validating how RPD-model can enhance users decision-making in regards to circular design of buildings.

References

- [1] Fauth, J. (2021), “Building permit process modeling”, *EWork EBusiness Archit. Eng. Constr*, Vol. 13, pp. 42–50.
- [2] Noardo, F., Ellul, C., Harrie, L., Overland, I., Shariat, M., Arroyo Ogori, K. and Stoter, J. (2020), “Opportunities and challenges for GeoBIM in Europe: developing a building permits use-case to raise awareness and examine technical interoperability challenges”, *Journal of Spatial Science*, Taylor & Francis, Vol. 65 No. 2, pp. 209–233.
- [3] Wold, J., Lædre, O. and Lohne, J. (2019), “Questionable practice in the processing of building permits in Norway”, *27th Annual Conference of the International Group for Lean Construction, IGLC 2019*, No. July, pp. 1151–1162.
- [4] Klein, G.A., Orasanu, J., Calderwood, R. and Zsombok, C.E. (1992), *DECISION MAKING IN ACTION: MODELS AND METHODS*, New Jersey.
- [5] Gasser, R., Fischer, K. and Wäfler, T. (2011), “Decision Making in Planning and Scheduling: A Field

Study of Planning Behaviour in Manufacturing Roland”, in Fransoo, J.C., Wäfler, T. and Wilson, J.R. (Eds.), Behavioral Operations in Planning and Scheduling, Springer-Verlag, Berlin Heidelberg, pp. 1–471.

- [6] Klein, G.A. (2017), Sources of Power: How People Make Decisions, MIT press, available at:<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/11307.001.0001>.
- [7] Kahneman, D. and Klein, G. (2009), “Conditions for Intuitive Expertise: A Failure to Disagree”, American Psychologist, Vol. 64 No. 6, pp. 515–526.

Towards automated building lifecycle assessment calculation

Petr Hradil^a, Rita Lavikka^a, Tarja Mäkeläinen^a

^a VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, P.O. Box 1000, FI-02044 VTT, Finland

Introduction

Building information modelling (BIM) is being increasingly adopted in building permit processes [1-2]. At the same time, countries are announcing compulsory climate declarations, mostly based on the building lifecycle assessment (LCA) [3-4]. For example, Finland will require such climate declaration and the use of BIM when applying for a building permit starting in 2025. These new requirements may burden the design offices, especially the small ones, without dedicated LCA and BIM experts and access to the relevant tools and databases. Hence, a national construction emission database was created [5] to support this transition and harmonise Finland's LCA reporting. Also, limits for the buildings' carbon footprint will be introduced in the following years.

LCA calculation is a complex and time-consuming task due to the large amount of information being processed. The work requires deep knowledge of processes involved in the lifecycle of the studied system, ability to model such processes, extract quantities from the system's documentation and match each material or product flow to its emission data, which can be in various databases. An LCA expert is usually needed to analyse and interpret the results. Building LCA is typically performed on a standardised modular system described in [6]. Therefore, only quantity take-off and assignment of the materials to the impact categories are needed. The results depend on the quality of the assessment tool [7]. During the early building permit phase, the architectural BIM model is on a rougher detail level, usually without product and material information. Thus, transparency of the building LCA methodology used is needed to trace the origin and purpose of the calculation outcomes because the accuracy and reliability of the results may not be sufficient for the other purposes.

Research on BIM-based LCA has generally increased over the past ten years [8-9]. Integrating BIM and LCA is expected to reduce manual work and time used for the LCA calculation and reduce embodied emissions during the design phase [9-10]. However, difficulties exist in performing an accurate building LCA based on BIM due to the quality of BIM models and interoperability between BIM tools and LCA tools [11].

Currently, BIM is mainly used to generate a bill of materials. This information is then entered into LCA software, where the materials are usually matched with their emission data either manually or semi-automatically [12]. Native BIM software can also include a plugin for emission databases, but no automatic process for BIM-based building LCA exists up to date, although the data operations performed during LCA can already be automated. Thus, this study aims to advance the automation of BIM-based building LCA. The final goal is to reduce building permit applicants' and permit authorities' resources needed for estimating the environmental impacts of planned buildings. Moreover, the findings will support software developers of the LCA services related to building permitting.

Methodology

This study developed a proof-of-concept (PoC) tool for automating the calculation of building LCA in the Finnish context [13]. The PoC is used to study the modelling requirements for further

automation of building LCA based on BIM. Two workshops were organised in 2023 to get feedback on the PoC and we are planning to communicate with the developers of the Finnish national construction emissions database and with CEN/TC350 concerning the interpretation of the environmental data.

Calculation process

The tool automatically extracts the information from the IFC model and relevant environmental databases, combines them and generates the report without user interaction. Therefore, the process is designed to overcome barriers caused by insufficient or mismatched data in the model and/or databases by automatically generating conservative assumptions and providing feedback to the designer about the parts of the model that can be improved. Additional barriers may still arise because of the ongoing development of the Finnish regulation and IFC requirements. If we can provide automated conservative solutions for all such potential problems, the PoC tool would demonstrate the ability of such a service to run on the background of the building permitting platform.

General modelling principles

According to the current Finnish proposal for the Climate Declaration Decree, the global warming potential (GWP) of the building site and the building shall be provided separately in kgCO₂eq per square meter of heated floor area of the building or its part with a specific use category and per year of the assessment. The carbon footprint is divided into Modules A to C following the principles of EN 15978 (see the attachment Table 1). It should be noted that only selected parts of Module B are considered, and the additional impacts beyond the system boundary (called carbon handprint in the Decree) shall be reported separately as Modules D1 to D6 [14]. These additional impacts are not consistent with any standard methodology. The specific modelling requirements are listed in the attachment Table 2.

Findings and discussion

Data quality

While developing and testing the PoC tool, we discovered several substantial challenges related to the quality of the model data or records in the environmental databases. In addressing the challenges, we followed two basic principles: (1) The calculation shall be fully automated and (2) in the case of any uncertainties, the most conservative results shall be produced.

- ◆ Selection of appropriate entities: The environmental impact of the building is typically calculated using all the model data (e.g., all the entities represented by 3D geometry), but some exceptions may apply. For instance, the building regulation restricts the LCA calculation only to certain product groups. It is therefore necessary to provide such a model, where it is possible to identify such products according to their IFC class, predefined type, or any other identifier in the linked property sets. The conservative approach is to calculate the impact of each entity unless it can be explicitly excluded from the assessment.

Table 1. Lifecycle stages covered by different data sources.

Reporting category	Carbon footprint									Carbon handprint					
Building lifecycle stage	Product	Construction process		Use		End of life				Potential benefits and loads					
Modules required in the Decree	A1-A3	A4	A5	B4	B6	C1	C2	C3	C4	D1	D2	D3	D4	D5	D6
Modules description	Raw material supply Transport to manufacturing Manufacturing	Transport to construction site	Construction installation process	Replacement	Use of energy	Deconstruction	Transport	Waste processing	Disposal	Material recovery, reuse and recycling	Energy recovery	Export of renewable energy	Carbon storage in the products	Carbonation potential	Planted trees
Relevant data in the national construction emissions database co2data.fi.	Product level and building level (services), biogenic and conservative values are provided separately	Product level or building level, same value as Module C2.	Building level, construction and earthwork values are provided separately	Building level, values are combined for B3-4 stages	Building level, values are separated by energy source	Building level	Building level	Product level, biogenic values are provided separately	Product level	Product level					

Table 2. Modelling requirements for the Finnish Climate Declaration

<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">General principles</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ All rooms should have space modelled as an IfcSpace element. ◆ All spaces should have net floor area declared. ◆ All spaces shall have an indication if they are heated. Note: If the heating is not declared, the space may be considered unheated, resulting in higher impacts per square meter of heated floor area. ◆ All spaces shall have an indication of whether they are new, renovated, or old. Note: Only new and renovated spaces are considered for climate declaration. ◆ All elements should have material and net volume declared. ◆ Building use name and/or category shall be declared in the IfcBuilding element. Alternatively, the use can be declared in IfcSpace or its aggregation (e.g. IfcZone or IfcStorey) in multi-use buildings. ◆ The area of the building site shall be provided. ◆ Earthwork is calculated as general impact per square meter (co2data.fi) and is not to be modelled. ◆ Building services are calculated as general impact per square meter (co2data.fi) and are not to be modelled.
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Material identification</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Each material should have a unique name and/or identifier that can be recognised in the lifecycle database(s) used in the LCA calculation. Note: For the materials not recognised in the database(s), conservative LCA values may be used. ◆ When using Environmental Product Declaration (EPD), material identification shall contain UUID and may contain the URL of the specific ILCD+EPD database to be used in LCA calculation. Alternatively, the exact name of the ILCD+EPD process can be provided together with the relevant database URL.
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Information needed but not necessarily in IFC</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Permanent building identification number ◆ Planned number of occupants/users of the building. ◆ Calculated energy consumption of the building separated by energy source. ◆ Length of the assessment period used. ◆ The main construction material of the load-bearing structures included in the assessment. ◆ Target lifetime of the building.
<p style="writing-mode: vertical-rl; transform: rotate(180deg);">Elements to be included in the model</p>	<p>Building site:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Ground and external structures and supports ◆ Surface materials of the site ◆ Foundations <p>Building:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ◆ Building frame and roof structures including basements ◆ Floors, ceilings, walls with surface treatments ◆ External walls and partitions, including doors, windows and stairs ◆ Terraces and balconies ◆ Space equipment (fixtures, kitchen appliances) ◆ Chimneys and fireplaces ◆ Space elements (e.g. bathroom modules) ◆ Main components of the heating, water supply, sewerage air conditioning, cooling, fire protection and power systems ◆ Lifts and escalators

- ◆ Missing information about the material: In certain cases, the entities may not have associated materials, or the material names may be ambiguous (“Undefined”, “Default” etc.). The tool assumes conservative values of CO₂ emissions for such entities as the highest possible value in the database for a certain product class.
- ◆ Material not matching the records in the environmental database: In common design practice, the only information about the material in the permitting phase is its name assigned by the designer, the BIM authoring tool, or its template. This name is typically not pointing directly to any specific record in the environmental database. The PoC tool, therefore, uses an extensive mapping dictionary of common material names linked to the Finnish national database. If the material name is not in the dictionary, the tool automatically uses conservative emissions for this material. It should be noted that the Finnish national database is not harmonised with any standard classification system, although it contains some references to the Finnish TALO2000 classification [15].
- ◆ Missing information about the quantities: Environmental data is typically related to a certain unit flow, for instance, mass, volume, surface area or just the number of products. The relevant quantities must be recognisable from the model. The PoC tool mainly relies on IFC BaseQuantities, but if the information is not found in the model, a thorough search of all element properties is performed. The last option is to calculate the quantities directly from the model geometry to ensure that a conservative result is delivered in any situation. The PoC tool uses only bounding boxes of the elements to optimise the performance of the calculation, but other methods (such as tetrahedral meshing) are also possible, if they return conservative results.
- ◆ Missing entities: In the permitting stage, verifying if the designer provided digital model of all components required for the compliance check is impossible. Therefore, in this case, the PoC tool cannot guarantee the conservativeness of the calculated results. Therefore, it is recommended to repeat the LCA assessment using as-built building information data, at least when such a shortcoming is discovered.

Feedback to the designer

The automated LCA tool cannot provide accurate outputs without user interaction but may be configured to return a conservative impact estimation. This value may be sufficient for reaching regulatory limits in some cases, but the designer may need to resubmit an improved model if the estimation is too high.

For this purpose, the PoC tool provides a detailed calculation log and overall feedback information package about the problematic entities and materials.

Conclusions

This study provides an understanding of opportunities and challenges for automating BIM-based building LCA calculations. The presented PoC tool is developed to meet the anticipated requirements of the upcoming Finnish regulations [14], and therefore it would need adjustments to be used in a different context. The environmental data format is compatible with the Swedish and future Estonian databases. Currently, there is on-going discussion on real-world implementation demonstration with partners of ACCORD project, Solibri, Cloud Permit and Future Insight.

Acknowledgements

This study was supported by ACCORD project. This project has received funding from the European Commission’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Programme under grant

agreement No 101056973, and UKRI grants No 10040207, 10038999 and 10049977. The information and views expressed lie entirely with the authors. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

References

- [1] Ullah, K., Raitviir, C., Lill, I., & Witt, E. (2020). BIM adoption in the AEC/FM industry – The case for issuing building permits. *International Journal of Strategic Property Management*, 26(4), 400–413. <https://doi.org/10.3846/ijspm.2020.13676>
- [2] Ullah, K., Witt, E., & Lill, I. (2022). The BIM-based building permit process: Factors affecting adoption. *Buildings*, 12(45). <https://doi.org/10.3390>
- [3] Malabi Eberhardt, L. C., Kuittinen, M., Häkkinen, T., Moinel, C., Nibel, S., & Birgisdottir, H. (2023). Carbon handprint – a review of potential climate benefits of buildings. *Building Research & Information*, 1–16. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613218.2023.2266020>
- [4] von Malmborg, F., Rohdin, P., & Wihlborg, E. (2023). Climate declarations for buildings as a new policy instrument in Sweden: a multiple streams perspective. *Building Research and Information*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613218.2023.2222320>
- [5] The Finnish Environment Institute. (2023, December). Emission data for construction products, processes, and services. <https://co2data.fi/>.
- [6] EN 15978. (2011). CEN EN15978:2011 Sustainability of construction works - Assessment of environmental performance of buildings - Calculation method. CEN.
- [7] Hollberg, A., Genova, G., & Habert, G. (2020). Evaluation of BIM-based LCA results for building design. *Automation in Construction*, 109. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2019.102972>
- [8] Najjar, M., Figueiredo, K., Palumbo, M., & Haddad, A. (2017). Integration of BIM and LCA: Evaluating the environmental impacts of building materials at an early stage of designing a typical office building. *Journal of Building Engineering*, 14, 115–126. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2017.10.005>
- [9] Nizam, R. S., Zhang, C., & Tian, L. (2018). A BIM based tool for assessing embodied energy for buildings. *Energy and Buildings*, 170, 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2018.03.067>
- [10] Meex, E., Hollberg, A., Knapen, E., Hildebrand, L., & Verbeeck, G. (2018). Requirements for applying LCA-based environmental impact assessment tools in the early stages of building design. *Building and Environment*, 133, 228–236. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2018.02.016>
- [11] Soust-Verdaguer, B., Llatas, C., & García-Martínez, A. (2017). Critical review of bim-based LCA method to buildings. In *Energy and Buildings* (Vol. 136, pp. 110–120). Elsevier Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2016.12.009>
- [12] Santos, R., Costa, A. A., Silvestre, J. D., & Pyl, L. (2019). Integration of LCA and LCC analysis within a BIM-based environment. *Automation in Construction*, 103, 127–149. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2019.02.011>
- [13] Hradil, P. (2023). AC(CO2)RD tool (<https://extgit.vtt.fi/petr.hradil/ac-co2-rd>). VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland.
- [14] Finnish Ministry of the Environment (2019) Matti Kuittinen (ed). Method for the whole life carbon assessment of buildings. Publications of the Ministry of the Environment 2019:22 <http://urn.fi/URN:ISBN:978-952-361-029-3>.
- [15] Rakennustieto. (2000). The Finnish Construction 2000 classification system https://tiedostot.rakennustieto.fi/The_Finnish_Construction_2000_classification_system.pdf. <https://www.rakennustieto.fi/nimikkeistot/talo-2000-nimikkeistot>.

A Maturity Model for Digital Building Permit: a path towards the digital transition

Mariana Ataide ^a, Orjola Braholli ^a, Francesca Noardo ^b, Dietmar Siegele ^a

^a *Fraunhofer Italia, Via A. Volta 13a, 39100 Bolzano*

^b *Open Geospatial Consortium, Technologielaan 3, B - 3001 Heverlee
Belgium*

Building permits ensure construction complies with building codes and urban regulations, but the traditional paper-based permitting workflows are often inefficient, non-transparent, overly complex, and prone to errors [1]. The digital transformation of building permit systems promises improved quality, transparency, and efficiency [2]. However, the process, involving building authorities, landowners, designers, constructors, and various other stakeholders - each of them with their procedures and methods - often falls short of adapting their own practices to an up-to-date technology, and taking advantage of potential benefits. There is a distinct lack of transparent communication, standardised data and procedures, besides data sharing and interoperability issues throughout the process.

Going from a paper-based or early digital (for instance the use of PDF documents) to a fully digitalised system is not a simple transition. It requires a holistic change encompassing process and information digitalisation, automation, systems integration, in addition to legal and organisational adaptation. To integrate the new technological methods and tools, organisations must assume a clear path to plan the implementation. Organisations should be supported in achieving their desired level of digitalisation, based on their current state, by providing them with a reference matrix that outlines the maturity scale for each aspect of the involved system, such as technology, information, organisation, and process. There are existing frameworks that evaluate the adoption of BIM or GIS [3–6]. However, maturity models currently lack customised focus on complete regulatory approval workflows. With wide variance across municipalities, structured methodologies are needed to assess readiness and guide staged advancement towards integrated digital permitting ecosystems.

Most maturity models available in literature concentrate on individual technologies, components, or dimensions rather than taking an universal view of the process digitalisation and organisational change management required for complete transformation [7–10]. Furthermore, there is a need for tailored evaluation methods and tools to weigh building permit procedures and assist in the gradual enhancement of digitalisation processes and systems.

Additionally, the literature highlights that most digital building permit implementations are still in their early digital stages, with a focus on document management and model rule-checking, while some few leading cities have tested more advanced capabilities [11]. Nevertheless, mainstream adoption still lags the visionary potential for end-to-end integration. Though automating discrete permitting phases shows benefits, challenges persist in devising interconnective frameworks, ecosystems, and strategic roadmaps for the full digital process transformation. Therefore, a maturity assessment methodology tailored to the nuances and goals of digital building permit transformation could provide invaluable implementation guidance for building authorities navigating this complex transition.

This study is guided by two central questions that emerge from the current body of literature. First, how can municipalities and other organisations involved in the building permitting process accurately assess their existing maturity across key dimensions such as procedural,

technological, organisational, and data structural? Second, how can these institutions leverage such assessments to devise strategic roadmaps that incrementally guide them towards the target future vision for digital transformation?

To answer the research questions, the present study defines the CHEK Digital Building Permit Maturity Model (CDBPMM) [12], which was developed as part of the “Change toolkit for Digital Building Permit” (CHEK)²¹ Horizon project, aimed at digitalising building permits. The maturity model was developed through a comprehensive approach integrating insights from multiple existing maturity models across various domain areas, academic literature on BIM, GIS and digital permitting procedures, and consultation with building permit and BIM/GIS experts. This knowledge was cross-referenced with the objectives based on a fully automated digital building permit process [13]²² synthesizing the CDBPMM. The roadmap was drafted using the maturity model, by formulating actions linked to each key maturity area to progress from one level of maturity to another. The tiers are dependent within each category. This approach enables an assessment of the current maturity status and identification of the targeted level, facilitating the formulation of a plan detailing actionable steps necessary to reach the desired level of maturity.

The CDBPMM comprises 35 key maturity areas (KMAs) spanning four categories - Process, Organisation, Technology, and Information (Fig. 1). Each KMA is assessed on a zero to five scale across six levels. The levels of maturity for each KMA evolve from Level 0- Non-Existent, where that capability does not currently exist in the organisation, indicating a complete lack of digital maturity; to Level 5 - Optimised/Automated, where the capability has full integration, automation, analytics-driven improvement, and strategic alignment. This last level is often envisaging some progress that might be done in the future and might be not achievable yet.

“Process” category refers to the procedures, workflows, and general approach digital management of the building permit process. Its 8 KMAs analyse the maturity of: permit workflow steps; the level of workflow automation and integration; optimisation aspects like benchmarks, response times, and process standardisation. Improved process maturity reflects more streamlined, standardised permitting enabled by data technologies.

“Organisation” category evaluates the structural readiness of the municipal body for adopting data-driven digital permitting. Its 9 KMAs examine: leadership vision, planning and governance for change adoption; staff knowledge, training, and internal collaboration to develop needed skills; and external ecosystem alignment across partners. Higher organisational maturity entails having the institutional support, workforce capabilities, and a cultural environment to transform traditional workflows.

“Technology” category deals with implementation and integration of core systems functionality enabling automated information flows for permitting decisions. Its 12 KMAs evaluate the maturity of: software infrastructure, tools and platforms availability; extent of systems interoperability and data exchange; and cybersecurity. Higher technology maturity means having robust, secured IT infrastructure fully in place to enable seamless digital regulatory workflows, likely interconnected within a flexible and interoperable distributed software ecosystem.

Finally, “Information” category focuses on data and metadata availability, standardisation, quality, analytics, and sharing capabilities required to make sound digital permitting determinations. Its 6 KMAs assess the maturity of: open data access frameworks across the workflow; breadth of real-time data; use of common standards ensuring compliance to Findability Accessibility Interoperability and Reusability (FAIR) principles [14].

²¹ Available at: <https://chekdbp.eu>

²² Available at: https://chekdbp.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/04/D1.1_CHEK_101058559_CHEK-DBP-process-map_V1.0-Final.pdf

CATEGORY	CAPABILITY SETS	KEY MATURITY AREAS
1. PROCESS	1.1 Process and Methods	1.1.1 Understanding of the process and mapping of steps
		1.1.2 Stakeholders are aware of process steps and required information they must provide
	1.2 Regulatory	1.2.3 Benchmarks and key performance indicators
		1.2.4 Standardised process
		1.2.5 Data templates, use of common data formats, and documentation requirements
	1.3 Procedure	1.3.6 Timelines and response time
		1.3.7 Accessibility of stakeholders
		1.3.8 Transparency
2. ORGANIZATION	2.4 Readiness for changes	2.4.9 Internal staff
		2.4.10 Higher management
		2.4.11 Infrastructure
		2.4.12 Legislative system
	2.5 Organizational structure of units	2.5.13 Strategic objectives for data ecosystem implementation
		2.5.14 Dedicated personnel
	2.6 Social aspect	2.5.15 Training, preparation and support
		2.6.16 Overall knowledge of technicians
3. TECHNOLOGY	3.7 Technology for data management	2.6.17 Stakeholders' knowledge
		3.7.18 Data management environment and network platform
		3.7.19 Data storage/ repository
	3.8 Technology for data analysis	3.7.20 Submission system and identification (eg. electronic signature)
		3.7.21 Communication system
		3.8.22 Verification of procedural data
		3.8.23 Data inspection and visualisation
		3.8.24 Data validation for building data
		3.8.25 Data validation for geospatial data
	3.9 Interoperability and open format	3.8.26 Content analyser and Regulations' Checking tool
3.9.27 Data format interoperability		
4. INFORMATION	4.10 Data standardisation and quality	3.9.28 Building data to geospatial data (eg. BIM to GIS)
		3.9.29 Geospatial data to building data (eg. GIS to BIM)
	4.11 Data and information	4.10.30 Data standards and guidelines
		4.10.31 Data quality control
	4.12 Codes and regulation	4.11.32 Building/intervention design data
		4.11.33 City context data
		4.12.34 Regulations formats
	4.12.35 Regulations accessibility	

Fig. 1: CDBPMM structure and key maturity areas.

The assessment by means of the maturity model allows for the definition of a structured roadmap. The roadmap outlines a strategic action plan for advancing through the maturity model by targeting foundational capabilities first to enable subsequent progression. It leverages mapped dependencies between key maturity areas (KMAs) - where advancement of certain KMAs relies on attaining maturity in their prerequisites. By linking these relationships, the roadmap strings together a logical order for maturing capabilities across the maturity model categories (Fig.2).

Fig.2: Dependencies between KMA's of the maturity model.

The roadmap provides guidance on specific actions needed to achieve higher KMA target maturity levels based on an organisation's priorities. It presents a clear progression plan tailored to the organisation's context, assisting local municipalities in navigating the challenges of multifaceted digital transformation. As lessons are incorporated, the roadmap and model improve decision-making support for strategic capability building.

This research presents the customised CDBMM and Roadmap, providing municipalities with a comprehensive approach to identify current weaknesses, define objectives, and establish a strategic plan for their permitting system. By revealing critical gaps and outlining development pathways, municipalities can realise the extensive quality, efficiency, and transparency gains promised by integrated digital permitting.

The frameworks' significance rests in enabling cities to kick-start their improvement efforts by means of self-assessment, while guiding them through the complex changes involved in the digital transformation via a simple and clear tool, which is accessible also to non-experts and is granular enough to allow planning small feasible steps to reach tangible outcomes. With constant technological change, the maturity model undertakes continual recalibration and configuration support so building authorities can adapt emerging best practices. As digital transformation penetrates permitting ecosystems, this research empowers stakeholders to gain a strategic vantage point in navigating the path ahead.

For future work, besides further testing the tool in the CHEK project and via the CHEK Community of Practice²³, a tool will be developed by combining the CDBPMM and roadmap: the “CHEK change management virtual assistant”. This tool will help municipalities and organisations to assess autonomously how mature their processes are and develop strategies for navigating the digital transformation. By identifying gaps in key areas and assessing how different regulatory approval components should mature, as well as providing advice and instruments (primarily derived from the CHEK results) to support each step, to empower cities on designing specific plans to improve the assessment, quality, efficiency, and transparency of their building permitting systems.

²³ Available at: https://chekdbp.eu/?page_id=5734

Acknowledgements

This study was developed within the ‘CHEK – Change toolkit for digital building permit’ project, funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe programme under G.A. No.101058559.

References

- [1] K. Ullah, C. Raitviir, I. Lill, E. Witt, BIM ADOPTION IN THE AEC/FM INDUSTRY – THE CASE FOR ISSUING BUILDING PERMITS, *Int. J. Strateg. Prop. Manag.* 24 (2020) 400–413. <https://doi.org/10.3846/ijspm.2020.13676>.
- [2] F. Noardo, T. Wu, K. Arroyo Ohori, T. Krijnen, H. Tezerdi, J. Stoter, GEOBIM FOR DIGITAL BUILDING PERMIT PROCESS: LEARNING FROM A CASE STUDY IN ROTTERDAM, *ISPRS Ann. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spat. Inf. Sci.* VI-4/W1-2020 (2020) 151–158. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-annals-VI-4-W1-2020-151-2020>.
- [3] B. Succar, Building Information Modelling Maturity Matrix, in: J. Underwood, U. Isikdag (Eds.), *Handb. Res. Build. Inf. Model. Constr. Inform. Concepts Technol.*, IGI Global, Hershey, PA, 2010: pp. 65–103. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-60566-928-1>.
- [4] URISA, GIS CAPABILITY MATURITY MODEL, (2013).
- [5] C. Wu, B. Xu, C. Mao, X. Li, Overview of BIM maturity measurement tools, *J. Inf. Technol. Constr.* 22 (2017) 34–62. <https://www.itcon.org/2017/3>.
- [6] K. Ullah, E. Witt, I. Lill, The BIM-Based Building Permit Process: Factors Affecting Adoption, *Buildings* 12 (2022) 45. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12010045>.
- [7] O. Alrwais, T. Horan, B. Hilton, Evaluating Local Government Usage of GIS: A New Maturity Model, in: 2015 Proc. 5, Association for Information Systems AIS Electronic Library (AISel), Fort Worth, 2015. <http://aisel.aisnet.org/siggis2015/5>.
- [8] C. Sun, H. Chen, R. Long, R. Liao, Research on BIM Application Two-Dimensional Maturity Model, *Buildings* 12 (2022) 1960. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12111960>.
- [9] G. Yilmaz, A. Akcamete, O. Demirors, BIM-CAREM: Assessing the BIM capabilities of design, construction and facilities management processes in the construction industry, *Comput. Ind.* 147 (2023) 103861. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compind.2023.103861>.
- [10] Z.-S. Chen, M.-D. Zhou, K.-S. Chin, A. Darko, X.-J. Wang, W. Pedrycz, Optimized decision support for BIM maturity assessment, *Autom. Constr.* 149 (2023) 104808. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2023.104808>.
- [11] M. Ataide, O. Braholli, D. Siegele, Digital Transformation of Building Permits: Current Status, Maturity, and Future Prospects, *Buildings* 13 (2023) 2554. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13102554>.
- [12] M. Ataide, O. Braholli, D. Siegele, CHEK - Maturity model for digital building process, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.10277474>.
- [13] O. Braholli, M. Ataide, I. Di Blasio, K. Raj, D. Siegele, CHEK To-be Digital Building Permit process map, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7789035>.
- [14] M.D. Wilkinson, M. Dumontier, Ij.J. Aalbersberg, G. Appleton, M. Axton, A. Baak, N. Blomberg, J.-W. Boiten, L.B. da Silva Santos, P.E. Bourne, J. Bouwman, A.J. Brookes, T. Clark, M. Crosas, I. Dillo, O. Dumon, S. Edmunds, C.T. Evelo, R. Finkers, A. Gonzalez-Beltran, A.J.G. Gray, P. Groth, C. Goble, J.S. Grethe, J. Heringa, P.A.C. ’t Hoen, R. Hooft, T. Kuhn, R. Kok, J. Kok, S.J. Lusher, M.E. Martone, A. Mons, A.L. Packer, B. Persson, P. Rocca-Serra, M. Roos, R. van Schaik, S.-A. Sansone, E. Schultes, T. Sengstag, T. Slater, G. Strawn, M.A. Swertz, M. Thompson, J. van der Lei, E. van Mulligen, J. Velterop, A. Waagmeester, P. Wittenburg, K. Wolstencroft, J. Zhao, B. Mons, The FAIR Guiding Principles for scientific data management and stewardship, *Sci. Data* 3 (2016) 160018. <https://doi.org/10.1038/sdata.2016.18>.

PROCEDURAL SYSTEM Research Track

The abstracts in this section were peer reviewed.

BIM-based building permit process: Finland's implementation path

Rita Lavikka^a, Anna-Riitta Kallinen^b

^a VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, Tekniikantie 21, 02150 Espoo, Finland

^b ARK Consulting, ARKCON, Insinööritoimisto Kallinen Ltd Kalpakuja 2, 00740 HELSINKI

Introduction

Many countries are interested in applying Building Information Modelling (BIM) to streamline building permit application, review, and approval because the current permit practices are considered time consuming and sometimes cause delays in construction projects [1,2]. However, developing a BIM-based building permit process is difficult because the phenomenon is multifaceted, including technologies, multiple stakeholders, permit practices, and the legal environment.

Research shows that technological, organisational, and environmental factors must be considered when implementing BIM (Ullah, Witt and Lill, 2022). For example, the permit applicants and authorities need technologies for submitting, reviewing, and approving the permit application. Also, stakeholders need competencies in applying BIM and be motivated to use BIM.

Several countries have had development projects to digitalise the building permit processes (Noardo et al., 2022). Still, studies providing advice on how to implement digital building permit processes are scarce, even though papers focusing on implementing change exist [1,3,5]. Some researchers argue that four maturity levels of digital building permit implementation exist: 1) manual paper-based, 2) digital document and workflow management using an online permit service, 3) digital information and workflow management applying BIM and GIS, and 4) automated plan and design review [6,7].

Finland has been a forerunner in developing and implementing BIM tools [8]. Also, the digitalisation of the Finnish building permit processes has been ongoing for several years [9–13], but the actions taken so far and their importance for the digitalization of permit processes is not yet analysed. This study describes the transformation process from paper-based workflows to digital building permit processes. The study has two research questions: 1) What is the maturity level in the Finnish building permit processes? 2) What has been done to achieve that level?

Methodology

Data consists of public reports, three building permit expert interviews, and 25 survey answers by Finnish permit experts in spring 2023. The interviewees represented Finnish building permit process authorities. A consent form was provided.

The study adopts the Technology, Organization and Environment (TOE) Framework [14] in categorising findings on transformation. The TOE framework can be used to understand innovation implementation; in this case, the implementation of BIM modelling practices, building permit services, and compliance checking software. The TOE framework has been used in other studies on BIM-based building permit implementation [1,3].

Findings and discussion

The current digitalisation level of the Finnish building permit processes

In Finland, 83% of 309 municipalities use an online building permit service. Two building permit services exist, and both allow the submission of Industry Foundation Classes (IFC)-based

building designs for the permit approval process. Though, the current submission process also allows for pdf document submissions. Some municipalities' authorities use native BIM software to review the design if an IFC file has been submitted to the permit service. The communication between the permit applicant and various permit authorities is handled through the building permit service. The neighbours' hearing can also be done via the permit service if the neighbour has provided email address.

The first residential BIM-based building permit was issued in Järvenpää city in 2022 [15]. The IFC model needed to include information on the structure, materials, and facilities of the building, as well as overall areas/volumes. The architecture followed the national common BIM requirements [16] and the municipality's building control's BIM guidelines [17]. The cityscape and location reviews of the building in the environment were carried out using the 3D service of Järvenpää. Regulatory compliance was manually checked in the Solibri Model Checker program. Since then, other BIM-based building permits have been issued. If the applicant inserts building project-specific data into the IFC, it can be automatically read in the permit service and added to the application.

Following the digital building permit implementation levels [6,7], the Finnish building permit processes seem to be on level two, where digital documents are used through an online permit service. However, the processes are moving toward level three, where BIM and GIS are used.

Actions toward digital building permit processes

The digitalisation of building permit processes started in 2001 when a data transfer schema was developed to transfer data between the municipalities' technical and environmental service processes' systems [12]. Since then, various R&D projects (2016-2023) have been conducted where technological solutions have been developed and demonstrated for digitalising building permit processes. Most of these development projects have been financially supported by national R&D funding bodies, such as Business Finland or the Finnish Ministry of the Environment. One of the success factors for digitalisation has been the involvement of different user groups – designers, building control, software providers, consultants, construction companies, associations, and property owners – in the R&D projects. This has helped in the adoption of the new BIM-based building permit process.

In 2016, the municipalities were allowed to use digital archiving for official long-term archives without requiring archiving of paper documents. From the beginning of 2025, the new Building Act will allow the archival of IFCs in the new Built Environment Information System.

In addition to technological developments and digital archiving, the national BIM requirements (2012) and municipalities' BIM modelling guidelines have advanced modelling quality and thus played a role in advancing digital building permit processes. BIM education has also been crucial. The Finnish Ministry of Environment has financially supported the BIM coordinator educational program (2021-2022), producing BIM experts.

Table 1 lists and categorises the actions toward digitalising building permit processes into technological, organisational, and environmental actions. The table shows that bottom-up developmental actions, taking place through technological and organisational actions, have been quite extensive. The R&D projects have always included both types of actions: technologies and digital solutions have been developed but at the same time, the educational needs of various stakeholders have been taken into account. This has been important since technological advancements necessitate users to properly take them into use.

Top-down (EU and national regulatory) environmental actions are not that many, but their impact is also noteworthy, especially the digital archiving of IFC and development of a national built environment information system, which will allow the data-driven analysis of the built

environment and hopefully allow the monitoring and steering toward low-carbon initiatives in the sector.

Table 1: The technological, organisational and environmental actions that have supported the digitalisation of the Finnish building permit processes.

YEAR(S)	TECHNOLOGICAL ACTIONS	ORGANISATIONAL ACTIONS	ENVIRONMENTAL ACTIONS
2001-2015	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KuntaGML schema to transfer data between systems of municipalities' technical and environmental service processes [12]. Work was done in KuntaGML and KRYSP development projects (2007-2009). • The first software-as-a-service -version of the building permit service platform (2015) in the joint SADe development program of the state and municipalities to digitalise Finnish public administration services (2009-2015) [13]. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Vera R&D project supported the development of native BIM modelling tools (2002). • National Pro IT R&D project developed national openBIM building construction process (2003-2005). • Senate Properties developed BIM requirements (2007). • National BIM requirements (2012), COBIM2012. • National BIM requirement Part 14 'using openBIM in building permit process' (2014). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU's Inspire Directive require the implementation of a service for providing spatial data related to the municipalities' environment (2007).
2016-2019	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • A national KIRA-digi program in 2016-2019 included three R&D projects on digitalising building permitting in Finland [11]. For example, interoperability between the needed information systems was developed. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • KIRA-digi project developed building control's inspection rules and digital archiving of IFC models (RAVA1, 2017). [10] • Standardisation and naming classification nomenclature for all building design disciplines, first version (2017). • Requirements study/report for new COBIM (2018). • New COBIM2020 national BIM requirements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The municipalities were allowed to use digital archiving for official long-term archives without the requirement of archiving paper documents (2016).
2020-2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • COBIM2020 part 14 (2021-2022), the first part of the COBIM2020, is a continuum of the RAVA2 project. The project updated the BIM guidelines to support BIM-based regulatory building permitting. • The National Land Survey of Finland is scanning the whole nation with 5 point/m² accuracy and is converting 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • RAVA2 project (2020-2021), financed by the Finnish Ministry of Environment, defined the first national propertyset and use cases for the regulatory (minimum) BIM-based Building Permit process. [18] • BIM-based building permit – scaling clinic (2021) developed and unified BIM-based building permit practices in several municipalities. The project was 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Finnish Ministry of Environment is renewing the Land Use and Building Act. The Finnish parliament approved, in its plenary session on the 1st of March 2023, the new Building Act,

YEAR(S)	TECHNOLOGICAL ACTIONS	ORGANISATIONAL ACTIONS	ENVIRONMENTAL ACTIONS
	<p>the buildings in CityGML at the LOD2 level. This information is available in the public National Topographic Database and can be used to present a city model without photo textures.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The building permit development project, RAVA3Pro, led by the City of Helsinki and funded by the Ministry of Finance, tested the automation of the building permit processes. The project includes 23 Finnish municipalities. • RAVA3Pro project supported integrating cityscape services into building permit services for neighbours' hearing (2023). • RAVA3Pro supported the integration of 4D scheduling into city model software, which is used for visualising building processes, environments and timelines together (2023). • Wider use of national rule checking in building control (2023). • Several cities have prepared a 3D city model either as a photogrammetry-based mesh model with photo texture or a laser-scanned model with photos converted in CityGML, usually with Terrasolid Ltd tools. 	<p>funded by the Finnish Ministry of the Environment, Finnish Property Owners and project partners.[19]</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 15-week BIM coordinator education program for building controllers in 2021-2022 (100 persons/year, total 500, supported by the Ministry of Environment 0,3 M€/year) • RAVA3Pro publishes national building control's BIM guidelines, use cases, propertysets, rulesets, and other studies and reports (2023). RAVA3Pro project also included BIM education for municipalities to increase BIM maturity level. [20] • ACCORD Horizon Europe project (2022-2025) develops the process for BIM-based building permit processes, building on next-level development after the RAVA3Pro results. • Project Ryhti has two parts: 1) Semantic data interoperability in the built environment and 2) The built environment information system Ryhti. The semantic part focuses on defining logical information models and vocabularies/codes for enhancing data interoperability in the built environment. It concentrates on data types needed in the authorities' processes. For example, information on zoning plans and building permits will be compiled and processed into a coherent and accessible form. The Ryhti information system is a national storage service for all planning and building permit-related datasets. The first 	<p>which will enter into force from the beginning of 2025. The building permits and land use plans will be made machine-readable and stored in the new Built Environment Information System Ryhti in IFC 4.0.2.1 format.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The Finnish National Archives has approved the IFC 4.0.2.1 format as the official archiving format (2023).

YEAR(S)	TECHNOLOGICAL ACTIONS	ORGANISATIONAL ACTIONS	ENVIRONMENTAL ACTIONS
		functionalities will be available in 2024.[21]	

Conclusions

Finland is one of the most advanced European countries in terms of digital building permit processes. The permit applicants use online building permit services that allow submitting IFC files with project-specific information. Some municipalities can do automatic code compliance checks, city 3D reviews, and online neighbour hearings. Next, the country is more widely adopting BIM-based building permit and automatic compliance checking processes, including digital archiving of IFCs to a national built environment information system. The findings of this study shed light on the technological, organisational and environmental actions – ranging from technological and process development R&D projects to BIM education – that have supported the implementation of BIM-based building permit processes in Finland. Future research is needed to identify which of the identified actions could best support other European countries in digitalising the building permit processes.

Acknowledgements

The short article has received funding from the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No 101056973. The information and views expressed lie entirely with the authors. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The UK Participants in Horizon Europe Project ACCORD are supported by UKRI grant numbers [10040207] (Cardiff University), [10038999] (Birmingham City University) and [10049977] (Building Smart International).

This article has also received funding from the RAVA3Pro project that developed the automation of the Finnish digital permit process of municipal building control. The project is led by the City of Helsinki and funded by the Ministry of Finance. The project involved 23 Finnish municipalities: Espoo, Helsinki, Hyvinkää, Hämeenlinna, Iisalmi, Joensuu, Jyväskylä, Järvenpää, Kirkkonummi, Lahti, Lohja, Mikkeli, Oulu, Pori, Salo, Seinäjoki, Sysmä, Tampere, Turku, Tuusula, Vantaa, Ylöjärvi and Äänekoski, and stakeholder cooperation with the Ministry of the Environment, VTT (Technical Research Centre of Finland Ltd.), the National Archives of Finland, the Senate Properties, and the Association of Finnish Local and Regional Authorities. The development work for proof-of-concept in software companies has been done in Finland by Cloudpermit, Trimble, Simplebim, Solibri, and Sova3D.

References

- [1] K. Ullah, C. Raitviir, I. Lill, E. Witt, BIM adoption in the AEC/FM industry – The case for issuing building permits, *International Journal of Strategic Property Management* 26 (2020) 400–413. <https://doi.org/10.3846/ijspm.2020.13676>.
- [2] J. Fauth, L. Soibelman, Conceptual framework for building permit process modeling: Lessons learned from a comparison between Germany and the United States regarding the As-Is building permit processes, *Buildings* 12 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12050638>.
- [3] K. Ullah, E. Witt, I. Lill, The BIM-based building permit process: Factors affecting adoption, *Buildings* 12 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390> (accessed February 12, 2023).
- [4] F. Noardo, D. Guler, J. Fauth, G. Malacarne, S. Mastrolembo Ventura, M. Azenha, P.O. Olsson, L. Senger, Unveiling the actual progress of Digital Building Permit: Getting awareness through a critical state of the art review, *Build Environ* 213 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.108854>.
- [5] T.H. Beach, J.L. Hippolyte, Y. Rezgui, Towards the adoption of automated regulatory compliance checking in the built environment, *Autom Constr* 118 (2020) 103285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103285>.
- [6] K. Shahi, B.Y. McCabe, A. Shahi, Framework for automated model-based e-permitting system for

- municipal jurisdictions, *Journal of Management in Engineering* 35 (2019). [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)me.1943-5479.0000712](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)me.1943-5479.0000712).
- [7] T. Bloch, J. Fauth, The unbalanced research on digitalization and automation of the building permitting process, *Advanced Engineering Informatics* 58 (2023) 102188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2023.102188>.
- [8] G. Aksenova, A. Kiviniemi, T. Kocaturk, A. Lejeune, From Finnish AEC knowledge ecosystem to business ecosystem: lessons learned from the national deployment of BIM, *Construction Management and Economics* 37 (2019) 317–335. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01446193.2018.1481985>.
- [9] P. Silius-Miettinen, Rakennusvalvonta digitaalisen muutoksen pyörteessä (Building control in the vortex of digital change, in Finnish), Dissertation, Tampere University of Technology, 2018.
- [10] J. Vastamäki, Tietomallipohjaisen rakennuslupaprosessin kehittäminen Vantaan rakennusvalvonnassa, 2018. https://www.kiradigi.fi/media/hankemateriaali/loppuraportit/kira-digi_raportti_28.3.2019.pdf (accessed February 4, 2024).
- [11] KIRA-digi, KIRA-digi program in 2016–2019 , (2019). <http://www.kiradigi.fi/en/experiments.html> (accessed February 4, 2024).
- [12] KuntaGML schema, (2023). <https://github.com/kuntaliitto> (accessed February 4, 2024).
- [13] M. Saarijärvi, I. Alanko, P. Nurminen, SADe program to digitalise public governance and services 2009–2014, 2016. https://julkaisut.valtioneuvosto.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/75089/SADE-ohjelma_ilman_liitteita.pdf (accessed February 4, 2024).
- [14] J.D. Eveland, L.G. Tornatzky, Technological Innovation as a Process, in: L.G. Tornatzky, M. Fleischer, A.K. Chakrabarti (Eds.), *The Processes of Technological Innovation*, Lexington Books, 1990: pp. 27–50.
- [15] Sova3D, The world’s first 3D BIM model-approved building permit In Järvenpää?, <https://sova3d.fi/i/uncategorized/the-worlds-first-3d-bim-model-approved-building-permit-in-jarvenpaa/> (2021).
- [16] H. Kulusjärvi, COBIM - Common BIM Requirements 2012 - Series 6 Quality assurance, 2012. https://asiakas.kotisivukone.com/files/en.buildingsmart.kotisivukone.com/COBIM2012/cobim_6_quality_assurance_v1.pdf (accessed November 5, 2023).
- [17] J. Kaaretkoski, J. Vastamäki, BIM in residential construction projects - guidelines by building control of Järvenpää and Hyvinkää (Tietomallit asuinrakennushankkeissa - rakennusvalvonnan ohje, in Finnish), 2022. <https://www.jarvenpaa.fi/files/1f830f7f99bfb89be79d7d4da709836890c78be1/tietomallipohjainen-lupakasittely-asuinrakennukset.pdf> (accessed November 5, 2023).
- [18] A.-R. Kallinen, RAVA2 development project on digital building permitting, (2021). <https://kirahub.org/rava2-kehityshankkeen-julkinen-lausuntokierros-on-kaynnistynyt/> (accessed February 4, 2024).
- [19] Rakli, Rakennuslupa tietomallilla -skaalauslinikka, (2021). <https://www.rakli.fi/rakennuslupa-tietomallilla-skaalauslinikka/> (accessed February 4, 2024).
- [20] A.-R. Kallinen, RAVA3pro, (2023). <https://kirahub.org/rava3pro/> (accessed February 4, 2024).
- [21] Finnish Ministry of the Environment, Project Ryhti, (2024). <https://ym.fi/en/project-ryhti> (accessed February 4, 2024).

Stakeholder attitudes and process readiness towards digital building permit processes in five European countries

Rita Lavikka^a, Thomas Beach^b, Katja Breitenfelder^c, Gonçal Costa^d, Ioannis Christovasilis^e, Panagiotis Patlakas^f, Christopher-Robin Raitviir^g, Markku Kiviniemi^a, and Jaan Saar^h

^a VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, Tekniikantie 21, 02150 Espoo, Finland

^b School of Engineering, Cardiff University, Cardiff, UK

^c Fraunhofer Institute for Building Physics IBP, Department Project- and Business Development, Valley, Germany

^d Human Environment Research (HER), La Salle, Ramon Llull University, Sant Joan de la Salle, 42, 08022, Barcelona, Catalonia, Spain

^e Aether Engineering s.a.s., Via Masaccio 252, Florence, 50132, IT

^f College of the Built Environment, Birmingham City University, Birmingham, UK

^g Tallinn University of Technology, Ehitajate tee 5, 19086 Tallinn, Estonia

^h Future Insight Group B.V., Grote Voort 207-G, 8041 BK Zwolle, Netherlands

Introduction

The digitalisation of building permit processes refers to using digital technologies to streamline building permit application, review and approval. For example, the permit applicant can use an online service to submit digital designs and other required information, and the authorities may use software to conduct automatic code compliance checks. A digital building permit process can improve municipalities' efficiency, reduce paper waste, and make it easier for permit applicants to navigate the process [1]. It can also reduce the time required for the designers' and authorities' review of regulatory compliance and increase the transparency of the design and construction process. Despite these benefits, the building permit process in many countries is still manual, and information is exchanged on paper or digitally in PDF.

Research on digital building permits has mainly focused on developing technical solutions [2–5] and somewhat neglected process, data quality, and people perspectives [5–8]. A few studies have examined industry attitudes towards digital building permits and the reasons for slowing down digitalisation. For example, according to a UK industry survey, the automation of building permit processes is desirable and feasible if human oversight is maintained [9]. The same survey revealed challenges to digitalising building permit processes: the lack of machine-readable regulations and rules, the low maturity level of building information modelling (BIM) and the low number of compliance-checking tools [9]. Another study highlighted the authorities' lack of expertise in BIM-based building permit processes [10].

This study aims to contribute to advancing the adoption of digital building permit processes. It considers this phenomenon an innovation implementation challenge and empirically investigates two research questions in five European countries: 1) What are the industry stakeholders' attitudes toward digital building permit processes? 2) What is the level of adoption of the digital building permit processes?

Methodology

The study applied a survey to gather expert views on the adoption and benefits of digital building permit processes and automated compliance checking in Europe. The survey inquired about the national adoption of digital building permit processes, possible outcomes, obstacles, and requirements for adopting digital building permits from technological, commercial, and political

perspectives. The survey was translated into multiple European languages and was open from 28.11.2022 to 31.1.2023.

The survey was advertised on social media and received 472 responses from 16 European countries and seven countries outside the EU. Most (346) of the responses came from Italy, followed by Spain (39), Finland (25), and Estonia (12). The respondents represented various disciplines, primarily architects (391), building control authorities (29), project managers, and other design disciplines.

In addition to the survey, the current building permit processes in five European countries were modelled using the Business Modelling Process Notation (BPMN) to understand the differences between the processes. Finland, Estonia, Germany, the UK, and Spain were selected as they represent countries with various sizes, geographical areas in Europe, and maturity levels in the digitalisation of building permit processes. Three interviews were conducted in each country to support the modelling. Researchers identified the interviewees with local experts, who usually represented the countries' building permit authorities. A consent form was delivered to the interviewed persons.

The interview data was categorised using the Technology, Organisation, and Environment (TOE) framework for innovation implementation [11], as this study aims to understand innovation implementation. The Technology includes technologies needed for innovation implementation. The Organisation refers to the organisation's resources in which the technology will be adopted. Finally, the Environment refers to the environment in which the organisation operates.

The study applies the maturity framework for digital building permit processes [12] to map the countries' digital building permit process maturity. This framework consists of four levels. The first level resembles a traditional paper-based permit process with a manual design review. On the second level, basic e-permitting, the applicant uses an online service to submit designs as a PDF, and the authority manually reviews digital drawings. The third level, automated model-based e-permitting, necessitates submitting the IFC model and semi-automated code compliance checking. Finally, the fourth level, fully integrated e-permitting, includes the integration of BIM and GIS and an integrated planning review with automated code compliance checking.

Findings and discussion

Stakeholder attitudes towards digital building permit processes

The survey results show that partial or full automation is considered possible in the next ten years. However, most respondents prefer maintaining a final human sign-off regardless of the level of automation achieved within the process, which confirms earlier findings [9]. Some countries – the UK, Finland, France, and Romania – favour partial automation, where some key aspects are automatically assessed. Estonia, Spain, and Italy trend toward automation with human approval. Building control professionals think partial automation is possible, whereas project managers envisage more automation.

The survey results reveal that the key desired outcomes from digital building permit processes and automated compliance checking are time savings, increased information certainty, cost savings, and a decrease in ambiguous information during the design and construction process. The key obstacles to adopting digital building permit processes are differing processes between municipalities, lack of digital skills, lack of software tools, and lack of standard specifications of design documentation. These findings support earlier findings [10].

The survey results show that the key requirements for digital building permit processes are standardised submission processes, the ability to link BIM to GIS, intuitive user interfaces, training and support, and open access to high-level result data.

Process readiness towards digital building permit processes

The modelled building permit process in each country is generic because it differs somewhat depending on the building type and size. The states and municipalities are local self-governing bodies with the right assigned to manage the local permit process within the limits set by the laws. Therefore, the permit practices between states and municipalities of the country may differ. However, the countries' generic building permit processes share some features. For example, the stakeholders in each country are the building permit applicant (often the principal architect), neighbours, the local building control authority, and other authorities, such as the rescue department, depending on the type and size of the building. The permit applicant can consult the building permit authorities before submitting the application.

Currently, the design is submitted as a PDF in each country. Estonia and Finland allow the submission of an IFC file. In some Finnish municipalities, submitting the IFC file and locating it in a city model for cityscape assessment is already technically possible. In all countries, authorities conduct compliance checking mainly manually by reviewing the PDF drawings. Estonia and Finland are working towards automatic compliance checking, where certain codes related to, e.g., accessibility, are automatically checked, but the checking results are verified by the authority, thus preserving human oversight.

The processes between countries also differ to some extent. For example, the number of building permit types varies from three to six. Also, the number of permits varies from a few thousand to several hundred thousand per year. The building control process in England differs a bit from other countries' processes. For example, the inspection and certification of building control issues can be undertaken by private providers. Also, while preferred design codes exist, Building Regulations in England allow various ways to demonstrate that an adequate standard has been met, including past versions of design standards or guidance in approved documents.

Table 1 explains the digital maturity level of the countries' building permit processes, following the TOE framework for innovation implementation. All countries have online services for submitting designs as PDFs, but compliance checking is mainly done manually. Thus, all countries are currently on the basic e-permitting level, but Finland is close to reaching the next level, 'automated model-based e-permitting', where the applicants submit an IFC model, and the authorities use software for automated code compliance checking with human oversight. R&D projects have already proved this successful, but the country-wide implementation takes time, even though BIM guidelines exist. The changes in the regulatory landscape seem to enhance permit process digitalisation. Estonia launched a country-wide 'automated model-based e-permitting' in February 2024.

Germany is creating a uniform basis, with national information exchange specifications, for the automated checking of building code requirements with BIM-based testing tools. Requirements for BIM models will also be developed. The UK has conducted national R&D projects to develop tools for compliance checking. Spain is involved in R&D projects and closely follows the best practices for implementation.

It seems that a top-down, regulatory 'push' has quite recently benefited Finland and Estonia in their journeys toward BIM-based building permit processes. However, it might be that these countries have also benefited from being small in terms of country size and number of stakeholders and somewhat agile in implementing technologies, such as BIM (see e.g., [13]), and IFC-based submission and compliance checking services.

Building permit applicants and authorities in all countries need BIM education to benefit from the BIM-based building permit process fully. However, further research is needed to identify each countries’ and stakeholders’ specific educational needs.

Table 1. Technological, organisational and environmental (TOE) factors in the building permit processes of the five European countries.

TOE factors	Finland	Estonia	Germany	UK	Spain
Technological factors	Two online building permit services exist and ~70% of 309 municipalities use a system. Permit applicants can submit IFC files. Some municipalities have BIM software to visually inspect BIM models and/or Solibri Model Checker for code compliance checks.	All 79 municipalities use the Estonian building permit service of the Building Registry. Permit applicants can submit IFC files. The service allows for 47 automatic checks against the Building Code. The permit applicant or its processor does not need additional software.	XPlanung and XBau are national specifications for exchanging and processing information in administrative procedures under building regulations law.	A variety of systems are used to manage submissions. Many local authorities use the Planning Portal to manage the submission or the metadata that goes along with an application via a web-based interface.	Electronic submission of building permits using digital certificates.
Organisational factors	Few municipalities provide guidelines for BIM-based building permit processes. National BIM guidelines for building permit processes are developed. The Finnish Ministry of Environment has financially supported BIM education in the sector.	National BIM guidelines for automated compliance checking exist.	A uniform basis for the automated checking of building code requirements with BIM-based testing tools will be created. Requirements for BIM models will also be developed.	Local authorities may have various workflow management tools to help them manage and assign submissions to building control professionals once submitted. Still, these only manage data in PDF format and are often repurposed document management systems.	There is no record of any city council processing permits automatically using BIM/GIS models. There is a pilot initiative of BIM- and Blockchain-based compliance checking led by the Professional Association of Building Engineers.
Environmental	The new Building Act in 2025 will allow	The mandate for using the Building Registry	Federal government's Online Access	The law does not require the adoption of	The Common Administrative Procedure

(regulatory) factors	the delivering IFC models to a forthcoming national registry.	is set in Building Code §40.	Law of administrative processes.	model-based submissions.	of Public Administrations (39/2015).
Maturity of building permit processes	Basic e-permitting, but work is ongoing toward semi-automated IFC-based e-permitting.	Basic e-permitting with some automated checks for technical data in the permit system since 2016 and semi-automated IFC-based e-permitting option since February 2024.	Basic e-permitting, but work is ongoing for digitalisation.	Basic e-permitting but R&D projects looking at digitalization.	Basic e-permitting

Conclusions

The study pictures positive attitudes among industry stakeholders towards the automation of building permit processes. Project managers are slightly more interested in full automation than permit authorities, but both parties prefer human oversight. Time savings, increased information certainty, and cost savings are expected, but differing processes between municipalities and a lack of digital skills and software tools slow down the implementation of digital building permit processes. All countries apply online services to submit designs as pdf. However, Finland and Estonia allow submitting IFC files and semi-automated compliance checks with human oversight. These findings provide a basis for further research in the ACCORD Horizon Europe project to support permit applicants and authorities in implementing digital building permit processes in each country.

Acknowledgements

This study was funded by the ACCORD project, grant agreement No 101056973 of the European Commission's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme. The information and views expressed lie entirely with the authors. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. The UK Participants in Horizon Europe Project ACCORD are supported by UKRI grant numbers 10040207 (Cardiff University), 10038999 (Birmingham City University) and 10049977 (Building Smart International).

References

- [1] K. Ullah, C. Raitviir, I. Lill, E. Witt, BIM adoption in the AEC/FM industry – The case for issuing building permits, *International Journal of Strategic Property Management* 26 (2020) 400–413. <https://doi.org/10.3846/ijspm.2020.13676>.
- [2] W. Solihin, C. Eastman, Classification of rules for automated BIM rule checking development, *Autom Constr* 53 (2015) 69–82. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2015.03.003>.
- [3] C. Eastman, J. Lee, Y. Jeong, J. Lee, Automatic rule-based checking of building designs, *Autom Constr* 18 (2009) 1011–1033. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2009.07.002>.
- [4] N.O. Nawari, Practical Approaches, in: *Building Information Modeling: Automated Code Checking and Compliance Processes*, CRC Press - Taylor & Francis Group, 2018: pp. 125–159.
- [5] T. Bloch, J. Fauth, The unbalanced research on digitalization and automation of the building

- permitting process, *Advanced Engineering Informatics* 58 (2023) 102188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2023.102188>.
- [6] J. Fauth, G. Pasetti Monizza, G. Malacarne, Understanding processes on digital building permits – a case study in South Tyrol, *Building Research and Information* 51 (2023) 518–532. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613218.2023.2178372>.
- [7] F. Noardo, D. Guler, J. Fauth, G. Malacarne, S. Mastrolembo Ventura, M. Azenha, P.O. Olsson, L. Senger, Unveiling the actual progress of Digital Building Permit: Getting awareness through a critical state of the art review, *Build Environ* 213 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.108854>.
- [8] J. Fauth, L. Soibelman, Conceptual framework for building permit process modeling: Lessons learned from a comparison between Germany and the United States regarding the As-Is building permit processes, *Buildings* 12 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12050638>.
- [9] T.H. Beach, J.L. Hippolyte, Y. Rezgui, Towards the adoption of automated regulatory compliance checking in the built environment, *Autom Constr* 118 (2020) 103285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103285>.
- [10] K. Ullah, E. Witt, I. Lill, The BIM-based building permit process: Factors affecting adoption, *Buildings* 12 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.3390> (accessed February 12, 2023).
- [11] J.D. Eveland, L.G. Tornatzky, Technological Innovation as a Process, in: L.G. Tornatzky, M. Fleischer, A.K. Chakrabarti (Eds.), *The Processes of Technological Innovation*, Lexington Books, 1990: pp. 27–50.
- [12] K. Shahi, B.Y. McCabe, A. Shahi, Framework for automated model-based e-permitting system for municipal jurisdictions, *Journal of Management in Engineering* 35 (2019). [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)me.1943-5479.0000712](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)me.1943-5479.0000712).
- [13] G. Aksenova, A. Kiviniemi, T. Kocaturk, A. Lejeune, From Finnish AEC knowledge ecosystem to business ecosystem: lessons learned from the national deployment of BIM, *Construction Management and Economics* 37 (2019) 317–335. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01446193.2018.1481985>.

Investigation and comparison of building permit processes in different sized municipalities at national level: the Italian case

Kavita Raj^{a*}, Judith Fauth^b, Silvia Mastrolemba Ventura^a, Sara Comai^a and Angelo Luigi Camillo Ciribini^a

^a Dept. of Civil, Architectural, Environmental Engineering and Mathematics, University of Brescia, Brescia, Italy

^b TU Wien, Research Unit Digital Building Process, Karlsplatz 13/E235-03, 1040 Vienna, Austria

*Correspondence: kavita.raj@unibs.it

The importance of digitalizing building permits internationally plays a key role in breaking down the barriers that characterize its time-consuming and human error-prone process as being based on manual controls. The standardization and digitalization of building permit procedures brings several benefits that can positively impact both the competent authorities and applicants. Benefits include achieving greater efficiency through automation of control processes that can further speed up approval times. These aspects are complemented by the achievement of a more transparent and accessible process that ensures the correct application of regulations, thereby reducing the risk of human errors. Additionally, there is an improvement in the quality of decisions and a reduction in errors in planning, design, and construction, which also benefits the context of environmental sustainability.

The European Network of Digital Building Permit (EUnet4DBP) has identified three pillars covering three issues that need to be addressed for building permit: (1) the analysis of the process, (2) building permit regulations and relevant requirements, and (3) technologies to run the process digitally. Regarding these objectives, there arises the necessity to understand the processes as carried out by public authorities in order to develop a solution that is scalable and adaptable on an international scale. This is crucial to avoid the implementation of a solution that, by not taking into account the needs of end-users, may prove ineffective once applied [1]. It is critical to address current problems, to evaluate and compare each scenario to study a better process, and with the awareness that tailored solutions are needed to overcome known obstacles [2].

Several studies can be identified in the literature on the analysis of the building permit process and the comparison of different processes at the international level. Pedro [3], in their study, analyse and compare the construction permit processes in 27 European nations, providing an overview that, at a general level, reveals many similarities but, in detail, highlights various specificities. In Rückert's report (2011) [4], processes in Germany, Denmark, Poland, and Lithuania were also compared, identifying similarities and divergences with the aim of supporting standardization and transparency. Similarly, the study conducted by Refvik [5] compared and analysed processes in selected nations across Europe, America, Asia, and Australia, identifying significant differences in the of the construction sector, considering national procedures for permit issuance. An in-depth investigation is exemplified by the comparative analysis of the procedural methodologies employed in Croatia and Slovenia [6]. This examination unveiled shared procedural patterns, thereby presenting certain prospective implementations that remain subject to further consideration. The conclusions highlight the potential of implementing each process with the best practices analysed, leading to benefits especially for the legal aspects, stages and stakeholders involved. Noardo [7] elaborate a comparison and harmonization of processes in the United Kingdom, the Netherlands, Sweden, and Slovenia based on an investigation of current processes. The harmonized workflow is high-level but is outlined to provide a foundation for the implementation of Building Information Modelling (BIM) and

Geographic Information System (GIS), known as GeoBIM. Fauth and Soibelman [8], considering the United States and Germany, have outlined a scalable framework, starting from a systematic mapping of as-is processes, aimed at international standardization. Within the context of the EU-funded CHEK® project [9], a study was carried out to compare and harmonize the processes of four European municipalities - of different scales - in Italy, Portugal and the Czech Republic [10]. The as-is processes were investigated, mapped and harmonized into a final workflow that is the input for the adoption within it of BIM and GIS. Regarding the building permit process in Italy, Fauth [11] investigated the case of South Tyrol. This study highlights what information and digital needs, on the organizational level, by presenting the knowledge acquired through the comparison with other processes for building permits.

These studies assess differences among various national models, aiming to identify best practices and areas for improvement to pursue the goals of efficiency and transparency in processes. However, such solutions risk not adapting to the procedural diversity that characterizes some countries resulting from different realities such as the size or number of inhabitants of municipalities. In the context of such diversity on a national territory, different ways and timescales might be identified so that any solutions harmonized on an international scale may risk not being functional for the most local realities.

The analysis of the process at the national level, in order to compare it with the equivalent result in other countries, runs the risk of not delving into the specificity of the national context itself. The mapping of the national process, which is generally valid because it is based on normative references or interviews with individual realities, risks missing typical nuances of how the same process is applied in different forms, for example in small, medium and large realities. This is even more evident in countries like Italy, where seventy percent of the municipalities have less than 5,000 inhabitants.

Within the EUnet4DBP research context, for the Italian case, three municipalities were selected based on population size to identify a compared process that considers possible diversity and best-practices. Have been selected a large-sized (more than 500,000 inhabitants) a medium-sized (between 500,000 and 50,000), and a small-sized municipality (less than 50,000 inhabitants). The methodology used for data collection and analysis involves the use of a semi-structured interview guideline from the research of Fauth [12]. The guide helps the interviewer touch on all the key points of the building permit process. In addition, using the same interview structure makes it possible to collect data in a systematic and comparable way. The methodology required to involve people working within the municipalities for managing the building permit process (table 1). The interviews were recorded and transcribed to be analysed. The transcript allowed for qualitative content analysis to be conducted on the text following a coding scheme that mainly reflects the structure of the interview guideline. The qualitative analysis of the text made it possible to identify some common patterns within the processes investigated for each municipality for subsequent rendering in visual form. The Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) standard was used for process mapping, which allows the responsibilities and roles of the stakeholders involved to be related as well as providing a chronological dimension of the flow.

Municipalities' size	N° of municipality's workers involved in each interview	Length of audio recording (min)
Small	1	40
Medium	2	90
Large	1	90

Tab. 5: Number of interviewees and length of audio recording.

The application of the methodology to the Italian case, using a guide for conducting interviews in data collection and implementing a coding scheme for mapping, allowed for a comparison of processes on a national scale. Indeed, based on the coding scheme, common phases were identified: (1) submission, (2) assignment, (3) administrative check, (4) content check, (5) participation of external/internal parties, (6) Issuance of the permit. A final map (figure 1,2) was generated through the comparative analysis of processes in each municipality. These steps are identifiable in all three processes, and this aspect derived from the national regulations framework. The applied method is suitable for comparing processes across municipalities of different scales, revealing common patterns but also highlighting specific organizational and task division distinctions instructed by local needs.

Fig. 1: Italy’s compared building permit process map (BPMN 2.0 standard representation) (PART 1).

Fig. 2: Italy's compared building permit process map (BPMN 2.0 standard representation) (PART 2).

The analysis and comparison of processes according to the number of inhabitants of municipalities brings to light aspects that cannot be omitted in order to ensure that international solutions do not lead to adoption barriers. In fact, although many aspects are largely driven by the national regulatory framework, -and are well identifiable in each process- the organizational and procedural set-up for issuing building permits can differ significantly at the national level depending on the size of municipalities. Aspects such as staff size should not be overlooked, which lead to upskilling needs and training programs. In detail, in small municipalities the same officers may be involved in different stages of the process while in large municipalities there may be a specialized staff with distinct roles for processing the applications. Other factors to consider and compare are technology and automation aspects, which in small municipalities may be limited compared to larger municipalities that are equipped with advanced information systems and automation to expedite the bureaucracy.

The method applied to Italian municipalities makes it possible to bring to light the characteristics that result from their size and organizational assets, which allow a comparison to be made at the national level before making a comparison and standardization of processes at the international level. The obtained results, also, can be refined by increasing the number of interviews, allowing for the development of three comparative processes for each level of dimension before developing a single comparative process. Although the approach employed does not solely rely on data quantity, considering in the future a larger number of data derived from a larger number of interviews, may impact the analysis process and the obtained results, leading to a more detailed understanding of the studied phenomenon and enhancing the validity of the conclusions.

The approach applied, supports the definition of solutions that are adapted to local realities ensuring a higher compliance of the result. While this study represents a first systematic

approach to comparing building permit processes, it is important for future developments to investigate them further, based on the goals that want to be pursued with digitalization and the introduction of new technologies for their automation. In addition, it is crucial to investigate the sub-processes in more detail by identifying which steps are the most critical in order to align any divergence more effectively.

Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union under the Horizon Europe Research & Innovation Programme (grant agreement no. 101058559 CHEK). Views and opinions expressed are however those of author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

References

- [1] Noardo, F., G. Malacarne, S. Mastrolemba Ventura, L. C. Tagliabue, A. L. C. Ciribini, C. Ellul, D. Guler, L. Harrie, L. Senger, A. Waha, and J. Stoter. 2020b. “Integrating expertises and ambitions for data-driven digital building permits – the EUNET4DBP.” *Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spat. Inf. Sci.*, XLIV-4/W1-2020: 103–110. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIV-4-W1-2020-103-2020>.
- [2] Meijer Frits, and Henk J. Visscher. Building regulations from an European perspective. (2008). COPRA, September 2008, ISBN 978-1-84219-434-8. <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:152541287>.
- [3] Pedro, J. B., F. Meijer, and H. Visscher. 2011. “Comparison of building permit procedures in European Union countries.” *RICS Constr. Prop. Conf.*
- [4] Rückert, K. 2011. Legal requirements: report on legal sustainability requirements and building permission procedures; a comparison of the legal framework in Germany, Denmark, Poland and Lithuania. Berlin: TU Berlin Publ.
- [5] Refvik, R., M. Skallerud, P. Slette, and A. Bjaaland. 2014. “ByggNett–Status survey of solutions and issues relevant to the development of ByggNett.” *Nor. Build. Auth.*, (n.d.).
- [6] Jovanović, T., A. Aristovnik, and T. R. Lugarić. 2016. “A comparative analysis of building permits procedures in Slovenia and Croatia: development of a simplification model.” *Theor. Empir. Res. Urban Manag.*, 11 (2): 5–23. JSTOR.
- [7] Noardo, F., C. Ellul, L. Harrie, I. Overland, M. Shariat, K. Arroyo Ogori, and J. Stoter. 2020a. “Opportunities and challenges for GeoBIM in Europe: developing a building permits use-case to raise awareness and examine technical interoperability challenges.” *J. Spat. Sci.*, 65 (2): 209–233. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14498596.2019.1627253>.
- [8] Fauth, J., and L. Soibelman. 2022. “Conceptual Framework for Building Permit Process Modeling: Lessons Learned from a Comparison between Germany and the United States regarding the As-Is Building Permit Processes.” *Buildings*, 12 (5): 638. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12050638>.
- [9] CHEK© 2022. CHEK - Change toolkit for digital building permit. Funded by European Union’s Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement No.101058559. <https://chekdbp.eu/>.
- [10] Braholli, O., Ataide, M., Di Blasio, I., Raj, K., Siegele, D., 2023. CHEK To-be Digital Building Permit process map. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7789035>.
- [11] Fauth, J., Monizza Pasetti, G., & Malacarne G. (2023) Understanding processes on digital building permits – a case study in South Tyrol, *Building Research & Information*, 51:5, 518-532, DOI: 10.1080/09613218.2023.2178372.
- [12] Fauth, J. 2022. “A process-oriented decision model for determining the permitability of construction projects.” Dissertation, Bauhaus-Universität Weimar. <https://doi.org/10.25643/bauhaus->

universitaet.4602.

Process Analysis and Comparative Evaluation of Building Permitting – PACE-BP

Tanya Bloch^a, Judith Fauth^b, Lucio Soibelman^c

^a Faculty of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Technion Israel Institute of Technology, Haifa, Israel

^b Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, United Kingdom

^c Sonny Astani Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Southern California, Los Angeles, California, USA

Introduction

The Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) industry is undergoing transformative changes driven by technological advancements, with a particular focus on digitalization and automation opportunities. One key area of interest is the building permit process. Building permit processes are complex and multidisciplinary [1]. While the core activities may be comparable across countries, the local laws, regulations, and policies governing these processes introduce significant variations [2–4]. This diversity hinders meaningful global comparisons, making it challenging to establish standards and guidelines for building permit process modelling [5]. The absence of a standardized approach for comparing these processes has been a longstanding issue in literature [6]. Existing methods for evaluating business process models often fall short when applied to building permit processes as they lack the ability to effectively capture specific complexities in these processes. The framework developed by [5] enhances clarity within individual processes but lacks a standardized approach for meaningful global comparisons. Bridging this gap is essential for advancing the understanding of building permit processes and fostering global improvements in efficiency, transparency, and consistency. Hence, our goal in this work is to introduce a systematic approach for evaluating and comparing building permit processes globally.

The PACE-BP Methodology

The proposed Process Analysis and Comparative Evaluation approach for building permitting (PACE-BP) is designed to provide a systematic and objective way to evaluate individual processes and compare between processes in different countries. The method heavily relies on a previously developed framework for building permit process mapping and modelling [5]. Hence, as a pre stage to implementing PACE-BP, a series of in-depth interviews with domain experts must be conducted and process maps using Business Process and Notation (BPMN) produced. Recognizing the complexity of trade-offs faced by different countries and stakeholders, PACE-BP goes beyond simply ranking the individual processes. It incorporates qualitative insights through interviews and literature to define evaluation parameters that include time consumption, data and information loss, resource consumption, coordination efforts, transparency, decision robustness, corruption vulnerability, flexibility, citizen friendliness and societal and political impact. These parameters are systematically assessed using measurable indicators that can be easily extracted directly from the BPMN maps, coupled with a defined correlation matrix that presents the relationships between the measurable indicators and the evaluation parameters. Measurable indicators are for example the number of involved stakeholders visible through the swim lanes in the BPMN, the number of handoffs between the stakeholders visible by the connections, etc. This process generates representative vectors for eventually calculating a similarity score between the given process maps.

Results and Discussion

The proposed process was demonstrated using four process maps for Germany, USA [5], Italy (the region of South Tyrol in particular) [7], and Israel [8]. The results were compared to the insight gained during the in-depth interviews performed in each of the countries. The research findings demonstrate that building permit processes cannot be simply ranked as best or worst. PACE-PB methodology introduces a new approach for evaluation, focusing on robustness and objectivity. The quantitative indicators derived from the methodology provide deeper insights into the differences between building permit processes across different contexts.

Practically speaking, policymakers and other stakeholders can leverage the proposed methodology to identify areas for improvement, leading to informed decision-making about regulatory changes, procedural adjustments, and new policy development. Local authorities, through feedback on organizational performance, can tackle key inefficiencies through organizational changes. Although there are cultural and geographical differences between the countries that reflect in the processes, we expect the main steps of applying, checking and issuing a permit to be present in most, making a comparison possible and meaningful.

It should be noted that the proposed methodology is focused on the viewpoint of authorities, hence, further research is required to include perspectives from different stakeholders, such as policymakers and additional experts not interviewed during the initial research. Quantitative research is essential for the validation of identified parameters and the correlation matrix, expanding the methodology's perspective. In conclusion, the PACE-PB methodology provides a valuable resource for stakeholders seeking to enhance and harmonize these processes across diverse contexts, fostering a more standardized and transparent global landscape for building permit processes.

References

- [1] F. Noardo, D. Guler, J. Fauth, G. Malacarne, S. Mastrolembo Ventura, M. Azenha, P.-O. Olsson, L. Senger, Unveiling the actual progress of Digital Building Permit: Getting awareness through a critical state of the art review, *Build. Environ.* 213 (2022) 108854. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.108854>.
- [2] D. Guler, T. Yomralioglu, A reformative framework for processes from building permit issuing to property ownership in Turkey, *Land Use Policy* 101 (2021) 105115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.105115>.
- [3] I. Kim, J. Choi, E.A.L. Teo, H. Sun, Development of K-BIM E-submission prototypical system for the openBIM-based building permit framework, *J. Civ. Eng. Manag.* 26 (2020) 744–756. <https://doi.org/10.3846/jcem.2020.13756>.
- [4] P.-O. Olsson, J. Axelsson, M. Hooper, L. Harrie, Automation of Building Permission by Integration of BIM and Geospatial Data, *ISPRS Int. J. Geo-Inf.* 7 (2018) 307. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi7080307>.
- [5] J. Fauth, L. Soibelman, Conceptual Framework for Building Permit Process Modeling: Lessons Learned from a Comparison between Germany and the United States regarding the As-Is Building Permit Processes, *Buildings* 12 (2022) 638. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12050638>.
- [6] K. Rückert, Legal requirements: report on legal sustainability requirements and building permission procedures; a comparison of the legal framework in Germany, Denmark, Poland and Lithuania, TU Berlin Publ, Berlin, 2011.
- [7] J. Fauth, G. Pasetti Monizza, G. Malacarne, Understanding processes on digital building permits – a case study in South Tyrol, *Build. Res. Inf.* 51 (2023) 518–532. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613218.2023.2178372>.

- [8] J. Fauth, T. Bloch, L. Soibelman, Process model for international building permit benchmarking and a validation example using the Israeli building permit process, *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management* (2023).

Analyzing Building Permit Processes Across Europe

Peter Nørkjær Gade^a, Judith Fauth^b, Stefanie Kaiser^c, Jernej Tekavec^d, Kavita Raj^e, Jonas Goul Pedersen^a, Silvia Mastrolembo Ventura^e, Jose Granja^f, Per-Ola Olsson^g, Antero Hirvensalo^h, Harald Urbanⁱ, Christian Schranzⁱ, Stojanov Trajche^j, Ruben Verstraeten^k, Snezana Rutesic^l, Christopher-Robin Raitviir^m, Anna-Riitta Kallinenⁿ, Stepanka Toma-nova^o, Celine Labrune^p, Pleskó Szilvia^q, Éva Veronika Lőrincz^q, Eilif Hjelseth^r

^a University College of Northern Denmark, ^b University of Cambridge, ^c Politechnica University of Timisoara, ^d University of Ljubljana, ^e University of Brescia, ^f University of Minho, ^g Lund University, ^h Tampere University, ⁱ TU Wien, ^j ZWEI LTD, ^k Ghent University, ^l University of Montenegro, ^m Estonian Ministry of Climate, ⁿ ARKCON, ^o Czech standardization agency, ^p Bureau Veritas Construction, ^q Opinion Builders Ltd., ^r Norwegian University of Science and Technology

The issuance of building permits is a critical process for urban development, ensuring compliance with legal standards and sustainability goals. This process presents a complex web of processes, regulations, and methodologies in Europe. Despite its importance in shaping urban landscapes, detailed investigations into the building permitting process have yet to be limited [1,2]. This knowledge gap obstructs optimizing these processes and curtails the potential for digital transformation, a crucial step in updating administrative functions. A study conducted by members of EU4DBP aims to address this deficiency by conducting a comparative analysis of building permitting processes in 19 European countries.

The goal is to lay a foundation for enhancing process efficiency and fostering a comprehensive European perspective. The insights from this study are expected to contribute to developing more effective policies and encourage the creation of improved solutions and practices in building permits. Our study adopts a multifaceted methodological approach to conduct a comparative analysis of the building permitting processes. The primary objective is to unearth commonalities and variations across different regions, thereby providing a comprehensive understanding of the intricacies involved in the permitting process. The methodology comprises several key phases: data collection, data preparation, data analysis, and validation processes.

The data collection phase is centered around conducting interviews with individuals who are experts in the field of building permits, primarily employed in municipalities across Europe. These interviews are designed to extract detailed, qualitative data regarding the various processes, regulations, and practices of issuing building permits. A standardized guideline was developed based on prior research and studies to maintain consistency and quality across all interviews. This ensured that the data collected was reliable and comparable across different municipalities. Once the data was collected, it entered the data preparation phase. Here, the focus was transcribing the interviews and organizing the information to facilitate efficient analysis. The transcription process is meticulous, ensuring the qualitative data is accurately captured and ready for analysis. This phase is crucial as it lays the groundwork for the subsequent analysis, forming the backbone of the research.

In the data analysis phase, a qualitative approach is adopted. The transcribed texts are scrutinized using a shared coding scheme. This coding scheme is designed to identify key themes, patterns, and variations within the data. One of the unique aspects of our analysis is the use of the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) 2.0 standard, as seen in Figure 1. This standard allows us to create generalized maps for each municipality's process, visually representing the building permitting processes and highlighting the similarities and differences across various regions.

Fig. 1: Example of a BPMN diagram based on interviews from Germany.

A comprehensive validation process is implemented to ensure the validity and reliability of our findings. This includes several components, such as consistent interview guidelines, the engagement of multiple interviewers to avoid bias, a unified coding system to ensure consistency in data analysis, peer debriefing, and member checking. Furthermore, collaborative efforts within the research team are emphasized to ensure a thorough and unbiased interpretation of the data. This methodology provides a robust framework for understanding the complexities of European building permit processes. By employing a systematic approach to data collection, preparation, analysis, and validation, the study aims to offer valuable insights into the current state of building permitting processes and pave the way for future advancements in digital transformation and process optimization.

The study seeks to contribute significantly to the field by uniformly modeling building permitting processes and offering a detailed understanding of these systems. This foundational work is poised to guide future studies to optimize these processes and develop solutions that more effectively meet the needs of municipalities across Europe. The study underscores the potential benefits of digital transformation in this sector, paving the way for a more streamlined and technologically advanced approach to urban development processes.

One of the most notable findings is the sheer diversity of regulatory frameworks governing building permits. Each country exhibits a unique regulatory landscape molded by its historical, cultural, and socio-political background. This diversity reflects the uniqueness of each country's approach to urban planning and development and poses significant challenges for harmonizing practices across Europe. Despite the variability in regulatory frameworks, common challenges resonate across the board. Bureaucratic complexities are a ubiquitous issue, often leading to significant delays in the processing of permits.

A key trend observed in several countries is the shift towards digitalizing the building permit process. Adopting digital tools and platforms is potentially enhancing efficiency, expediting processes, and fostering transparency. For instance, countries like Estonia and Denmark have made significant strides in digitalizing their building permit processes using comprehensive e-submission systems. Yet, the use of BIM in the permit processes is limited. However, the extent and effectiveness of digital adoption vary widely, with some countries still in the nascent stages of implementing digital solutions.

The study also highlighted several practices and innovations in certain countries, ranging from streamlined application procedures to integrated platforms that allow for multi-agency

coordination through e-submission systems. For example, a few countries have implemented such systems where applicants can complete all necessary procedures in a single platform, significantly reducing the complexity and duration of the permit process. These best practices offer valuable insights and models that other countries could adapt to enhance their building permit systems.

The findings from this study have significant policy implications. They highlight the need for policies adaptable to the specific contexts of different countries and conducive to adopting best practices. Policymakers are encouraged to consider both the unique challenges and the shared experiences of different countries in formulating building permit policies. Moreover, there is a clear indication that policies should support and facilitate digital transformation in the building permit process, as this has been shown to enhance efficiency and transparency. Additionally, the study underscores the importance of stakeholder engagement in policy development, suggesting that inclusive and collaborative approaches can lead to more effective and widely accepted building permit systems.

In conclusion, the comparative analysis of building permit processes in 19 European countries reveals a complex landscape marked by diversity in regulatory frameworks, common challenges, varying degrees of digital transformation, innovative best practices, the significance of stakeholder engagement, and far-reaching policy implications. These findings contribute to a deeper understanding of the building permit processes in Europe and provide a foundation for future reforms and improvements in this critical aspect of urban development.

References

- [1] Ponnewitz, J., & Bargstaedt, H. J. (2019, September). The building permit—How to standardize traditionally established processes. In 20th Congress of IABSE, New York City (pp. 1561-1565).
- [2] Fauth, J. (2021). Building permit process modeling. *EWork EBusiness Archit. Eng. Constr*, 13, 42-50.

Automated Regulatory Compliance: Insights from a Design Research

Joao Soliman-Junior

*Innovative Design Lab (IDL), Department of Design and the Built Environment, School of Arts and Humanities,
University of Huddersfield, Queensgate, Huddersfield, UK, HD1 3DH*

Regulatory compliance is an essential driver in the design of building projects, spanning across different development stages and relating to the fulfilment of constraints, rules and recommendations expressed in regulatory documents. In this process, designers generally abide by the rules and constraints described in the requirements (i.e., adopting a prescriptive approach to design); or use regulatory information to prompt their own creative process [1].

The nature of design has been described by existing research in several ways, considering its iterative, complex, and evolutionary character. Design problems are generally multi-dimensional and highly interactive, in which the development of a solution integrates and addresses a series of different and potentially conflicting requirements [2, 3]. Design consists of a cyclic process through which partial solutions are developed, refined and evaluated over time [4].

An important characteristic of design relates to the problem-solution co-evolution, as design problems and solutions are interdependent, developed simultaneously and complementary [3, 5]. This process does not consist of fixing a problem and searching for an acceptable solution but developing and refining simultaneously both the problem and ideas of potential solutions, through analysis, synthesis and evaluation [3, 5]. During design, these two notional design spaces (i.e., problem and solution spaces) are generally bridged through cognitive processes associated with creativity and subjectivity [5].

Human knowledge is needed to interpret and translate requirements either to develop a design solution [6] or to assess and check design against requirements [7], whereas subjectivity and creativity are intrinsic to both processes [5]. However, regulatory compliance is often understood as detached from the overall design development [8]. Existing digital compliance approaches do not properly consider the iterative design character, as well as its intrinsically creative and subjective nature, also reflected in current regulatory frameworks through ambiguity [9, 10]. The above suggests a disconnection between the building design process and existing digital regulatory compliance approaches, which is associated with several limitations observed in practice and research.

This abstract builds upon the development of a PhD research that adopted Design Science Research (DSR) as a methodological approach. During the research process, a series of 11 semi-structured interviews was developed with designers and professionals involved in the design of healthcare buildings in the UK, in addition to two empirical studies conducted within the healthcare design process. The different sources of evidence used to support the research development led to a rich information repository of qualitative data, which was analysed following an inductive approach. Although the research was focused on the construction of a model to enable automated regulatory compliance in healthcare building design, important insights related to the interplay between the design process and digital-automated regulatory compliance emerged during its development and are reported in this abstract.

Designers suggested that the iterative nature of the design process is closely related to design decision-making from the perspective of (i) translating regulatory requirements into design

attributes and specifications; but also (ii) regarding the verification of whether they meet expected regulatory requirements. This process confirms the important relationship between regulatory compliance and design decision-making expressed by existing literature. It suggests that regulatory information (and the associated compliance process) should be better integrated with the design resolution considering the characteristics which are intrinsic to this process (e.g., iteration, interdependency, problem-solution co-evolution), as opposed to mainly feeding automated regulatory compliance checking systems.

The exploration developed within the design development process highlighted that there is an ongoing change on designers' perception regarding the application of digital tools (and automation) to address regulatory compliance. As reported on [11], the mainstream view of automation as a substitute for human-based activities is limited and paradoxical due to the challenges arising from requirements' subjectivity and ambiguity in this context. An evolving understanding of digital and automated approaches to support designers' decision-making was observed during the empirical stage of this research, with a major focus on addressing regulatory compliance as an input to decision-making, rather than only assessing design's compliance after decision-making. This evolving perception is presented in Figure 1, with the traditional approach for automated regulatory compliance represented in (a), whereas the evolving understanding represented in (b). It is important to highlight that the process represented in (a) is prone to a considerable number of non-compliances, which are generally identified at late design stages leading to extensive rework. The process outlined in (b) helps incorporating regulatory compliance into design decision-making, and, therefore, reducing the number of non-compliances observed in design solutions and in reviews / gateways.

The analysis of these processes suggests that both approaches complement each other, occurring in different stages of the design process (i.e., before and towards decision-making; and after decision-making), and supporting the development of better compliant design solutions. Furthermore, the approach represented in (b) suggests a shift in the way automated regulatory compliance is perceived in practice and explored from a research perspective, allowing this process to be better aligned with design itself, and its intrinsic characteristics. It also highlights the need to foster the development of digital platforms, databases and interfaces that are well-aligned with the overall design characteristics, processes and tools, as evidenced by designers.

From an implementation perspective, different software tools and systems may be able to support this process, which is largely associated with (i) Information Delivery Specifications (IDS) considering the validation of Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) files; as well as with (ii) commercial automated checking software (e.g., Solibri) and databases to support requirements' management more broadly (e.g., Activity Database – ADB, which is a commercial software application that aims to support the development of healthcare-related projects in England).

The format in which current regulatory documents are developed and published has been described by the research participants as increasing the challenge of automated regulatory compliance from the design perspective. There are practical issues reported by designers related to: (i) accessing regulatory information, due to the high number of individual documents and the fact they are dispersed over different domains, increasing the complexity of the regulatory compliance process; (ii) relevance of regulatory information, as in many cases documents are outdated and inconsistent; and (iii) language and format in which regulatory information is presented, which are generally highly ambiguous and unfit for existing digital approaches for automated regulatory compliance. In this context, the use of paper-based (or digital PDF) documents increases the challenges associated with requirements' storage, reuse, standardisation, traceability and comprehensiveness, which consist of essential elements of a digitally-enabled requirements' management process [12].

As a result of the challenges outlined above, during the empirical activities developed as part of the research process, regulatory documents were often consulted and referred to in relation to compliance following an inconsistent approach. This has increased the difficulties associated with the implementation of automated regulatory compliance in practice, especially considering the diversity of requirements identified in regulatory documents, which can be subjective, ambiguous and ill-defined.

a) traditional approach for automated regulatory compliance

b) evolving understanding of automated regulatory compliance

Fig. 1: Evolving understanding of automated regulatory compliance from the design perspective.

The exploration of automated regulatory compliance from a design perspective provided several contributions, enabling the identification of important insights needed to further support its implementation and achieve the practical benefits that have been discussed by existing literature for several years. This study highlighted that automated regulatory compliance could assume a steering role in the design process, supporting decision-making and changing the paradigm upon which research on this subject has been mostly focused so far. By analysing regulatory compliance from a design point of view, it was possible to better understand why subjectivity and

ambiguity manifest in regulatory requirements. They consist of intrinsic characteristics of the design process and cannot be simply disregarded from research on automated regulatory compliance. Further exploration is needed on how such characteristics can be adequately addressed as part of automated regulatory compliance approaches, including their practical implementation with existing software and tools yet to be developed, as well as their dependency on human consideration in a context of data-driven decision making.

References

- [1] Von der Tann, L., Angelino, M., Crick, R., & Taylor, C. (2018). Rethinking design standards as learning frameworks. ICIF White Paper Collection. International Centre for Infrastructure Futures (ICIF). <https://doi.org/10.14324/000.wp.10060293>
- [2] Koskela, L. (2000). An exploration towards a production theory and its application to construction: Dissertation. [Dissertation, Aalto University]. VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland.
- [3] Lawson, B. (2005). How designers think (4th ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780080454979>
- [4] Christensen, B. T., & Ball, L. J. (2016). Dimensions of creative evaluation: Distinct design and reasoning strategies for aesthetic, functional and originality judgments. *Design Studies*, 45, 116–136. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.destud.2015.12.005>
- [5] Dorst, K., & Cross, N. (2001). Creativity in the design process: co-evolution of problem–solution. *Design Studies*, 22(5), 425–437. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-694X\(01\)00009-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0142-694X(01)00009-6)
- [6] Darlington, M., & Culley, S. (2004). A model of factors influencing the design requirement. *Design Studies*, 25(4), 329–350. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.destud.2003.12.003>
- [7] Solihin, W., & Eastman, C. M. (2016). A knowledge representation approach in BIM rule requirement analysis using the conceptual graph. *Journal of Information Technology in Construction*, 21(March), 370–401. <http://www.itcon.org/2016/24>
- [8] Hjelseth, E. (2016). Classification of BIM-based model checking concepts. *Journal of Information Technology in Construction*, 21(October), 354–370.
- [9] Nawari, N. O. (2019). A Generalized Adaptive Framework (GAF) for automating code compliance checking. *Buildings*, 9(4), 86. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings9040086>
- [10] Zhang, Z., Ma, L., & Nisbet, N. (2023). Unpacking ambiguity in building requirements to support automated compliance checking. *Journal of Management in Engineering*, 39(5), 04023033.
- [11] Soliman-Junior, J., Tzortzopoulos, P., & Kagioglou, M. (2022). Designers' perspective on the use of automation to support regulatory compliance in healthcare building projects. *Construction Management and Economics*, 40(2), 123–141. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01446193.2021.2022176>
- [12] Baldauf, J. P., Formoso, C. T., & Tzortzopoulos, P. (2021). Method for managing requirements in healthcare projects using building information modelling. *Engineering, Construction and Architectural Management*, 28(8), 2090–2118. <https://doi.org/10.1108/ECAM-12-2020-1040>

Building Permit Process Digitalization: A Municipal Implementation Process Map

Orjola Braholli ^a, Mariana Ataide ^a, Dietmar Siegele ^a, Ilaria Di Blasio ^a, Kavita Raj ^b

^a Fraunhofer Italia, Via A. Volta 13a, 39100 Bolzano

^b University of Brescia, Piazza del Mercato, 15, 25121 Brescia BS

Introduction

A building permit is a legal authorization granted by municipal authorities to start the construction after verifying the proposed design adheres to building and urban planning regulations [1]. Its process is vital for safe and sustainable development but remains complex and inefficient for both applicants and building authorities. It involves extensive paperwork submissions that undergo exhaustive manual verification checks to ensure compliance across codes and regulations pertaining to construction, zoning, safety, accessibility and more [1].

On the other side, cities today face massive development and infrastructure demands to support urban growth and sustainability goals. ²⁴ Traditional permitting processes act as a major bottleneck, lacking transparency, and responsiveness and don't meet rising urbanization and climate goals.

Digitalization and process re-engineering offer a transformative solution to address these long-standing problems. Digitalization can significantly improve efficiency and productivity by streamlining workflows, reducing processing times, and minimizing errors through automation [2,3]. Digital platforms and building information modelling (BIM) provide a transparent and auditable trail, enhancing accountability and reducing inconsistencies [4]. Automated rule-checking and compliance validation using BIM models ensure that proposed designs adhere to building codes, zoning regulations, and relevant standards, improving overall quality and safety [5,6]. Fourthly, BIM models and digital platforms facilitate seamless collaboration and information sharing among stakeholders, such as architects, engineers, developers, and regulatory authorities [7].

Moreover, by integrating BIM models with geographic information systems (GIS) data and urban planning tools, digitalized permitting processes support sustainable and resilient urban development, enabling better analysis and decision-making related to energy efficiency, resource utilization, and environmental impact [8]. Finally, modular and flexible digital permitting systems can be adapted and scaled to meet the unique needs of different municipalities, enabling a consistent and standardized approach across regions or countries [9].

This extended abstract presents a comprehensive framework for transforming the building permit process through digitalization and process re-engineering, addressing the critical challenges faced by traditional methods and unlocking numerous benefits for stakeholders and urban environments.

Challenges in traditional building permit process and mapping the transformation process.

The CHEK project²⁵ analyses processes in 6 European municipalities to establish a harmonised baseline. The findings expose extensive inefficiencies stemming from redundant documentation,

²⁴Available at: [Urban Development Overview \(worldbank.org\)](https://www.worldbank.org/) Accessed: 08.03.2024.

²⁵ Available at: [D1.1 CHEK_101058559_CHEK-DBP-process-map_V1.0-Final.pdf \(chekdbp.eu\)](https://www.chekdbp.eu/)

duplicate compliance reviews across agencies, and data silos from the use of fragmented tools and systems. This hampers officials' capacity to validate and approve projects in communities despite urgent needs. There is a pressing necessity to modernize permitting through comprehensive digitization coupled with optimized, holistic workflows based on machine-readable building data models. This research maps a bold vision to transform permitting through digitization and process re-engineering.

Transitioning from manual processes requires clearly defining an optimized digital workflow. The transformations must outline detailed steps to enable integrated data sharing, automated parametric compliance checks and validations while retaining the necessary quality control safeguards and security measures for responsible oversight.

The absence of such clearly documented transformation guidance is a key barrier deterring municipalities from embarking on digitization initiatives despite their need and will. Defining detailed specifications around evolving to advanced digital permitting systems could catalyze modernization.

Though specific procedures vary, commonalities exist in building permitting processes internationally and across Europe, with identifiable macro-phases including submission, documentation/content control and review, permit issuance, and third-party authorizations [2,3,10,11]. Despite lack of standardization, European countries share similarities in responsibilities, tasks, and overarching phases encompassing application, compliance checking, approval, and external stakeholder input.

The BIM-based digital building permit process map presented in CHEK offers municipalities a structured framework to streamline permitting and reduce errors through enhanced collaboration, transparency, and efficiency. By following this digitalized process, stakeholders can access shared information to consistently review submissions. Moreover, BIM can semi-automate compliance checking. This process map can provide municipalities tools to implement digitalization, moving towards automated and optimized building permit workflows.

Proposed approach: Digital building permit process

Furthermore, the study addresses the scalability gap in digital building permitting solutions by testing solutions across diverse representative municipalities and extending implementation more broadly. The modular "deconstruct and reconstruct" design of the CHEK-to-be process map increases adaptability to local procedures and needs. This modular structure enhances scalability, allowing the map to be customized for use by a wider community of municipalities.

To address the issues, the study leveraged the assessment insights from studying current municipal workflows to systematically re-conceptualize an optimal building permit digitization strategy. Referencing also previous studies [3,4,11–16] on process mapping it employed business process modelling techniques to map and redesign the existing workflows.

The building methodology of the to-be process map focuses on unifying historically siloed data, systems and stages into a streamlined digital fabric centralized around machine-readable building data models. This building information modelling approach using international non-proprietary data schemas like Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) aims to embed verifiable compliance by design rather than through document reviews. The visual models formally capture all regulatory parameters at the outset enabling automated checking.

The output delivers an in-depth building permit process map laying out 13 phases from data collection, unofficial and official validation, e-submission, procedural data verification and automated rule-checking, integration of third-party evaluators to occupancy permits and city GIS updates. Each phase prescribes the essential actors, activities, checks, tool chains, validations

and level of transparency required to guide adoption. This structured pathway is intended to provide actionable directions for administrators and technology implementers.

Transformation phases

The research produced a comprehensive building permit digitalization process map tailored for municipalities to adopt in a staged manner at their own pace. The guidelines deliberately support flexibility in deployment and allow integrating different technology solutions for various components like online portals, document management, workflow coordination, visualization, analysis, and reporting tools [9].

However, the process map fundamentally envisages transforming current permitting by holistically centralizing and streamlining all historically fragmented systems, processes, data, and departments around interactive geospatial information and building information submissions. This shift to “information model-based permit” aims to thoroughly overhaul and reinvent largely manual workflows struggling to support the pace and complexity of now days urbanization trends.

The process has three main phases – pre-submission, digital building permit and post-approval. Each of the phases is divided into sub-phases and actions. Fig. 6 illustrates the process in a summarized way.

Fig. 6: CHEK TO-BE process map.

The to-be process map modernizes permit approvals across three key phases:

Pre-submission: The applicant collects permit data specifications like building codes, zoning regulations and assessment rules from the municipal geospatial data portal. Custom 3D templates can be generated. A converter utility transfers relevant spatial context into the BIM authoring software for integrating site constraints into early design stages. The applicant models the development proposal and runs automated compliance diagnostics against regulations using the self-same libraries which the authorities employ. This pre-check provides predictive visibility allowing proactive modifications prior to submission if rules are infringed rather than corrective work after rejection.

Digital Building Permit: The applicant submits the model for an automated validity check on whether it meets open BIM standards to ensure data interpretability. Structured metadata is also extracted into the workflow system. If compliant, it would be possible to initiate rule checking workflows and further visual assessments in a transparent process tracking comments and versions. The automated validation routines assess designs against parametric building code requirements. Outcomes are categorized as pass, fail or manual review. Failed rules generate change requests notified to the applicant. The process iterates correction cycles until full compliance.

Post-Approval: The applicant is mandated to update as-built models' post-completion for regulators to confirm conformance. The municipality can additionally integrate the verified asset models into its GIS infrastructure inventory for analytics, maintenance planning, emergency response and future permitting. This continual digital twin enrichment enhances civic operations²⁶.

The re-engineered process intends to balance innovation aspirations with pragmatic adoption barriers like change aversion, thin resources, and technical debt constraints. It allows flexible tools adoption across phases while advancing the system capabilities in a sustainable cadence through incremental maturation rather than disruptive replacement.

Each has detailed steps ranging from rule checking and needed data specifications through final as-built updates. All requisite validations, software tools, algorithms, automation routines, data ingestion APIs and governance policies are delineated for each milestone to help the municipalities structure implementation process maps attuned to local realities and priorities. Officials can readily actuate changes suited to immediate resource availability while maintaining continuity towards the end-vision.

Benefits and scalability

This research delineates a clear to-be process map for phasing in a future-state digital building permit system guided by CHEK principles. It provides granular requirements and allows flexibility in technology solutions. The framework aims to contribute to the re-shaping process of the building permit practices across Europe, starting from the analysis of current processes to ensure enhanced compliance of the result. Widespread adoption can set the stage for ecosystem-based construction regulation powered by accurate information models and automated analytics. The impact could remake how we build and develop modern sustainable cities.

The work emerging from this research provides cities a launch pad to enhance the process of how we responsibly build and develop urban spaces and buildings. The methodologies and findings yield an important template for replication in a larger scale.

Acknowledgements

This study was developed within the 'CHEK – Change toolkit for digital building permit' project, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement No.101058559.

References

- [1] F. Noardo, D. Guler, J. Fauth, G. Malacarne, S. Mastrolembo Ventura, M. Azenha, P.-O. Olsson, L. Senger, Unveiling the actual progress of Digital Building Permit: Getting awareness through a critical state of the art review, *Build. Environ.* 213 (2022) 108854. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.108854>.
- [2] F. Meijer, H. Visscher, Quality control of constructions: European trends and developments, *Int. J. Law Built Environ.* 9 (2017) 143–161. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJLBE-02-2017-0003>.
- [3] F. Noardo, G. Malacarne, V.S. Mastrolembo, L.C. Tagliabue, A.L.C. Ciribini, C. Ellul, D. Guler, L. Harrie, L. Senger, A. Waha, J. Stoter, Integrating expertises and ambitions for data-driven digital building permits - the EUNET4DBP, *ISPRS Arch.* 44 4 W1 44 (2020) 103–110. <https://doi.org/10.15488/10827>.

²⁶ Only the digital building permit phase is under the scope of the CHEK project.

- [4] D. Guler, T. Yomralioglu, A reformative framework for processes from building permit issuing to property ownership in Turkey, *Land Use Policy* 101 (2021) 105115. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2020.105115>.
- [5] C. Eastman, J. Lee, Y. Jeong, J. Lee, Automatic rule-based checking of building designs, *Autom. Constr.* 18 (2009) 1011–1033. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2009.07.002>.
- [6] W. Solihin, J. Dimiyadi, Y. Lee, C. Eastman, R. Amor, The Critical Role of Accessible Data for BIM-Based Automated Rule Checking Systems, 2017. <https://doi.org/10.24928/JC3-2017/0161>.
- [7] U. Isikdag, J. Underwood, *A Synopsis of the Handbook of Research on Building Information Modelling*, 2010.
- [8] G. Celeste, M. Lazoi, M. Mangia, G. Mangialardi, Innovating the Construction Life Cycle through BIM/GIS Integration: A Review, *Sustainability* 14 (2022) 766. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su14020766>.
- [9] O. Braholli, M. Ataide, I. Di Blasio, K. Raj, D. Siegele, CHEK To-be Digital Building Permit process map, (2023). <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.7789035>.
- [10] J. Fauth, L. Soibelman, Conceptual Framework for Building Permit Process Modeling: Lessons Learned from a Comparison between Germany and the United States regarding the As-Is Building Permit Processes, *Buildings* 12 (2022) 638. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings12050638>.
- [11] J.B. Pedro, F. Meijer, H. Visscher, Comparison of building permit procedures in European Union countries, in: Manchester, 2011.
- [12] A. Balaid, M.Z. Abd Rozan, S.N. Hikmi, J. Memon, Knowledge maps: A systematic literature review and directions for future research, *Int. J. Inf. Manag.* 36 (2016) 451–475. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2016.02.005>.
- [13] J. Fauth, G. Pasetti Monizza, G. Malacarne, Understanding processes on digital building permits – a case study in South Tyrol, *Build. Res. Inf.* 51 (2023) 518–532. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09613218.2023.2178372>.
- [14] M. Messaoudi, N.O. Nawari, BIM-based Virtual Permitting Framework (VPF) for post-disaster recovery and rebuilding in the state of Florida, *Int. J. Disaster Risk Reduct.* 42 (2020) 101349. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2019.101349>.
- [15] D. Piazza, M. Röck, G. Malacarne, A. Passer, C. Marcher, D.T. Matt, BIM for public authorities: Basic research for the standardized implementation of BIM in the building permit process, *IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci.* 323 (2019) 012102. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/323/1/012102>.
- [16] J. Ponnewitz, H.-J. Bargstaedt, The building permit – how to standardize traditionally established processes, in: New York, New York, USA, 2019: pp. 1560–1564. <https://doi.org/10.2749/newyork.2019.1560>.

[A conceptual framework for managing the building permitting process in Brazilian municipalities](#)

Douglas Malheiro de Brito^a, Dayana Bastos Costa^b, and Emerson de Andrade Marques Ferreira^b

^aPost-Graduation Program in Civil Engineering, Federal University of Bahia, Aristides Novis Street, Salvador, Brazil

^bDepartment of Structural and Construction Engineering, Federal University of Bahia, Aristides Novis Street, Salvador, Brazil

Introduction

Despite many research efforts to achieve higher levels of digitalization and even some automation for the building permitting process, the common practice in many municipalities around the world has been the simple conversion of permitting manual, based on paper documentation, for the implementation of digital document management systems, but with manual analysis.

However, according to Bloch and Fauth (2023), the next level of digitalization is focused on managing information rather than documents, through the adoption of systems based on models developed in accordance with the building information modelling (BIM) methodology, integrating information from the geographic information system (GIS). Finally, at the highest level of maturity, the digital process will be integrated with decision-making support tools, based on automated code checking.

From a scientific point of view, there is a gap between research that investigates cases in a top-down approach, in which there is no detail necessary to support digitalization and automation, and studies aimed at developing automated tools in a bottom-up approach, which has great limitations for generalizing and connecting individual efforts into a holistic solution (Bloch; Fauth, 2023).

In this sense, Fauth et al. (2023) emphasize the need for a broad understanding of the building permitting process itself, including processes, regulations and tools used, instead of providing decentralized autonomous solutions, which do not consider, evaluate and digitalize all the sub-processes involved. The cited authors also highlight that the quantitative measurement of parameters, such as time savings and increased satisfaction, constitute opportunities for contributions to future research.

Therefore, it is possible to identify a research gap in proposing frameworks that enable the understanding, execution and monitoring of actions to digitalize the building permits by municipalities. The main objective of this study is to propose a conceptual framework of a model for managing the digitalization process of building permitting in Brazilian municipalities. This study is part of doctoral research that proposes a model for managing the process of digital building permitting in medium to large Brazilian municipalities at the construction permit stage.

Research Method

The research method adopted is Design Science Research (DSR), also known as Constructive Research, in which the researcher understands a question, designs and evaluates a possible solution (HEVNER et al., 2004).

The first stage encompasses a comprehensive review of existing initiatives and literature on digital building permits and automating code checking. In addition to evaluating scientific papers,

regulations (such as ISO-19650) and technical publications, documents issued by the Regulatory Room of buildingSMART International, ongoing projects by the European Network for Digital Building Permits (EUnet4DBP), and the guidelines proposed in the Construa Brasil Project (2022) are considered to identify the factors that influence the sequencing and prioritization of the digitalization stages. Sequencing is an important part of digitalization planning, as construction permit types require several digitalization steps.

At the same time, a case study was conducted in the municipality of Salvador in Brazil, which has around three million inhabitants. The choice was made because it is one of the pioneering municipalities in Brazil to begin in 2016 the digitalization process for BIM applications of the type of construction permits for single-tower multi-residential housing.

Data collection occurred through document analysis and semi-structured interviews on site and via video conference with the responsible team from the municipality and the company that developed the Tekto platform for digital building permitting, aiming to map the main processes, stakeholders and their interrelationships, as per detailed in Brito et al. (2023). Furthermore, the collection also sought to identify possible metrics for estimating and monitoring performance and benefits in relation to traditional processes.

Then, based on the identification of international initiatives and the case study, the conceptual framework for managing the digitalization process of building permitting in Brazilian municipalities was explained in the stages of planning and sequencing; digitalization, and monitoring until restarting the process. Finally, the discussion stage of the results aims to formalize this research's theoretical and practical contributions.

Findings

The proposed conceptual structure is represented in Figure 1 through a roadmap, the first stage of which covers the planning and sequencing of digitalization, where the municipality explains the types of existing construction permits according to prioritization criteria, current maturity levels and intended and the selection of indicators for monitoring performance in relation to traditional processes. As a result of this first stage, part of the existing construction permits is prioritized, according to the quantity demanded and the current concession deadlines.

The next stage is the digitalization of the permits prioritized in the municipality, which will be supported by the artifacts delivered by the model in the previous stage, such as a structure for defining the information requirements of projects that use BIM and a requirements protocol for development and implementation of the Common Data Environment (CDE) for digital permits. The completion of this stage occurs when the digital permits is available for request by applicants, which may generate a new digitalization stage or the monitoring of already digital permits using a protocol for monitoring performance and benefits achieved.

Monitoring will take place until it is possible to update legislation and the municipal Building Code, supported by a protocol of best practices for evaluating codes, aiming to enable the resumption of new digitalization stages with more automation in checks and, consequently, higher levels of maturity, restarting the proposed roadmap.

The municipality analysed in the case study completed the first stage of digitalization in mid-2022, when it made the construction permit available to applicants for projects submitted in BIM, modelled using Revit software, for the typology of single-tower multi-residential. The forecast is that digitalization will be expanded, sequentially, to other types of construction permits existing in Salvador, such as: other residential, commercial and infrastructure projects, which can be planned and sequenced based on the application of this framework.

The model's prioritization criteria for planning and sequencing digitalization involve the historical average of the number of requests and average deadline for approval for each type of construction permit, prioritizing those proportionally most requested or time consuming. Furthermore, the model suggests an extension, characterized by the number of types of construction permits prioritized simultaneously in digitalization, proportionally smaller as the municipality intends to reach higher levels of maturity, which involve the use of BIM models and the automated code checking.

Fig. 1: Conceptual framework for managing the digitalization process of building permitting in Brazilian municipalities.

As well as the extent of digitalization, the model recommends other categories of indicators for monitoring the transition, such as: reduction of deadlines and time for analysis; reduction in the number of requests for clarification or design changes; increased capacity to issue permits, and potential return on investment. Figure 2 shows the proposed indicators for each category.

The main theoretical contribution is the proposition of a conceptual framework that enables the understanding, implementation and monitoring of digitalization. The results contribute to filling the research gap in generating more holistic solutions, which consider bottom-up and top-down approaches, as well as suggesting quantitative indicators for measuring digitalization.

As a practical contribution, the model can guide professionals involved in digitalization in Brazilian municipalities and can assist in the development and evaluation of strategies to overcome challenges and barriers to advancing digitalization. Future stages of the research will operationalize the conceptual structure into a model to be applied in some Brazilian municipalities in the process of digital building permitting, aiming to evaluate the potential, ease of adoption, barriers and impacts of using the model.

Categories	Indicators
Extension	Percentage of permits that can be issued digitally in the municipality
	Percentage of digital permits issued in relation to the total number issued
Reduction of deadlines and time for analysis	Average percentage of reduction in the issuance deadline in relation to the traditional process
Reduction in the number of requests for clarification or design changes	Average percentage of reduction in the number of clarifications or changes in design for issuing digital permits
Increased capacity to issue permits	Average percentage of increase in permit issuance capacity
Potential return on investment	Potential payback time on digitalization investment
	Potential increase in annual revenue from issuing permits

Fig. 2: Categories of indicators for monitoring performance in relation to traditional processes.

References

- [1] Bloch, T., & Fauth, J. (2023). The unbalanced research on digitalization and automation of the building permitting process. *Adv. Eng. Informatics*, 58, 102188.
- [2] Brito, D. M. B; Costa, D. B.; & Ferreira, E. A. M. (2023). *The Interrelation of Processes and stakeholders for digital building permitting in the Brazilian AECO Sector*. In Book of Short Papers of the 10th International Workshop When Social Sciences meets Lean and Digital technologies: 10 years and beyond. University of Huddersfield.
- [3] Construa Brasil Project (2022). Guia Orientativo de Boas Práticas para Códigos de Obras e Edificações. Brasil. Secretaria Especial de Produtividade e Competitividade, Ministério da Economia. <https://www.gov.br/produtividade-e-comercio-exterior/pt-br/ambiente-de-negocios/competitividade-industrial/construa-brasil/produtos/2209ConstruaBrasilGuiaOrientativodeBoasPraticasParaCodigosdeEdificacoes.pdf>.
- [4] Construa Brasil Project (2022). Guia Orientativo de Boas Práticas para Obtenção de Alvarás de Construção. Brasil. Secretaria Especial de Produtividade e Competitividade, Ministério da Economia. <https://www.gov.br/produtividade-e-comercio-exterior/pt-br/ambiente-de-negocios/competitividade-industrial/construa-brasil/produtos/2209ConstruaBrasilGuiaOrientativodeBoasPraticasParaObtencaodeAlvarasdeConstrucao.pdf>.
- [5] Fauth, J., Monizza, G. P., & Malacarne, G. (2023) *Understanding processes on digital building permits – a case study in South Tyrol*, *Building Research & Information*, 51:5, 518-532.
- [6] International Organization for Standardization (2018). Information Management using Building Information Modeling – Part 2: Delivery Phase of the assets (ISO Standard No. 19650-2:2018). <https://www.iso.org/standard/68078.html>.

TECHNOLOGICAL SYSTEM Research Track

The abstracts in this section were peer reviewed.

Geometry level of information needs for digital building permit regulations

S. EL Yamani^{a*}, J. Stoter^a, F. Noardo^b, A.Hakim^a, K. Arroyo Ochori^a, J.van der Vaart^a

^a 3D Geoinformation, Delft University of Technology, Delft, the Netherlands.

^b Open Geospatial Consortium Europe, Technologielaan 3, B - 3001 Heverlee, Belgium.

Abstract

In the evolving landscape of digitalization, automating building permit processes are crucial for municipalities and other governmental bodies. Our research addresses the complexities of modeling digital building permit regulations, considering the level of the information needs (LoIN) for geometry-based regulations in four municipalities (Prague, Lisbon, Vila Nova de Gaia, and Ascoli Piceno) as case study. We propose a methodology and guidelines for geometrical building modeling, addressing challenges of integrating geoinformation with Building Information Modeling (BIM) for environmental based digital building permit (DBP) checks. This paper provides BIM-IFC geometrical interpretation choices, ensuring a seamless conversion into 3D city models. It offers insights for software companies, developers, and standardization organizations towards in implementing DBP checks, and preliminary results for a future scalable approach.

Key words: *Digital building permit, CHEK project, GEOBIM, BIM, IFC.*

Introduction

The increasing adoption of Building information models (BIM) in early urban design phases and developments in digital systems have highlighted the need for automating building permit processes worldwide. Current manual, 2D plan-based methods suffer from inaccuracies and inefficiencies, causing errors and delays in the construction pipeline. These outdated processes lack adaptability, leading to multiple resubmissions and significant financial setbacks for municipalities and the Architecture, Engineering, Construction, and Operation (AECO) Industry[1], [2].

To address these issues, (partly) automated DBP processes can be considered. Through digital processes it will be possible to avoid errors in regulations interpretations and improve consistency because the complexity of 3D geo-related regulations can be assessed and measured accurately (e.g., building height, distance building-building).

Despite prior attempts worldwide to digitize and automate building permit processes, including notable initiatives like the European network for Digital Building Permit (EUnet4DBP)¹, there remains a predominant focus on analyzing building data sets, often using Industry Foundation Classes (IFC), without adequately integrating BIM and 3D city models for comprehensive geometrical modeling in digital building permit checking [3], [4].

The Open GeoSpatial Consortium (OGC) offers standards like CityGML and CityJSON for integrating and digitizing 3D city models. These standards, including CityGML and CityJSON, employ the concept of Level of Detail (LoD) to define the granularity of both geometric and semantic information in building and city data models. Recently, CityGML has updated its LoD classification in version 3.0 to cater to various applications.

In the context of Building Information Modeling (BIM), concepts such as Level of Development, Level of Accuracy, and Level of Information have been introduced to extend the model framework. However, these concepts often lack standardization, resulting in diverse interpretations of the required level of detail, especially concerning geometric requirements.

To address this issue, BuildingSmart has introduced Level of Information Need (LoIN) as a new standard (EN 17412-1). LoIN emphasizes tailoring information granularity to suit specific needs for information exchange based on contextual use. The evolution of the Level of Development concept is progressing through the concept of Level of Information Need (LOIN), which serves as a necessary foundation for developing notions of Level of Geometry (LOG) and Level of Information (LOI).

While previous research has focused on specific aspects of digital building permit requirements, such as building height in Rotterdam or LoIN in Victoria, there remains a lack of a scalable approach for addressing the geometric information needed across different regulatory contexts. Our project addresses this gap by analyzing the geometric requirements of four municipalities across different European scales. We provide insights based on developed GEOBIM solutions for extracting envelope data and converting it to CityJSON format. This approach, which has been lacking in previous research, aims to address the challenge of scaling geometric information from BIM to geospatial data, offering a tested and feasible solution for the entire process.

This paper aims to harmonize the involved BIM and GEO information to provide the necessary geometrical information for digital building permit checking. This involves a methodology that considers the BIM and GEO connection, incorporating proper generalization techniques. The objective is to offer a comprehensive solution to interpret geometrical modeling requirements for effective digital building permit checking.

This research is carried out as part of the CHEK project. The ‘Change toolkit for DBP’ (CHEK)^{2,3} project is a European initiative to develop digital tools and methods for DBP checks based on the integration of building and 3D city data.

This project combines multidisciplinary and multisectoral aspects, aiming to support municipalities in the transformation towards DBP.

This work aims to propose a scalable methodology detailed in the following section, to assist designers and software developers in modeling data requirements to support DBP processes. The goal is to facilitate optimal geometrical decisions for the conversion from BIM to 3D geoinformation, aligning with regulatory interpretations and supporting scalable building permit regulations for municipalities as shown in Figure 1. To ensure scalability and accessibility, we have chosen to use international open standards—specifically, CityGML/CityJSON by the Open Geospatial Consortium and Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) by BuildingSmart—as our reference data formats [5].

Methodology

The methodology focuses on implementing BIM guidelines to be able to extract the required geometry from BIM models, facilitating the conversion from IFC to CityJSON/CityGML to align with DBP regulations. The guidelines are tailored to the selected project regulations, encompassing BIM, 3D city models, legal requirements, and urban zones, each presenting unique complexities and data inputs.

The primary emphasis is on geometrical regulations, including Distance from other city objects, Maximum Building Height, Minimum Area, and Maximum Buildability Index. The goal is to comprehensively analyze these regulations across the four municipalities, offering suitable interpretations. Then, data requirements are identified based on LoINs and modeled to deliver a

structured IFC with geometrical information, enabling designers and architects to convert it into a 3D city environment (CityGML/CityJSON), and to verify the specified regulations.

Regulations are chosen based on thorough investigations⁴ conducted across the four municipalities.

Fig. 1: Goal of a scalable approach to facilitate the implementation and integration of BIM with GEO data for municipalities and assist stakeholders in the process of digitalization.

Fig. 2: methodology steps for BIM based regulations geometrical requirements.

Figure 2 outlines the methodology steps, emphasizing legal regulations chosen by the four municipalities as preliminary guidelines for the DBP process. The automation of these regulations involves identifying geometrical requirements for 3D building models, such as the building envelope, floors, façade, and georeferencing information. The outcome comprises geometrical LoIN guidelines to guide designers and software developers in meeting these requirements during the design phase. In the following, we will address the issues to be considered in the geometrical

LoIN guidelines as identified by the interpretation of the selected regulations in the four municipalities, which will be further elaborated in the proposed paper.

1. Distance:

Analyzing building permit issuance at the BIM level involves primarily assessing BIM requirements. In contrast, the BIM2Geo conversion incorporates the new design into a 3D city model, enabling distance checks in relation to its environment for four regulations: (1) distance building-building, (2) building-parcel boundaries distance, (3) building-road distance, and (4) balconies-road distance. BIM2Geo conversion enables accurate distance measurements by meeting the geometrical data needs, such as openings, façade details, balcony overhangs, footprint/ground floor extraction, and BIM georeferencing (Figure 3).

Fig. 3: illustrates Distance data requirements for the Municipality of Vila Nova de Gaia (reference: CHEK project Deliverable).

2. Maximum Building Height:

The building height is determined from the building's footprint at ground level to the roof's highest point. This calculation requires factors like facade details, extracted envelopes, and georeferencing (to refer the building to the height model of the surrounding terrain). Calculations use ground level as a baseline, excluding underground parts. Measurement starts from ground level, or the lowest vertex of the building as shown in Figure 4 as an example based on GAIA and LISBON municipalities national regulations definition of building height.

The maximum building height is defined differently depending on each municipality it can be either a maximum height number, or calculated based on the average surrounding building height and in some cases based on the maximum building floors as the case of Portuguese regulations.

1. Minimum Area: Building Spaces

Compliance with municipality regulations determining the minimum area requires extracting BIM spaces, encompassing area and volume determinations.

Fig. 4: illustrates Building height and maximum building height definitions for Lisbon and GAIA's regulations (illustrations credits to University of Minho).

2. Maximum Buildability Index:

Determining the buildability index of a parcel involves ground floor extraction for the built area, extruded to the building's height level.

The geometrical requirements that arise from the above-mentioned regulations, need to be further analyzed to make the optimal choices in terms of the most suitable level of information need to prepare the IFC to be converted, so that the output contains the accurate relevant geometries. In the final paper we will describe the results from our research on the correct interpretation of regulations in terms of geometrical requirements, addressing various aspects as presented in Figure 5:

- **Accuracy:** Our research covers identifying the minimum accuracy requirement for municipalities, understanding accepted tolerances in practice, and determining the Level of Detail (LOD) necessary for the conversion to 3D City models.
- **Georeferencing:** We will define the source and target coordinate reference systems, including their specifications, and ensure their proper storage within the BIM environment. Additionally, we will clarify the version of IFC used and ensure the accurate storage of georeferencing and conversion data within the IFC file. The relevant information is stored in IFC using `IfcProjectedCRS` and `IfcMapConversion`.

To facilitate this process, we have developed a georeferencing tool called `IfcGref`, a web application designed for controlling, assigning, or modifying georeferencing information in IFC models, which are the standard format for exchanging BIM data. `IfcGref` allows users to visualize the roof outlines of IFC models on the target coordinate reference system (CRS) map. This Flask-based tool, accessible at <https://ifcgref.bk.tudelft.nl>, offers a comprehensive solution for designers, engineers, and software developers.

It supports georeferencing operations from IFC 4 onwards, ensuring backward compatibility with earlier versions. By leveraging attributes like `SourceCRS`, `TargetCRS`, and other key parameters, `IfcGref` enables precise coordinate transformations. Its user-friendly interface simplifies file upload and verification processes.

- **Spaces extraction:** The feasibility of extracting rooms from BIM-`IfcSpace` is further analyzed and guidelines will be formulated for structuring spaces correctly. It is also considered whether to export areas as elements and spaces as complexes.

Voxelization appears to be the most reliable method for approximating spaces, despite its inherent inaccuracies in room shape and dimensions (height, area, and volume). A challenge arises from the fact that data stored in the IFC file may not always be entirely reliable. In BIM software like Revit, IFC spaces are often invisible shapes that may not fully align with surrounding geometry (e.g., walls, floors), complicating detection of potential issues for BIM modelers. Furthermore, BIM software may alter geometry during export to IFC, posing challenges for resolution by modelers.

Even if room geometry is accurately extracted, there remains a concern regarding incorrect semantic classification. While IFC space can be categorized as "partial," "Element," or "Complex," they are typically labeled as elements, making it difficult to differentiate rooms from other building components.

Given these challenges, conducting a voxelization comparison by comparing the footprint's area and the room's volume with that of the voxelated shape can serve as a straightforward indicator of potential geometric inaccuracies. If significant discrepancies are observed, it could alert users to potential issues with specific rooms, indicating possible geometric inconsistencies.

- **Building envelope extraction:** The elements of the BIM to be considered are identified, exploring the use of specific IFC models within the BIM, and assessing spatial structure segmentations like storeys and bounding boxes for approximating the envelope. The reference surface and criteria for generalizing the building envelope are also determined.

To accomplish this, we employ the IFC BuildingEnvExtractor, a tool developed by van der Vaart (2023), available at https://github.com/jaspervdv/IFC_BuildingEnvExtractor. This tool extracts multiple abstracted Levels of Detail (LoD) shells from IFC files, aligning with the LoD specifications outlined by Biljecki et al. (2016). The number of extractable shells depends on the input model's quality. The tool defines three extraction levels, each with similar methods. Low-level shells (LoD0.0 & 1.0) are generated by approximating the smallest bounding box around the input model, applicable to any valid IFC file. Mid-level shells (LoD0.2, 1.2, 1.3 & 2.2) isolate the roof structure of the input model, projecting or downward extruding it. Accurate output depends on a well-modelled roof. High-level shells (LoD3.2) are derived from the surfaces of objects constructing the outer envelope, requiring well-constructed objects in the original BIM model for accurate extraction.

- **Façade alignment:** The right geometrical tolerance for façade details and overhangs are analyzed, including considerations for the Level of Detail (LOD) necessary to guarantee overhang accuracy.

Overhangs require evaluation at LoD3.x to ensure precision; lower LoDs do not adequately support overhangs. However, for buildings with simpler shapes, LoD2.x may suffice. The choice between footprint-based or roof outline-based LoD2.x depends on the evaluation requirements.

An intriguing option arises when considering larger tolerances. At LoD3.x, the shell extractor employs 1e-6 tolerances. Thus, a successful LoD3.x export likely accurately reflects the IFC shell geometry. However, at a city scale, this level of accuracy is often unnecessary. Utilizing a voxelized shape may suffice, particularly for slightly flawed models, providing satisfactory results for most evaluation purposes. Additionally, it supports overhangs, which LoD2.x does not.

- **Floor extraction:** A methodology for extracting floors based on IfcBuildingStorey and IfcSlab, the proper modeling of IfcBuildingStorey features, and exploring the potential for rule-based automation in floor extraction [6]

While floor extraction seems straightforward in theory, it proves more challenging in practice. Our current approach, LoD0.2, involves:

1. Retrieving IfcBuildingStorey objects.
2. Obtaining IfcSlab objects associated with each IfcBuildingStorey.
3. Generating outlines of these slabs.

However, there are challenges. Sometimes IfcBuildingStorey objects are missing from the model, which can be rectified by notifying the BIM modeler. Additionally, not all objects are correctly linked to IfcBuildingStorey, though this issue is partially mitigated by analyzing a subset of related objects (specifically, the slabs). Nevertheless, incorrect slab associations may still pose challenges.

Fig. 5: BIM2GEO Geometrical LoIN approach

3. Case study

The case study of this research involves four municipalities, each defining their regulations differently. For instance, for maximum building height, the Prague municipality defines regulated building height as the distance from the lowest point of adjacent terrain to the level of the main cornice. One of the scenarios to be tested is the extraction based highest point roof until the level of footprint to assess the maximum building height of this specific case.

During the regulations data requirements interpretation, the information to be included in the data requirements, either for building or city information, or both are reported in the third and/or fourth columns, as well as any additional detail understandable from the regulations or reported by the municipality technician about their specification (level of detail, object to be represented, accuracy needed, semantic information and so on).

This information will be reviewed with developers of the checking software to clarify with them which software will check what regulations, and, consequently, how the information needs to be

further specified and mapped to the reference standards (IFC and CityGML/CityJSON). Check the methodology illustration Figure 6.

From a broader perspective, the maximum building height complexities across the four municipalities can be categorized as follows (Figure 7):

1. Regulations' definitions regarding maximum building height may overlap and vary depending on national or municipal levels.
2. At the municipal level, the approach to computing building height can be based on either the number of building floors or vertical dimension calculation.
3. On sloped terrain, there may be varying tolerances in building height computation between municipalities (e.g., 1.5m for Portuguese regulations).
4. When existing roads are present near the building surroundings, the computation of building height from the lowest part may be based on either the nearest sidewalk elevation or the road elevation, with different road requirement levels, as depicted in the figure.

Fig. 6: Methodology followed for regulations interpretation and formalization for information need definition as an input to software's developers.

4. Results :

Apart from further detailing our methodology as well as further refining the geometrical LoINs based on the regulation analyses of the four municipalities, the final paper will include testing the feasibility of automating the selected regulations based on the developed extraction approach, aligning with municipalities' interpretations.

From these experiments, guidelines will be proposed to ensure stakeholders comply with these guidelines when modeling BIM for the DBP process.

Accurate georeferencing and precise extraction of building envelopes are paramount for conducting meticulous measurements, such as computing distances between buildings or determining building heights from ground level to the roof. Without precise georeferencing, these computations may lead to inaccuracies. An illustrative case study involving four municipalities with distinct regulatory frameworks showcases the importance of these processes. For instance, in Prague, regulated building height is defined as the distance from the lowest point of adjacent terrain to the main cornice level. To demonstrate, when assessing maximum building height in the Portuguese context using an IFC model from Vila Nova de Gaia (IFC4), the workflow involves validating IFC geometry, georeferencing the model using tools like the IFC Georeferencing solution, visualizing outcomes to ensure accuracy and compliance, extracting building envelopes through a voxelization approach like the extraction-based highest point roof method,

and finally computing building heights based on regulatory requirements and the footprint elevation introduced in the tool (Figure 8).

Building Height - Level of complexities :

1-At the same Regulation level of applicability :

GAIA and LIS example, regulations overlap and different computations definitions :

- National level : based on vertical dimension computation, and 45° rule (a)
- Municipality level : Building height based on floor numbers (b)
- Pilot Case level : Based on overlapping both definition and specificities depending on urban zone

3- A sloped terrain :

For a sloped terrain different tolerance of the building height :

GAIA+LIS : the building height is measured from the building median plan with tolerance of 1.5m to both building extremities.

APC: If slope < 15% max height is measured on the lower part of the façade (the highest front height is considered)

Prague : In the case of buildings on a slope, height can be stipulated separately for parts of buildings.

2-At the Municipalities regulations definitions :

Computation based

(a) APC: This is the height of each part of the elevation into which the building can be broken down, including setbacks, measured from the ground line to the roof line.

(b) LIS+GAIA (national):

Building height:
The height of the building is the vertical dimension measured:
→ from the threshold to the highest point of the building, including the roof and other built volumes on it.
→ but excluding: chimneys and accessory and decorative elements, plus the elevation of the threshold, where applicable.

(c) Prague:
Art. 27 - chapter 1 - Regulated building height is defined as the distance measured vertically from the lowest point of the adjacent terrain to the level of the main cornice. The level of the main cornice is defined as the intersection of the horizontal edge of the roof and the top edge of the roof. In the case of buildings on a slope, height can be stipulated separately for parts of buildings.

4- Existence of Road/Roads :

Taking the elevation of the next as the starting point of the building height computation but the specificities and level of information needed is quite different (Road, sidewalk, etc).

Fig. 7: complexities of building height and maximum building height 4 municipalities.

Fig. 8: Building height computation results based on the IfcEnvelopeExtractor and geometrical modeling requirements to be submitted to designers[6].

Conclusion

Our ongoing efforts involve finalizing geometrical information requirements based on regulations from four municipalities, upgrading the IfcEnvelopeExtractor tool, and aiding software developers in implementing regulation computations. However, we face challenges such as navigating regulatory complexities, structuring IFC models for designers, collecting municipal data for software developers, and coordinating pilot case demos.

From our endeavors, we've learned several valuable lessons. Flexibility is crucial in digitalizing building permit processes, and the true impact of implementation is best understood through practical use cases. Modeling guidelines must be iterative, and it's essential to consider differences in tolerances and accuracy between human and digital processes. These insights form a solid foundation for advancing digitalization efforts in building permit processes.

References

- [1] S. El Yamani, R. Hajji, and R. Billen, "IFC-CityGML Data Integration for 3D Property Valuation," *ISPRS Int J Geoinf*, vol. 12, no. 9, Sep. 2023, doi: 10.3390/ijgi12090351.
- [2] Hajji et al., "Building Information Modeling for a Smart and Sustainable Urban Space," *ISTE Ltd and John Wiley & Sons, Inc*, 2021.
- [3] N. Hobeika, J. Van Liempt, F. Noardo, K. Arroyo Ohori, and J. Stoter, "Geobim Information To Check Digital Building Permit Regulations," *International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences - ISPRS Archives*, vol. 43, no. B4-2022, pp. 529–535, 2022, doi: 10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIII-B4-2022-529-2022.
- [4] F. Noardo, T. Wu, K. A. Ohori, T. Krijnen, and J. Stoter, "Automation in Construction IFC models for semi-automating common planning checks for building permits," *Autom Constr*, vol. 134, no. March 2021, p. 104097, 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.autcon.2021.104097.
- [5] H. Ledoux, K. Arroyo Ohori, K. Kumar, B. Dukai, A. Labetski, and S. Vitalis, "CityJSON: a compact and easy-to-use encoding of the CityGML data model," *Open Geospatial Data, Software and Standards*, vol. 4, no. 1, pp. 1–19, 2019, doi: 10.1186/s40965-019-0064-0.
- [6] J. Van Der Vaart, "Automatic building feature detection and reconstruction in IFC models," 2022.

Code compliance checking approach for elements implicitly contained in building models

Simon Fischer^a, Daniel Pfeiffer^a, Harald Urban^a, Christian Schranz^a

^a Research Unit Digital Building Process, TU Wien, Karlsplatz 13/235-03, 1040 Vienna, Austria

Digital building permission is a rising use case of BIM in recent years. As reported by Noardo et al. [1] research in this field has focused most on the development of code compliance checking systems. The objective of a code compliance checking system is the automation of code checking with a high degree of automation. However, fully automated checking is not feasible for all requirements. One hurdle is ambiguity in the building code, which requires human interpretation. This challenge was already recognised in literature [1–6]. A second hurdle concerns elements (and their information) that are not explicitly modelled and therefore must be generated first from the information implicitly contained in a building model. The use of implicit information has the advantage of reducing redundant information that might contradict itself. However, problems occur when the implicitly contained information allows different options to generate the new elements. This challenge was detected in the research project BRISE-Vienna for the escape route and fire compartment analysis. BRISE-Vienna [7] is a EU-funded research project conducted in Austria that developed a comprehensive digital permission process for the Vienna Building Authority [8–10].

The development of automated checking approaches for escape routes and fire compartments started with a comprehensive analysis of the building code requirements, followed by the definition of general approaches to address the challenges identified. The most promising approach was then implemented and validated.

The case of escape route analysis for the code compliance checking system of BRISE-Vienna is described in detail in Fischer et al. [11]. An escape route analysis concerns an escape route network that consists of several individual routes. Each individual route itself must fulfil certain requirements, like a maximum route length. The escape route network must fulfil requirements on a combination of escape routes, like using doors and rooms that provide enough space for the cumulative number of people from different escape routes. Building models provide information about the course (geometry of the building elements) and the combinability (number of people in starting locations) of escape routes implicitly. Therefore, individual escape routes and combined escape route networks can be generated. However, buildings often provide more than one escape route from a particular starting location (see Fig. 1). Thus, different combinations for escape route networks exist and can be found by automatic generations. By this, it remains unclear which escape route network corresponds to the planner's intention.

A second example of the problem occurred for the checking of fire compartments. Possible boundaries of fire compartments are given implicitly by the defined fire ratings of room boundary elements. The requirements on these potential boundaries of fire compartments increase with the area of the fire compartment. Therefore, the use of different room bounding elements for fire compartments effects the requirements and the checking result. The existence of different combinations leads again to uncertainty about the planners' intent.

The problem can be described generally as follows: Validation of elements not explicitly defined in the building model while the implicitly contained information allows different options to

generate them. Within BRISE-Vienna different approaches to solve the problem were analysed according to their fit in the openBIM permission process of the Vienna Building Authority.

Fig. 1: Different options for an escape route to connect the left and right entrance.

The first approach is a fully automated generation and checking of the escape routes. Using an iterative algorithm enables the calculation of a possible combination of the required elements if one exists. However, a legal problem occurs regarding the openBIM permission process [11]. The party that specifies information like the exact course of escape routes is liable for it. If the building authority uses a fully automated generation to define the escape routes, the building authority is liable for these elements. This means a reversal of liability (from the planner to the building authority). This is not feasible in Austria because of legal reasons.

Another approach is to request the planners to explicitly define the escape routes and fire compartments in the BIM model. By this, the advantage of the BIM model containing the relevant information implicitly is lost. The planning must be done beforehand by the planners and is decoupled from the permission.

A third approach is to divide the process in two separate automatic steps: generation and validation (see Fig. 2). This allows human interference between two automated steps. The generation determines possible options for the generated elements and therefore provides a pool of options for planners. During the manual selection the individual elements are combined to one desired network. The second automated step, the validation, checks the combined elements considering the requirements for the network. Planners use it before and building authority agents after submission. The manual selection of desired elements between the two automated steps makes planners liable for them and this approach applicable to the building permission process of the Vienna Building Authority.

Fig. 2: Process of the Generation-Validation approach.

In BRISE-Vienna the concept of generation and validation was implemented for escape route analysis [11] and formally prepared for fire compartment analysis. We developed an escape route checking rule for the software Solibri Office [12] which was used in BRISE-Vienna generally. Solibri Office provides an API (application programming interface) based on the programming language JAVA that enables the creation of an individual checking rule. The developed algorithms were validated using a fictional escape route test model and real-world models (see Fig. 3). The fictional model included test cases for special requirements relevant for the escape route analysis. The real-world models were provided during a pilot phase and served to validate the algorithms under realistic circumstances. The escape route test model [13] and one of the real-world models [14] are publicly available.

Fig. 3: 3D-view (first row) and generated escape routes (second row) of four real-world models [11].

Fig. 4 shows the difference between the implemented escape route generation and validation for the office rooms on the ground floor of the escape route test model. While the escape route generation provides several possible paths for the start rooms (left), the escape route validation only includes routes selected by the planner (right). However, both automated steps use the same operating principle, which can be broken down into three core components: Generating an indoor navigation model, applying a path finding algorithm, and checking the elements along the determined paths. The selection of escape routes between the two steps was realised by predefining sequences of doors. In the escape route analysis of Fischer et al. [11], two routes are considered as different, if they do not use the same sequence of doors. Therefore, the sequence of doors is a valid feature to predefine different routes.

For fire compartment analysis the concept works similarly. For the generation, planners are automatically given several different variants of possible fire compartment configurations depending on the total area, longitudinal extent, and number of storeys. The planners can then select the preferred variant, whereby a variant consists of several fire compartments and a fire compartment consists of several associated rooms. The validation by the Vienna Building Authority afterwards can be conducted automatically using the same criteria (total area, longitudinal extent, and number of storeys) but only considering one selected configuration.

Fig. 4: Comparison between the escape route generation (left) and escape route validation (right) methods in the escape route test model [11].

The results of the implementation in Fischer et al. [11] demonstrate the functionality of the developed concept. We use implicit data of building models to generate and validate elements. This reduces the effort to explicitly define or model information that is already contained in the building model. This also provides a single source of truth, because explicitly modelled elements might contradict the information implicitly defined by other elements. Furthermore, the combination of automated generation and validation with a manual selection in between provides a high level of automation and still complies with Vienna's legal situation. Additionally, planners retain control over the final decision of the desired elements by manually defining them in the BIM model. Existing research has emphasised the importance of such human oversight in automated systems due to ambiguity and the need for domain knowledge [4–6]. The results encourage to avoid explicit modelling of virtual elements that can be generated from other information in the building model. Doing so, the specific model requirements for the BIM use case digital building permission can be reduced. The approach was tested for two specific use cases. Therefore, future work should include an analysis of other regulations related to this approach. Moreover, implicitly contained information is harder to visualize and distribute. A promising extension for future work is to permanently save the generated elements by creating new IFC domain models, like an escape route model. By this, the generated explicit elements can be used in other use cases and the single source of truth is maintained, since they are derived from implicit information.

References

- [1] F. Noardo, D. Guler, J. Fauth, G. Malacarne, S. Mastrolembo Ventura, M. Azenha, P.-O. Olsson, L. Senger: *Unveiling the actual progress of Digital Building Permit: Getting awareness through a critical state of the art review*, Building and Environment 213 (2022) 108854.

- <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.108854>.
- [2] M. Uhm, G. Lee, Y. Park, S. Kim, J. Jung, J.-K. Lee: *Requirements for computational rule checking of requests for proposals (RFPs) for building designs in South Korea*, *Advanced Engineering Informatics* 29 (2015) 602–615. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2015.05.006>.
- [3] S. Macit İlal, H.M. Günaydın: *Computer representation of building codes for automated compliance checking*, *Automation in Construction* 82 (2017) 43–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2017.06.018>.
- [4] P. Ghannad, Y.-C. Lee, J. Dimyadi, W. Solihin: *Automated BIM data validation integrating open-standard schema with visual programming language*, *Advanced Engineering Informatics* 40 (2019) 14–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2019.01.006>.
- [5] T.H. Beach, J.-L. Hippolyte, Y. Rezgui: *Towards the adoption of automated regulatory compliance checking in the built environment*, *Automation in Construction* 118 (2020) 103285. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103285>.
- [6] T. Bloch, J. Fauth: *The unbalanced research on digitalization and automation of the building permitting process*, *Advanced Engineering Informatics* 58 (2023) 102188. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2023.102188>.
- [7] UIA – Urban Innovative Actions: *BRISE-Vienna – Building Regulations Information for Submission Involvement*, 2019. <https://uia-initiative.eu/en/uia-cities/vienna-call4> (accessed February 29, 2024).
- [8] T. Krischmann, H. Urban, C. Schranz: *Entwicklung eines openBIM-Bewilligungsverfahrens*, *Bauingenieur* 95(9) (2020) 335–344. <https://doi.org/10.37544/0005-6650-2020-09-61>.
- [9] C. Schranz, H. Urban, A. Gerger: *Potentials of Augmented Reality in a BIM based building submission process*, *Journal of Information Technology in Construction* 26 (2021) 441–457. <https://doi.org/10.36680/j.itcon.2021.024>.
- [10] A. Gerger, H. Urban, C. Schranz: *Augmented Reality for Building Authorities: A Use Case Study in Austria*, *Buildings* 13 (2023) 1462. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13061462>.
- [11] S. Fischer, C. Schranz, H. Urban, D. Pfeiffer: *Automation of escape route analysis for BIM-based building code checking*, *Automation in Construction* 156 (2023) 105092. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2023.105092>.
- [12] Solibri Inc: *Solibri Office*, 2024. <https://www.solibri.com/solibri-office> (accessed February 29, 2024).
- [13] S. Fischer, C. Schranz, H. Urban, D. Pfeiffer: *Custom Escape Route Test Model in IFC format*, [Data set], TU Wien, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.48436/RA5G9-TBB65>.
- [14] S. Fischer, C. Schranz, H. Urban, D. Pfeiffer, *Real-World Escape Route Test Model in IFC format*, [Data set], TU Wien, 2023. <https://doi.org/10.48436/2HEB4-XQB83>.

ILS Space: applying and extracting a higher order spatial taxonomy from IFC building models

Rolf Jonker^a, Thomas Krijnen^b, Abe Reurings^a
Bart de Lathouwer^a

^a Rotterdam Municipality

^b AECgeeks, The Netherlands

Background

The evolution of Building Information Modeling (BIM) offers unprecedented capabilities for collaboration and data management in the construction sector. However, limitations remain in terms of capturing, representing and extracting the more implicit, higher order functional concepts that are integral to building permit evaluation. Examples of this include zones that aggregate spaces, such as the group of spaces representing a single apartment, or the complete rentable area of a storey and a consistent singular representation of the building envelope or facade.

In principle, within the IFC schema, it is possible to provide additional representations to the IFCBuilding or provide a multitude of IFCSpatialZones. However, doing so would place an immense burden on the modeler. Off-the-shelves tools also do typically not have the functionality to provide these additional higher order forms. Most importantly, it ought to be possible to infer these from the more explicit lower level representations that are provided. Technology should make our lives easier, not harder.

State of the art

The challenges with varying quality and content contained in BIM models and examples of geometric methods to counter such challenges are investigated in [3]. Many other works acknowledge the lack of certain higher order constructs in IFC. [1] proposes a semantic enrichment for pre-processing BIM models to contain richer constructs. [5] describes a translation of legal documents to semi-formal language combined with a preprocessing step to derive content from BIM models. The importance of modelling and exchange of spaces in a legal context is investigated in [4] and Existing work shows how voxelization can be used to close gaps between space geometries [2].

ILS Space

This research builds upon the ideas formulated in ILS Space. ILS Space is an Information Delivery Specification (IDS) defining data exchange requirements for information about spaces in and around buildings based on the IFC Schema. ILS Space encompasses a comprehensive taxonomy of interior and exterior space categories. It is derived from local Dutch building regulations and norms such as NEN 2580, a standard for calculating areas and contents of buildings. As such, it differentiates between exterior areas such as built, unbuilt, overbuilt, and underbuilt areas. Interior areas include for example Gross Floor Area, Net Floor Area, Tarra Area, Living area and Functional area. In addition ILS Space is based on the new Environment Buildings Decree (Bbl) of the Netherlands. An important principle of the Bbl is to maximize the freedom of an architect or entrepreneur in organizing a building when applying for a building permit, during construction, and also for changes to the layout in the future. The technical building regulations in the Dutch decree are therefore aimed at setting the regulations at the highest possible level, for the largest possible architectural area. The practical implementation of this is done in the Bbl, by defining

different types of space. In addition to the taxonomy of the NEN2580, ILS Space outlines and exemplifies the procedures by which rooms are to be geometrically fused in order to derive composite areas, based on the Bbl. Hereby there is a distinction between spaces bounded by load-bearing and non-load-bearing partitions as load-bearing partitions can be removed or adjusted by the tenants and are therefore included in areas such as Rentable Area.

Bruto Vloer Oppervlak (BVO) Gross Floor Area (GFA)	Netto Vloer Oppervlak (NVO) Net Floor Area	Gebruiks Oppervlak (GO) User Surface Area	Ruimte voor gebouwinstallaties / MEP/HVAC Spaces	Verhuurbaar Vloer Oppervlak (VVO) Rentable Area	Nuttig Oppervlak (NO) Living Area	Functioneel Nuttig Oppervlak (FNO) Functional Area	Ruimte voor gebouwinstallaties / MEP/HVAC Spaces
			Parkeerruimte / Parking space				Rijwielstalling / bicycle shed
			Verticaal verkeersoppervlak / Vertical Circulation Area				Sanitaire ruimten / sanitary room
			Horizontaal verkeersoppervlak / Horizontal Circulation Area				Bergruimte/ storage
							Programma (PvE) Requirements
							Indelingsverlies / Unusable space
							Separatiewanden / Partition wall
							Glaslijncorrectie / Additional area bounded by glassline
							Scheidingsconstructies tussen gebouwde functies / Partition structures between built functions
							Niet toegankelijke leidingschachten / Inaccessible utility shafts
Tarra Oppervlak (TO) Tare Area			Statische bouwdelen / Structural components				
			Ruimtes lager dan 1,5 m / Spaces lower than 1,5m				

Fig. 1: Different type of spaces defined by the NEN 2580 (top) and the Dutch Environment Buildings Decree (bottom)

When aggregating adjacent spaces separated by a partitioning element into such a higher order area, only the segment of that partition that lies between both spaces is to be incorporated. While the wall may extend beyond that, the protruding portions of that bounding element should not be considered part of the aggregated area. Geometrically speaking we're not looking for the union of

those two spaces and the wall, but an operation more akin to extruding a facet of that space to meet the other space insofar it doesn't interfere with the load bearing structure.

Fig. 2: The logic behind space aggregation: a) two spaces and a non-loadbearing wall on the left b) the boolean union of these, which is not the intended end-result as it misses the door void and includes a part of the wall that extends beyond the spaces and c)

The primary goal of ILS Space is to support the information need for digital building permit checks, asset management and to interoperate with cadastral systems. Our focus is on minimizing the workload for modelers.

BIM and IFC

BIM primarily serves as a collection of physical products as construction documentation, rather than a holistic conceptual model of the building's functional behavior. IFC, while a widely adopted standard for BIM data exchange, is best perceived as a point-to-point communication mechanism between parties rather than a comprehensive conceptual representation of the entire building. While information delivery specifications are getting more widespread, the expressiveness of these specifications is often limited and complying with them is sometimes hard. Digital building permit procedures are often at the end of the data lifecycle in which it is not often possible anymore to impose constraints on the exchanges. In BIM, the individual products are modelled as individual solid volumes in their own coordinate system, which results in precision issues when joining them.

Solution

A geometrically robust and semantically flexible approach is sought that is able to build up higher order spatial structures from the individual spaces in BIM models. We aim to impose as little requirements on the data as possible. For that matter, we for example do not depend on space boundaries (the optional relationship in IFC to encode the specific areas where spaces touch their enclosing elements), because availability of these is limited, validity often not ideal and there is a fundamental limitation with being unable to create relationships between different aspect models (the complementary models provided by subcontractors for their specific discipline are typically exchanges as separate files).

The developed procedure can be outlined as follows. Initial assessments involve the evaluation of individual spaces and building elements as polyhedral solid volumes, which are subsequently decomposed into convex subsets. These convex portions are then expressed as the intersection of a set of half-space solids, creating a hierarchical structure of [element] > [convex part] > [half-space plane equation]. This hierarchical representation is encoded in an RDF graph and enriched with geometric predicates such as [touching] and [opposites].

To identify spatial connections, SPARQL queries are employed. These queries help identify all pairs of neighbouring spaces, the intervening element, and the corresponding half-space plane equations by which these connections are established. By iterating over the query results, the necessary rewriting steps for facilitating contact between spaces are determined. Note that

vertices and edges within the set of half-spaces are implicitly defined as the intersection of these half-spaces. Therefore, rewriting the plane equations from one side of the wall to the opposite is adequate to extend the volumes and ensure that the spaces are in contact. The approach makes use of CGAL's exact computation paradigm to ensure robustness in the computations.

Furthermore, the SPARQL query enables the selective matching of space pairs for merging based on their category and allows for filtering enclosing elements based on load-bearing characteristics or other attributes. The solution is made available as a microservice that rewrites IFC models to contain richer aggregates semantics on spaces and areas and also has a User Interface for manual inspection.

```

select ?i1 ?i2 ?e1 ?e2 ?w ?wi1 ?wi2 where {
    ?elem a <http://example.org/classes/Element> .
    ?elem <http://example.org/classes/ifcType> "IfcWall" .
    ?elem <http://example.org/classes/LoadBearing> FALSE .

    ?elem <http://example.org/classes/boundedBy> ?p1 .
    ?elem <http://example.org/classes/boundedBy> ?p2 .

    ?p1 <http://example.org/classes/opposite> ?p2 .

    ?p1 <http://example.org/classes/touches> ?q .
    ?p2 <http://example.org/classes/touches> ?r .

    ?sp1 <http://example.org/classes/ifcType> "IfcSpace" .
    ?sp2 <http://example.org/classes/ifcType> "IfcSpace" .
    ?sp1 <http://example.org/classes/boundedBy> ?q .

    ?sp2 <http://example.org/classes/boundedBy> ?r .
    ?q <http://example.org/classes/hasEquation> ?eq1 .
    ?r <http://example.org/classes/hasEquation> ?eq2 .

    ?sp1 <http://example.org/classes/hasIndex> ?i1 .
    ?sp2 <http://example.org/classes/hasIndex> ?i2 .
    ?p1 <http://example.org/classes/hasIndex> ?wi1 .
    ?p2 <http://example.org/classes/hasIndex> ?wi2 .
    ?elem <http://example.org/classes/hasIndex> ?w .
    ?q <http://example.org/classes/hasIndex> ?e1 .
    ?r <http://example.org/classes/hasIndex> ?e2 .

    filter(?p1 != ?p2)
}
    
```

Fig. 3: SPARQL query being used to interrogate the network of halfspace solids, illustrating the combination of geometric predicates and semantic content from the IFC model, in order to query for the pairs of halfspaces.

Conclusion

In building permit evaluation there is a need for describing or deriving higher order spatial constructs. ILS Space provides a taxonomy of such spaces and zones for the Dutch regulatory landscape. An implementation has been built and described in this paper with the computational means to construct such zones from individual physical spaces based on the aggregation logic in ILS Space. This can enable digital support for regulatory compliance checks where space of higher order is a crucial component.

Fig. 4: A screen-shot of the developed platform with a random color on individual spaces to highlight the demarcation between the spaces.

Fig. 5: The result after processing in the service, showing the aggregated area for all living areas and bedrooms as computed by the platform.

References

- [1] Bloch, T., Katz, M., Yosef, R., & Sacks, R. (2019, July). Automated model checking for topologically complex code requirements—security room case study. In EC3 Conference 2019 (Vol. 1, pp. 48-55). University College Dublin.
- [2] Krijnen, T. F., El-Diraby, T., Konomi, T., & Attalla, A. (2021). Thermal analysis of IFC building models using voxelized geometries. In Proceedings of the 38th International Conference of CIB W78.
- [3] Noardo, F., Wu, T., Ohori, K. A., Krijnen, T., & Stoter, J. (2022). IFC models for semi-automating common planning checks for building permits. *Automation in Construction*, 134, 104097.
- [4] Oldfield, J., Van Oosterom, P., Beetz, J., & Krijnen, T. F. (2017). Working with open BIM standards to source legal spaces for a 3D cadastre. *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information*, 6(11), 351.
- [5] Preidel, C., Bus, N., Borrmann, A., & Fies, B. (2018). Pre-processing IFC building models for code compliance checking based on visual programming. proceedings of ICCCBE.

Design and development of a digital compliance workbench

Nicholas Nisbet^{ab}, Zijing Zhang^a, Selçuk Çidik^a

^a University College London, London, UK

^bAEC3 UK Ltd, UK

Abstract

This paper reports on the design and development of a digital compliance workbench. It examines a series of experimental developments over the course of 15 years to allow domain experts from the regulatory sector and from the design sector to create and deploy automated compliance checking. It explores the criteria that such a system must meet, examining each of Eastman's 4-stage approach. Conclusion are drawn about the requirements for such a system, and the future development of the workbench and other solutions.

Problem statement

Many authors have summarised the research effort on automated compliance checking over the last 20 years. Most papers have focussed on the deployment of specific technologies related to BIM so as to implement a selected clause or class of clauses. There has been relatively little work on how this research work could be implemented as a complete system. A paradigm based on direct coding was established around the turn of the century by the Solibri desktop (2023) and Singapore ePlanCheck service (Solihin, 2018) and was described by Eastman (2009). Lee et al. (2020) reviewed IfcDoc, KBim, ePlanCheck, ACABIM, and SNACC, though not all of those are intended as automated compliance checking solutions. The direct coding paradigm has been unchallenged at least until the DCOM project (Beach et al, 2023). Zhang (2023) has offered some criteria from the point of view of designers. Bloch et al (2023) and Fauth et al (2022) have looked at the building permitting process in several jurisdictions from the point of view of the authority.

Specific research question

There is a gap in envisioning how applicants and inspectorates might implement newer techniques. and what the benefits might be over traditional coding approaches.

Method

This paper examines the development of a automatic compliance workbench 'AEC3 Require1', exploiting opportunities for increased accuracy, efficiency and completeness, so as to explore the requirements for and obstacles to the deployment of compliance checking. Using Eastmans 4 steps (2019)

Iteration (1) "rule interpretation and logical structuring of rules for their application";

Iteration (2) "building model preparation, where the necessary information required for checking is prepared";

Iteration (3) "the rule execution phase, which carries out the checking";

Iteration (4) the reporting of the results.";

Introduction

RASE is a knowledge ontology that can be represented as coloured mark-up in regulatory documents. The RASE methodology was first developed in 2007 to support the US ICC in their SmartCodes initiative. The motivation for a new method was that neither the existing desktop compliance tool (Solibri) nor bespoke programmed solution (ePlanCheck) could deliver the accuracy and efficiency needed to automate the range of building code (regulation) found in 3000 county jurisdictions across the USA. A second motivation was that it was found that no spreadsheet/database template could manage the syntactic complexity of the ICC regulations. The RASE ontology was adopted as a flexible and efficient solution. Initially an off-the-shelf XML editor was used to add the RASE markup into ICC's proprietary XML document format. PNNL was commissioned to develop a 'SmartCodesEditor' to support the mark-up process and hide the technicalities of XML. Three separate rule engines were developed to demonstrate a fully automated code compliance system. Both Solibri and ePlanCheck were reconfigured to load and execute rules generated from the marked-up documents. A new solution named 'Xabio' was developed by AEC3 UK Ltd to exploit the methodology further including fully customized reporting and the generations of explanations and recommendations around the checking results. All three solutions consumed the rules as IFC constraint model and used IFC as the target project model.

In work for the USACE, RASE was generalized for use with HTML, reverting to an off-the-shelf XML editor. Text to be marked up was scraped from the WBDG website as HTML. Tables of medical room requirements were mapped systematically into HTML sentences with mark-up added systematically. This approach embedded several non-value-adding processes and assumptions. In order to allow domain experts to engage with the process, AEC3 began considering what a compliance workbench might look like.

Narrative

This paper considers the subsequent design and development of a compliance workshop so as to explore the requirements for and obstacles to the deployment of compliance checking. Using Eastmans 4 steps (2019)

Iteration (1) “rule interpretation and logical structuring of rules for their application”; this stage of the development reduced the interpretation required, replacing it with RASE colored markup and where needed additional metadata to confirm numeric constraints. Multiple presentations (beyond the IFC constraint model) were developed to support the validation and re-use of the normative content.

Iteration (2) “building model preparation, where the necessary information required for checking is prepared”; this stage required the development of an interface to a dictionary of mappings, and further development of the handling of unknowns.

Iteration (3) “the rule execution phase, which carries out the checking”; this stage required the implementation of a Case based approach where multiple federated regulations can be checked against multiple federated models.

Iteration (4) the reporting of the results.”; this stage reintroduced a checking engine, previously implemented as a stand-alone command line application. Several refinements were introduced, including the reporting and enquiry for unknown values, the generation of certificates and other presentations. Other outputs include BCF. Finally a 3d view was added

Discussion

DCOM mirrors in a distributed architecture the same functions as found within the workbench. Several features of 'AEC3 Require1' remain unique.

- The flexibility of presentations and integrations from the RASE markup.
- The flexibility and deep diagnostics from the results.
- Authoring interfaces for managing dictionary resources.
- The management of a case as the key metaphor for applicants and inspectorates.
- The management of supplementary submittals.

Conclusion

The development of the compliance workbench has evolved to become a complete solution to the decision making element of a full DBP process, handling both the inputs and the common knowledge. If automated compliance checking is going to be adopted widely, then alternatives to the conventional coding paradigm are needed. The development of the compliance workbench has evolved to become a complete solution to the decision making element of a full DBP process. It provides a benchmark of functionality and opportunities which can be used in the next generation of solutions such as DCOM and the current EU projects.

Acknowledgements

The development of 'AEC3 Require1' has been supported by AEC3 UK ltd.

References

- AEC3 Require1 2023: http://www.aec3.eu/require1/Help_en-GB/help_en-GB_300.html .
- Beach, T., Yeung, J., Nisbet, N. and Rezgui, Y., 2024. Digital approaches to construction compliance checking: Validating the suitability of an ecosystem approach to compliance checking. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 59, p.102288. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2023.102288>
- Bloch, T. and Fauth, J., 2023. The unbalanced research on digitalization and automation of the building permitting process. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 58, p.102188.
- Eastman, C., Lee, J.M., Jeong, Y.S. and Lee, J.K., 2009. Automatic rule-based checking of building designs. *Automation in construction*, 18(8), pp.1011-1033.
- Fauth, J. and Soibelman, L., 2022. Conceptual framework for building permit process modeling: Lessons learned from a comparison between Germany and the United States regarding the as-is building permit processes. *Buildings*, 12(5), p.638.
- Lee, Y.C., Ghannad, P., Dimyadi, J., Lee, J.K., Solihin, W. and Zhang, J., 2020, March. A comparative analysis of five rule-based model checking platforms. In *Construction Research Congress 2020* (pp. 1127-1136). Reston, VA: American Society of Civil Engineers.
- Solibri. 2023. Solibri Model Checker [Online]. Available: <https://www.solibri.com/solibri> office [Accessed 2023-12-12].
- Solihin, W. and Eastman, C., 2015. Classification of rules for automated BIM rule checking development. *Automation in construction*, 53, pp.69-82.
- Zhang, J., Cui, B., Gao, Y. and Zhang, D., 2023. Factors Influencing the Acceptance of BIM-Based Automated Code Compliance Checking in the AEC Industry in China. *Journal of Management in Engineering*, 39(6), p.04023036.

IFC-Based Platform Prototype for Rule Editing and Code Compliance Check

Bruno Muniz^a, José Granja^a, Miguel Azenha^a

^a *University of Minho, ISISE, ARISE, Department of Civil Engineering, Guimarães, Portugal*

Although urban permitting is one of the main tools for guaranteeing the quality and performance of the building stock, it is characterized by procedures that are poorly assisted by technological resources. Indeed, current procedures for permitting are largely based on the analysis of two-dimensional drawings and PDFs' or paper [1] Therefore, delays in issuing building permits are common and are considered one of their main issues, alongside the frequent complaints about lack of clarity and subjectivity in the entire process of evaluation [2]. The large regulatory frameworks also imply a challenge, which has historically been combated at the European level through measures to reduce control and transfer responsibilities to private individuals [3].

The BIM methodology, which focuses on the sharing of building information and is backed up by technological resources, has helped to optimise the permitting process by enabling it to be digitalised, which is evident in several well-established cases of implementation [4]. In this context, the main benefit is the use of building information models to automate the process of compliance checking of designs against the requirements of building regulations [5]. Nevertheless, there is still much room for improvement, especially when it comes to interpreting the extensive regulatory framework and implementing them in machine-interpretable format [6].

Another crucial challenge lies in the scalability of applications, which are mostly based on closed solutions or have limited rule editing capabilities [7]. Hence, the scope for carrying out automatic checks is limited by the inability to easily code and edit regulations [8]. In turn, several studies propose not only the development of applications capable of editing verification rules but also the use of visual programming languages that are easily accessible to building permit specialists [8–12].

The development of a system capable of creating machine-interpretable regulations must promote an intermediate layer of abstraction between a building data model and building permit regulations. This can be done by implementing methods such as RASE [13], for the extraction of semantic components from natural language, in combination with the development of an object model [2, 14], which can then be mapped to the building data model.

To deal with these challenges, this work has developed a prototype platform that allows machine-interpretable regulations to be created from a visual language and compliance checks to be carried out from IFC files. In order to fulfil this objective, 2 major tasks had to be performed: (i) the implementation of an object model that implements the entities and concepts found in the regulations used in building permit processes; (ii) the development of the prototype platform for performing checks and the visual programming language to be used for coding and editing the rules of the regulations.

The first task was to analyse a sample of clauses from Portuguese national and municipal regulations used in permitting. The RASE methodology was used to semantically systematise the concepts found in the texts of these clauses, which served as the basis for developing a conceptual model of permit entities and properties. Afterwards, by analysing the IFC data model and attempting to map it to the conceptual model, it was possible to implement the permit object model using tools such as IfcOpenShell. The mapping was essential for establishing which

resources would need to be adopted to obtain information from the IFC file, which demonstrated a significant need to adopt classification systems adapted to the building permit concepts in order to allow, for example, differentiation between spaces.

The work also relied on geometric processing in order to obtain some information from the IFC, which while potentially a solution for generating more succinct information requirements, also proved to be a major programming challenge. Therefore, this work integrated the Trimesh mesh processing library with lfcOpenShell's model query resources, in order to facilitate the information and processing of geometric information with methods at a higher level of abstraction.

The second task, which consisted of developing the prototype platform and the visual programming language, was facilitated through the use of a series of frameworks and libraries, the most important of which were: (a) Django, a framework used for integration with the object model, database management and the creation of APIs (b) React, a framework used to create user interfaces through a modular structure, which provides greater scalability and ease of integration with the libraries for viewing models and the library for editing verification rules; (c) Blockly, a library for creating block visual programming languages and implementing editors; (d) Xeokit, a library for viewing IFC files.

The process of creating the programming language involved programming block generators that could create code, in Python language, that utilised the objects created using the permit object model. In this way, by combining programming blocks, which have a high level of abstraction, it is possible to automatically generate lower level code, store it and then use it to run the checks. The implementation of the rule editor also enabled the coding of the verification rules simpler and straightforward, which can make, allied with other visual features such as a colour palette to distinguish the different types of blocks created, the coding of machine-interpretable regulations more accessible to people that are not specialised in programming languages.

Figure 1. Platform's rule editor.

The work has confirmed that the compliance check process can be partially automated, considering the work was based on a limited set of clauses. This automation can involve the use of visual programming languages, based on open formats and tools. In addition, the use of an object model that implements the concepts used in building permits at a high level can promote a greater layer of abstraction and facilitate the implementation of scalable verification systems, which employ objects that can be reused to code various verification rules. Finally, the

implemented systems can serve as the fundamental components of a semi-automatic verification system and can be expanded to create an increasingly comprehensive system.

Acknowledgements

This work was partly financed by FCT / MCTES through national funds (PIDDAC) under the R&D Unit Institute for Sustainability and Innovation in Structural Engineering (ISISE), under reference UIDB / 04029/2020 (doi.org/10.54499/UIDB/04029/2020), and under the Associate Laboratory Advanced Production and Intelligent Systems ARISE under reference LA/P/0112/2020.

This work was also financed by the scholarship (BI-ISISE-UMINHO-CHEK-B03) awarded to the first author, funded by the Horizon Europe 2021-2027 Research and Innovation Programme, under the project Change Toolkit for Digital Building Permit CHEK, with reference 101058559.

References

- [1] F. Noardo, D. Guler, J. Fauth, G. Malacarne, S.M. Ventura, M. Azenha, O. Olsson, L. Senger, Unveiling the actual progress of Digital Building Permit: getting awareness through a critical state of the art review, 2021. <https://www.bimacademy.global/insights/infrastructure/the-golden-thread-of-information-putting-the-hacki>.
- [2] S. Malsane, J. Matthews, S. Lockley, P.E.D. Love, D. Greenwood, Development of an object model for automated compliance checking, *Autom. Constr. Part A* (2015) 51–58. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2014.10.004>.
- [3] J.B. Pedro, F. Meijer, H. Visscher, Comparison of building permit procedures in European in European Union countries Cova da Moura Rehabilitation Needs Assessment View project Building Regulations for Construction Works in Existing Buildings View project Comparison of building permit procedures in European Union countries, 2011. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/257527312>.
- [4] C. Eastman, J. Lee, Y. Jeong, J. Lee, Automatic rule-based checking of building designs, *Autom. Constr.* 18 (2009) 1011–1033. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2009.07.002>.
- [5] K. Shahi, B.Y. McCabe, A. Shahi, Framework for Automated Model-Based e-Permitting System for Municipal Jurisdictions, *J. Manag. Eng.* 35 (2019) 04019025. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(asce\)me.1943-5479.0000712](https://doi.org/10.1061/(asce)me.1943-5479.0000712).
- [6] Z. Zhang, N. Nisbet, L. Ma, T. Broyd, Capabilities of rule representations for automated compliance checking in healthcare buildings, *Autom. Constr.* 146 (2023) 104688. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2022.104688>.
- [7] N.O. Nawari, A Generalized Adaptive Framework (GAF) for automating code compliance checking, *Buildings* 9 (2019). <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings9040086>.
- [8] H. Kim, J.K. Lee, J. Shin, J. Choi, Visual language approach to representing KBimCode-based Korea building code sentences for automated rule checking, *J. Comput. Des. Eng.* 6 (2019) 143–148. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JCDE.2018.08.002>.
- [9] S. Daum, A. Borrmann, Simplifying the Analysis of Building Information Models Using tQL4BIM and vQL4BIM, (2015).
- [10] P. Ghannad, Y.C. Lee, J. Dimyadi, W. Solihin, Automated BIM data validation integrating open-standard schema with visual programming language, *Adv. Eng. Inform.* 40 (2019) 14–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2019.01.006>.
- [11] C. Preidel, A. Borrmann, Automated code compliance checking based on a visual language and building information modeling, 32nd Int. Symp. Autom. Robot. Constr. Min. Connect. Future Proc. (2015). <https://doi.org/10.22260/ISARC2015/0033>.

- [12] A. Wülfing, R. Windisch, R. Scherer, A visual BIM query language, in: A. Mahdavi, B. Martens, R. Scherer (Eds.), *EWork EBusiness Archit. Eng. Constr.*, CRC Press, 2014: pp. 157–164. <https://doi.org/10.1201/b17396-30>.
- [13] E. Hjelseth, N.N. Nisbet, Capturing normative constraints by use of the semantic mark-up RASE methodology, in: 2011. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Capturing-normative-constraints-by-use-of-the-RASE-Hjelseth-Nisbet/8820d782f37a3bccc5922dc5e6ee1b344a027828> (accessed February 22, 2023).
- [14] J.K. Lee, Building environment rule and analysis (BERA) language and its application for evaluating building circulation and spatial program, Georgia Institute of Technology, 2011. <https://smartech.gatech.edu/handle/1853/39482> (accessed March 3, 2023).

[Breaking the boundaries of Automated Code Checking through Semantic Enrichment and Graph Neural Networks](#)

Maen Alnuzha^a, Tanya Bloch^a

^a Faculty of Civil and Environmental Engineering, Technion Israel Institute of Technology, Haifa, Israel

Introduction

Development of Building Information Modelling (BIM) has introduced an opportunity to automate various processes in the Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) domain, including design review. Yet, in practice, despite the presented opportunities, design review processes continue to involve cumbersome paper trails and time-consuming manual work. The concept of Automated Code Checking (ACC) has been introduced as early as 1975 in a visionary paper written by Eastman [1]. The subject has been an active research area since [2], however even the most advanced developments in the field are limited in the scope of regulations they can address, and the level of automation that can be achieved. Existing commercial tools for ACC often rely on hard-coded rules applied to BIM models, leading to challenges such as arbitrary object representations and the absence of a unified naming conventions. The need for precise and rich data representation hinders the development of fully automated code checking tools. Semantic Enrichment (SE) of BIM models [3] offers an automated method to align conceptual representations in models with those specified in rule sets. Majority of work on SE heavily relies on the use of logical constructs to represent and manipulate information within the models, for deducing new facts about the models [4], [5], [6], [7], [8], [9], [10]. However, with the construction industry gradually transitioning to a more data-driven paradigm, recent research has shifted its focus towards exploring Machine Learning (ML) approaches for semantic enrichment [11], [12], [13], [14]. Moreover, researchers are exploring the application of Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) for semantic enrichment [15], leveraging the unique capabilities of GNNs in capturing relationships and dependencies within graph-structured data. While there has been a suggested paradigm shift for ACC by framing it as a classification task for ML or GNN [16], it is crucial to emphasize that these models are still heavily reliant on data extraction, processing, and enrichment. Even with advanced ML techniques, these models cannot perform optimally on raw BIM data, underscoring the importance of pre-processing and enrichment as critical steps in the data preparation phase. This indicates that the quality and richness of data in BIM models remain pivotal for successful of code checking processes.

Aims and Methodology

The overall goal of this work is to demonstrate the applicability of GNN models for complex semantic enrichment tasks in support of ACC workflows. We do so by focusing on a complex clause from the Israeli Home Front command regulations for security rooms [17]. Security rooms (bomb shelters) are designated spaces within a building specifically designed and constructed to provide protection during emergency situations related to military actions. According to the regulations, these rooms are required to be vertically stacked, forming a shaft that may also incorporate other functional spaces. Any modifications, such as the removal of walls or the addition of openings within these spaces, can potentially detach the security room from its foundational structure. The regulations allow for some vertical discontinuity, subject to specific conditions. A crucial determining factor necessitates additional measures is based on the percentage of walls in each security room that continuously reach the foundation. The regulations specify three ranges for vertical continuity, each prescribing additional requirements:

1) scenarios where at least 70% of the walls are continuous and reach the foundation, 2) the ratio of supporting walls falls between 50% and 70%, and 3) the ratio of supporting walls is less than 50%. The manual calculation of this supporting walls ratio involves careful consideration of various factors. These complex calculations are avoided by addressing this task as a node classification task performed by GNN.

Implementation and results

Upon identifying the security rooms, they are assembled into a shaft, inclusive of any walls falling geometrically within the bounding box of these rooms. This process aims to recognize supporting walls associated with other functional spaces. Subsequently, the shaft undergoes automatic translation into a graph, encompassing security rooms, walls, doors, and windows. We then develop and implement a two-layer GNN designed for node classification, specifically to categorize security components based on the ratio of supporting walls. The GNN is trained to classify nodes into three distinct classes, determined by vertical connection length proportions (>70%, 50-70%, <50%), complemented by an additional "dummy" category denoted as "not applicable" for nodes representing windows and doors.

The training phase was performed using a synthetic data set that consists of 710 BIM models of shafts representing security rooms and other components that are expected to be found in these shafts. The synthetic data set was generated and labelled manually. Overall, the graph representation of the data set consists of 51,630 nodes and 78,811 edges, capturing the connections and relationships between the components in the shafts. The training was performed several times, using different combinations of data, graph structures and different GNN model architectures, and achieved a commendable accuracy rate ranging between 81-94%. Among the different GNN models we tested, the Graph Attention Network (GAT) model was the best data structure, reaching the top accuracy of 94.58%. The trained model was utilized for generating predictions on a real test case model, and achieved a prediction accuracy of 86.84%.

Discussion and Conclusions

Semantic enrichment of BIM models holds significant promise for improving ACC processes. Previous studies of semantic enrichment demonstrated a variety of applicable computational methods, including rule-based systems, ML, and graph-based approaches. Graph analysis for building representation offers an opportunity to address the intricate challenge of evaluating regulatory restrictions that consider the interconnected nature of model elements. Notably, GNNs emerge as a powerful tool in classifying model elements into meaningful categories, exhibiting efficacy without the necessity for precise numerical values. The ability to tackle such complex code clauses by leveraging semantic enrichment to enhance ACC, can pave the way for achieving higher levels of automation in the process for a wider scope of regulations that can be checked automatically.

Despite the promising results achieved in this work, it is important to note that GNNs are not the best solution for all regulatory requirements. In fact, additional work needs to be done for understanding the nature of the different regulations and matching each with the most promising method for automation. In addition, GNN based process faces certain limitations, primarily the lack of real-world models for training purposes. Many designers and professionals are hesitant to share their models, leading to a scarcity of real-world data. The diversity in regulations presents another challenge, requiring the generation of more synthetic data to cover all possible cases that might be encountered in real design. Addressing these limitations is crucial for further advancing the effectiveness and applicability of semantic enrichment and GNNs in the context of ACC.

References

- [1] C. Eastman, “The use of computers instead of drawings in building design,” *AIA J.*, vol. 63, no. 3, pp. 46–50, 1975.
- [2] R. Amor and J. Dimyadi, “The promise of automated compliance checking,” *Dev. Built Environ.*, vol. 5, p. 100039, Mar. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.dibe.2020.100039.
- [3] T. Bloch, “Connecting research on semantic enrichment of BIM - review of approaches, methods and possible applications,” *J. Inf. Technol. Constr.*, vol. 27, pp. 416–440, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.36680/j.itcon.2022.020.
- [4] J. Beetz, J. Van Leeuwen, and B. De Vries, “Towards a topological reasoning service for IFC-based building information models in a semantic web context,” in *Proceedings of the Joint International Conference on Computing and Decision Making in Civil and Building Engineering*, 2006, pp. 3426–3435.
- [5] M. Belsky, R. Sacks, and I. Brilakis, “Semantic enrichment for building information modeling,” *Comput.-Aided Civ. Infrastruct. Eng.*, vol. 31, no. 4, pp. 261–274, Apr. 2016, doi: 10.1111/mice.12128.
- [6] I. Brilakis, M. Belsky, and R. Sacks, “A Semantic Enrichment Engine for Building Information Modelling,” *Comput.-Aided Civ. Infrastruct. Eng.*, pp. 261–274.
- [7] S. Daum and A. Borrmann, “Checking spatio-semantic consistency of building information models by means of a query language,” in *Proc. of the Intl Conference on Construction Applications of Virtual Reality*, 2013.
- [8] P. Pauwels, R. De Meyer, and J. Van Campenhout, “Interoperability for the Design and Construction Industry through Semantic Web Technology,” in *Semantic Multimedia*, vol. 6725, T. Declerck, M. Granitzer, M. Grzegorzec, M. Romanelli, S. Rüger, and M. Sintek, Eds., Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2011, pp. 143–158. doi: 10.1007/978-3-642-23017-2_10.
- [9] R. Sacks, L. Ma, R. Yosef, A. Borrmann, S. Daum, and U. Kattel, “Semantic Enrichment for Building Information Modeling: Procedure for Compiling Inference Rules and Operators for Complex Geometry,” *J. Comput. Civ. Eng.*, vol. 31, no. 6, p. 04017062, Nov. 2017, doi: [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CP.1943-5487.0000705](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CP.1943-5487.0000705).
- [10] J. Werbrouck, P. Pauwels, M. Bonduel, J. Beetz, and W. Bekers, “Scan-to-graph: Semantic enrichment of existing building geometry,” *Autom. Constr.*, vol. 119, p. 103286, 2020.
- [11] T. Bloch and R. Sacks, “Comparing machine learning and rule-based inferencing for semantic enrichment of BIM models,” *Autom. Constr.*, vol. 91, pp. 256–272, Jul. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.autcon.2018.03.018.
- [12] A. Karmakar and V. S. K. Delhi, “Requirements of Machine Learning and Semantic Enrichment for BIM-Based Automated Code Compliance Checking: A Focus Group Study,” in *Advances in Information Technology in Civil and Building Engineering*, vol. 357, S. Skatulla and H. Beushausen, Eds., in *Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering*, vol. 357., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2024, pp. 65–74. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-35399-4_6.
- [13] B. Koo, S. La, N.-W. Cho, and Y. Yu, “Using support vector machines to classify building elements for checking the semantic integrity of building information models,” *Autom. Constr.*, vol. 98, pp. 183–194, Feb. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.autcon.2018.11.015.
- [14] B. Koo, R. Jung, and Y. Yu, “Automatic classification of wall and door BIM element subtypes using 3D geometric deep neural networks,” *Adv. Eng. Inform.*, vol. 47, p. 101200, 2021.
- [15] Z. Wang, R. Sacks, and T. Yeung, “Exploring graph neural networks for semantic enrichment: Room type classification,” *Autom. Constr.*, vol. 134, p. 104039, Feb. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.autcon.2021.104039.
- [16] T. Bloch, A. Borrmann, and P. Pauwels, “Graph-based learning for automated code checking – Exploring the application of graph neural networks for design review,” *Adv. Eng. Inform.*, vol. 58, p.

102137, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.aei.2023.102137.

- [17] Home Front Command, “Specifications for Building Shelters,” Protective structures department, Home Front Command, Ramle, Israel, 2010. [Online]. Available: http://www.oref.org.il/SIP_STORAGE/files/6/3196.pdf

Formalization of building codes and regulations in knowledge graphs

Gonçal Costa^a, Edlira Vakaj^b, Thomas Beach^c, Rita Lavikka^d, Maxime Lefrançois^e, Antoine Zimmermann^e, Thamer Mecharnia^e, Vladimir Alexiev^f, Amna Dridi^b, Hansi Hettiarachchi^b, Nataliya Keberle^f

^a Human Environment Research (HER), La Salle, Ramon Llull University, Barcelona, Spain

^b Faculty of Computing, Engineering and Built Environment, Birmingham City University, Birmingham, UK

^c School of Engineering, Cardiff University, Cardiff, UK

^d VTT Technical Research Centre of Finland, Espoo, Finland

^e Mines Saint-Etienne, Univ Clermont Auvergne, INP Clermont Auvergne, CNRS, Saint-Etienne, France

^f Ontotext, Nikola Gabrovski, Str. Twins Centre, Bulgaria

1. Introduction

The Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) industry is subject to many building codes and regulations that apply to the design and construction of buildings. These regulations often involve complex language and technical vocabulary that can give rise to different interpretations, depending on their context and purpose, and therefore a difficulty in their application. The introduction of Building Information Modelling (BIM), as well as authoring tools capable of creating and exporting 3D representations of buildings, is paving the way for compliance checking to become more automated and less dependent on interpretation. This should allow for better quality by reducing the time needed for checking and avoiding human errors. However, despite attempts to provide new BIM-based methods and approaches to achieve this goal in the past two decades, none of these methods have proven to be close to being a definitive solution.

The basis for checking compliance against regulations using a BIM model is to have a description of the regulations in a computable form. In turn, this makes it necessary to define data requirements for models, guaranteeing that regulations can be checked consistently. Within this framework, several scenarios can be considered to address the problem. One is to consider the descriptive part of the regulation separate from the execution part, that is, compliance checking procedures. Typically, those in charge of writing the regulations publish them in plain text documents in PDF format. Therefore, the next evolutionary step is to manage construction regulations in a machine-readable way underpinned by semantics, thus ensuring they can be interpreted precisely by the software used for checking buildings against them.

One approach to address automation in regulatory compliance checking, considering the above scenario, is using Semantic Web technologies, ontologies, and semantic rule languages 0. Within this context, the contribution of this article is to present the rule formalization process aimed at transforming building codes and regulations described in plain text into machine-readable documents using a domain-specific rule language. The formalisation process has been devised during the development of the Automated Compliance Checks for Construction, Renovation or Demolition Works (ACCORD)²⁷, a research project funded by the Horizon Europe program. ACCORD aims to digitalize building permit and compliance processes. The research focuses on the use of BIM and GIS models along with other data sources to automate the regulatory compliance checking process through a semantic framework that integrates processes, regulations, data, and digital construction permit tools.

²⁷ <https://accordproject.eu/>

2. Methodology

The methodology that underpins the rule formalisation process – depicted in Figure 1– consists of the following four steps:

1. **Content extraction and conversion to structured data format:** most building regulations and codes are currently provided in plain text documents via PDF format. However, their content is commonly organized into a list of chapters, sections, or articles, each addressing a specific aspect the building must comply with (e.g., Structural Safety or Accessibility), together with the corresponding title and the text itself. One way to provide structured content can be through a spreadsheet document.
2. **Identify clauses and formalise logical relationships:** in this step, paragraphs, clauses and individual words and phrases that contain regulatory content are identified, and how these paragraphs and clauses logically interact is also formalised. A method that can be used to carry out this step is Requirement, Application, Selection, Exception (RASE) 0. The method consists of enriching the text with metadata, highlighting the formal logical relationships between individual terms. The result is a hierarchical structure of nested boxes, with highlighted text forming the leaf elements of this structure. This allows other readers, including machines, to pick out the key phrases and how they logically relate.
3. **Rule formalisation:** this step formalises the extraction of individual logical decisions. This may involve simple logical operations, a simple mapping of a term to a value (e.g., width = 5), or complex logical relationships involving several terms. To deal with complex cases, an additional rules language can be used to define them.
4. **Mapping words to execution context:** the mapping to the execution context is performed using the buildingSMART data dictionary (bSDD) service. This way, those terms identified in the previous steps are mapped to terms within the bSDD. The definitions stored within this data dictionary inform how the data associated with those terms can be retrieved/calculated.

Two approaches are considered for the implementation of the methodology described above: a manual process using the RASE method and through Natural Language Processing (NLP). Figure 1 also provides more details of each of these approaches.

Fig. 1: Rule formalisation process.

The implementation of the methodology has required the development of a semantic data model to represent the building codes and regulations and a building compliance rule language. An ontology in OWL provides a semantic representation of a data domain. Its purpose for the rule formalisation process is to cover both general concepts (e.g., time, processes, and file/document metadata) and domain-specific aspects related to the AEC industry (e.g., building topology and construction projects) for this domain. To create the ontology, the reuse of existing ones in the AEC field was considered, either adopting their terminology and vocabulary or aligning with them. A benchmarking criterion was used to evaluate and compare them according to a set of metrics (accessibility, online availability, and evaluation methods: FAIR, OOPS, OQuaRE). The result was the Architecture Engineering and Construction Compliance Checking and Permitting Ontology (AEC3PO²⁸)⁰. The ontology acts as an interface connecting: (1) knowledge-providing, building codes, regulations, and standards, (2) compliance and permitting processes and documentation, and (3) compliance and permitting actors. AEC3PO has been validated through a survey with different experts and through the OOPS (Ontology Pitfall Scanner!) evaluation tool⁰.

Connected to AEC3PO is the Building Compliance Rule Language (BCRL), which complements the instances by providing a description of the checks using a specific and dedicated grammar. Additionally, NLP techniques have been applied to automate part of the rule extraction to help regulatory experts in the rule formalisation process.

3. Results

A set of regulations has been selected from different countries (Finland, Estonia, Germany, the United Kingdom, and Spain). Each non-English regulation has been translated into English to have a common linguistic base to simplify the complexities in a first development version of the process. From these regulations, a set of formalised regulatory documents has been generated in an open, machine-readable format, in YAML-DL⁰ and RDF formats for each regulation.

Figs. 2 and 3 Fig. 3: Excerpt of the same text shown in show an example of how the part of a regulatory text is tagged following the RASE method. Then, Fig. 4 shows how one of the clauses of this text is transformed into the ACCORD domain-specific rule language in YAML-DL format.

4. Next steps

Once the rule formalisation process has been satisfactorily applied to generate a set of machine-readable documents, the next step is the development of a rule formalisation tool that will assist regulatory experts in the process of formalising regulations into the ACCORD domain-specific rule language. The tool is developed for professionals who are experts in regulations and building codes but unaware of the internal implications of their formalisation. It is also expected to be able to apply NLP techniques to provide an alternative to the current manual method with the aim of generating documents automatically. Nevertheless, the most significant step involves providing access to the microservices designed to perform the checks reusing the semantic rules, therefore demonstrating the validity of the proposed approach in ACCORD. Such microservices will be part of the ACCORD compliance checking orchestration platform to be developed. Finally, the focus group method will be applied through surveys and interviews, first to verify the conceptualisation approach of the tool and then to evaluate the user experience to provide better support and interaction.

²⁸ <https://w3id.org/lbd/aec3po/>

The ramp referred to in subsection 1 above shall be easily noticeable and straight with a smooth, hard and non-slippery surface, width of at least 900 millimetres and, if the ramp is not connected to a fixed structure, a protective edge of at least 50 millimetres in height. There shall be a horizontal landing with a length of at least 1,500 millimetres at the lower and upper end of the ramp. The gradient of the ramp may not exceed five per cent. However, if the elevation difference is no more than 1,000 millimetres, the ramp may not have a gradient of more than eight per cent. In that case, the elevation difference of a continuous ramp may not be more than 500 millimetres, after which there shall be a horizontal intermediate landing with a length of at least 2,000 millimetres. However, in an outdoor area the ramp may have a gradient of more than five per cent only if it can be kept in a condition comparable with that of an indoor ramp. Provisions on railings, handrails and other arrangements intended to prevent falling down and misstepping are laid down by decree issued under section 117d, subsection 2 of the Land Use and Building Act.

Fig. 2: Extract from the Finnish regulations on the operational safety of buildings.

The ramp referred to in subsection 1 above shall be easily noticeable and straight with a smooth, hard and non-slippery surface, width of at least 900 millimetres and, if the ramp is not connected to a fixed structure, a protective edge of at least 50 millimetres in height. There shall be a horizontal landing with a length of at least 1,500 millimetres at the lower and upper end of the ramp. The gradient of the ramp may not exceed five per cent. However, if the elevation difference is no more than 1,000 millimetres, the ramp may not have a gradient of more than eight per cent. In that case, the elevation difference of a continuous ramp may not be more than 500 millimetres, after which there shall be a horizontal intermediate landing with a length of at least 2,000 millimetres. However, in an outdoor area the ramp may have a gradient of more than five per cent only if it can be kept in a condition comparable with that of an indoor ramp. Provisions on railings, handrails and other arrangements intended to prevent falling down and misstepping are laid down by decree issued under section 117d, subsection 2 of the Land Use and Building Act.

Fig. 3: Excerpt of the same text shown in Fig.2 tagged using the RASE method.

```

However, if the elevation difference is no more than 1,000 millimetres, the ramp may not have a gradient of more than eight per cent. In that case, the elevation difference of a continuous ramp may not be more than 500 millimetres, after which there shall be a horizontal intermediate landing with a length of at least 2,000 millimetres.
- $id: 2.3.6.5
  identifier: 2.3.6.5
  text: ". In that case,"
  $type: Statement
- text: the elevation difference of a continuous ramp may not be more than 500 millimetres
  $id: Government_Decree_on_Accessibility_of_building/2.3.6.6
  identifier: 2.3.6.6
  isOperationalizedBy:
    $type: DeclarativeCheckMethod
    text: ':Contains not exists => (:type == :Landing) && :ElevationChange < 0.5 '
  $type:
  - CheckStatement
  - Requirement
- $id: 2.3.6.7
  identifier: 2.3.6.7
  text: ","
  $type: Statement
- text: "after which there shall be a horizontal intermediate landing with a length of at least 2,000 millimetres"
  $id: Government_Decree_on_Accessibility_of_building/2.3.6.8
  identifier: 2.3.6.8
  isOperationalizedBy:
    $type: DeclarativeCheckMethod
    text: ':Contains exists => (:type == :Landing && :Width >=2 )
  $type:
  - CheckStatement
  - Exception

```

Fig. 4: Excerpt of the generated part of the document using the ACCORD domain-specific rule language in YAML-DL format corresponding to the clause shown at the top.

5. Conclusions

We introduced a rule formalisation process to automate compliance checking of building codes and regulations against building models. The basic components of our solution include the AEC3PO ontology and a novel Domain Specific Language (DSL) for building compliance built upon AEC3PO. The next step will involve implementing the rule formalisation process in a graphical tool. An issue to be resolved here is finding an appropriate method for transforming the content provided in images and tables into structured data. The use of Semantic Web and NLP technologies has proven to be useful for solutions in the field of building compliance checking. However, how to provide accurate and complete regulation data, the complexity of modelling compliance requirements, and the difficulty of interpreting natural language texts still require more research.

6. Acknowledgments

The research reported has been conducted in the ACCORD project, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme, HORIZON-CL4-2021-TWIN-TRANSITION-01-10: Digital permits and compliance checks for buildings and infrastructure under grant agreement no 101056973, and UK Research and Innovation programme (UKRI) under grant agreement no 10040207.

References

- Vakaj, E., Lefrançois, M., Dridi, A., Beach, T., Gaber, M., Costa, G., & Tan, H. (2023). Semantisation of Rules for Automated Compliance Checking. In *Linked Data in Architecture and Construction Week*, Matera, Italy.
- Hjelseth, E., & Nisbet, N. (2011). Capturing normative constraints by use of the semantic mark-up RASE methodology. In *Proceedings of CIB W78-W102 Conference*, pp. 1-10. Sophia Antipolis, France.
- Mecharnia, Lefrançois, Zimmermann, Vakaj, Dridi, Hettiarachchi, Vladimir Alexiev, Keberle, Tan, Noardo, Makkinga, Cheung (2023). D2.1: Existing ontologies, standards, and data models in the building data domain relevant to compliance checking. ACCORD project. Available on: https://accordproject.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/09/ACCORD_D2.1_Technical_Report_Existing_Models.pdf.
- Poveda-Villalón, M., Gómez-Pérez, A., & Suárez-Figueroa, M. C. (2014). OOPS! (Ontology Pitfall Scanner!): An On-line Tool for Ontology Evaluation. *International Journal on Semantic Web and Information Systems (IJSWIS)*, 10, 7–34.
- Kellogg, G., Polli, R., Scherbakov, A., and Thibodeau, T. (2022). YAML-LD. Available at: <https://github.com/json-ld/yaml-ld> (Accessed February 19, 2024).

Achieving Extensibility within a Standards-based Platform for the Digital Building Permit in Montevideo

Laura González^a, Bruno Rienzi^a, Raquel Sosa^a, Valentina Cornelius^a, Martín O’Neil^a, Gustavo Guimerans^a, Janet Cortés^a, Fabricio Álvarez^a, Andrés Nebel^a, Mauricio Calcagno^b, Maximiliano Riva^b, Federico Reale^b, Carolina Viñas^c, Gerardo Agresta^d, Juan José Prada^d and María Eugenia Corti^d

^a *Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad de la República, Montevideo, Uruguay*

^b *Pyxis, Montevideo, Uruguay*

^c *DICA & Asociados, Montevideo, Uruguay*

^d *Intendencia de Montevideo, Montevideo, Uruguay*

The automation of the Building Permit (BP) process is of utmost importance for the digital transformation of the Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) sector [1]. Indeed, several Digital Building Permit (DBP) solutions aiming to automate this process have emerged during the last years [2] as well as guidelines for developing such solutions which, in particular, recommend the use of standards to promote their interoperability and portability [1]. Extensibility [3] is another relevant quality attribute when building these solutions, to be able to expand them in order to verify additional BP requirements or to leverage functionality provided by other software components, without the need of modifying the core of the solutions.

This work describes how extensibility was achieved within a standards-based DBP platform developed for Montevideo (capital of Uruguay) [4], in the context of a program for the innovation in public services [5] of the national research and innovation agency of Uruguay (ANII) [6]. This development was carried out by an interdisciplinary team with members with diverse DBP-related skills (e.g. AEC, BIM, software engineering) and coming from organizations of different sectors: Intendencia de Montevideo [7] (public administration), Facultad de Ingeniería [8] (academia), Pyxis [9] (software industry), Dica & Asociados [10] (AEC industry).

The following paragraphs: i) analyze related work; ii) present a general description of the DBP approach [4] and, in particular, of the DBP platform; iii) describe how extensibility was achieved within this platform to be able to verify new BP requirements and leverage additional software components; iv) illustrate the operation of the extensible platform by describing how a BP requirement applying to Montevideo is verified; and v) describe how the proposal was assessed as well as how the results of this work may be leveraged.

Several DBP solutions have emerged during the last years [1][2]. Pilot projects have been carried out for specific locations (e.g. Smart Build Environment in Sweden [11], and XPlanung / XBau in Germany [12]). There are also proposals for specific 3D modeling tools such as Revit (e.g. SMARTreview APR [13], SoftTech BIMDCR [14]). In addition, some solutions enable the definition of checking rules using a proprietary language to verify BP requirements on building models specified in standard formats (e.g. Solibri Office [15]). Although these initiatives have provided contributions to the DBP area, most existing solutions are usually partial, tailored-made or tool-specific, hindering the achievement of software quality attributes such as extensibility, interoperability and portability.

In order to continue advancing in the DBP area and to promote the accomplishment of such quality attributes, in our previous work we proposed an open and standard-based approach for the DBP in Montevideo [4]. The proposal leverages Building Information Modeling (BIM) and

follows current guidelines for DBP such as interdisciplinary work, open standards, and machine readable

requirements [16]. Particularly, it uses several standards such as Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) [17], BIM Collaboration Format (BCF) [18] and Decision Model and Notation (DMN) [19], aiming to promote interoperability with other systems, portability of solutions (e.g. BP verification logic), and vendor neutrality (by enabling AEC applicants and municipalities to select standards-compliant products that best fit their needs and constraints). The proposal was developed based on Design Science Research (DSR) [20], resulting in two main artifacts: a compliance management life cycle and a DBP platform supporting such cycle.

Fig. 1 shows the general idea of the approach [4]: i) AEC Applicants model a building project using some BIM tool and following guidelines (e.g. Uniclass 2015 as classification system); ii) applicants export the project to an IFC File and upload it to the platform; iii) the platform validates its structure using an IFC Checker; iv) the platform verifies BP requirements, by leveraging data providers (to obtain data regarding models) and a repository of digitalized and executable BP requirements (based on DMN); v) the platform generates a BCF File to communicate compliance violations (if any) using a BCF Reporter; vi) applicants download the BCF File and visualize its content in some BIM tool.

Fig. 1: Open and Standards-based DBP Approach (adapted from [4])

The platform supports extensibility of BP requirements and data providers by design, without the need of modifying its core code. To this end, specific elements (e.g. data providers, BP requirements) are explicitly considered at the conceptual and component design levels of the platform.

Fig. 2 presents an excerpt of the conceptual model of the proposed platform. BP Requirements require data from the building / environment (i.e. control data) in order to be verified using a DMN Decision. A datum may require other data to be obtained. Data providers obtain these data using different mechanisms which characterize them as: Extractors (process IFC files to extract data), Calculators (calculate data with specialized libraries), or Consumers (obtain data from external systems).

Fig.2: Conceptual Model of the Platform (adapted from [4]).

Fig.3 presents the general design of the platform including its main components. The core of the DBP platform is composed of a frontend (DBP Frontend) and a backend (DBP Backend). The main database (Main DB) stores information of: i) the BP requirements that are supported by the platform; ii) the data required to verify these requirements; iii) the providers that obtain these data; and iv) identifiers of the DMN decisions that enable the verification of each BP requirement. The state database (State DB) stores building data that are obtained from data providers. The DMN Engine stores executable DMN decisions, that enable the verification of BP requirements. Data providers (i.e. Data Consumers, Data Calculators, Data Extractors) obtain building data as requested by DBP Backend. Given that obtaining these data may be a time-consuming task, the interaction between DBP Backend and data providers is based on asynchronous messaging. In particular, data providers asynchronously return obtained data through the *completeCalculationChannel*.

Fig.3: DBP Platform Development View.

In order to extend the platform with a new BP requirement such as the Maximum Height requirement: i) its information (e.g. requirementID = MAXHEIGHT) has to be stored in the Main DB, including the data needed to verify it (e.g. buildingHeight, parcelMaxHeight) and the identifier of the DMN Decision containing the associated verification logic; ii) this DMN decision has to be deployed within the DMN Engine; and iii) if the needed data have not been yet required by other requirement, a data provider has to be extended or included to obtain such data.

In order to extend the platform with a new data provider: i) its information has to be stored in the Main DB, including its name, description, communication channel for data requests, type (e.g. Extractor) and the data it provides; and ii) the data provider has to be implemented (e.g. leveraging a software library to perform specialized geometric calculations). All data providers have to receive data requests in a dedicated channel, send data responses to a predefined channel, and adhere to a message structure.

Fig.4 illustrates the operation of the extensible platform by presenting the interactions that are performed when verifying the MAX-HEIGHT requirement. This requirement states that buildings height cannot exceed the permissible maximum height for their parcels. The interactions involve four main components: DBP-Core, IFC-APY (an IFC data extractor), DMN Engine and IDM-GIS (a data consumer which interacts with a Geographic Information System to obtain information regarding parcels). After a verification request, DBP-Core obtains which data are required (i.e. buildingHeight, parcelMaxHeight) to verify MAX-HEIGHT (1). DBP-Core obtains data dependencies (2) (parcelNumber is required to obtain parcelMaxHeight). DBP-Core obtains Data

Providers for the required data (3). DBP-Core interacts with IFC-APY to obtain the values of buildingHeight and parcelNumber (4). Using the parcelNumber value, DBP-Core interacts with IDM-GIS to obtain the parcelMaxHeight value (5). DBP-core interacts with the DMN Engine to verify the MAX-HEIGHT requirement based on the obtained data values (6).

The technical feasibility of the approach was validated through the development of a prototype [4], which supports the verification of fifteen BP requirements applying to Montevideo and is based on diverse open-source and standards-compliant solutions such as BIM Modeling Tools (e.g. BlenderBIM [21]), libraries (e.g. IfcOpenShell [22], SymPy [23], BIMTester [24]) and engines (e.g. jBPM [25]). Particularly, the extensibility of the platform was assessed during the iterations of the DSR process [26], as new BP requirements were included in each of them and data providers (three in total) were incorporated when required (e.g. to perform specialized calculations such as geometries intersection).

Fig.4: Verifying MAX-HEIGHT Requirement (adapted from [4]).

These results may be leveraged by researchers and practitioners working on DBP solutions, as they provide a detailed design and a reference implementation to support extensibility within a standards-based DBP platform. Additional material regarding the DBP approach, platform, reference implementation prototype and demos is available in [27].

Acknowledgements. Supported by project DPU_S_2021_2_172901 funded by Agencia Nacional de Investigación e Innovación (ANII), Uruguay. For their contributions to the project, we acknowledge: Lilián Navickis, Elizabeth González, Francisco Ponzoni and Sandra Cotto (Facultad de Ingeniería); Analia Semblat, Brian Puerta and Enrique Rodríguez (Pyxis); Ignacio Turcatti and Gabriel Díaz (Dica & Asociados); Álvaro Rettich, Álvaro Marques, Lucía Juambeltz and Joaquín González (Intendencia de Montevideo).

References

- [1] F. Noardo, D. Guler, J. Fauth, G. Malacarne, S. Mastrolembu Ventura, M. Azenha, P.-O. Olsson, L. Senger: *Unveiling the actual progress of Digital Building Permit: Getting awareness through a critical state of the art review*, Build. Environ. 213 (2022) 108854. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.108854>.

- [2] R. Sacks, C. Eastman, G. Lee, P. Teicholz: BIM Handbook – A Guide to Building Information Modeling For Owners, Engineers, Contractors, and Facility Managers, 3rd Edition, John Wiley & Sons, Hoboken, New Jersey. ISBN 978-1-119-28753-7.
- [1] Noardo, Guler, Fauth, Malacarne, Mastrolembro Ventura, Azenha, Olsson, Senger: Unveiling the actual progress of digital building permit: Getting awareness through a critical state of the art review. *Building and Environment* 213 (2022).
- [2] Noardo, F., Malacarne, G.: Digital building permit: a state of play – i eunnet4dbp international workshop on digital building permit. Tech. rep., EUNnet4DBP (2021).
- [3] Kazman, R., Echeverría, S., Ivers, J.: Extensibility. Tech. Rep. CMU/SEI-2022-TR-002, Carnegie Mellon University, Software Engineering Institute’s Digital Library (Apr 2022).
- [4] González, L., Rienzi, B., Sosa, R., Cornelius, V., O’Neil, M., Navickis, L., González, E., Guimerans, G., Cortés, J., Ponzoni, F., Álvarez, F., Nebel, A., Cotto, S., Aguiar, Y., Calcagno, M., Riva, M., Reale, F., Puerta, B., Rodríguez, E., Viñas, C., Turcatti, I., Díaz, G., Agresta, G., Prada, J.J., Corti, M.E., Rettich, Á., Marques, Á., Juambeltz, L., González, J.: An open and standards-based approach for the digital building permit in montevideo. In: Sales, T.P., de Kinderen, S., Proper, H.A., Pufahl, L., Karastoyanova, D., van Sinderen, M. (eds.) *Enterprise Design, Operations, and Computing. EDOC 2023 Workshops*. pp. 60–76. Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham (2024).
- [5] IDM: Verificación automática del permiso de construcción en Montevideo (2021), <https://innovacionpublica.anii.org.uy/desafios/construccion-inteligente/>
- [6] Agencia Nacional de Investigación e Innovación (ANII), <https://www.anii.org.uy/>
- [7] Intendencia de Montevideo (IDM) - Municipality of Montevideo, <https://montevideo.gub.uy/>
- [8] Facultad de Ingeniería - Universidad de la República, Uruguay, <https://www.fing.edu.uy/>
- [9] Pyxis, <https://pyxis.tech/>
- [10] Dica & Asociados, <https://dica.com.uy/>
- [11] Smart Built Environment: Smart Built Environment, <https://www.smartbuilt.se>
- [12] Krause, K.U., Munske, M.: Geostandards xplanung und xbau. *ZfV-Zeitschrift für Geodäsie, Geoinformation und Landmanagement* (2016).
- [13] SMARTreview APR: SMARTreview APR, <https://www.smartreview.biz>
- [14] SoftTech: BIMDCR, <https://softtech-engr.com/bimdcr>
- [15] Solibri: Solibri Office, <https://www.solibri.com/solibri-office>
- [16] Noardo, Malacarne, Mastrolembro-Ventura, Tagliabue, Ciribini, Ellul, Guler, Harrie, Senger, Waha, Stoter: Integrating expertises and ambitions for data-driven digital building permits-the eunet4db. *The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences* (2020).
- [17] Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) - ISO 16739-1:2018 (2018), <https://www.iso.org/standard/70303.html>
- [18] buildingSMART: BCF. <https://technical.buildingsmart.org/standards/bcf/>
- [19] OMG: Decision model and notation. <https://www.omg.org/spec/DMN/> (2021).
- [20] Hevner, A.R., March, S.T., Park, J., Ram, S.: Design science in information systems research. *MIS Q.* 28(1), 75–105 (3 2004).
- [21] Blender BIM, <https://blenderbim.org/>
- [22] IfcOpenShell, <https://ifcopenshell.org/>
- [23] SymPy, <https://www.sympy.org/>

- [24] BIMTester, <https://wiki.osarch.org/index.php?title=BIMTester>
- [25] jBPM, <https://www.jbpm.org/>
- [26] Peffers, Tuunanen, Rothenberger, Chatterjee: A design science research methodology for information systems research. *J. Manage. Inf. Syst.* 24(3), 45–77 (2007).
- [27] FING - PYXIS - DICA - IDM: Complementary material: code and videos. (2024), <https://www.fing.edu.uy/owncloud/index.php/s/lynEymKnSqe7tTH>

Optimisation of the fire safety certificate process in the digital and model-based building permit procedure

Janna Walter ^a, Joaquín Díaz ^a

^a Department of Architecture and Civil Engineering, University of Applied Sciences Mittelhessen, Giessen, Germany

Fire safety is considered a key public safety issue worldwide, with different countries taking different approaches. Despite national differences, most countries in Europe and around the world agree on the basic objectives of their fire safety regulations. These objectives include the protection of human and animal life, the prevention of fire injuries and the protection of property and building contents. In particular, the focus is on measures to prevent the outbreak of fire, prevent the spread of fire and smoke, enable the rescue of people, and assist firefighting. National regulations specify the necessary fire safety requirements for various aspects, which vary depending on the building, use and activities. In countries such as Germany, Austria, Switzerland, the United States or the United Kingdom, a fire safety certificate is required as part of the building permit process to demonstrate that the relevant fire safety requirements have been met in order to comply with public law regulations and their protection objectives.

In Germany, the fire safety certificate usually consists of a textual part and visualisations, which are generally produced digitally. Digital submission of the building application is already required by law in some German federal states. Some parts of Germany, such as Hesse, multiple printed documents are still required [1]. This time-consuming and costly media disruption is to be replaced in future by the digital building application or BIM-based building application. The "digital building application" mainly refers to the submission of the conventional building application in electronic form in order to comply with the requirements of the Federal Government's Online Access Act. In the future, however, the aim should be to work with generated machine-readable information and digital building information models created using the BIM planning method, rather than with scanned versions of previous documents and plans. Due to the lack of standardisation of fire safety processes and information within the BIM approach, those involved in fire safety design are not yet able to fully exploit the potential and benefits of digital building information models [2], [3]. Individual fire design processes can already be implemented based on models [2], [3], [4], [5].

This research aims to highlight current developments and future prospects in the field of fire safety in the context of the digital and model-based building application process. The study analyses the detailed process steps from the creation of a fire safety certificate to the handover to the architect or the submission of the building application. This analysis forms the starting point for identifying the specific information requirements at each stage of the digital and model-based process. As part of the work of the VDI and buildingSMART committees, the conventional fire safety process was analysed based on AHO Booklet 17 [6], which deals with fire safety services under building regulations. The Association of German Engineers (VDI) is an organisation that represents technical experts and engineers in Germany and develops standards and guidelines. The AHO (Committee of the Associations and Chambers of Engineers and Architects for the Fee Structure) is an association of engineering and architectural organisations whose main task is to represent and coordinate the fee and competition interests of engineers and architects. This was used as the basis for the model-based process, which, among other things, enabled the processes to be compared and analysed. The committees are made up of fire engineers, fire equipment manufacturers, insurers and academics. The individual process

phases were analysed in detail in the context of information requirements, which enabled the identification of specific information requirements for each phase of the digital and model-based process [7], [8].

The study shows that the conventional process for the digital certification of fire safety by the fire safety planning section already achieves the requirements for the implementation of the digital building application. Obviously, fire certificates are generally digital and only need to be uploaded. However, the current practice of having to print out the certificates and send them by post is time consuming and costly. However, this also requires an adaptation of the legal basis in the federal states, which does not yet fully meet the requirements for the electronic submission of applications, notifications and construction documents. For model-based fire safety certification in the BIM-based building permit process, the analysis shows that, on the one hand, the work process in the individual process steps of a fire safety engineer will change. On the other hand, a standardisation of fire safety-related information and processes is required for the transparent provision of fire safety-related information in the building information model. In the context of fire safety verification procedures in Germany, both national DIN (German Institute for Standardisation) standards and harmonised CEN standards must be considered in order to comply with legal requirements and standards. In addition to these standards, the specific legal requirements in Germany must also be considered. This is an indication of the complexity of fire safety and the need for standardisation.

The research provides architects and engineers with practical findings and tools for the effective fulfilment of information requirements in the fire protection verification process. Building authorities benefit from the simplification of the approval process and the provision of all necessary information. Construction companies can plan and realise construction projects more efficiently by knowing all the information requirements. For society and users, the research ensures that buildings meet the highest fire safety standards, and that the construction process is transparent and efficient.

The results of this research serve as a basis for the development and optimisation of information requirements in the digital and model-based building application process. This not only contributes to significant efficiency gains and cost savings, but also ensures that construction projects fulfil the highest standards in terms of fire safety and quality. It also serves as a basis for further research in an international context on the standardisation of fire safety-relevant information for the building permit process.

References

- [1] Hessisches Ministerium für Wirtschaft, Energie, Verkehr und Wohnen: *Bauvorlagenerlass Hessen (BVErl) vom 20. Januar 2022*, https://wirtschaft.hessen.de/sites/wirtschaft.hessen.de/files/2022-02/final_erlass_20_01_22.pdf
- [2] J. Walter, T. Obermeier, J. Díaz: *BIM in fire protection planning: attributes and classes relevant to practice*. In: *Bauingenieur* 96 (5), 182-190 (2021).
- [3] O. Matthiesen: *Fire protection in the model*, *Build-Ing.* (2020), Online, URL: <https://www.building.de/fachartikel/detail/brandschutz-im-modell/>
- [4] A. Davidson, J. Gales.: *BIM and fire safety Engineering – Overview of state of the art*. In: *International Journal of High-Rise Buildings*, Vol 10, No 4, 251-263 (2021). DOI: 10.21022/IJHRB.2021.10.4.251.
- [5] J. Norén, F. Nystedt, M. Strömgren, R. Möllard, M. Delin: *Fire protection engineering in a BIM environment*. Briab Brand & Riskingenjörerna AB (eds), Malmö, Schweden (2018).
- [6] AHO-Heft 17 – Leistung für den bauordnungsrechtlichen Brandschutz

- [7] J. Walter, J. Díaz: *Extending the IFC-Standard for fire safety building permit*, eWork and eBusiness in Architecture, Engineering and Construction: ECPPM 2022. London, United Kingdom, CRC Press, <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003354222-96>, 2023.
- [8] J. Walter, J. Díaz: *An Approach for Fire and Smoke Compartmentation Using the IFC-Structure*. In: Skatulla, S., Beushausen, H. (eds) *Advances in Information Technology in Civil and Building Engineering*. ICCBE 2022. Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering, vol 357. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-35399-4_41

Automatic verification of requirements in BIM models for building permit

Filippo Chiappini^a, Daniel Napps^b, Silvia Mastrolemba Ventura^a, Markus König^b Angelo Ciribini^a,

^a *Department Civil, Environmental, Architectural Engineering and Mathematics (DICATAM), University of Brescia, Via Branze 43, 25123, Brescia, Italy*

^b *Department of Civil Engineering, Ruhr University Bochum, Universitätsstrasse 150, 44801, Bochum, Germany*

Introduction

Nowadays, the digitalization of the Architecture, Engineering, Construction and Operation (AECO) industry is challenging many interdisciplinary stakeholders. People involved in this field are used to do their job using traditional approaches based on many years of experience. However, digitalization requires a change and adaptation to today's occupational requirements. A greater specialization in many areas within the construction sector necessitates a deeper analysis to allow checking compliance of processes, with greater control and clarity of the workflow aimed at the success of projects. It is well known that AECO is one of the most fragmented sectors, where it is quite difficult to achieve a detailed overview of a whole project. However, the introduction of Building Information Modeling (BIM) has helped to manage issues related to the exchange of information between different stakeholders (e.g., clients, architects, engineers, construction companies) [1]. However, further steps need to be taken to achieve a clear interoperability of data within the construction process [2]. This is useful for creating greater cooperation between the various stakeholders involved in the project, in order to achieve better coordination.

The adoption of these technologies and processes is still an open issue for public authorities. The authorities that issue building permits should specify the path to be followed. The review of models for a specific property regarding local legal conditions is an elementary component and, in a modified form, essential in many countries. In this way, the control carried out by the municipalities from the 2D drawings to the BIM models could improve the quality of the inspections concerning the requirements expressed in building regulations. The following *Figure 1* is a list of the requirements it has been attempted to verify.

CHEK List of regulations

Fig. 1: Requirements considered

Moreover, all these steps could be carried out more quickly and cost-effectively by the authorities [3]. Unfortunately, the interpretation of building regulations and the resultant information extraction to be understood by an automated process through a software is quite challenging. [4] [5] Typically, building requirements are written to be human-readable, not machine-readable: for analysis by a machine, sentences should be very clear, without the possibility of having different interpretations. In addition, Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools must be able to quantify each sentence of a normative text logically and mathematically.

Various authorities are organizing themselves to solve this issue, often through joint projects and research efforts. At European level, Horizon Europe funded projects CHEK (Change toolkit for digital building permit) [6], ACCORD (Automated Compliance Checks for Construction, Renovation or Demolition Works) [7] and DigiChecks [8] are working on this, and Germany is currently trying to introduce an automatic building check into the workflow for issuing building permits. Even international projects such as Dubai's Mandatory BIM Submission for Building Permits [9] that are currently addressing this issue resulting in a high level of importance for the topic in science and practice.

Objective

The aim of this research is to develop an automated process for checking building models based on municipal building regulations. Once the building regulations have been processed using Natural Language Processing (NLP) methods, instead of being analyzed by municipal employees, the requirements to be met are automatically checked on the digital model of the building submitted for the building permit.

However, translating human-readable requirements into machine-readable ones, as previously mentioned, appears to pose a considerable challenge. Furthermore, the manual process of analyzing requirements, whereby humans must read extensively and extract pertinent information, is exceedingly time-consuming. Automated analysis of these documents may potentially provide a solution to the problem. The BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) [10] [11] model is a prominent example of transformer models. Projects are already initiated to extract information from regulatory texts [12] [13] [14] however, it is crucial to establish a direct connection between the extracted requirements and the model being analyzed.

Additionally, in order to improve the interoperability between different stakeholder and develop an automated rule checking, it is essential to consider the IFC dataset created by buildingSMART International, which stakeholders use to exchange projects. The complexity of the IFC data schema presents challenges for its versatility and conversion to other file formats. These difficulties arise from the underlying language used in the IFC format, specifically the architecture of the EXPRESS structure [15]. The main objective regarding create a more flexible data scheme is to improve alternative file formats that provide better manageability for automatic checks on the model's information requirements. An example of this is the Information Delivery Specification (IDS) [16], which was one of the first to be developed by Building SMART. However, there are still some technical limitations that need to be addressed. One significant approach considered in this work is the use of ontologies in linked data [17]. For an introduction to the use of ontologies applied to graph data, please refer to the following works [18] [19] [20].

Methodology

First and foremost, it is essential to distinguish between two distinct processes that require analysis, as explained in *Figure 2*. The examination of building regulations and their conversion into information requirements, and the workflow of the building from its inception to the preparation of information requirements that necessitate verification by public authorities in order to obtain a building permit - colloquially referred to as formal building checks.

When analyzing building regulations, there are two main steps. The first step involves standardizing the building regulations according to the NISO STS standard [21]. This is done as a precautionary measure to ensure that any changes or alterations made to the regulations can be traced. Additionally, this step is useful for NLP to extract the requirements that need to be verified. This work utilizes a Bidirectional Encoder developed by Google known as BERT. An explanation of the functioning of BERT can be found in the paper of Schönfelder and König [22]. The second part of the work utilizes ChatGPT, one of the most important Large Language Models (LLMs). As stated in [23], ChatGPT has demonstrated high capabilities in creating queries in SPARQL [24] format to be submitted to the building model translated into RDF.

After verifying that the model is formally compliant, it is translated into RDF files using the relevant ontology from the Linked Data approach developed in [25]. The workflow for verifying the presence and subsequent verification of requirements using ontologies is expressed in the following works [26] [27] [28]. These works consider the principles that ontologies should contain [29] [30]. The requirements are then checked using queries generated by ChatGPT and applied to a viewer such as GraphDB [31], which can import any type of model in RDF format and submit different types of SPARQL to verify the building regulations required by municipalities. Once the procedure has undergone all necessary checks as per the considered regulations, the process is complete. Otherwise, modifications to the model are required. Subsequent research will necessitate a formal evaluation of the model, in addition to the technical check. Technical checking should be performed after rule inspection.

Fig. 2: Workflow approach

Expected research findings

The methodology presented is an academic contribution that firstly allows municipalities to develop standardized building regulations with a view to analyzing and verifying them using artificial intelligence methods, and secondly proposes a flexible approach to analyzing the data present in the model according to the principles of linked data.

On the other hand, the development of standardized building regulations would enable greater effectiveness of an NLP model capable of extracting and verifying compliance with these requirements in projects. In this view of building permit approval, the project manager would only be responsible for developing a project model that includes the required building requirements and ensures their compliance. The responsibility for verifying and analyzing building regulations would fall to the public administration, thus enabling compliant analysis across the entire national territory.

Regarding the application of the analyzed building regulations to a practical case, it has been considered the building regulations of the four municipalities used as pilots within the CHEK project: Ascoli Piceno, Prague, Lisbon, and Vila Nova de Gaia. The results aim to improve upon F1 score of 95% predicted by previous research [18]. To verify the accuracy of the translation of building models from IFC to IFC-LBD, we considered simple residential buildings.

In future works, Geographic Information System (GIS) could be integrated into research as a means of checking urban regulations and building regulations for which the interaction of the building with the urban context has to be considered (e.g., urban indices and distances).

This research aims to address building permit issues that impede the entire AECO sector and hinder the shift to digital control of projects. Primarily, adopting a digitalized approach could bolster the assessment's quality by exploring alternative solutions and determining the optimal choices to ensure a safer building for people and more environmentally sustainable infrastructure. Indeed, enhanced familiarity with the digital model of the project and its various aspects, courtesy of the prospective mandatory implementation of BIM models in private and public projects, can effectively address challenges related to building permit issuance. Consequently, through an automated digitization check, authorities can reduce the time taken to issue building permits and improve control.

References

- [1] André Borrmann, Markus König, Christian Koch and Jakob Beetz. *Building Information Modeling*. Technologische Grundlagen und industrielle Praxis. (2015)
- [2] Zijing Zhang, Ling Ma and Tim Broyd. Towards fully-automated code compliance checking of building regulations: challenges for rules interpretation and representation. In European Conference on Computing in Construction. (2022)
- [3] Judith Fauth, Tanya Bloch, Francesca Noardo, Nicholas Nisbet, Stefanie-Brigitte Kaiser, Peter Nørkjaer Gade and Jernej Tekavec. *Taxonomy for building permit system – organizing knowledge for building permit digitalization*. (2024)
- [4] Simon Fischer, Christian Schranz, Harald Urban and Daniel Pfeiffer. Automation of escape route analysis for BIM-based building code checking.
- [5] Nicholas Nisbet, Zijing Zhang, Ling Ma, Weiwei Chen and Mustafa Selcuk Cidik. *Semantic correction, enrichment and enhancement of social and transport*.
- [6] ACCORD – *Automated Compliance Checks for Construction, Renovation or Demolition Works*. European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grand agreement n° 101056973.

- [7] CHEK Digital Building Permit-*Change Toolkit for Digital Building Permit*. European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and innovation programme under grand agreement n° 1010 58559.
- [8] DigiChecks Digital Building Permit-*Change Toolkit for Digital Building Permit*. European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and innovation programme under grand agreement n° 1010 58541.
- [9] <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/dubais-mandatory-bim-submission-building-permits-your-fahdah-qofwvf/> (last accessed: February 2024)
- [10] Ashish Vaswani, Noam Shazeer, Niki Parmar, Jakob Uszkoreit, Llion Jones, Aidan N. Gomez, Łukasz Kaiser and Illia Polosukhin. *Attention Is All You Need*. In Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems, pages 6000–6010, Red Hook. (2017)
- [11] Jacob Devlin, Ming-Wei Chang, Kenton Lee and Kristina Toutanova. *BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding*. In Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long and Short Papers), pages 4171–4186, Minneapolis. (2019)
- [12] Junlong Peng and Xiangjun Liu, *Automated code compliance checking research based on BIM and knowledge graph*. In www.nature.com/scientificreports. (2023)
- [13] Stefan Fuchs and Robert Amor, *Natural Language Processing for Building Code Interpretation: A Systematic Literature Review*. (2021)
- [14] Botao Zhong, Xuejiao, Hanbin Luo, Qirui Zhou, Timothy Rose and Weili Fang, *Deep Learning-based extraction of construction procedural constrains from construction regulations*. (2020)
- [15] The EXPRESS Definition Language for IFC Development, https://standards.buildingsmart.org/documents/Implementation/The_EXPRESS_Definition_Language_for_IFC_Development.pdf (last accessed: February 2024)
- [16] <https://www.buildingsmart.org/what-is-information-delivery-specification-ids/> (last accessed: February 2024)
- [17] Pieter Pauwels, Aaron Costin and Mads Holten Rasmussen, *Knowledge Graphs and Linked Data for the Built Environment*. In Bolpagni Marzia, Gavina Rui, Riberio D. (eds) *Industry 4.0 for the Built Environment*. Structural Integrity, vol 20. Springer. (2022)
- [18] Mads Holten Rasmussen, Maxime Lefrançois, Ferninand Schneider Georg and Pieter Pauwels, *BOT: the Building Topology Ontology of the W3C Linked Building Data Group*. (2020)
- [19] Mads Holten Rasmussen, Pieter Pauwels, Maxime Lefrançois, Georg Ferninand Schneider, Christian Anker Hviid and Jan Karlshøj, *Recent changes in the Building Topology Ontology*. (2017)
- [20] Donkers Alex, Yang Dujuan, de Vries Bauke and Baken Niko, *Semantic Web Technologies for Indoor Environmental Quality: A Review and Ontology Design*. (2022)
- [21] Sven Zentgraf, Sherief Ali and Markus König, *Concept for Enriching NISO-STs Standards with Machine-Readable Requirements and Validations Rules*. In CONVR2023 23rd International Conference on Construction Applications of Virtual Reality. (2023)
- [22] Phillip Schönfelder and Markus König. *Deep Learning-Based Entity Recognition in Construction Regulatory Documents*. In 38C_ International Symposium on Automation and Robotics in Construction (ISARC 2021)
- [23] Yuan Zheng, Olli Seppänen, Sebastian Seiß and Jürgen Melzner. *Testing Chat-GPT-Aided SPARQL Generation for Semantic Construction Information Retrieval*. In CONVR2023 23rd International Conference on Construction Applications of Virtual Reality. (2023)
- [24] WC3 Recommendation, <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-query/> (last accessed: February 2024)
- [25] Mathias Bonduel, Jyrki Oraskari, Pieter Pauwels, Maarten Vergauwen and Ralf Klein (2018). *The IFC to linked building data converter: current status*. In Maria Poveda-Villalón, Pieter Pauwels and Ana Roxin (Eds.), *LDAC 2018 Linked Data in Architecture and Construction: Proceedings of the 6th*

- Linked Data in Architecture and Construction Workshop London, United Kingdom, June 19-21, (pp. 34-43). (2018)
- [26] Judith Fauth and Sebastian Seiß, Ontology for building permit authorities (OBPA) for advanced building permit processes. (2023)
- [27] Sven Zentgraf, Phillipp Hagerdon and Markus König, Multi-requirements ontology engineering for automated processing of document-based building codes to linked building data properties. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science. (2024)
- [28] Sven Zentgraf, Judith Fauth, Philipp Hagedorn, Sebastian Seiss, Kay Smarsly, Markus König, and Jürgen Melzner. *OntoBPR: Ontology-based workflow and concept for building permit reviews*. (2023)
- [29] María Poveda-Villalón, Paola Espinoza-Arias, Daniel Garijo and Oscar Corcho. *Coming to Terms with FAIR Ontologies, A position paper*. (2020)
- [30] Daniel Garijo and María Poveda-Villalón. Best Practices for Implementing FAIR Vocabularies and Ontologies on the Web. (2020)
- [31] Graph DB, https://graphdb.ontotext.com/documentation/10.4/?_hsmi=221550809 (last accessed: February 2024)

Mapping the processes and developing the rule sets for automated compliance checking of health and safety regulations in UK's infrastructure projects

Zijing Zhang^{a,b,d}, Tala Kasim^a, Maxwell Fordjour Antwi-Afari^a, Algan Tezel^c, Doug Potter^b

^a Aston University / Birmingham, UK

^b Arcadis Consulting UK Ltd / Manchester, UK

^c University of Nottingham / Nottingham, UK

^d University College London / London, UK

Introduction

The construction industry faces adverse health and safety (H&S) performance challenges. It is well-known that construction fatalities are three times higher than the all-industry rate in the UK. These H&S performance issues are further manifested in infrastructure projects that are typically large and complex, and involve many workers and onsite machinery [1]. To ensure desirable H&S outcomes in the UK, the design and construction processes must comply with the H&S regulations, especially the Construction (Design and Management) Regulations 2015 [8]. However, such compliance checking is traditionally conducted manually, which can be inefficient, laborious, and error-prone [5, 7, 14].

Automated compliance checking (ACC) is a tool for assessing compliance. In ACC, the design is checked against the regulations and requirements, with the results including “pass”, “fail” or “unknown” [5]. ACC has the potential to significantly improve the quality and efficiency of the traditional compliance checking process [16]. In the past 50 years, extensive research efforts have been devoted to the ACC field, where several studies have looked at compliance with the H&S regulations. For example, Zhang, Teizer [12] and Zhang, Teizer [13] developed rule sets for ACC against Occupational Safety and Health Administration (OSHA) regulations [11] based on existing safety in design best practices. They focused on workways and egress rule sets, and geometrical attributes such as the dimensions of holes in slabs and openings in walls, respectively. Moreover, Getuli, Ventura [6] used parametric rule sets to represent Italian Construction H&S normative texts, which were executed in Solibri Model Checker to check compliance automatically.

Problem statement

Although there have been some existing ACC studies on the H&S aspect, they focused on product-related regulations and clauses (i.e., looking at the objects and properties to check compliance), and little research has focused on the ACC of process-orientated regulations. This research thus selected the Construction (Design and Management) Regulations 2015 (CDM 15) in the UK as an example to look at its compliance checking during the design stage. For the design stage, the CDM 15 regulations specify the principal designer's duties (regulation 11) and the designer's duties (regulations 9 and 10) [8]. These regulations are outcome-based, objective-driven, and process-focused. There is no provision of detailed prescriptive guidance regarding how compliance can be achieved. Previous ACC research has mainly focused on prescriptive, product-focused regulations, whilst compliance with such process-focused and outcome-based regulations has not yet been checked automatically [2, 15]. Based on the current situation in the UK's infrastructure sector, two general research gaps are identified: 1) The implementation of ACC against the CDM 15 regulations will require clear and operable rule sets that are not currently

available; 2) there needs to be improved processes in the H&S management in UK's design organisations in the construction industry to achieve better efficiency and assurance in CDM compliance.

Research questions and gap

Given the current situation in this research domain and the gaps identified, this research aims to support the development of ACC for the CDM 15 regulations in the UK by developing processes and rule sets for H&S by design in infrastructure projects. Note that this is an ongoing research effort, and the proof-of-concept prototype development is out of the scope of this paper. Developing clear processes and rule sets is important because in the typical compliance-checking scenario, the rules are readily available in the regulatory documents, and the ACC process starts with interpreting the rules. However, in the case of H&S by design, due to the process-based and outcome-driven nature of the CDM 15 regulations, outlining clear H&S by design processes that comply with the CDM 15 regulations and developing related metrics will be a starting point for ACC development.

To achieve the research aim, the following research questions need to be answered:

What would be a good H&S by design process in UK's infrastructure projects that supports greater compliance with the CDM 15 regulations?

In UK's infrastructure projects, what metrics and/or rule sets would ensure that H&S by design processes have improved compliance with the CDM 15 regulations?

Methods

Design Science Research (DSR) is used to develop processes and rule sets for automated compliance checking of the CDM 15 regulations. DSR is a research methodology where researchers try to solve real-life problems by creating innovative artefacts (the processes and rule sets in this case) and thereby contributing to the body of knowledge [9]. DSR is suitable because this research aims to address the compliance checking problem by developing artefacts for ACC of the CDM 15 regulations.

In DSR, artefact development is an iterative process. In this paper, there are several iterations required in developing the artefact, as follows:

Questionnaires and semi-structured interviews are conducted to gather opinions and ideas from H&S by design experts in a UK infrastructure design organisation. Questionnaires are distributed to project managers working on infrastructure projects. Whilst questionnaires help to understand how H&S by design is conducted in a large number of projects, their weakness lies in that they cannot provide sufficient depth for developing detailed and standard H&S by design processes. After analysing the questionnaire responses that reflect the current practice of H&S management in the design and engineering of different infrastructure projects, semi-structured interviews are conducted to help gain a more in-depth understanding and develop detailed process maps.

Based on the input data in 1), two draft H&S by design process maps are produced concerning the design and the design change scenarios of the H&S by design processes.

The produced H&S by design process maps are reviewed by experts using focus group interviews. The focus group method is used as it facilitates discussions and idea exchanges, and generates collective views on a topic [4]. It is also a time-efficient way to generate substantial content [3].

Based on the comments from Stage 3, the process maps are revised and finalised.

Based on the process maps developed in Stage 4, semi-structured interviews are conducted to gather metrics to check compliance.

The proposed metrics developed in Stage 5 are then reviewed by experts in another focus group interview and adjustments are made.

Results and Discussion

Health and safety by design process maps

Fig 1 and Fig 2 show the H&S by design process maps that are produced as a result of the interviews, questionnaires and focus groups with experts in H&S by design in the UK's infrastructure sector. The first process map shows the process of H&S by design in the design stage, which includes project stakeholders and CDM duty holders. The second process map shows the process of H&S by design in the construction stage (design change).

Checking compliance with the CDM 15 regulations is essentially checking whether the H&S by design process follows the standard process in the produced process map. As such, the process maps provide a good starting point towards automated compliance checking of the CDM 15 regulations.

Fig. 1: H&S by design process map (design stage).

Fig. 2: H&S by design process map (construction stage).

Rulesets/metrics to measure compliance

The rule sets and/or metrics are developed following the steps outlined in the methods section. These rule sets/metrics are developed to support the compliance checking process and are complementary to the process maps. As there are too many metrics, here in the extended abstract we will only present the structure of the metrics spreadsheet and some examples instead of the full list of metrics.

The metrics structure resulted from a thorough analysis of the CDM regulations. Eight common components that construct (or result from) the CDM clauses have been found by the authors, the components and some examples are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Components of the CDM regulations and examples.

Components	Types of each component	Example(s)
Clause original texts	Not applicable	If the client fails to appoint a principal designer, the client must fulfil the duties of the principal designer as set out in regulations 11 and 12.
Number	Not applicable	Regulation 4 (1); Regulation 5 (3)
Compliance impact (trailing outcome)	Not applicable	Not accepting the post unless they have the skill, knowledge,

		experience to fulfil the role or have the organisational capability.
Subject	Type of actor; Named actor; evidence	Client; principal designer; contractor; the Health and Safety Executive; evidence (e.g., contracts, emails, meetings, documents)
Verb	Interact; report; specify; or verbs related to factors	Interact; report; specify; coordinate
Object	Type of actor; type of report; type of specification; type of factors; named actor/clause/entity/entry; evidence	Pre-construction information; principal contractor; designer;
Exception	Not applicable	As soon as is practicable; so far as is reasonably practicable; except any exempt information as mentioned by the CDM regulations
Time element	Explicit time element (mentioned directly in the clause); implicit time element (not directly mentioned in the clause)	At the start of the shift in which the work is to be carried out; after any event likely to have affected the strength or stability of the excavation; client to provide pre-construction information (which is related to the award of the contract)

As shown in Table 1, in each clause there is a clause number and clause original texts, as shown in the “examples” column. Each clause has a compliance impact (trailing outcome), which explains what impact the clause has regarding CDM compliance. The texts in each clause are related to five components, namely subject, verb, object, exception and time element, where exception and time element are optional (these do not exist in all clauses). The subject, verb and object refer to the constructs of the clause. Subjects in CDM clauses can be classified into two main types, namely type of actor (the instance of which is called “named actor”) and evidence, with examples shown in Table 1. Verbs are usually “interact”, “report”, “specify”, or “verbs related to factors (e.g., coordinate with stakeholders)”. Objects in CDM clauses also have several types, including type of actor, type of report, type of specification, type of factors and evidence. And similarly, their instance can be “named actor/clause/entity/entry”. The examples are shown in Table 1. A common expression in the CDM clauses is “so far as is reasonably practicable”,

which sets out the exception to the duty specified in the rest of a clause. It is essentially to say that it is acceptable that not all measures are taken as it may not be financially practicable. In addition, it is important to consider the time element of CDM clauses as in some cases, CDM compliance relies on timely actions.

Discussion

This research presents H&S by design process maps, compared with previous ACC research about H&S regulations such as Hossain and Ahmed [10], this research makes a distinct contribution as it is concerned with process compliance rather than product compliance (i.e., focusing on objects and attributes). The findings of this research can make an impact through its implementation in practice. In practice, the processes in the process maps are expected to be followed as standard procedures. Metrics are developed to measure how well the processes are followed automatically. When checking against the metrics, the process maps need to be considered as the time element as compliance with the CDM regulations is time sensitive.

This research also highlights that ACC has a broader meaning: not only as a tool to check compliance and provide a one-off report but also as a decision support tool during the design process to achieve better business value. This resonates with the design organisation's aspirations. The CDM 15 regulations and internal company processes can be checked in this ACC workflow.

Conclusion

This paper presents the processes and rule sets (metrics) for the automated compliance checking of the UK's H&S regulations (CDM 15 regulations) in infrastructure projects focusing on the design stage. With the results of this paper, ACC systems could be developed to check compliance with the CDM 15 regulations.

This study is one of the first to focus on developing rule sets and processes to check compliance in design risk management from a health and safety perspective. Based on this research, researchers could conduct future studies to develop an ACC system to check compliance in the H&S aspects against the CDM 15 regulations, similar H&S regulations in other countries and other outcome-based, objective-driven and process-focused requirements. For practitioners, the process maps produced in this research can serve as a guideline to improve their H&S management processes in design and construction (design change) stages and achieve better compliance outcomes with the CDM 15 regulations.

This study has limitations. The process maps and metrics are developed based on experts' input. Future research could collect more data from experts to improve and refine them further.

Acknowledgements

Appreciation is expressed to the company and all participants for their support in this study. The authors would also like to thank UKRI, as this investigation was developed through a Knowledge Transfer Partnership (KTP) project supported by Innovate UK. The authors would also like to thank Nicholas Nisbet for his suggestions on this study.

References

- [1] Alhammadi, S.A., et al., *Occupational health and safety practice in infrastructure projects*. International journal of occupational safety and ergonomics, 2022. **28**(4): p. 2631-2644.
- [2] Amor, R. and J. Dimyadi, *The promise of automated compliance checking*. Developments in the built environment, 2021. **5**: p. 100039.

- [3] Berg, B., *Qualitative research methods for the social sciences*. 2001.
- [4] Cooper, D.R. and P. Schindler, *Business research methods*. 2014: Mcgraw-hill.
- [5] Eastman, C., et al., *Automatic rule-based checking of building designs*. *Automation in construction*, 2009. **18**(8): p. 1011-1033.
- [6] Getuli, V., et al., *BIM-based code checking for construction health and safety*. *Procedia engineering*, 2017. **196**: p. 454-461.
- [7] Han, C.S., J.C. Kunz, and K.H. Law, *Client/server framework for on-line building code checking*. *Journal of computing in civil engineering*, 1998. **12**(4): p. 181-194.
- [8] Health and Safety Executive, *Construction (Design and Management) Regulations 2015*, Health and Safety Executive, Editor. 2015.
- [9] Hevner, A., et al., *Design science research in information systems*. *Design research in information systems: theory and practice*, 2010: p. 9-22.
- [10] Hossain, M.M. and S. Ahmed, *Developing an automated safety checking system using BIM: a case study in the Bangladeshi construction industry*. *International Journal of Construction Management*, 2022. **22**(7): p. 1206-1224.
- [11] Occupational Safety and Health Administration. *Regulations (Standards - 29 CFR)*. 2023 08/12/2023]; Available from: <https://www.osha.gov/laws-regs>.
- [12] Zhang, S., et al., *Building information modeling (BIM) and safety: Automatic safety checking of construction models and schedules*. *Automation in construction*, 2013. **29**: p. 183-195.
- [13] Zhang, S., et al. *Automated safety-in-design rule-checking for capital facility projects*. 2013.
- [14] Zhang, Z., L. Ma, and T. Broyd. *Towards fully-automated code compliance checking of building regulations: Challenges for rule interpretation and representation*. 2022. EC³ (European Conference on Computing in Construction).
- [15] Zhang, Z., L. Ma, and N. Nisbet, *Unpacking ambiguity in building requirements to support automated compliance checking*. *Journal of Management in Engineering*, 2023. **39**(5): p. 04023033.
- [16] Zhang, Z., et al., *Capabilities of rule representations for automated compliance checking in healthcare buildings*. *Automation in Construction*, 2023. **146**: p. 104688.

DMN as a visual interface for building constraint creation

Emma Nuyts^a, Jeroen Werbrouck^a, Ruben Verstraeten^a

^a Department of Architecture and Urban Planning, Ghent University, Jozef Plateastraat 22, 9000 Gent

Automated Compliance Checking in the Architecture Engineering and Construction industry

Automated Compliance Checking (ACC) is rapidly gaining ground in the Architecture, Engineering and Construction (AEC) industry. ACC has been a research topic for several decades, but as it is closely related to building permits, the topic is benefiting from the recent attention that building permits are receiving due to digitisation efforts across Europe. Indeed, pushing the building permit process to a higher level of digital maturity opens opportunities for (semi-)automatic checking of regulations. In this context, the transformation of rules expressed in ambiguous natural language into machine-processable formalisms remains an important issue in the ACC domain.

Need for human-friendly interfaces

Little attention has been paid to the creation of machine-processable specifications in a human-friendly interface. The study of user interaction is particularly important because it is usually people without any programming knowledge, such as building code writers or architects, who would benefit most from this automated review process. A common way to ensure smooth user interaction is to use a Visual Programming Language (VPL). This allows program elements to be manipulated graphically rather than textually [1]. While Preidel & Borrmann [2] propose the Visual Code Checking Language (VCCL) for this purpose, and Senthilvel & Beetz [3] propose a workflow using the open-source visual programming editor PyFlow, no standardised process and decision notations were implemented in this research.

The Object Management Group (OMG) has standardised two such notations: the Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN) [4] for modelling processes, and the Decision Model and Notation (DMN) [5] for modelling decisions. Häußler et al. [6] investigated the feasibility of implementing code-checking rules using BPMN and DMN, with the guidelines on the design of railway structures as a use-case. Considering only the rules relevant to the digital railway model, 68% can be represented using BPMN and DMN. Furthermore, Dimyadi & Amor [7] state that BPMN and DMN are promising approaches for the representation of guideline content. Especially since these notations are already used by the AEC industry as Information Delivery Manuals (IDMs).

DMN defines only four graphical elements with three linking categories, as shown in Figure 1. The decision element represents the determination of an output value using multiple input values. The logic for this determination is defined in one or more knowledge models, consisting of decision tables or analytical models. Finally, the knowledge source represents an authority (a domain expert or source document) for the decisions [5].

This leads to the following research question: *Can the DMN standard be used as a visual interface for creating machine-processable specifications?* By providing a graphical representation of the constraint definition process using a standardised notation, stakeholders can understand how compliance checking rules are derived and interconnected.

Fig. 1: Elements of the DMN notation

Methods for compliance checking

As there are many approaches to the creation of machine-processable constraints, a comparative analysis of these approaches was conducted. Eight of the most common approaches were compared using a categorisation of constraint types: information availability, value, relational, mathematical and conditional constraints. This categorisation does not include performance-based constraints and therefore focuses only on prescriptive constraints. As shown in Figure 2, of the approaches investigated, only the XML Schema Definition Language (XSD) [8], Semantic Web Rule Language (SWRL) [9], SPARQL Protocol and RDF Query Language (SPARQL) [10] and Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL) [11] were able to model all five types of constraints [12].

	information availability	value	relational	mathematical	conditional
SMC	●	●	●	●	●
IDS	●	●	●	○	○
XSD	●	●	●	●	●
JSON schema	●	●	●	○	●
OWL (+SPARQL)	●	●	●	○	●
SWRL (+SPARQL)	●	●	●	●	●
SPARQL	●	●	●	●	●
SHACL	●	●	●	●	●

Fig. 2: Conclusion of a comparative analysis of compliance checking approaches [12]

While it would be beneficial to create a visual interface for all four approaches, this abstract will focus on one approach. SHACL is chosen because it is the only approach that defines a standardised validation report. Furthermore, unlike SWRL and SPARQL, it allows the definition of constraints based on negation-as-failure (NAF). In the context of compliance checking, this is valuable for determining whether a particular constraint is not satisfied due to missing information.

There is also existing research on the (automated) creation of SHACL shapes, e.g. Šenkýř [13] investigated the automation of text to SHACL shapes. However, to achieve the best results, the text should be tailored to patterns based on the strengths of SHACL. To reduce the various degrees of freedom that written text allows, a DMN representation can act as a standardization of these complex sentence patterns. Furthermore, Duan et al. [14] investigated the mapping of

XSD to SHACL. However, this research is more useful for domains that already define constraints in XSD and want to transition to Semantic Web technologies, whereas building guideline content is not widely available in XSD.

Mapping DMN to SHACL

As an example of the mapping procedure from DMN to SHACL, the stair formula as defined in Art. 20 §3 of the Flemish regulation on accessibility is examined. This article states that “the sum of twice the riser and once the tread of each step must be between 57 and 63 cm”. An indication of the riser height and the tread length is given in Figure 3. These properties are described in a Resource Description Graph (RDF) [15], which is a standardized method for publishing structured data (also known as Linked Data) on the Web, to create interlinked datasets. It aims to facilitate the seamless integration and discovery of data from different sources, enabling machines to navigate and understand the web of data [16].

Fig. 3: Indication of the tread and riser of a stair

The SHACL shapes defining the mathematical definition and the evaluation constraint are shown in Figure 4, as proposed in [17].

Figure 5 shows the mapping of the graphical DMN standard to the textual SHACL shapes. A DMN knowledge source is mapped to the target class of a shape, which leads to the input data required to check the constraint. This is defined by a path in SHACL. The next step in the DMN is a node with a decision table, of which the table is indicated by two dotted lines in the figure. The mapping of decision tables depends on the return type of the table. If the table returns a number, a mathematical formula is created and mapped to a SHACL-SPARQL function. However, if the table returns a Boolean, the table is mapped to a value constraint. Since SHACL only reports elements that do not satisfy the constraint, shapes are only created with a boolean return type of false.

The same workflow can be used for information availability and relational constraints. The conditional types of constraints are implemented by default in the DMN notation, as each decision table has the structure of 'when [input] then [output]'. For more complex DMN graphs, the 'required decision' tag should be handled. This can be used to check whether all required previous decisions have already been made, which may lead to multiple iterations to complete the graph. Future research will focus on the mapping of more complex constraints and investigating the feasibility of modelling performance-based constraints in both DMN and SHACL. It would furthermore be beneficial to test the creation of DMN constraints with the envisioned userbase, architects and building regulation authors, who have no previous knowledge of DMN or computer programming.

```

@prefix beo: <https://pi.pauwel.be/voc/buildingelement#> .
@prefix ex: <https://example.org#> .
@prefix props: <https://w3id.org/props#> .
@prefix schema: <https://schema.org/> .
@prefix sh: <https://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#> .
@prefix xsd: <https://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> .

ex:stairFormula
a sh:SPARQLFunction ; #define a function
sh:parameter [ #declare the first parameter
  sh:path ex:riser ; #first parameter is the riser height
  sh:datatype xsd:double ; #the riser is a decimal
] ;
sh:parameter [ #declare the second parameter
  sh:path ex:tread ; #second parameter is the tread length
  sh:datatype xsd:double ; #the tread is a decimal
] ;
sh:returnType xsd:double ; #the returned value is a decimal
sh:select """ #start a SPARQL select query
  SELECT ((2 * $riser + $tread) AS ?result)
  WHERE {
  }
  """ .

ex:stairSlope
a sh:NodeShape ; #apply the shape to a focus node
sh:targetClass beo:StairFlight ; #target all nodes with class 'StairFlight'
sh:expression [
  ex:lessThan ( #the self-defined lessThan(a,b) will return True if a < b
    570 #first parameter (a)
    [ #second parameter (b)
      ex:stairFormula ( #refer to the stairFormula(riser, tread) function
        [sh:path (props:riserHeightIfcStairFlight schema:value)]
        [sh:path (props:treadLengthIfcStairFlight schema:value)]
      )
    ]
  )
] .
    
```

Fig. 4: SHACL shapes for mathematical and value constraints as proposed in [17]

Fig. 5: Mapping between the graphical DMN notation and SHACL

Conclusion and limitations

We investigated the feasibility of using the DMN standard as a graphical interface for creating SHACL shapes that constrain building data. The use of the standard is most beneficial for domain experts without programming knowledge when modelling complex decision trees. In addition, current trends in the digitisation of building permits aim to create federated information ecosystems based on Linked Data technology, widening the technological knowledge gap with domain experts. Our research aims to mitigate this development. However, some limitations of the current research are the manual mapping of DMN to SHACL, rather than an automated link. Further research is needed to assess whether DMN and SHACL can handle performance-based rules.

References

[1] P.P. Ray, A Survey on Visual Programming Languages in Internet of Things, Sci. Program. 2017 (2017) 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2017/1231430>.

[2] C. Preidel, A. Borrmann, Towards code compliance checking on the basis of a visual programming language, J. Inf. Technol. Constr. (2016) 402–421.

[3] M. Senthilvel, J. Beetz, A Visual Programming Approach for Validating Linked Building Data, in: EG-ICE 2020 Workshop Intell. Comput. Eng., Berlin, Germany, 2020: pp. 403–411.

[4] Business Process Model and Notation (BPMN), (2011).

[5] Decision Model and Notation (DMN), (2023).

[6] M. Häußler, S. Esser, A. Borrmann, Code compliance checking of railway designs by integrating BIM, BPMN and DMN, Autom. Constr. 121 (2021) 103427. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103427>.

[7] J. Dimyadi, R. Amor, Regulatory knowledge representation for automated compliance audit of BIM-based models, in: 30th Int. Conf. Appl. IT AEC, Beijing, China, 2013: pp. 68–78.

- [8] W3C, XML Schema Definition Language (XSD) 1.1 Part 1: Structures, (2012). <https://www.w3.org/TR/xmlschema11-1/> (accessed July 4, 2023).
- [9] W3C, SWRL: A Semantic Web Rule Language Combining OWL and RuleML, W3C (2004). <https://www.w3.org/Submission/SWRL/> (accessed April 19, 2023).
- [10] W3C, SPARQL Query Language for RDF, W3C (n.d.). <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf-sparql-query/> (accessed February 19, 2023).
- [11] W3C, Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL), W3C (2017). <https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/> (accessed February 19, 2023).
- [12] E. Nuyts, M. Bonduel, R. Verstraeten, Comparative analysis of approaches for automated compliance checking of construction data, *Adv. Eng. Inform.* 60 (2024) 102443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aei.2024.102443>.
- [13] D. Šenkýř, SHACL Shapes Generation from Textual Documents, in: R. Pergl, E. Babkin, R. Lock, P. Malyzhenkov, V. Merunka (Eds.), *Enterp. Organ. Model. Simul.*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2019: pp. 121–130. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-35646-0_9.
- [14] X. Duan, D. Chaves-Fraga, A. Dimou, XSD2SHACL: Capturing RDF Constraints from XML Schema, in: *Proc. 12th Knowl. Capture Conf. 2023*, ACM, Pensacola FL USA, 2023: pp. 214–222. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3587259.3627565>.
- [15] W3C, RDF 1.1 Concepts and Abstract Syntax, (2014). <https://www.w3.org/TR/rdf11-concepts/> (accessed August 29, 2023).
- [16] A. Hogan, *The Web of Data*, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2020.
- [17] E. Nuyts, J. Werbrouck, R. Verstraeten, L. Deprez, Validation of building models against legislation using SHACL, in: *Matera, Italy, 2023*: pp. 164–175.

[Building Standards Compliance for SMEs: A Case study of Scotland](#)

Michael Tong^a, Billy Hare^a

^a *Department of Construction & Surveying, Glasgow Caledonian University, Cowcaddens Road, Glasgow, G4 0BA*

Introduction

The Scottish Government is committed to the digital transformation of the building standards system through its Building Standards Futures Board. Through the investment of a programme of research to capture and used to inform and develop opportunities for the digital transformation of parts of the building standards system that fall outwith the scope of the Digital Planning Programme. This research will also inform the development of interoperability to improve the value of data within the building standards system.

Background

The Building Standards Division (BSD) within the Scottish Government are responsible for creating the building standards legislation and guidance to ensure that buildings are safe, energy efficient and sustainable. An eBuilding standards national portal was introduced in 2016[1]. The portal enables the electronic submission of applications for building warrants and other forms, such as completion certificates, start of works notices and notifications of completion of work stages. While hugely successful in terms of the numbers of initial applications for building warrants and resubmitted plans being submitted through the portal for example, there is considerably less use of the portal when the post approval forms are concerned. As standards and guidance have evolved, there is now more documentary evidence of compliance required to be in place, for local authority verifiers to consider when assessing the competence of a completion certificate submission. These documentary requirements, such as air tightness test certificates, sound testing results, energy performance certificates etc. have considerably added to the information attached as files to a completion certificate submission, submitted through the eBuildingStandards portal. It is also most common that this documentary evidence is not submitted piecemeal, but rather collected and bundled up as a body of evidence at completion stage, regardless of what stage of construction the evidence was produced. This submission of large pieces of data at completion stage, and the requirement for it to be reviewed by the local authority before acceptance, in addition to undertaking site inspection, creates a bottle neck at completion stage, precisely when expectations for clients are set high that they will gain access to their completed project imminently after submission.

In 2012 local authorities began issuing Construction Compliance Notification Plans (CCNP) with building warrant approvals. These plans set out what the minimum interventions the local authority building standards teams consider appropriate for them to consider the eventual submission of a completion certificate. These interventions can be inspections, but can also be alternative evidence, such as certification, photographs etc. The CCNP also sets out expected periods of notification where inspections are requested, so that the local authority can manage their resources effectively, as well as contact details for the case surveyor. The responsible person (in most cases the building owner) has a legislative responsibility to ensure the works comply with the approved warrant. They may appoint others to act on their behalf but the responsibility to ensure compliance remain with them. It is therefore for the owner, perhaps through agency with their contractor or professional advice, to assure themselves that their

project complies with all requirements of the building regulations. Experience has shown that when this assurance is collated into a body of evidence, it provides rich data for the building owner, which can be used for a variety of reasons, not least to provide further assurance to the building standards verifier. It is also true that awareness of the CCNP process amongst building owners and contractors is low, especially for small to medium sized projects in Scotland.

Research Aim

The aim of this research is to demonstrate that digital tools and technologies can be sustainably used by construction SMEs, in evidencing compliance with the requirements of the Building (Scotland) Act 2004[2], associated legislation and guidance. The digitalisation of construction SMEs is quite significant not only for improving the efficiency in their day-to-day operations but also for enhancing collaboration and integrated information sharing across the construction supply chain. Identifying and prioritising the digitalisation needs of individual construction SMEs while considering the diversity in their operational practices is an under represented area of focus. Efforts made in this research to demonstrate and provide guidance on adopting digital tools for evidencing compliance could promote increased digitalisation usage to exploit benefits, overcome challenges and encourage an improved quality mindset.

Methods

The research aim can be sub-divided into three research questions:

Question 1: what are the advantages and challenges of digital tools and technologies for Construction SMEs?

Question 2: what processes and solutions need to be considered for the effective adoption of such digital tools and technologies?

Question 3: what digital solutions are available for evidencing compliance and how can we influence Construction SMEs to use them?

The methods used to answer these questions were qualitative, in order to explore this complex and under researched area. These consisted of a technical and peer-reviewed literature review, one-to-one interviews with participants of software trials to gain insights, lived experiences and perceptions of the issues raised in the previous exploratory work.

Main findings

There will be a need to facilitate SMEs to develop customised Digital Transformation Strategies that takes into consideration both internal and external intelligence to identify drivers and opportunities using available templates. There will also be a need to enable SMEs to determine relevant digital processes that aligns with their digital transformation strategy.

Facilitate in the identification of digital solution areas and exploit specific types of software that will help expedite digital maturity for individual SMEs.

Create an environment that will enable SMEs to transform into a digital company culture by promoting the four primary principles of: the right mindset; the right toolset; the right behaviour and the right feedback loops.

References

- [1] Scottish Government: *Building standards collection*. <https://www.gov.scot/collections/building-standards/>
- [2] Legislation.gov.uk – The Building (Scotland) Regulations 2004. <https://www.legislation.gov.uk/ssi/2004/406/contents/made>

Transformer-based Semantic Parsing of Building Regulations: Towards Supporting Regulators in Drafting Machine-Readable Rules

Stefan Fuchs^a, Johannes Dimyadi^{a,b}, Michael Witbrock^a, Robert Amor^a

^a School of Computer Science, The University of Auckland, New Zealand

^b CAS (Codify Asset Solutions Limited), Auckland, New Zealand

Introduction

Eastman et al. [1] conceptualised Automated Compliance Checking (ACC) of building design as a four-step process:

- 1) Building regulations must be converted into a formal, machine-readable representation.
- 2) The building design information needs to be retrieved and prepared for compliance checking. This includes the derivation of new concepts.
- 3) In the reasoning stage, the building design information is evaluated against legal requirements. This assessment includes spatial reasoning, existential checks, and quantitative evaluations.
- 4) Compliance checking results need to be reported to the user, including all non-compliant building elements and the requirements they do not meet.

This research focused on the translation of legal requirements into a formal representation. In current practice, the legal requirements were frequently hard-coded into software tools or specified in vendor-specific formats and limited to quantitative requirements [2]. As an alternative, open standards were proposed for representing entire legal documents in a machine-readable format, facilitating ACC [3]. However, translating building regulations into such a formal representation is a time-intensive and complex task that necessitates specialised knowledge [4]. The advancements in Natural Language Processing (NLP) over the past decade offer promising potential to reduce the time experts need to spend on this task by automating parts of the translation process [5,6].

Research questions

This synthesis provides an overview of the findings from four years of research focusing on the following research questions and draws implications for researchers and practitioners.

- ◆ RQ1: How can NLP be used to translate building regulations into a formal representation automatically?
- ◆ RQ2: How can NLP methods be made scalable to the variety of building regulations?
- ◆ RQ3: How can the quality of a formal representation of building regulations be ensured while keeping the formalisation effort to a minimum?

Methodology

Figure 1 presents an overview of the conducted studies. Additional details and references to the publications covering these aspects are provided below.

Fig. 1: Methodology overview.

A systematic literature review was carried out to determine the common practice on how NLP is used to interpret building regulations, and the ongoing gaps in research were identified [7].

A series of experimental studies were conducted to investigate the potential of pre-trained transformer models to formalise building regulations. This approach treated the formalisation of building regulations as an end-to-end semantic parsing task. This entails inputting an entire regulatory clause into a transformer model as the source text. The model then autoregressively generates the corresponding formal representation shown in Figure 2. During those studies, transformer models with different architectures, sizes, pre-training objectives, and data mixtures were evaluated. Synthetic training data was explored to improve the semantic parsing performance [8]. Furthermore, the impact of the consistency of the training data was investigated by applying a range of data-cleansing steps [9]. The task was simplified by reducing syntactic boilerplate and performing hierarchical semantic parsing [10]. Finally, the capability of large language models to formalise building regulations with only a few exemplars was evaluated [11].

Fig. 2: Source-target structure for the end-to-end semantic parsing task.

A proof-of-concept was developed to show that transformer models can not only be used to fully automate the translation of building regulations into formal representations but also to support regulators in an efficient semi-automated translation process. Therefore, transformer-based autocompletion was integrated into a new user interface for translating and editing LegalRuleML rules [12].

Answer to the research questions

The following sections answer the research questions based on the studies that were conducted.

RQ1: How can NLP be used to translate building regulations into a formal representation automatically?

NLP can help with the interpretation of building regulations in many regards. The most important tasks were parsing legal documents, classifying legal clauses, extracting information, transforming the extracted information into formal representations, and aligning the regulation concepts with the building concepts. Several gaps in the current literature were identified, such as the scalability and performance of existing information extraction and transformation approaches, the scarcity of available datasets, the isolated treatment of regulatory clauses, and the quality assurance strategies [7]. Scalability refers to the ability to handle diverse complexities, topics, and types of requirements, while performance focuses on the closeness to the ground truth.

Therefore, several studies [8,9,10,11] were conducted, where building regulations were translated into a formal representation via multi-task pre-trained generative neural networks as a general and scalable solution compared to existing information extraction and transformation approaches.

RQ2: How can NLP methods be made scalable to the variety of building regulations?

Treating the formalisation of building regulations as an end-to-end semantic parsing task allows the use of existing formalised building regulations as training data, which avoids the need to create datasets with the sole purpose of training a machine learning model and enables continuous improvements of the machine learning model with newly formalised building regulations [8].

Through the use of neural networks, continuously improving the semantic parser becomes more feasible in practice. It avoids the need for hand-crafting rules or feature engineering since the models learn the important features and semantic parsing rules from the data alone.

Choosing the transformer architecture added to the scalability of the semantic parsing approach since the training of transformer models can be strongly parallelised, allowing one to pre-train them with enormous amounts of general domain text data (or other modalities) and various tasks. This pre-training provides the model with a broad understanding of language and related tasks, which allows the model to be refined with less training data [8,11].

A formal representation of the New Zealand Building Code in LegalRuleML [13] was developed into a semantic parsing dataset, combining information extraction, transformation and, partially, alignment [8]. It covers ten different topics, constitutive and prescriptive statements, various lengths and complexities, enumerations, and clauses with multiple sentences. This variety increases the semantic parsing complexity significantly and requires a scalable solution.

The semantic parsing performance strongly depended on the consistency of the training data and the complexity of the representation format. Improvements were achieved by pre-training on a greater variety of tasks [8], increasing the formalisation consistency [9], simplifying the representation format [10], and adding hierarchical parsing steps [10]. Using larger models pre-trained on even more data boosted the performance further and could give freedom regarding the choice of representation formats since only a few exemplars are enough to teach the language model the semantic parsing task [11].

RQ3: How can the quality of a formal representation of building regulations be ensured while keeping the formalisation effort to a minimum?

Neither manual, rule-based, nor ML-based formalisation of building regulations is perfect. To maximise trust and minimise the translation effort, we propose a semi-automated process that could increase consistency and decrease effort by using transformer models. Keeping humans in the loop to review formal representations and make necessary amendments ensures correctness and trustworthiness.

To demonstrate the feasibility of this semi-automated method, we developed a LegalRuleML editor that integrates a neural network capable of generating complete translations of clauses and providing context-dependent autocompletion options. Starting with a comprehensive translation and refining the translation using the autocompletion feature facilitates an efficient workflow [12].

Discussion and conclusion

This line of research contributed to the body of knowledge by advancing ACC through a method for establishing a correct and trustworthy formal representation of building regulation. Multi-task pre-trained generative neural networks present a general, well-performing, and scalable solution to this complex semantic parsing task. In future work, we plan to expand the semantic parsing approach to a formal representation, which is fully aligned with the building design information (e.g., Industry Foundation Classes (IFC)) and, accordingly, directly executable for ACC.

Furthermore, the transformer-based end-to-end semantic parsing paradigm to support the formalisation of building regulations could make it more feasible to establish and maintain a certified formal representation of building regulations. We envision tools such as the LegalRuleML editor to be used by regulators and domain experts to formalise existing regulations and draft new regulations as human and machine-readable rules in parallel. Therefore, an ongoing study evaluates the regulators' perceptions of formal representations and parallel drafting.

References

- [1] C. Eastman, J. M. Lee, Y. S. Jeong, J. K. Lee: Automatic rule-based checking of building designs, *Automation in construction*, 18(8) (2009) 1011-1033.
- [2] C. Preidel, A. Borrmann: BIM-based code compliance checking, *Building information modeling: Technology foundations and industry practice* (2018) 367-381.
- [3] J. Dimyadi, G. Governatori, R. Amor: Evaluating LegalDocML and LegalRuleML as a Standard for Sharing Normative Information in the AEC/FM Domain, *Joint Conference on Computing in Construction (JC3)*, (2017) 637-644.
- [4] W. Solihin, C. Eastman: Classification of rules for automated BIM rule checking development, *Automation in construction*, 53 (2015) 69-82.
- [5] P. Zhou, N. El-Gohary: Ontology-based automated information extraction from building energy conservation codes, *Automation in Construction*, 74 (2017).
- [6] R. Zhang, N. El-Gohary: Hierarchical representation and deep learning-based method for automatically transforming textual building codes into semantic computable requirements, *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, 36(5) (2022) 04022022.
- [7] S. Fuchs, R. Amor: Natural language processing for building code interpretation: A systematic literature review, *CIB W78* (2021) 11-15.
- [8] S. Fuchs, M. Witbrock, J. Dimyadi, R. Amor: Neural semantic parsing of building regulations for compliance checking, *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 1101 (2022).

- [9] S. Fuchs, J. Dimyadi, M. Witbrock, R. Amor: Training on digitized building regulations for automated rule extraction, In eWork and eBusiness in Architecture, Engineering and Construction: ECPPM 2022, CRC Press (2023).
- [10] S. Fuchs, J. Dimyadi, M. Witbrock, R. Amor: Improving the semantic parsing of building regulations through intermediate representations, EG-ICE 2023 Workshop on Intelligent Computing in Engineering, Proceedings (2023).
- [11] S. Fuchs, M. Witbrock, J. Dimyadi, R. Amor: Using large language models for the interpretation of building regulations, 13th International Conference on Engineering, Project, and Production Management (EPPM2023) (2023).
- [12] S. Fuchs, J. Dimyadi, A. S. Ronee, R. Gupta, M. Witbrock, R. Amor: A LegalRuleML editor with transformer-based autocompletion, EC3 Conference 2023, European Council on Computing in Construction, 4 (2023) 0-0.
- [13] J. Dimyadi, S. Fernando, K. Davies, R. Amor: Computerising the New Zealand building code for automated compliance audit, New Zealand Built Environment Research Symposium (2020).

The IDS as a means of exchanging information requirements in public administrations: the use case of the digital building permit

Giancarlo de Marco^a, Cinzia Slongo^a, Dietmar Siegele^a and Dominik Matt^{a,b}

^a Fraunhofer Italia Research, Via Alessandro Volta 13A, 39100 Bolzano (BZ)

^b Faculty of Science and Technology, Free University of Bolzano, Via Antonio Rosmini 9, 39100 Bolzano (BZ)

General statement

A paradigm shift has taken place in the Architecture, Engineering, and Construction (AEC) sector as a result of the digitalized opportunities offered by Building Information Modelling (BIM). Our research focuses on the potential of the Information Delivery Specification (IDS) as a useful tool for the exchange and validation of Information Requirements (IR), which are one of the most significant factors contributing to the challenge of providing consistent information throughout the lifecycle of an asset. Specifically, the PRiORity case study will present the knowledge gained from working with a Public Authority through some pilot projects. Specifically, it explored an efficient way of structuring IR to facilitate verification of Digital Building Permits (DBP), and their validation through IDS. Finally, a comparison of different workflows based on open tools is presented in order to gain an understanding of the current limitations and identify possible lessons to be learnt from the current state of IDS, in order to improve its future implementation.

Introduction

The research on DBP is evolving and spreading. The central role of PA in promoting BIM practices as a driving force for change is acknowledged. Critical Success Factors (CSFs) have been developed as a possible metric to evaluate the success of BIM implementation in several countries, such as USA, UK, South Korea and Brazil, providing clarity regarding administrative aspects to the public sector [1,2]. Specifically, according to Shahi et al., DBP can evolve from a traditional and paper based process to an automatic, digital, BIM and GIS integrated process [3]. This means that manual checks have to be performed digitally. At the approval phase, adequate Automated Compliance Checking (ACC) has become necessary. Currently, national and municipality specific requirements are expected to be met and checked with tools created for a general and international market [4]. To achieve specific checks, other ways have to be found. Through efficient methods of organising data and querying [5–8], different rules structures for their verification can be drafted [9,10]. These findings can be used to leverage the forthcoming buildingSMART standard, Information Delivery Specification (IDS) as an open tool performing local compliant checks.

Clear and well-structured information transfer is crucial to the success of the construction industry at all stages, in particular for the DBP. Various methods for requesting IR are available [11]. The importance of clear, well-structured and formatted IR is rooted in the necessity for consistent, reliable and uniform quality monitoring [12], encompassing both quality assurance and quality control [13]. This study focuses on using IDS as an open tool for DBP checking. Currently, there are not commercial or academic applications beside creating and checking IDS. It is possible to demonstrate how to verify the presence of information requirements within the IFC model using open-source tools.

The role of Information Delivery Specification (IDS) in BIM for Public Authorities

The Information Delivery Specification (IDS) is a new bSI standard. It consists of an XML file with the extension *.ids. Its nature is dual in that it is intended to be read both by humans and by computers. The IDS has two main parts: a description and specification. The description is designed for human to read and contains, among other things, the title, purpose, and version. The specifications are split into Applicability and Requirements. The rules have a name, a description, an instruction and specifies the IFC version. Applicability serves to filter and clarify to which IFC element the Requirements apply, i.e., the information that is searched. Both the Applicability and the Requirements can be populated with conditions specified by six facets [14]. See Figure 1.

Fig. 1 Structure of the Information Delivery Specification

IDS enters the openBIM workflow between the PA and the designer, see Figure 2. Three roles can be identified, respectively: the creator, the modeller(s) and the validator. The creator and the validator belong to the PA group while the modeller belongs to the designer group. The creator generates the IR in the form of an *.ids and sends it to the modeller(s) so that they can create the model based on the requirements. The model can be enriched using the buildingSMART Data Dictionary (bSDD) service. Through the BIM Collaboration Format (BCF) issues that may arise can be resolved. Once the model is ready to be shared, it is transferred to the PA where the validator verifies that the produced work meets the requirements [15]. Finally, the PA issues the DBP.

Methodology

Due to a broader assembly of entities only the latest schema, IFC 4x3, has been considered providing an effective and reliable data structure to base IDS on for public projects. Firstly, IR have been identified from the previously available resources used in PRiORity project and have been tested. Based on the results of these tests, we developed a similar structure better aligning with the IFC 4x3 schema. The new structure was designed to facilitate the expression of IDS itself and enable potential expansion by relying entirely on the IFC schema, see Figure 3. Two main tests were carried out, to represent potential professional workflows. The first test required writing the IDS from scratch, while the second test focused on automated generation using the existing data structure. Both tests were developed using open and non-proprietary applications to promote an open approach. It is important to mention that not all the solutions found were free, and therefore, not all market options were explored. Two methods were used to verify the IR within blenderBIM. The first method consisted into writing IDS using the usBIM.IDSeditor [16]

application and using the models developed for the PRiORity project to verify the IR within blenderBIM. The second method used IDS converter [17] to automate the production an analogous *.ids file. It emerged that the former method is more usable and flexible than the latter. IDS converter implied that a fixed and rigid excel template should be used to create the IDS. Any changes made to the template would require manual correction of each referenced cell, thus resulting in an error-prone workflow.

Fig. 2: openBIM workflow for DBP, including IDS

		CLASSIFICATION 7.4.2; 7.5.2; 7.5.3; 7.6.3; 7.9.1; 7.9.2; 9.3.1	1.2.2	
Adopted schema: IFC4x3 (IFC4.3_ADD2)		IFC ENTITY IfcAudioVisualAppliance 'AMPLIFIER; CAMERA; COMMUNICATIONTERMINAL; DISPLAY; MICROPHONE; PLAYER; PROJECTOR; RECEIVER; RECORDINGEQUIPMENT; SPEAKER; SWITCHER; TELEPHONE; TUNER	IfcBeam BEAM; JOIST; HOLLOWCORE; LINTEL; SPANDREL; T_BEAM	
Property Set	Property Name	Type of parameter		
Identifizierung_Identificazione	Technologische Einheiten_U	IfcLabel	1	1
Pset_BeamCommon	Name	IfcIdentifier		1
Pset_BeamCommon	IsExternal	IfcBoolean		1
Pset_BeamCommon	LoadBearing	IfcBoolean		1
Pset_BeamCommon	FireRating	IfcLabel		1
Pset_BeamCommon	Status	IfcLabel		1

Fig. 3: Proposed data structure for IDS

Results and promising developments in IDS implementation for Public Authorities

The results of this study showed that some expected requirements are difficult to express in a machine-readable format but, if achieved, allow to reduce the workload ensuring quality in the DBP validation process. When dealing with facets and by leveraging the data structure, simple or complex restrictions as well as different levels of cogency can be required. The use of the Entity facet in the Applicability layer, thus relying on the IFC scheme, proved to lead to a faster and more manageable result. However, although checks of geometry, calculated values or dynamic values

are outside the scope of IDS, certain geometric conditions can be evaluated if required appropriately. Attribute or Property Facets may address this issue by requesting geometry information derived from the model and not investigating conditions in relation to other objects.

Figure 4 Information Requirement for DBP

Checking the minimum requirements for DBP may include, for example, verifying that certain `IfcSanitaryTerminal` have a minimum drainage outlet or that a single room should have a minimum gross area of 9 square meters, see Figure 4 for requirements and see Figure 5 for results.

Figure 5 Results of IDS test

Despite the inherent challenges, the construction industry has made promising progress in implementing IDS, thus pairing the development for its uses. Other applications beyond DBP are foreseen, for instance IDS can be applied to other phases of the construction process, like the construction, or the management phase. Developers are currently working on reliable tools to automate the import of IDS., Therefore, it is expected that PAs will make efforts to properly structure their IR to be ready to adopt IDS as soon as it is fully released. This will enable them to check requirements automatically based on open standards.

Conclusion

IDS stands out as a promising tool for requiring information for the DBP release. Currently, tested tools have limitations in visualizing non-compliant objects. However, the improved ability to describe, request and verify the IR contained in a template file will greatly facilitate PA activities. In fact, on the transmission side, PAs will allow designers to create models using their own authoring software based on shared IR template(s), ready to contain information. The PA's subsequent verification will allow a simplification of the technical formalities required for the release of the DBP. For example, it will be easy to verify that the submitted models comply with the respective urban planning regulations, as well as with national minimum standards. The findings of this study are relevant to the Public Authorities involved in the PRiORity project and for any Appointing Party as it is possible to perform semantic checks on IFC models based on openBIM practices and using opensource tools. This paper helps fill the gap for public authorities in understanding what can be expected from BIM and what can be required. The results highlight the need for further research for clearer expression of IR, alternatively the population of data structure to promote standardised municipality and national requirements.

Acknowledgement

This research study is part of the PRiORity project. The PRiORity has been financed by the Autonomous Province of Bolzano, CUP: F53C21000140003.

References

- [1] D.M. de Brito, E. de A.M. Ferreira, D.B. Costa, Framework for Building Information Modeling Adoption Based on Critical Success Factors from Brazilian Public Organizations, *J. Constr. Eng. Manag.* 147 (2021) 05021004. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)CO.1943-7862.0002086](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)CO.1943-7862.0002086).
- [2] M.F. Antwi-Afari, H. Li, E.A. Pärn, D.J. Edwards, Critical success factors for implementing building information modelling (BIM): A longitudinal review, *Autom. Constr.* 91 (2018) 100–110. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2018.03.010>.
- [3] K. Shahi, B.Y. McCabe, A. Shahi, Framework for Automated Model-Based e-Permitting System for Municipal Jurisdictions, *J. Manag. Eng.* 35 (2019) 04019025. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)ME.1943-5479.0000712](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)ME.1943-5479.0000712).
- [4] D. Greenwood, S. Lockley, S. Malsane, J. Matthews, Automated compliance checking using building information models, (n.d.).
- [5] W. Solihin, J. Dimyadi, Y.-C. Lee, C. Eastman, R. Amor, Simplified schema queries for supporting BIM-based rule-checking applications, *Autom. Constr.* 117 (2020) 103248. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.autcon.2020.103248>.
- [6] F. Noardo, D. Guler, J. Fauth, G. Malacarne, S. Mastrolembro Ventura, M. Azenha, P.-O. Olsson, L. Senger, Unveiling the actual progress of Digital Building Permit: Getting awareness through a critical state of the art review, *Build. Environ.* 213 (2022) 108854. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.108854>.
- [7] A.A. Siddiqui, J.A. Ewer, P.J. Lawrence, E.R. Galea, I.R. Frost, Building Information Modelling for performance-based Fire Safety Engineering analysis – A strategy for data sharing, *J. Build. Eng.* 42 (2021) 102794. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jobbe.2021.102794>.
- [8] T.P. McGinley, T. Vestergaard, C.-H. Jeong, F. Pind, An OpenBIM workflow to support collaboration between Acoustic Engineers and Architects, *J. Phys. Conf. Ser.* 2069 (2021) 012164. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/2069/1/012164>.
- [9] W. Solihin, C. Eastman, A knowledge representation approach in BIM rule requirement analysis using the conceptual graph, *ITcon* 21 (2016) 370–401.

- [10] E. Hjelseth, N. Nisbet, CAPTURING NORMATIVE CONSTRAINTS BY USE OF THE SEMANTIC MARK-UP RASE METHODOLOGY, (n.d.).
- [11] A. Tomczak, L.V. Berlo, T. Krijnen, A. Borrmann, M. Bolpagni, A review of methods to specify information requirements in digital construction projects, IOP Conf. Ser. Earth Environ. Sci. 1101 (2022) 092024. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1755-1315/1101/9/092024>.
- [12] S. Wang, J. Yu, BIM-based government engineering quality supervision system, J. Asian Archit. Build. Eng. 0 (2023) 1–14. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13467581.2023.2278890>.
- [13] C. Han, T. Han, T. Ma, Z. Tong, S. Wang, A BIM-based framework for road construction quality control and quality assurance, Int. J. Pavement Eng. 24 (2023) 2209903. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10298436.2023.2209903>.
- [14] Information Delivery Specification standard, (2023). <https://github.com/buildingSMART/IDS> (accessed November 29, 2023).
- [15] Masterclass - Information Delivery Specification (IDS), 2023. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SyWRjXT2K7k> (accessed November 29, 2023).
- [16] IDS BIM - Information Delivery Specification | usBIM.IDS | ACCA software, (n.d.). <https://www.acca.it/ids-bim-information-delivery-specification> (accessed November 20, 2023).
- [17] C. Dias, ids_converter, (2023). https://github.com/c4rlosdias/ids_converter (accessed November 20, 2023).

Concept for Leveraging Road Digital Twins for Enhanced Planning and Building Permit Processes

Judith Fauth^a, Ioannis Brilakis^a

^a *Department of Engineering, University of Cambridge, Cambridge, UK*

Introduction

In a world characterized by resource scarcity, particularly in terms of skilled labor and materials, the utilization of existing resources has become increasingly imperative. This necessity extends beyond traditional perspectives, encompassing sectors with a significant impact on society. In the dynamic field of urban development, decision-makers are captured by the complex interplay between roads, buildings, and neighborhoods. At the core of this evolving landscape is the emergence of road digital twins (RDT), exerting a transformative influence on the urban fabric. A compelling aspect of RDT development lies in its profound impact on planning and building permit (PBP) processes, introducing nuanced dimensions to decision-making dynamics. As RDTs seamlessly integrate into the urban context, they provide 3D city models with a rich interconnectedness that extends beyond the physical confines of roads and buildings. Within this paradigm, the role of RDTs in PBP processes becomes evident, providing a wealth of information poised to reshape decision-making at crucial junctures. The PBP process, when viewed through the lens of RDTs, assumes a catalytic role for acceleration, improvement, facilitation, and influence, impacting both PBP authorities and applicants alike. This article introduces a research concept aimed at harnessing the potential of RDTs to enhance PBP processes.

PBPs hold a pivotal role in the architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) industry, ensuring compliance with regulations concerning legality, safety, and sustainability. While there has been a growing interest in automated code compliance checking, there remains a need for more fundamental research to address diverse information requirements throughout the PBP process [1] [2]. PBP processes are predominantly manual and time-consuming, leading to significant delays in acquiring permits, with far-reaching implications for construction projects [3]. Digitalization offers potential solutions through the use of digital data and tools to streamline and automate PBP procedures [4]. Nevertheless, the complexity of PBP processes, entailing the involvement of multiple stakeholders from various sectors, including the public sector, presents a challenge that extends beyond the mere development of digital tools [5] [6].

Digital twins represent an up-to-date version of the physical and functional properties of a system [7]. While digital twins have shown significant promise in the digitalization of the AEC industry, there has been limited exploration of their potential in the context of PBP processes. A rare instance, highlighted by [8], suggested potential approaches for building authorities in the context of the building life cycle. Yet, to date, no research has addressed the efficiency of PBP processes through the integration of adjacent data sources, such as RDTs.

The main challenges in this endeavor revolve around the complexity and uncertainty inherent in the information, processes, and diverse stakeholders [9]. Here, RDTs offer a valuable repository of necessary information. The proposed research aims to bridge these areas, unlocking value for both sectors and establishing what makes the information from RDTs connectable, usable, and interpretable. Furthermore, as in neighboring domains, another challenge is the lack of essential data needed to advance the digitalization of PBP [10] [11].

The exploration of the nexus between RDTs and PBP processes gives rise to pivotal questions that emphasize the depth and significance of this intersection. The forthcoming concept aims to address the following questions and considerations.

Question block 1 (Q1): What specific use cases can be discerned for the seamless integration of RDTs into PBP processes? How do RDTs augment decision-making across various stages of the PBP process? What types of information are imperative for RDT-based PBP processes, and at what level of granularity must this information be presented to serve these use cases? To what extent does the quality and quantity of information influence decision-making in PBP processes?

Question block 2 (Q2): From a management perspective, what elements constitute a business model for RDT-based PBP in terms of processes, people, rules, and technology? How might the incorporation of RDTs optimize the efficiency and effectiveness of PBP procedures?

Question block 3 (Q3): Can RDT-based PBP processes contribute to heightened certainty in construction activities, and to what degree can RDTs mitigate risks associated with time and cost calculations in construction projects through PBPs?

These questions collectively form the foundation of an in-depth exploration into the transformative potential of RDTs in the domain of PBP processes, shedding light on the technical and managerial dimensions that characterize this evolving terrain.

The Research Concept

To overcome the lacking connection of RDTs and PBPs, a concept was developed to demonstrate the potential relationships, methods, and mid-term achievements to be addressed. The concept comprises four distinct steps as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig.1: Overview of the concept steps

Step 1 is dedicated to the identification and development of information packages (IPs). Despite the existence of RDTs, they are presently disconnected from parallel sectors like PBP. To derive value from RDTs for PBP, it is crucial to define the requisite IPs that link RDTs and PBP. Step 1 focusses on the IP definition and the respective data collection. The objectives of this step are to define the IPs and gather suitable data for analysis. This lays the foundation for the study and ensures scalability. On the other hand, Step 1 refers to the data analysis and aims to identify two types of information from RDTs: "what" information for PBP and "when and who" information for studying the process steps and stakeholder involvement. Possible examples of IPs include the assurance of site development, the accessibility of plot of land and utilities provision (water, sewage, disposal, etc.), the usage rights documentation, the justification of objections from neighbors and prevention of downstream legal actions, the participation of other involved agencies of public interest, and dynamic regulations (e.g., the saturation of mandatory charging stations for electro vehicles). Step 1 addresses Q1 and Q2.

Step 2 is concentrated on the knowledge management of the gathered information.

With valuable implicit and explicit knowledge collected from Step 1, a structured system (such as an ontology) is needed to organize this knowledge which also leads to defined rule sets and queries based on the IPs (e.g., ‘give me all information required for usage rights documentation’). A validation with different use case scenarios (e.g., new buildings, renovation, etc.) strengthen the adaptability and the robustness of the knowledge management system. Step 2 addresses Q1 and Q2.

Step 3 is concerned with an uncertainty analysis. Uncertainty is a significant challenge in PBP, impacting project time, cost, and decision-making. Therefore, step 3 seeks to investigate these uncertainties and build a decision model that is solid, robust, and objectified for decision-makers. Therefore, the analysis does not only consider ambiguity in the law in terms of regulations but involves organizational and procedural aspects as well. Step 3 addresses Q3.

In Step 4, a business case evaluation is considered as the final step. The knowledge and solutions gained through this research are expected to generate value to the industry. Step 4 focuses on developing business cases based on the knowledge acquired from Step 1, Step 2, and Step 3. These cases involve offerings like charging applicants for automated querying of required information for the building application to be submitted to the building permit authorities. For example, this approach might support the RDT maintainer to reinvest in the maintenance of the RDTs or physical twins. Step 4 addresses Q1, Q2, and Q3.

Discussion and conclusions

The proposed concept seeks to explore the relationship between PBP and RDTs throughout the buildings and road life cycle, ultimately influencing different stages of RDTs and beyond. The potential to increase certainty in construction and reduce time delays holds significant implications for both research and practice. The research findings are expected to facilitate more accurate and transparent decision-making in PBP and enhance efficiency for stakeholders (such as PBP authorities, building control offices, applicants, RDT maintainers, and public agencies).

The social implications contribute to more transparent and efficient PBP processes. This, in turn, affects housing costs, housing demand, and the effective use of taxpayer funds. Additionally, it leads to reduced costs and timelines for construction projects, benefiting the society as a whole.

This concept is not without its limitations, as the use of RDTs may have restrictions in terms of the information they can provide. Different international perspectives may lead to disagreements. It is essential to note that this research focuses on building permits, not road or infrastructure permits. In addition, and depending on the data availability, there might be alternative data sets to identified to progress the steps.

In conclusion, this research endeavor offers a unique opportunity to bridge the gap between PBP and RDTs, potentially revolutionizing the efficiency and transparency of the PBP process. By connecting these two distinct domains, the research has the potential to offer innovative solutions breaking down domain-specific information silos and enhance decision-making in the AEC sector.

Acknowledgements

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 101034337.

References

- [1] F. Noardo, D. Guler, J. Fauth, G. Malacarne, S. Mastrolembo Ventura, M. Azenha, P.-O. Olsson, L. Senger: *Unveiling the actual progress of Digital Building Permit: Getting awareness through a critical state of the art review*, *Build. Environ.* 213 (2022) 108854. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.108854>.
- [2] J. Fauth: *A process-oriented decision model for determining the permitability of construction projects* [English translation of German dissertation] (2022) Weimar: Bauhaus-Universität
- [3] S. Malsane, J. Matthews, S. Lockley, P.E. Love, D. Greenwood: *Development of an object model for automated compliance checking*, *Automation in Construction*, 49, 51–58 (2015)
- [4] K. Ullah: *Readiness assessment for BIM-based building permits using multiple criteria analysis* [Dissertation] (2022) Tallinn: Tallinn University of Technology.
- [5] F. Noardo, C. Ellul, L. Harrie, I. Overland, M. Shariat, K.A. Ohori, J. Stoter: *Opportunities and challenges for GeoBIM in Europe: Developing a building permits use—Case to raise awareness and examine technical interoperability challenges*, *Journal of Spatial Science*, 65, 209–233 (2020).
- [6] E. Papadonikolaki, I. Krystallis, B. Morgan: *Digital transformation in construction-Systematic literature review of evolving concepts*, *Engineering Project Organization Conference (EPOC)* (2022).
- [7] R. Sacks, I. Brilakis, E. Pikas, H.S. Xie, M. Girolami: *Construction with digital twin information systems*, *Data-Centric Engineering*, 1 (2022).
- [8] A. Ammar, H. Nassereddine, N. AbdulBaky, A. AbouKansour, J. Tannoury, H. Urban, C. Schranz: *Digital twins in the construction industry: A perspective of practitioners and building authority*, *Frontiers in Built Environment*, 8 (2022).
- [9] F. Noardo, T. Wu, K. Arroyo Ohori, T. Krijnen, J. Stoter: *IFC models for semi-automating common planning checks for building permits*, *Automation in Construction*, 134 (2021) 104097.
- [10] A. Barbini, G. Malacarne, G. Massari, G. Pasetti Monizza, D.T. Matt: *BIM objects library for information exchange in public works: the use of proprietary and open formats* *WIT Transaction in Built Environment*, 192, 269–280 (2019).
- [11] P. Nørkjær Gade, D. Holmberg Lauritzen, M. Andersen, E. Hjelseth: *How practice is represented in BIM-based model checking research – A literature review and reflections*. In: Hjelseth, Sujan & Scherer (eds), *eWork and eBusiness in architecture, engineering and construction: ECPPM 2022*. London, UK, CRC Press (2022).

Definition of BIM and 3DCitymodel information requirements for digital building permits

Sara Comai^a, Silvia Mastrolembo Ventura^a, Francesca Noardo^b, Kavita Raj^a and Angelo Luigi Camillo Ciribini^a,

^a Dept. of Civil, Architectural, Environmental Engineering and Mathematics, University of Brescia, Brescia, Italy

^b Open Geospatial Consortium, Belgium

To start the construction phase of a building, it is necessary to have a building permit. This is a permit issued by the public authorities after careful verification that the project complies with the building regulations valid at both building and city level [1]. The development and linking of methods for issuing building permits, supported by digital tools, could improve the current manual procedures for processing regulatory information requirements and related compliance processes. With the increasing adoption of Building Information Models (BIM) in building design processes, several municipalities are investing in the semi-automation of these checks both by using BIM methods and tools, but also by increasingly integrating them with geographical datasets [2]. Research on the adoption of BIM and neutral building data schemes such as Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) aimed at verifying project compliance with building regulations is not recent. However, in recent years, research has been focusing on the integration of BIM and Geographic Information System (GIS) model data [3]. Furthermore, in order to be able to run a compliance check, it is necessary to prepare building information models and 3D city models according to the appropriate information requirements [4].

The interaction between BIM and GIS for the issuing of building permits is analysed in the CHEK project. CHEK project is a larger project that aims to remove barriers that, to date, prevent municipalities from adopting digital processes for building permits by developing, linking and aligning scalable solutions for the regulatory and policy environment, open standards and interoperability (geospatial and BIM).

The research described in this paper focused on the application of a methodology for the interpretation of the building regulations of municipalities belonging to the European Union with the aim of extracting the BIM and GeoBIM information requirements (entities, attributes and relationships) needed to apply for a building permit. An empirical approach was adopted for this research in order to obtain results as close as possible to the real needs of the municipalities. The research activities were carried out in close cooperation with four municipalities between 45.000 and 1.300.000 inhabitants (i.e., in ascending order of size, Municipality of Ascoli Piceno - Italy, Municipality of Vila Nova de Gaia - Portugal, Municipality of Lisbon - Portugal, Municipality of Prague - Czech Republic) in three European countries.

To this end, the five-step process for identifying the entities and attributes required to perform the conformity check is briefly described.

- Identification of relevant building permit checks: provision of a list of the most frequently performed checks, focusing on the checks carried out directly by municipalities, rather than by external checking authorities. The list was validated and approved by the municipalities themselves, who identified and provided the related regulatory articles accordingly;
- Interpretation of the rules: interpretation of the articles of the building and national regulations using the sentence-centred method and semantic mark-up RASE methodology [5;6] to define the Requirement, the Applicability, the Selection and Exception within the

regulatory articles. Subsequently, each element (Requirement, Applicability, Selection, Exception) was detailed to identify the data type (alphanumeric, numeric, boolean), the comparison operators (e.g., \leq , \geq , =), the value (e.g., float number, integer number, classification) to be compared and the unit of measurement (e.g., m, m², m³), if necessary [7]. The doubts that emerged from the analysis were resolved in dedicated meetings involving the municipalities.

- Definition of conceptual models: the analysis of the regulations in the previous step was preliminary to the identification of information requirements for the preparation of the building and city models. These requirements were then represented in the form of a conceptual model using the Unified Modelling Language (UML) [8].
- Validation: the conceptual models representing the identified information requirements were validated by experts, such as municipal officials and planners and regulatory bodies.
- Comparison of results: the conceptual models and information requirements of the municipalities were compared with each other to highlight any needs for flexibility and scalability of the results obtained.

The controls relevant to building permits that emerged from the analysis can be divided into 5 sections: (1) urban indices, (2) distances, (3) parking standards, (4) building space requirements for usability and, finally, (5) accessibility. The priority that emerged during the meetings with the municipalities relates to issues on the interaction between the building and its context. Therefore, the methodology was validated on the building indexes of the parcels and the maximum building height, two issues related to section (1), on distances (between existing building-building subject of the building permit; building and street; building and parcel boundary and balcony and parcel boundary), section (2) and finally on the minimum area of spaces and dwellings, related to section (3). 80 normative sentences were analysed as follows: 32 normative articles for Ascoli Piceno, 14 normative articles for Vila Nova de Gaia, 17 normative articles for Lisbon and, finally, 17 normative articles for Prague.

In the case of distance, 38 entities were identified, of which 21 related to the 3Dcitymodel and 17 related to the BIM model, objects necessary for verification. A total of 44 attributes were identified for 3Dcitymodel entities and 29 attributes for BIM model entities were identified. This attributes will need to be included in the information model and control rules. The attribute that characterises each entity is the ID code, an alphanumeric attribute that allows the entity to be uniquely identified. In addition to this, there are boolean attributes (e.g., 'is external' for walls), alphanumeric attributes derived from a code list (e.g., 'intended use' for spaces) and numeric attributes (e.g., 'height' for building).

The development of the CHEK list of regulations and the interpretation of the first sets of regulations were the first steps towards defining a methodology and framework for assessing the overall body of regulations of the municipalities according to the automation potential of the regulations (i.e., how automated the control of a regulation can be) and the preparation of the regulations for formalisation (i.e., how much information can be extracted from the regulations). By comparing the results obtained in four municipalities differing in location and size, it was possible to analyse the scalability of the approach, assessing similarities and differences, as well as proposing recommendations for the drafting of effective and unambiguous regulations. Although the municipalities work on different scales (number of inhabitants), the regulations are very similar, in fact, they regulate the same urban planning and building issues. The ambiguities that emerged relate both to the words chosen for writing the regulations and to the identification of construction elements, as they are not adequately detailed in the regulatory articles. An example of ambiguity for the municipality of Prague case, Annex 1 – Chapter 2 of building

regulations [9] “The spacing angle is fulfilled if no obstacle infringes upon the open space demarcated above a vertical angle of 45°”. The word “obstacle” means any object interfering with the building view, such as a wall, a column, a ground etc. However, it could be not obvious to understand it for someone who is external to the municipality practice. The interpretation process required significant input from civil servants to resolve ambiguities due to, for example, references to other legal texts, or tacit knowledge difficult to interpret by those who do not work with the process on a daily basis. Furthermore, it proved essential to interpret not only the selected normative phrases, but also the definitions contained in building regulations and other normative texts. All this was made even more complicated by the need to translate the regulatory references of the four municipalities from three European countries and thus three different languages into English, in order to be able to compare the results obtained, for an evaluation of the scalability of the method and the proposed solutions. The translation into English, although performed with European tools [10], resulted in errors and consequently incorrect analyses of the normative article, which was later resolved by discussion with municipal officials. The analysis of building regulations in the original language would avoid this problem, although in some cases the need for translation could force the definition of specific meanings for some of the terms used in the regulation.

In conclusion, the current results show how, despite the fascinating narrative of automated technical solutions, the obstacles to be faced and overcome involve understanding many multifaceted meanings. The work led to the identification of the entities and their attributes that must be present in the model submitted for the building permit. After a standardisation of the data in neutral formats, it will be possible to verify the compliance of the information model with the regulations. The research developed shows some limitations in terms of potential scalability of results, due to so high diversity, at this stage. The case studies are location- and regulation-specific, for example. However, the type of problems found is an example generally applicable to the whole building permit use case. To extend the analysis to a larger number of regulations among those indicated as relevant for the BP release, other types of controls be considered, for example the accessibility. This research shows the need for a comprehensive and systematic approach to the analysis of regulations to identify the actual level of information needs for the digital building permit use case. It also means understanding how a consolidated approach to the methodology that emerged from this research can be implemented in practice to enable each municipality to effectively define its own set of standards and related information requirements.

Acknowledgement

This project has received funding from the European Union under the Horizon Europe Research & Innovation Programme (grant agreement no. 101058559 CHEK). Views and opinions expressed are however those of author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

References

- [1] F. Noardo, D. Guler, J. Fauth, G. Malacarne, S. Mastrolemba Ventura, M. Azenha, P.-O. Olsson, L. Senger: *Unveiling the actual progress of Digital Building Permit: Getting awareness through a critical state of the art review*, Build. Environ. 213 (2022) 108854. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.108854>.
- [2] K. Otori, A. Diakite, T. Krijnen, H. Ledoux, J. Stoter: *Processing BIM and GIS models in practice: Experiences and recommendations from a GeoBIM project in the Netherlands*, ISPRS International Journal of GeoInformation (2018). <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijgi7080311>.
- [3] N. Hobeika, J. Van Liempt, F. Noardo, K. Arrow Otori, J. Stoter: *GeoBIM information to check digital*

- building permit regulations*. The International Archives of the Photogrammetry, Remote Sensing and Spatial Information Sciences, 43 (2022) 529-535. <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIII-B4-2022-529-2022>
- [4] S. Mastrolemba Ventura, S. Comai, F. Noardo, K. Raj, A.L.C. Ciribini: *Integrated geobim requirements definition for digital building permit*. In 23rd International Conference on Construction Applications of Virtual Reality (CONV23) Conference, 530-541 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.36253/979-12-215-0289-3.51>
- [5] E. Hjelseth, N. Nisbet: *Capturing normative constraints by use of the semantic mark-up RASE methodology*. In Proceedings of CIB W78-W102 Conference, 1-10 (2011). <https://itc.scix.net/pdfs/w78-2011-Paper-45.pdf>
- [6] N. Nisbet, L. Ma, G. Aksenova: *Presentations of rase knowledge mark-up*. In EC3 Conference (2022). https://ec-3.org/publications/conferences/EC32022/papers/EC32022_162.pdf
- [7] A. Tomczak, L. Berlo, T. Krijnen, A. Borrmann, M. Bolpagni: *A review of methods to specify information requirements in digital construction projects*. In IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science, 1101(9), 092024 (2022). IOP Publishing.
- [8] Object Management Group, 2023. <https://www.uml.org>. Last accessed: December 2023.
- [9] Pražské stavební předpisy 2018, Municipality of Prague. https://iprpraha.cz/uploads/assets/dokumenty/psp/psp_2018_web.pdf Last accessed: December 2023.
- [10] eTranslation, The European Commission's Machine Translation system. https://commission.europa.eu/resources-partners/etranslation_en, Last Access: December 2023.

Advancing Automated Compliance Checking Through Visual Programming in the Context of Australian Building Codes

Nikoo Mirhosseini^a, Davood Shojaei^a, Soheil Sabri^{a,b}

^a Centre for SDIs and Land Administration, Department of Infrastructure Engineering, The University of Melbourne, Victoria, Australia

^b Urban Digital Twin Lab, School of Modeling, Simulation, and Training, University of Central Florida, Florida, USA

In the architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC) industry, the management of building codes, regulations, and standards forms the bedrock of safety, structural rigidity, and environmental sustainability. Such a foundational influence, coupled with the increasing complexity and dynamic nature of regulations, poses critical challenges for professionals. In response, Automated Compliance Checking (ACC) systems have shown substantial promise in mitigating these obstacles by allowing an efficient, accurate, and streamlined means of validation and enforcement of these codes.

Lately, the integration of Visual Programming Languages (VPL) into ACC systems, by harnessing platforms such as DynamoRevit, has marked a major milestone in the evolution of compliance management (Wu et al., 2021). VPL's ability to streamline the creation of complex algorithms for professionals lacking traditional coding skills is transformative, elucidating a computational design mechanism previously confined to specialized programmers.

As such, this research aligns itself with the dynamic intersection of low-code now-code capability and ACC system, leveraging the DynamoRevit platform's capabilities. It specifically investigates the strict and nuanced energy regulations legislated by the Australian Building Codes (ABC) (Australian Building Codes Board, 2019).

Our innovative solution, a Dynamo-based Revit plugin, integrates Dynamo's graphic-oriented rule set development with a robust Big Data analytics and Artificial Intelligence (AI)-empowered decision-making layer. This combination permits non-specialists to visually manage the ACC process. It also establishes the capacity for precision-oriented compliance prediction and large-scale data analysis, ensuring the maintenance of building information modelling (BIM) data's rich detail.

Another key design principle of the Revit plugin underscores its scalability and adaptability to a constantly evolving set of industry standards and design provisions. Critical to the operational competency of the plugin was its integrated algorithms' capability to interpret, analyse, and handle geometrically complex 3D models, a feature instrumental to any effective BIM-centric compliance checks (Liu, et al., 2022).

Beyond this, the plugin embraces the universality of Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) standards, thereby aiding its ingestion and processing of geometric and semantic data from BIM models generated on various platforms. Complementary to this, the integration of custom scripts to parse XML or JSON formatted building code updates allows the plugin to maintain contemporaneity with the latest regulatory amendments.

Empirically validating our work, meticulously evaluated a case study in Victoria demonstrate the plugin's robust characteristics, highlighting its ability to navigate intricate compliance challenges and shed light on its potential as a significant addition to DynamoRevit's offerings.

Nonetheless, these advancements and their potential are not without their barriers. One of the most obstacles lies at the heart of managing the increasing intricacies presented by the evolving building regulations (Wu and Zhang, 2022). Our approach, however, lies in effectively tackling this by leveraging the dynamism of Dynamo's visual programming, its complex geographical information handling, advanced machine learning algorithms, and real-time feedback, all of which contribute to minimizing the incidence of errors and downscaling rework costs (Greenberg & Khan, 2021).

The combination of these technologies and methodologies in the ACC system counteracts the current limitations of compliance checking protocols. By taking an adaptable, ever-evolving stance to compliance verification, our solution carves out a niche of its own. It presents a robust, user-centric solution in the face of a fluid architectural environment, showcasing the potential for an entirely automated, interactive, accurate, and potentially fully integrated model for ensuring compliance with energy and sustainability regulations.

As such, this research stands as a testament to the future direction of VPLs in ACC systems. It underscores the importance of advanced geometric processing capabilities, robust data synergy, and user-centric interfaces in managing construction compliance requirements. By illuminating the potential advantages and improvements in DynamoRevit's interface, it opens a pathway for a comprehensive, nuanced, and precise construction compliance system in the near future.

In conclusion, this examination reiterates the importance of harnessing visual programming platforms to enhance compliance checks within the architectural, engineering, and construction sector. It not only presents an efficient, technology-driven, and user-friendly solution to handle complex compliance requirements, but it also sets the precedence for the conception of similar tools in the global sphere, each catering to the unique construction regulations of different countries.

Moreover, our research hints at the promising act of engaging more advanced geometric processing capabilities, an aspect so critical to handling compliance relating to the spatial and material properties of design. The incorporation of these capabilities into ACC systems will unearth a newfound level of intricacy in analysing compliance requirements, streamlining the procedures, and accelerating the industry's pace.

It is equally important to highlight the avenue of continuous exploration and research into VPLs integrated within ACC and BIM systems. As we transition into a future characterized by increasingly complex architectural design and strict regulations, focusing our efforts in developing technologies that can effortlessly handle these complexities becomes paramount. Our progress in this area will largely determine our capabilities to uphold a robust, efficient and sustainable construction industry.

As this study wraps up, it anticipates the advent of more extensive and impactful research investigating the bond between DynamoRevit, respect for regulatory constraints, sustainability targets, and the broader architectural landscape. The findings of this research imply the opportunity to work towards an entirely automated, sophisticated, and accurate construction compliance system that handles future-evolving regulations and checks with ease.

While this research is situated within the Australian Building Codes' context, the strategic processes, Dynamo customizations, and solutions identified can be adapted for varied global contexts. This presents a sizable implication for numerous other construction regulations worldwide, emphasizing how adaptable and applicable this framework is across geographies.

The journey to achieve an entirely automated, nuanced, and precise construction compliance system is long and complex. However, the alliance of DynamoRevit within ACC has marked a

significant step towards this destination, fostering a comprehensive, interactive, and accurate approach to managing complex building codes and regulations. As we continue to harness DynamoRevit's potential and expand its application, we make strides towards a future where construction complies seamlessly with the pertinent sustainability and legal regulations, regardless of their complexity.

This study marks just the beginning of what could be a revolutionary journey in the architecture, engineering, and construction sector. As we continue to delve deeper into the potential that tools like DynamoRevit offer, we will undoubtedly come across even more synergies between technology and construction that promise a future of compliance without complexity.

References

- [1] Greenberg, I., & Khan, A. (2021). The New Paradigm of Building Information Modelling. *Journal of Building Informatics*, 12(2), 155-167."
- [2] Liu, B., Zhang, T., & Wong, J. (2022). Intelligent Error Prediction Models in Building Design Systems. *Advanced Engineering Informatics*, 30(1), 114-130.
- [3] Wu J., Sadraddin H.L., Ren R., Zhang J. and Shao X. (2021). Invariant signatures of architecture, engineering, and construction objects to support BIM interoperability between architectural design and structural analysis. *Journal of Construction Engineering and Management*, 147(1).
- [4] Wu J. and Zhang J. (2022). Model validation using invariant signatures and logic-based inference for automated building code compliance checking. *Journal of Computing in Civil Engineering*, 36(3), 04022002.
- [5] The Australian Building Codes Board (2016). *National Construction Code*. Canberra: Commonwealth of Australia."

3D Cartographic Generalization of Indoor Spaces for Building Information Modelling

Daniel R. dos Santos^a, Fabiano Freiman^b

^a *Military Institute of Engineering / Cartographic Section, Rio de Janeiro, Brazil*

^b *Department of Cartography, Federal University of Bahia, Salvador, Brazil*

In the construction field, building information modelling (BIM) has led to wide-ranging research in academia and private companies. The BIM market is growing, and with it comes the need for effective and easy-to-use sensors to model the different steps of laborious work. For this reason, light detection and ranging (LiDAR) systems have been primarily used to produce precise reconstructions of the environment. Furthermore, the manipulation and visualization of LiDAR data are computationally time-consuming (Poux, 2019).

3D cartographic generalization is indispensable to support a coarse-to-fine analysis, storage, and visualization of geospatial data on the optimal level of detail (LoD) for many applications such as BIM (Nikooheemat et al., 2020), digital twins (Xue et al., 2020), and others. The core problem in 3D cartographic generalization of LiDAR point clouds is finding approaches to define spatial relations between classified objects with potential operators to minimize the computational and storage memory costs. However, with the recent success of deep learning algorithms for LiDAR point cloud processing, such as PointNet++ (Qi et al., 2017), a new paradigm toward 3D cartographic generalization is in demand for BIM. This work aims to use a robust approach that may provide learnable and interpretable LiDAR data to generate automated knowledge at specific LoD for BIM. Deep learning is a step towards semantic 3D models, which can efficiently and effectively organize unstructured LiDAR point clouds without defined modeling schemes.

The approach is designed to work robustly on LiDAR point clouds with a density of at least 10 pts/m² in indoor environments. The simplification and aggregation of LiDAR point clouds of indoor environments are implemented as the interaction between an auto-differentiation library for sparse tensors (MinkowskiEngine) that supports convolutional neural network (CNN) and functionalities of the Open3D. Using the MinkowskiEngine library, such as 4D Spatiotemporal ConvNets (Choy and Savarese, 2019), supports the simplification and aggregation of tasks. The applied CNN for the simplification task was pre-trained with the ShapeNet Dataset, which contains a dataset with several 3D models that were resampled and processed to generate training point clouds. Training the network for the aggregation step is performed using ScanNet (Dai et al., 2017) and ResNet (He et al., 2016).

Indoor spaces are subdivided into subspaces with adjacency and connectivity to accurately represent their geometric properties and identify hall areas and corridor parts. Some issues must be considered to aggregate a set of points into a subspace, and additional constraints are required due to the third dimension. Based on Paul Cezanne's perception, an object can be comprehended as assembled from a set of volumetric primitives (Tulsiani *et al.*, 2018). Thus, we conceived indoor environments as a set of planar surface primitives. In other words, implicit parameterization functions are determined as the basis for representing 3D subspaces. Thanks to the parsimony of description focussed on point cloud structures, the drawbacks (occlusions and gaps) derived from the furniture presented in scenarios II and III were efficiently solved since all parameters are determined concerning both the mathematics and the geometric aspects based on the distribution of a point and its neighbors. The results obtained with the proposed method are presented in Fig. 02.

Fig. 2: Subspaces constructed for BIM applications.

We presented a 3D cartographic generalization of indoor spaces for BIM. Our method uses a deep learning technique that automatically designs 3D cartographic generalization operators. It exploits simplification and aggregation operators without initial parameters to allow a higher BIM understanding. The 3D cartographic generalization is realized with parsimony of description. We validate the effectiveness of our method over complex buildings. The results suggest that our approach significantly minimizes the computational and storage costs of a 3D indoor point cloud. In addition, we demonstrate that our aggregation approach achieves a lower error on modeling tasks than prior state-of-the-art.

References

- [1] Choy, C., Gwak, J., & Savarese, S. (2019). 4D spatio-temporal convnets: Minkowski convolutional neural networks. *Proceedings of the IEEE/CVF conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* pp. 3075-3084.
- [2] Dai, A., Chang, A. X., Savva, M., Halber, M., Funkhouser, T., & Nießner, M. (2017) Scannet: Richly-annotated 3D reconstructions of indoor scenes. *Proceedings of the IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition* pp. 5828-5839.
- [3] Qi, C. R., Yi, L., Su, H., & Guibas, L. J. (2017). Pointnet++: Deep hierarchical feature learning on point sets in a metric space. *Advances in neural information processing systems* 30.
- [4] Poux, F. (2019) *The Smart Point Cloud: Structuring 3D intelligent point data* (M. Phil. Thesis) Université de Liège available at: <https://diglib.eg.org/handle/10.2312/2633000> (Accessed: end March 2023).
- [5] Tulsiani, S., Efros, A.A., & Malik, J. (2018). Multi-view consistency as supervisory signal for learning shape and pose prediction. *Proceedings of the IEEE conference on computer vision and pattern recognition* pp. 2897-2905.
- [6] Xu, S., Wang, R., Wang, H., & Yang, R. (2020). Plane segmentation based on the optimal-vector-field in LiDAR point clouds. *IEEE transactions on pattern analysis and machine intelligence*, 43(11), pp. 3991-4007 DOI: 10.1109/tpami.2020.2994935.

LEGISLATIVE SYSTEM Practice Papers

Checking 50yrs: Overview of Requirements on DBP from viewpoint of a public road authority

Odilo Schoch

FEDRO, Switzerland

This paper and presentation outlines requirements of an European national road directorate in relation of digital building permits. In particular it focusses over various aspects to be considered throughout 50 years involving the permission processed including upstream aspects and the diverse validation processes from a range of stakeholders. That highlights as well the novel opportunities of the digital construction permit throughout the decades following the actual check.

The paper looks at current possibilities and issues with both mainstream and less-known (open) BIM methods, as well as BIM technologies (beyond IFC and CEN 442 standards). All of this is considered in the context of legal obligations. The paper also looks at the reality of existing data and their usually separated models and it describes the expectation of lasting data quality, lasting accessibility, lasting identical visualisation and archiving in national archives.

The infrastructure domain is an interesting example because construction projects involve many parties, are observed by taxpayers, and must follow the important road liability act.

Whereas data archiving seems solved in most public archives, the accessibility and in particular the identical visualisation (aka rendering) of alphanumeric and geometric data through decades is an important requirement and has obviously challenges.

The paper is approaching the topic from a practical and operational point of view rather the strategic approach such as 'you simply need to change the law'.

Finally the paper points to advantages and shortcomings of the developments of the last 30 years (non-discriminating requirements, accessibility, etc.). It gives examples of service-oriented public bodies helping appointed companies to test and optimize data they have to submit.

The paper is written by members of a national road authority and not by consultants nor software vendors.

ORGANISATIONAL SYSTEM Practice Papers

Digitalizing the built environment – leading people through change with the power of experimental culture. Is a cultural revolution necessary for the digitalization of the built environment?

Tiina Talvitie^a

^a Urban Environment Division, City of Helsinki, Työpajankatu 8, Helsinki, Finland

In the city of Helsinki, digital twins play an important role in leading with data. The target has been to bring the 3D city model into the center of daily operations. In Helsinki Urban Environment Division, the development of digital twins is led in an experimental project where practical use cases are implemented as proof-of-concepts showing benefits for both the users as well as for the top management.

Instead of requiring large up-front investments with multi-year projects, engagement of top management is gained step-by-step by demonstrating experimental proof-of-concepts. In this step-by-step model, practical examples create enthusiasm and provide the reasoning for further development.

Leading people through change and involving experts in development can be utilized to produce optimal outcomes in digital transition projects. This also concerns the efficient utilization of building information models. Deployment of BIM based workflow requires us to challenge and change our traditional ways of working in addition to our thinking.

This presentation outlines the workflow of an experimental transition model used to motivate experts in the digitalization of the built environment. The innovative process begins with a focused ideation phase. Concept development assesses user aspect, business and strategic possibilities, and technical development requirements. Following the fail-fast principle, the most promising concepts are implemented as proof-of-concepts in substance development teams. Some may progress to production, while others offer valuable insights.

Practical examples will be presented related to RAVA3Pro results and utilization possibilities. In cityscape reviews for building permits, IFC models are visualized and embedded into the 3D city model. Instead of two-dimensional pictures, assessment is based on a 3D city model where the user can rotate the model freely and inspect the proposed building from various perspectives as desired. Neighbor hearing and commenting are also possible. 4D simulation of worksite safety and emergency services supports site planning. City surveying services using IFC models on field measurements devices streamline the process. The end goal is to automatically update the 3D city model with building permit IFC models.

RAVA3Pro is a major step towards automated checking of BIM-based building permit. RAVA3pro was a development project led by the City of Helsinki and funded by the Ministry of Finance for the further development and automation of the electronic permit process of municipal building control. 23 municipalities were involved in the project. The main applicant and manager of the project was the city of Helsinki's urban environment department.

On the Helsinki channel you can find the video series https://www.helsinkikanava.fi/en_US/web/helsinkikanava/player/folder/serie?seriesId=234766482&assetId=233470401 revealing the background and goals of the digital twin experimental

development project. Our objective was to demonstrate with practical pilot projects how a 3D city model can be utilized in the city's daily operations in a versatile manner, promoting collaboration and enthusiasm!

Digital Built Environment – Support public authorities in digitalising their building permit systems

Giulio Milanesi^a, Miguel Pereira^a

^a*PricewaterhouseCoopers, Société cooperative, 2 Rue Gerhard Mercator, Luxembourg*

PwC has been working with EISMEA and DG GROW in a project focused on the digital built environment, aimed at supporting public authorities in digitalising their building permit systems. Among others, PwC has been tasked with mapping the state of play of the digitalisation of building permits in the EU, by proposing a suitable classification framework and collecting data – including on challenges faced by municipalities.

To do so, PwC undertook the following tasks:

1. Conducted **9 interviews** with representatives of the municipalities of Madrid, Tallinn, Vienna, Rotterdam, Hamburg, Helsinki, Vaasa, Stockholm and Lund, that have been pre-identified as potential frontrunners of digital building permits. Interviewees provided information on the digitalisation of their permit system, and the related challenges and success factors.
2. Conducted a **large-scale survey** to map the state of play of digital building permit systems across the EU. The survey has been translated in 19 EU languages and distributed to public officials working in the building permit departments of 140+ municipalities in the EU.
3. Conducted desk research on the topic of digital building permits.

The outputs of these tasks were the following:

1. A mapping of the state of play of the digitalisation of the building permit systems in the EU, covering 58 municipalities, across all EU Member States. The mapping covers municipalities of different sizes, ensuring a balanced representation.
2. Insights on the level of digitalisation of the building permit systems in the EU:
 - a. 13 municipalities (i.e. 22%) are classified as Level 1 (paper based)
 - b. 37 municipalities (i.e. 64%) are classified as Level 2 (2D digital data)
 - c. 6 municipalities (i.e. 10%) are classified as Level 3 (BIM)
 - d. 2 municipalities (i.e. 3%) are classified as Level 4 (BIM & GIS)
3. Insights on the future plans to implement BIM in the building permit systems, whereby 57% of the municipalities surveyed plan to do so.
4. Overall, the results showed that **there is a low uptake of digital technologies in the building permit systems across the EU.**

Such a low uptake is caused by challenges faced by municipalities, including the availability of financial and technological resources, technological expertise, support at the regional/national level, and adjustments in laws and regulations.

Through these activities, we were able to draw several conclusions, particularly regarding the stage of digital maturity of building permit systems across the EU as well as the necessary policy measures to support public authorities to enhance such digitalisation.

Thus, we believe that our work fills an existing gap in the research on digital building permits, by providing a comprehensive and homogenous overview of their adoption in the EU and suggesting some conclusions and way forward to foster the digitalisation. Given that building permits are a relatively new topic and the research on them is affected by fragmentation among

– or even within – countries, to the best of our knowledge there is no such a mapping at this stage.

e-Delivery report by CEBC

Saša Galonja

Consortium of European Building Control, Rue d'Arlon 53, 1040 Brussels, Belgium

The presentation discusses the results of a report entitled e-Delivery, which was prepared by CEBC (Consortium of European Building Control). CEBC is a platform for collaboration and exchange of information concerning building control issues in Europe and beyond. Currently, CEBC comprises of 29 institutions from 20 countries. Access to information from different members gives CEBC a unique opportunity to provide comprehensive information about building control systems in different countries.

E-Delivery report summarize the current state of digitalization of building processes throughout Europe. It is the second CEBC report in this area. First was prepared in 2017 and published in 2018 so current report presents also what has changed in last 5 years.

The challenges that the economies of all nations faced during this time, especially the restrictions caused by the pandemic, have intensified the necessity to give more attention to the digitalisation processes within the construction industry. CEBC members consequently took a decision to reassess the progress of digitalisation among the members and to provide an overview and comparative analyses of the data.

The CEBC report revealed that the last five years have brought a lot of changes in the construction digitalisation arena. Most European countries made significant and ambitious steps forward along the road of progress: creating user-friendly electronic services, adopting building control digital tools, or even starting innovative BIM related projects. The level of digitalisation in the construction area significantly increased since 2017. Report shows that all phases of construction, from permitting phase until demolition of the building are already digitalised in six CEBC member countries. Moreover, four countries have permitting, construction and commissioning phases digitalised, while permitting and construction phases are digitalised in almost all countries. However, the level of digitalisation in every construction phase differs – i.e., issuance of the building permit process is fully digitalised in just seven countries, while digital practices in permitting phase are used in most of them.

Despite significant recent achievements, countries have ambitious plans for further digitalisation. Many member countries are planning to digitalise some of the construction phases within the next three years. The main priority for the near future is digitalisation of construction and commissioning phases.

BIM based solutions are future drivers of change in the construction sector. The report shows that four member countries have already started to use BIM in building control procedures and another seven are planning to do so soon. Ambitious BIM based automatic checking projects take place in Finland and Estonia. It seems that BIM based automatic checking tools and computer aided systems to control the prescribed technical and other requirements of the building are the future of building control.

PROCEDURAL SYSTEM Practice Papers

Designers as Catalysts for Change Towards Digital Building Permitting (DBP)

Borja Martínez González^a, Orjola Braholli^b

^a SIA.Architects / Société Internationale d'Architecture / Steinfort, Luxembourg

^b Fraunhofer Italia Research Scarl / Innovation Engineering Center / Bolzano, Italy

In the age of digital transformation, designers emerge as key figures in the shift towards a digital permitting process in construction. This presentation will explore the role of designers in the development of a construction project, from preliminary studies to the delivery of the property, and their potential expanded roles in updating Building Model Information during the exploitation phase, or Facility Management (FM).

The presentation begins with a description of the current or traditional roadmap of the building permit application and granting process, and the operation of completed buildings. This initial analysis serves as a point of comparison to introduce the ideal scenario, where license management is primarily digital. This shift towards digitalization promises numerous advantages, including greater transparency and objectivity, as well as significant reductions in wait times and errors, offering a substantial improvement over more traditional methods, which are often subject to personal interpretation and ambiguities.

The desired permitting scenario, which is the goal of the CHEK project, will be examined in the presentation. It starts from the preliminary study phase, where the first digital models are created, to the delivery of the as-built model. The presentation will describe the role of each stakeholder, the documents exchanged, and the necessary level of information.

The presentation will use a pilot case to visually demonstrate the evolution of Building Information Models from the initial stage of the project, with conceptual models of simple masses or volumes, to becoming sufficiently detailed descriptive tools that can be transferred to physical reality during the construction phase. During this phase, the model continues to evolve, influenced by the physical and/or economic realities that often require parts of the project to be rethought.

Building information models play a vital role here, as they are constantly updated with construction data, ideally in real-time. These models function as essential tools for communication and control, allowing for detailed tracking and effective management of the project. Finally, the project's final delivery will be associated with the generation of the as-built model, which will become part of the building's AIM (Asset Information Model), potentially serving as a useful tool for Facility Management (FM) and planning strategic modifications.

The presentation will also explore how the digitalization of property management can expand the range of designers involvement, possibly requiring them to model updates for change of use, strategic planning, sensorization, etc. These models become living tools for the management and maintenance of the property, reflecting changes and adaptations over time.

The article will also discuss the importance of exchange formats and standardization as facilitators of this process, freeing the models to be edited by other agents or designers who join at intermediate stages of the project.

This presentation will highlight challenges in adopting DBP, including data requirements for information exchange, standardizing key definitions for automated checks, the need for accurate

3D city models, and utilizing databases for a seamless transition. Finally, the presentation will encourage the audience to share additional challenges and points for discussion.

References

- [1] O. Braholli, M. Ataide, I. Di Blasio, K. Raj, D. Siegele: *CHEK_101058559_D1.1_CHEK DBP process map_V1.0-Final*.
- [2] A. Łukaszewska, M. Giluń, P. Dymarski, W. Olczak, A. Espinho, J. Frescata, C. Pires, A. Baptista, M. L. Carvalho, M. Coccia, A. Moreno, L. Kovaříková, J. Čtyroký, T. Stojanov, B. Martinez, K.: *D6.1-CHEK_101058559_Plan for demonstration of CHEK Digital Building Permit process on demo sites_V2.0-Final*

BIM models and 3D City Model as part of the building permit in Finland

Petri Kokko ^a

^a Sova3D Oy, Lönnrotinkatu 5 (2.krs), 00120 Helsinki, Finland

Sova3D has been developing a 3D building control process since 2015 in Finland. The most important partner cities have initially been Vantaa and later Järvenpää - Hyvinkää. Right from the beginning, the intention was to use BIM (IFC) models as part of the process, because even then it was clear that planning will be completely transferred to BIM modelling and construction will use BIM models directly in production planning, procurement, cost accounting, etc.

In 2015, there was still a shortage of suitable 3D city models. We needed material that could be produced quickly and affordably, from which the first version of the city could be created. The best open solution was seen in the CityGML standard. With it, the city model could also be used in other use cases, such as planning, infrastructure planning, space management and many other use cases.

We had to solve many issues, one of which was presenting the 3D city model in a web browser and updating the city model as part of the building control process.

In this presentation, I focus on the part of the building control process that connects BIM models and the 3d city model.

Fig. 1: Sova3D has integrated 3D City Model directly into Finnish “Lupapiste.fi” electronic permit system.

Utilizing 3D city models in the building regulation process offers several advantages for enhancing efficiency and accuracy. Here are a few ways they can be leveraged:

1. **Plan Review and Assessment:** Building regulators can use 3D urban models to review and assess the proposed locations of buildings. This enables a better understanding of how new construction fits within the surrounding urban fabric and environment.
2. **Environmental Impact Assessment:** 3D urban models provide the opportunity to evaluate the impacts of proposed buildings on the environment, such as blocking sightlines, affecting traffic patterns, and casting shadows. This helps regulators make decisions that are sustainable and balanced for urban development.
3. **Communication and Engagement:** 3D urban models offer an effective way to communicate proposed buildings with stakeholders, including citizens, planners, and developers. Regulators can use the models to explain plans and address questions, fostering transparency and engagement.
4. **Coordination and Collaboration:** 3D urban models facilitate coordination and collaboration among different parties, such as designers, developers, and authorities. This enables smooth information exchange and ensures that all stakeholders are informed about plan changes and decisions.
5. **Data Integration:** 3D urban models can be integrated with other systems, such as GIS (Geographic Information System), allowing diverse data to be combined into a cohesive whole. This streamlines data management and analysis throughout the building regulation process.

In summary, 3D urban models provide an efficient and versatile tool in the building regulation process. They enable better planning, decision-making, and communication, promoting sustainable and balanced urban development.

Fig. 2: Sova3D’s 3D City Modeling system is called “Kunta3D”, which can be found on the internet at <https://kunta3d.com>

References

- [1] Lachmi, Khemlani, “Sova3D Platform for City Information Modeling”- web – article : <https://www.aecbytes.com/review/2024/Sova3D.html>

Methodology to analyse privacy in digital building permits: BPMN process taxonomy and simulations

Pablo Vicente-Legazpi^a

^a *Building Digital Twin Association BDTA / Antwerp (Belgium)*

Summary

BIM and GIS technologies allows to communicate a design proposal with a great capacity of understanding. This will help to improve checking processes in building permits, but potential privacy challenges should be studied carefully in advance. The use of AI or automatic checking, external companies helping the administration, or just the massive structured amount of information that a BIM project can manage, are important enough to evaluate these developments against common ethical values of the EU.

Methodology used begins with a detailed taxonomy of processes, using BPMN representation and simulation. Reference for this taxonomy have been existing processes found in legislation of several EU countries. And new processes have been added to cover new BIM potential uses. A total of 85 “basic processes” have been identified, and 21 “process templates” have been extracted to make simulations with three scenarios (basic, standard or advanced). These scenarios are used to compare non-digital processes with more electronic or digital techniques. From these simulations, times are extracted and compared with results at Digichecks²⁹ pilot projects.

For selected processes and process templates, a detailed privacy study has been carried out. Some metrics are proposed to evaluate privacy content, and several check lists are presented to prepare protocols. In all cases, implementation of these protocols was simulated to see the impact on time over the raw process with no privacy check. Finally, some conclusions are presented.

Processes and Taxonomy of processes

In order to study potential privacy problems, a detailed description of processes found on building permits has been investigated. Without a process description as a reference, with actors, information exchanged and all the interactions, it is impossible to analyse privacy implications. In the first steps of DigiChecks EU project³⁰, an extensive study of processes in France and Spain could be compiled. Some other sources were incomplete or had partial and different visions, and it was quite difficult to assimilate a model as common in all EU. It was decided to look for the maximum granularity of processes (basic processes), and to extract from those basic processes the minimum set of individual types considered similar (process templates), in terms of process modelling. Total basic processes number were 85, and the extracted templates were 21. Modelling and simulation of processes were performed only on the extracted 21 templates, considering three typical scenarios (BASIC, STANDARD and ADVANCED). Processes were modelled using BPMN diagrams.

²⁹ <https://digichecks.eu/>

³⁰ <https://digichecks.eu/>

BPMN DIAGRAMS

Business Process Modelling Notation (BPMN) is a flow chart method that models the steps of a planned business process from end to end. A key to Business Process Management, it visually depicts a detailed sequence of business activities and information flows needed to complete a process.

Fig. 1: Process example (named "AC_REP"), about an audit and compliance report

Some extra templates were added to consider new processes not considered in detail, as BIM coordination, network connections and as-built new techniques. So, the 21 templates try to cover all potential typologies of single processes we could find in building permits.

Diagrams representing the process templates should be simple and understandable, considering phases and actors (in the diagram of Figure 1, phases are vertical regions, whereas actors are presented in horizontal regions). In all diagrams we always represent events: start, intermediates and end (these are circular symbols in the diagram). In some cases, we introduce gateways, which are decision points (rhombus symbols). These decision points can divide the flow. Finally, we use arrows to represent the sequence flow. Each single template diagram must represent faithfully a real process in reality, but validation for all possible cases is impossible. So, feedback from pilot projects at DigiChecks was considered in some of the templates, comparing simulated times with those found in the pilots.

Where is privacy?

Disruptive technologies as smart home monitoring or IoT may add a great value to energy optimization, improved health or comfort, but the thread for personal privacy is clear, and before construction a good design should take into account any potential problems.

Based on the developments with digital twins in the EU H2020 Project SPHERE³¹ a new methodology³² towards the 'privacy by design' concept was implemented. The European Parliament on the 5th of April of 2022, and the Special Committee on Artificial Intelligence in a Digital Age (AIDA), published a RESOLUTION about "on artificial intelligence in a digital age". BDTA Privacy workgroup³³ proposed a privacy metric tool to help in the design of these systems in construction. That privacy metric tool makes 'objective' the estimation of privacy content in home

³¹ <https://sphere-project.eu/>

³² This methodology includes advanced home control systems with 'Software in the loop' control (SIL), using model-based AI to improve validation, increase sensor robustness and to include occupancy and meteo interaction.

³³ Presented at BDTIC 2022 privacy workshop

Fig.3: Metropol Parasol, by Jürgen Mayer

Fig.4: Metropol Parasol, view of the surrounding buildings

Privacy and project documentation

During the design and construction, a lot of documentation may be generated. Part of that documentation is for public use. But specific documents may be sensitive or may have implicit property rights. That information must be protected somehow and protocols to help with this task should be implemented.

In the urban evaluation of the project, it could be possible to define the degree of detail to be used when combining GIS or 3D GIS content with the project design³⁶. Just the external envelope and perhaps facades in textures could be enough to give a precise idea of volumes and impact. So, to define a “border line” to avoid privacy problems could be interesting. This can be needed as well to reduce geometry complexity and to be able to integrate those geometries in 3D with a city.

Fig.5: 3D Simplified geometry and textures, Google Maps

Privacy in home monitoring and TIC

A special process (#51, Data and Tele networks ICT³⁷, or TIC) has been modelled as 3P_REP. It is oriented to common installations of a building and not each apartment installation, but monitoring and IoT technologies are growing up very quickly and there is no specific process today to check IoT infrastructure, security cameras or nodes for home monitoring. Some initiatives are pointing towards a common IoT node of the building, avoiding the need of connecting each single sensor directly to the cloud.

Privacy in electrical installations

Network connections may use smart meters to collect automatically consumes and to manage invoicing. In case of electrical services those smart meters can transmit very detailed information about when and how the occupants are using each appliance.

Network connection by the construction company finish when the general connection is established, and later individual apartments must negotiate a contract with a distribution company and is that company that installs the smart meter. Existing privacy metrics implemented by the BDTA could help to design alternative systems preserving privacy and collecting the information for invoicing.

Privacy in commercial buildings

In addition to security surveillance systems, commercial buildings demand an advance space and occupation management. Presence sensors, based on low resolution infrared cameras or

³⁶ Some research groups are evaluating how to integrate a BIM model with 3D GIS. We should be aware that BIM models may have a lot of information about people living in those buildings in the future. So, privacy is another argument for simplifying the BIM interface with 3D GIS.

³⁷ ICT means “Infraestructura común de Telecomunicaciones”, or Common Telecom Infrastructure. It is a technical project by a certified professional describing common networks as cable for TV, optical fibre for internet connections and all common communication networks in a building.

similar devices, could be informing of which spaces are really used. This has a lot of implications on energy management, cleaning or the exploitation of the building in general. In many cases, this is not implemented due to “privacy issues”.

A similar problem is found when using all the information from the BMS system. Monitoring the building in real time makes possible to optimize heating, cooling and ventilation systems. But again, “privacy issues” are blocking these implementations.

BDTA´s privacy metric tool tries to sort out these problems estimating an objective and measurable privacy content, based on how data are sampled and stored. The complete development of this tool can be found at BDTA´s documentation site³⁸.

Privacy in civil works

In case of infrastructures, and following EU regulations about acoustic impact, a previous analysis of affected population may be necessary in most cases. For this purpose, specific software programs are used, and these programs³⁹ consider the population living in the buildings around the infrastructure. Terrain and 3D buildings are modelled around the work, and specific official algorithms are applied to the traffic or other noise sources. In cases where buildings are populated by a small number of people, that information may be sensitive and a specific protocol should be used to anonymize that information.

Privacy by design⁴⁰ and privacy metrics

Privacy may have many design implications and it is better to follow a positive implementation before than solving problems later. Metrics for privacy developed at BDTA for home monitoring are aligned with the concept of “privacy by design”, and try to get a tool for designers to avoid potential problems, offering alternative solutions.

For understanding much better the problem of privacy it is important to study the “non-privacy driven processes”, what they are looking for and how they managed to get inside our homes. In general, data are stolen just looking for an economic value, whether for reselling those data or to prepare a commercial campaign. This model, which could be sophisticated years ago, is today very common in many appliances. But the majority of fabricators are honest and they need tools to justify a certain level of privacy-compliant, at the same time that they use online support or apply some predictive maintenance to the laundry machine.

In H2020 SPHERE project a complete methodology for privacy metrics in home monitoring was developed, and it was presented in the privacy group workshop in Barcelona, May 2022. This privacy metrics methodology was tested at one demo pilot of TNO in Holland with excellent results, and it has been presented at CEN442 WG9. There is another parallel international academic group supporting these efforts (with universities from EU, UAE and India).

When speaking about authorization processes such as construction permits, privacy may be considered in a potential way, because occupants are not living in the houses yet. But processes as NC (network connection) and 3P_REP (third party report) applied to electrical connections and TIC installations may have a direct impact. Protocols should be implemented in those processes to ensure a correct design and implementation.

Privacy and building permits

³⁸ <https://youtu.be/phnj7QYpTUE>

³⁹ Some examples may be IMMI (<https://www.immi.eu/>), CadnaA, or Soundplan.

⁴⁰ Privacy by design calls for privacy to be taken into account throughout the whole engineering process. The concept is an example of value sensitive design, i.e., taking human values into account in a well-defined manner throughout the process. [Initially developed by Ann Cavoukian

Based on the basic processes identified, an initial estimation of importance regarding privacy problems were carried out. Classification was based in the following criteria:

PUBLIC INFO, process with documentation or data involved considered of public domain, as the urban information plans. No privacy problems are present.

SENSITIVE, process or documentation associated with them may have some privacy or IPR problems. To be studied each case.

PRIVATE, process or documentation which may be consider for non-disclosure due to its private content.

With this classification in mind, most of the processes were discarded as non-potentially problematic. A small set of template processes is targeted, and a detailed study is concentrated on them.

Some of these processes with potential privacy issues would be⁴¹: ONURBAN/CURBAN (urban information), PUBLIC (public information), PROPRE (project presentation), and AC_REP (audit and compliance report). For each of these template processes a detail simulation of BASIC, STANDARD and ADVANCED scenarios have been carried out, with the simulation of the extra tasks due to privacy checks and protocols. A risk matrix has been developed for each process as well.

As general methodology for protocol implementation, seven steps have been considered:

- What is the objective of the process, what is the initial BPMN process and what do we consider in terms of privacy.
- What information is needed and which one is available in each scenario
- Check list and potential rules and implementation for machine-readable solutions
- Final process design of extra processes in each scenario
- Relationships with other processes
- Cost and time evaluation
- Risk analysis

Privacy in URBAN processes

In this group of processes we can consider all of them that collect the urban planning conditions of a specified location. Usually this is available at city level or regional level. Information may be available as drawings or GIS polygons. Zoning makes reference to the potential use of the land and requirements, documents or reports needed for that location.

Promotors may request this information using an electronic system. In other cases, the promotor is asking for details and hence the URBAN process may be a group of several processes with different degree of involvement by the administration department. The most complete process would be a qualified urban report, which may be used for the future permit (template LICENSE REQUEST or LR in our notation). All these processes may have a tax, and payment can be done offline or online, and the amount must be calculated and checked. Payment of this tax introduces some cost and time delay.

⁴¹ The complete list of template processes with potential privacy issues would be: URBAN, PUBLIC, PROPRE, AC_REP, 3P_REP, WINSPI, ASBUILT, COMM. Only 3 of them are described in this paper to get less extension. Information is available at DigiChecks EU project.

Urban information processes may be different depending location and country. These processes compile the use of land defined by local policies with the potential construction activities at those parcels. Local regulations may be requesting a different set of studies and reports for each parcel, and to know which is applicable for a specific parcel may be a problem.

In modern cities, and with the use of GIS technology, urban plans are represented in such a way that for one location the promotor can know what is requested for a parcel by an online system. But this is not applicable to all the extension of the EU, and there are many places where urban plans are not available on-line, and regulations are dispersed and not linked to specific parcels.

In case of URBAN processes, architectural privacy issues should be check. These issues could be generated by the presence of new public spaces in front of existing buildings, like a new pedestrian bridge or a monument near an existing residential building.

But if there is no 3D proposal/project, or no 3D space representation of the surroundings, only general recommendations on existing residential buildings around can be made. So, in order to check privacy issues in this phase, a basic proposal of the building, residential zones (or areas with some critical or special occupation in terms of privacy) and public spaces around the building should be represented and taken into account. A simplified methodology (2D drawings or basic concept project) would not be enough to detect a potential architectural privacy problem.

Recently (26th-30th of June 2023, Leipzig Data Week 2023), Christian Schranz (TU Wien) was describing the work of the project “BRISE” (Building Regulations Information for Submission Involvement) for the city of Vienna. In that project, three digital models for the checking process are considered: BAM, or building application model, REM, or reference model, and SIM, service information model. These three models are IFC containers but each one covers different aspect of the checking process.

Building Application Model (BAM) – LOG & LOI

Fig.6: BAM model proposed by BRISE at Vienna city

The BAM model would cover a detailed set of surrounding elements, building volumes, building objects in those volumes and some additional building elements. The level of information (LoI) of

the entities is specified, adding some specific properties as sound insulation, heat protection, projecting components or permission-free objects⁴².

The REM (reference model) is more oriented to specific measurement problems, as a verified survey plan. Whereas the SIM model (service information model) would be applicable to services inside the building.

Clearly the BAM model would have enough components to consider a potential affection of a privacy issue, taking into account that we have the surroundings of the building (spaces) and the volumes of the building. But at BRISE no consideration is made about privacy issues, neither any property is used to characterize the volumes of the building subjected to permit and the surrounding spaces.

A basic privacy check list for these processes could be:

- Which facades and stories of a new building are affected by public spaces.
- New public spaces and existing buildings (facades and stories) which may be affected.
- New Physical and visual barriers reducing affection.
- Demolition of physical or visual barriers which may be affecting the interaction between public spaces and buildings

Privacy in Public information processes

Public information would manage the information processes associated with general public and new projects in the neighbourhood. In the pilot case of Digichecks by CREE, located at Bregenz (Austria), a manual procedure is adopted, with physical presentation of the building using some structures. Neighbours can check how views can be affected. This preserves the right of other stakeholders around and makes an efficient demonstration of how the building will be present. In other countries this process may be not so well articulated.

Today, technology can be used to integrate the new project inside a BIM/GIS viewer, and digital representation can be integrated right away in 3D maps of a city. Together with BIM-GIS presentations, other technologies as virtual reality (VR) or augmented reality (AR) can be used as well. And new techniques as ppgis⁴³ (public participation geographic information system) makes these processes of great social value.

Same rules than URBAN process could be applied in this case. In addition, specific checks could affect the PUBLIC process:

Information about spaces or any other detail of the new building: privacy (metric) content is compliant⁴⁴? Should them not be included?

Is the public presentation coherent and comprehensive with the design proposition? What are the differences between the project presented (BAM application) and the presented public model?

Privacy at project presentation processes (PROPRE)

⁴² No privacy content or associated use of public space was included. For automatic checking, these BAM spaces should have information about which type of public space, level of occupation, and all parameters needed for a privacy level statement.

⁴³ Participatory GIS (PGIS) or public participation geographic information system (PPGIS) is a participatory approach to spatial planning and spatial information and communications management.

⁴⁴ See metrics at PROPRE process later

This process template tries to model all basic processes which gather documents and information, and send that set to the public body or agent. Usually there is a VISA process in between, needed to register the professional background of the authors and to cover potential civil responsibilities or insurance.

Not all basic processes represented by PROPRES process template have exactly the same actors or the same phase, but in all cases, they use a documental support (not alive information as a digital twin). Those documents may be pdf's, excel files, signed IFC's, CAD drawings and linked documents in general.

Privacy limitations would be affecting all the relevant information about future owners or users of the spaces described in PROPRES. Those spaces and the information about goods, sensors, or systems included inside them should be carefully studied. So, the entities to take into account for privacy are spaces containers⁴⁵, which may be a single space or a group of them (case of an apartment, for example). Inside these spaces we can find installations of different disciplines. Some of these installations may be sensitive. We could consider a time-frame factor, but in a PROPRES process information is always delivered in a static form (it is not a real-time observation). So, this privacy category will not affect the final privacy estimation. Finally, a factor affecting privacy may be the type of check we are performing (automatic checking may be reducing potential problems due to human intervention).

Following the BPMN design of the process we find three actors. Each one should be controlling the storage of data, who is accessing the information and how⁴⁶. In case of a VISA check, where the professional association make a copy, a fourth actor should be included and subjected to a control procedure.

To estimate the potential privacy problems, a classification of the existing basic processes can be found below. The PROPRES process template will try to model all these basic processes.

Basic process	SCORE coefficient			PROCESSES
Coordinated project	1.000			Potential risk
Coordinated Memory	1.000			Medium risk
Total budget	0.100			Low risk
PROJECT (s)	1.000			No risk
MEMORY (s)	1.000			
COST ESTIMATION (s)	1.000			
TECHNICAL PROJECT, VISA	1.000			
ADDITIONAL: ELEVATORS IN FACADE	0.001			
ADDITIONAL: PROVISIONAL CONTAINERS	0.001			
ADDITIONAL: CRANES	0.001			
ADDITIONAL: SCAFFOLDING AND PLATFORMS	0.001			
ADDITIONAL: PERFORMANCE SOLUTION PROJECT	1.000			
CERTIFIED STUDY OF SAFETY AND HEALTH, WITH	0.010			
BASIC PROJECT CERTIFIED, EXECUTION PROJECT	1.000			
BUILDING LOGBOOK	1.000			
TOPOGRAPHY 1/1000	0.010			
BASIC PROJECT	1.000			

⁴⁵ This means not just the spaces entity, but all entities included in that space and itself.

⁴⁶ These actors would be the project author, the documents registry of the administration and department of the administration auditing or controlling the information. And the additional actor in case of VISA Check would be the professional association.

Fig.7: Basic processes modelled with PROPRES process template and potential privacy risk

Together with the Basic process, other considerations as the entity (container), discipline, timeframe or type of checks should be considered. In the following table, a metric for a final estimation of PROPRES process privacy content can be found, taking into account all these factors. Some examples are calculated as well. The maximum value (1) indicates a potential privacy risk, whereas less than 0.5 could be considered as low risk.

PROPRES metrics for privacy content							
CATEGORY							
Entity (container)	SCORE	Discipline	SCORE	Timeframe	SCORE	Checks	SCORE
Building	0.1	Fire	0.1	Permanent	1.000	Signature	0.1
Common spaces	0.2	Water	1	Real-time device	1.000	VISA	0.1
Apartment	0.5	Electrical	1	weekly	0.100	IDS check	0.1
Bedroom	1	Ventilation	1	monthly	0.050	Code Check	0.5
Storie	0.2	Data	1	annual	0.010	Manual check	1
		Cameras	1	seasonal	0.010		
		Lighting	1				
		Heating	0.5				
		Noise	0.1				
		Contamination	0.1				
		Traffic	0.1				
		Furniture	0.1				
Algorithm:							
PRIVACY ESTIMATOR = BASIC Process coefficient * (entity score * Discipline * TimeFrame * Checks)							
EXAMPLES							PRIVACY ESTIMATOR
coordinated project (detail of bedroom spaces) , with electrical installation /signature check							0.1
coordinated project (detail of bedroom spaces) , with electrical installation / MANUAL check							1
BASIC PROJECT with detail of stories, apartments, all installations / IDS Check							0.05
Project with apartment distribution, furniture and materials quality (sale process)							0.1

Fig.8: METRIC for the estimation of privacy content in PROPRES processes

In case of PROPRES template process and regarding privacy, a possible check list could be:

What is the basic process we are considering (Fig.7: Basic processes modelled with PROPRES process template and potential privacy risk)

Author: Protocol for (1) storage of data, (2) who is accessing the information and (3) how.

Registry: Protocol for (1) storage of data, (2) who is accessing the information and (3) how.

Urban department (or receptor of the project): Protocol for (1) storage of data, (2) who is accessing the information and (3) how.

Professional Association (VISA check): Protocol for (1) storage of data, (2) who is accessing the information and (3) how.

Which types of spaces are affecting the PROPRES process (METRIC Fig.8).

Which disciplines are included in the reports and documents (fire protection, electricity, data, ventilation, ..., METRIC Fig.8).

Which checks are going to be performed and how they are (manual processes, automatic or combined, METRIC Fig.8).

Privacy in Audit and Compliance report (AC_REP)

AC_REP process template is representing a big number of basic processes. All these processes have in common that there is an audit procedure and a compliance problem associated. Some of them may need information presented with the license request (LR integrated process). That information sometimes are complex models about urban regulations, structural codes, energy performance estimations or cost estimations. For these tasks external consultants or experts may be needed.

In AC_REP processes it would be applicable the same privacy metrics used for urban processes and for PROPRES process. But specific protocols must be applied in case of AC_REP processes. Using the same metric than PROPRES, we can set up scores and coefficients for AC_REP basic processes, producing a new metric for AC_REP.

AC_REP AND 3P_REP METRICS for privacy content									
CATEGORY									
Entity (container)	SCORE	Discipline	SCORE	Timeframe	SCORE	Checks	SCORE		
Building	0.1	Fire	0.1	Permanent	1.000	Signature	0.1		
Common spaces	0.2	Water	1	Real-time device	1.000	VISA	0.1		
Apartment	0.5	Electrical	1	weekly	0.100	IDS check	0.1		
Bedroom	1	Ventilation	1	monthly	0.050	Code Check	0.5		
Storie	0.2	Data	1	annual	0.010	Manual check	1		
		Cameras	1	seasonal	0.010				
		Lighting	1						
		Heating	0.5						
		Noise	0.1						
		Contamination	0.1						
		Traffic	0.1						
		Furniture	0.1						
		Gardens	0.1						
		Structural	1						
		Cost	1						
		Algorithm:							
		PRIVACY ESTIMATOR = BASIC Process coefficient * (entity score * Discipline * TimeFrame * Checks)							
EXAMPLES							PRIVACY ESTIMATOR		
Audit of cost estimation of detailed take off of a project							1		
Audit/structural analysis by third party							1		
Audit/coordination of a BIM project elaborated by a third party							1		
Urban viability report, presented by a third party							0.0001		

Fig.9: Privacy metrics evaluation for AC_REP processes

Impact of privacy implementation

In all processes involving some kind of privacy check, an increase of tasks are needed. To study the impact of the implementation using BPMN diagrams gives a precise idea of reliability. In the

following table we can see results of simulation considering the template processes and scenarios.

PROCESS	SCENARIO	NO PRIVACY	WITH PRIVACY	TASK	EXTRA(h)	%
ONURBAN	BASIC	11		16	5	45
	STANDARD	8		10	2	25
	ADVANCED	4		5	1	25
CURBAN	BASIC	186		186	0	0
PUBLIC	BASIC	600		600	0	0
PROPRE	BASIC	362		423.54	61.54	17
	STANDARD	10		11.5	1.5	15
	ADVANCED	3		3.78	0.78	26
AC_REP	BASIC	100		128	28	28
3P_REP	BASIC	50		53	3	6
WINSP	BASIC	38		38	0	0
	ADVANCED	38		38	0	0
ASBUILT	STANDARD	17		18	1	6
COMM	BASIC	95.4		96	0.6	1
	ADVANCED	140		145	5	4

Fig.10: Extra cost expected and process templates, in hours and percentage

We can see that there are two important scenarios where privacy implementation can be causing some delays (BASIC scenarios in both cases). In processes where an intensive flow of documents and data exists, privacy implementation is only feasible using electronic platforms.

Privacy in building permits, risk analysis

The following table there is a summary of risks associated with the implementation of privacy protocols.

item#	Risk description	Mitigation and contingency plans	Probability	Severity	RISK SCORE
ONURBAN, CURBAN process					
5	Building spaces not available	Rejection of ONURBAN request, use of IDS specification	3	5	High
6	Building spaces with no attributes	Rejection of ONURBAN request, use of IDS specification	3	5	High
7	Not enough human resources for checking	Use of external collaborators of administrations	3	5	High
9	No architectural privacy check	Redundancy with PUBLIC information process	5	5	Critical
PUBLIC process					
5	Building spaces not available	Rejection of ONURBAN request, use of IDS specification	3	5	High
6	Building spaces with no attributes	Rejection of ONURBAN request, use of IDS specification	3	5	High
7	Not enough human resources for checking	Use of external collaborators of administrations	3	5	High
9	No architectural privacy check	Redundancy with PUBLIC information process	5	5	Critical
15	Lack of communication campaigning	There is no campaigning of information oriented to close neighborhood. Public target is not contacted in any way	4	5	Critical
16	No good communication	Communication channels with general public are not adequate	4	5	Critical
PROPRE process					
8	Unsecure storage of data at prof. association	Implementation of a secure server or elimination of storage for some of the documents	5	4	Critical
9	Unsecure storage of data at admn	Implementation of security at the storage. Electronic support and digitalization	5	4	Critical
AC_REP process					
2	Complex iterations in design processes	A non stable design process may be producing continuous changes. A project execution management system could avoid these problems, and correct versioning and communication between promoter and external consultant and auditor should improve times	5	3	High
COMM PROCESS					
2	No precise measurement of performance	More precise equipment (temporary). Use of IR technology for thermal footprint. Use of extra equipment for thermal flow.	4	4	High
3	No precise reference to compare performance	Parallel simulation in real-time considering meteorology and occupation	5	5	Critical
4	Uncontrolled data in cloud about performance	In site control of data. Local storage. Local analysis	5	3	High
5	Monitoring problems or non existing monitoring	Temporary portable equipment for measurements	3	5	High

Fig.11: Risk summary table, high and critical risks only

There are 7 critical risks and 10 others evaluated as high. This methodology should be localized in any case, and cannot be used as a general rule for any place.

Conclusions

A complete review of some process templates affected by potential privacy issues have been presented. These processes have been described with detail using BPMN diagrams, performing simulations before privacy implementation. Later, implementation of privacy protocols, the impact calculated in that simulation and a risk analysis have been added.

Privacy metrics tools have been developed (for example, see Fig.8: METRIC for the estimation of privacy content in PROPRE processes). Main risks associated to each process have been analysed, but they must be localized

TECHNOLOGICAL SYSTEM Practice Papers

[An approach to GeoBIM using 3D City Database and BIMServer](#)

Bruno Rienzi^a, Raquel Sosa^a, Laura González^a, Braian De Barros^a, Bruno Ferrando^a, Franco Ferrari^a, Esteban Leopardi^a, Guillermo Maiese^a, Juan Ignacio Medina^a, Enrique Rodriguez^a, Lucas Talín^a, Sebastián Álvarez^a

^a *Facultad de Ingeniería, Universidad de la República, Montevideo, Uruguay*

GeoBIM combines the capabilities of Geographic Information Systems (GIS), which deal with spatial data and mapping, with Building Information Modeling (BIM) [1], which focuses on the digital representation of physical and non physical characteristics of buildings. By integrating these two technologies, Geo-BIM enables a more comprehensive understanding of the built environment, providing insights into both the spatial and building domains, particularly in areas such as urban planning, infrastructure development, construction projects, and facility management [2][3].

The advantages of incorporating spatial information into BIM projects are twofold. Firstly, it enables the assessment of compliance with specific construction regulations that involve using spatial information from the environment, especially in the field of the Digital Building Permit (DBP) [4]. For example, the calculation of whether the building adheres to the Floor Area Ratio (FAR) can be achieved by utilising a cadastral layer. Secondly, various analyses regarding how the building impacts the surroundings (e.g. a large building in a small residential area can increase traffic, block sunlight, etc.) and vice versa (e.g. a skyscraper built near the seashore is prone to suffer the corrosive effects of saltwater) can be performed [2].

In the majority of studies, GeoBIM involves the transformation of BIM models (IFC [5] files) to CityGML [6] files [7][8][9]. These transformations are mainly performed by desktop applications (e.g. FME [10]) [2][7][8]. However, an alternative approach in which transformations are unnecessary can be followed in some cases that involve the use of both models. Following this approach, a POC was developed, in which the CityGML models are stored in 3D City Database [11] and BIM models are stored in BIMServer [12]. An intermediary software module, implemented in Python, was responsible for retrieving the data from both sources and performing calculations combining spatial and BIM data.

A LOD-1 CityGML model is used to represent a city block, where each parcel is represented by a prism. The base of the prism corresponds to the parcel area, and its height is the maximum allowed construction height on that parcel. Therefore, the Building objects in this model do not represent existing buildings but rather a Maximum Bounding Volume (MBV) within which a real building can be constructed.

The software module retrieves georeferenced building models from BIMServer and the city block model from 3D City DB. Then the following calculations are performed: containment of the building within an MBV, percentage of the parcel area that building occupies, and difference between the height of the building and the height of the MBV.

The POC was carried out by students as part of an undergraduate course on GIS, and it enabled compliance control of some of the construction regulations addressed by the Open DBP Platform proposed in our previous work [13] (e.g. in regulations involving the Floor Area Ratio, Maximum Allowed Height and Front Setback). This presentation displays the details of this work, along with the conclusions and recommendations obtained from both the approach and the tools used.

References

- [1] International Organization for Standardization (ISO), ISO 19650-1:2018. Organization and digitization of information about buildings and civil engineering works, including building information modelling (BIM). Information management using building information modelling. Part 1: Concepts and principles, International Standard (2018). URL <https://www.iso.org/standard/68078.html>
- [2] F. Noardo, D. Guler, J. Fauth, G. Malacarne, S. Mastrolembo Ventura, M. Azenha, P.O. Olsson, L. Senger, Unveiling the actual progress of digital building permit: Getting awareness through a critical state of the art review, *Building and Environment* 213 (2022) 108854. doi:10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.108854.
- [3] X. Liu, X. Wang, G. Wright, J. Cheng, X. Li, R. Liu, A state-of-the-art review on the integration of building information modeling (bim) and geographic information system (gis), *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information* 6 (2017) 53. doi: 10.3390/ijgi6020053.
- [4] F. Noardo, G. Malacarne, Digital Building Permit: A State of Play – I EUnet4DBP International Workshop on Digital Building Permit, Technical report, EUnet4DBP (2021).
- [5] Industry Foundation Classes (IFC) - ISO 16739-1:2018 (2018).
URL <https://www.iso.org/standard/70303.html>
- [6] OGC, CityGML.
URL <https://www.ogc.org/standards/citygml>
- [7] M. Mandrile, BIM as multiscale facilitator for built environment analysis, Master's thesis, Univerza v Ljubljani (2020).
- [8] R. Eriksson, P. Johansson, T. Olsson, K. Andersson, K. Engvall, A. Hast, L. Harrie, Requirements, development, and evaluation of a national building standard—a swedish case study, *ISPRS International Journal of Geo-Information* 9 (2) (2020).
- [9] S. Chognard, A. Dubois, Y. Benmansour, E. Torri, B. Domer, Digital construction permit: A round trip between gis and ifc, in: *Advanced Computing Strategies for Engineering*, Springer, Cham, 2018, pp. 287–306.
- [10] SAFE Software, FME.
URL <https://fme.safe.com/>
- [11] 3D City Database, 3D City Database.
URL <https://github.com/3dcitydb/>
- [12] BIMServer, BIMServer.
URL <https://github.com/opensourceBIM/BIMserver>
- [13] L. González, B. Rienzi, R. Sosa, V. Cornelius, M. O'Neil, L. Navickis, E. González, G. Guimerans, J. Cortés, F. Ponzoni, F. Álvarez, A. Nebel, S. Cotto, Y. Aguiar, M. Calcagno, M. Riva, F. Reale, B. Puerta, E. Rodríguez, C. Viñas, I. Turcatti, G. Díaz, G. Agresta, J. J. Prada, M. E. Corti, Á. Rettich, Á. Marques, L. Juambeltz, J. González, An Open and Standards-based Approach for the Digital Building Permit in Montevideo, in: T. P. Sales, S. de Kinderen, H. A. Proper, L. Pufahl, D. Karastoyanova, M. van Sinderen (Eds.), *Enterprise Design, Operations, and Computing. EDOC 2023 Workshops*, Springer Nature Switzerland, Cham, 2024, pp. 60–76.

ACABIM: Open Compliance Audit for New Zealand Regulations

Robert Amor^a, Johannes Dimyadi^b

^a School of Computer Science, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand

^b CAS Ltd, Auckland, New Zealand

The ACABIM Automated Code Compliance Checker (ACCC) has been developed from over a decade of research and development activity. Its primary goal is to support Building Consent Authorities (BCA) in New Zealand to assess building designs against the applicable codes and standards, and hence provide the regulatory consent to enable a design to progress to the construction phase. ACABIM has been developed with an open standard approach to the provision of information for ACCC. In particular it supports:

- The ISO 16739 open BIM standard IFC (Industry Foundation Classes) that represents a building, its geometry and components, and the relationships between those components.
- The OASIS Open Standard LegalRuleML (LRML) that represents formal features specific to legal norms, guidelines, policies and reasoning.
- The OMG Standard BPMN (Business Process Model and Notation) that represents the design checking process that a BCA would use for its formal compliance audit process.

ACABIM exists as a cloud-based service with a well defined API that enables integration with the consenting tools and workflows which exist within a BCA. The system follows a human-guided philosophy for its consenting workflow, which is well suited to New Zealand's performance-based codes. In the human-guided approach, the BPMN process supports full automation for parts of the codes which are easily computable. In New Zealand this is the majority of the Acceptable Solutions (AS) which are offered for each performance-based code. ACABIM provides interfaces to existing simulation and calculation methods and can use the supplied BIM model to populate the input file for these tools. These simulation and calculation methods often support the Verification Methods (VM) which are specified to demonstrate compliance with performance-based objectives. ACABIM also enables expert engineers to be brought into the consenting process to provide judgement for other performance-based provisions that exist within the codes.

Working with a beta-customer of one of New Zealand's largest cities (Christchurch City Council), the ACABIM system now has access to a set of 15 priority national codes that have been translated into LRML and audit processes that the council uses in its day-to-day consenting activities. Using BIM models from large commercial and smaller residential designs, they were able to determine the time and cost savings that would accrue with even this small number of codes (there are approximately 600 applicable codes and standards used for consenting in New Zealand).

This presentation will demonstrate the ACABIM system performing audits on a range of significant BIM models from Christchurch City Council for consenting checks that are able to be fully automated, as well as checks that require the utilisation of simulation tools.

Enhancing Smart Cities through Semantic Planning Law Data – The ACCORD-project and the Berlin TXL Use-Case

Kai-Uwe Krause^a, Stefan Höffken^b, Katja Breitenfelder^c, Konstantin Schneider^b, Hülya Lasch^a

^a Agency for Geoinformation and Surveying / Coordination Office for Semantic Standardisation, Neuenfelder Straße 19, 21109 Hamburg

^b Tegel Projekt GmbH / Team Smart Cities/FUTR HUB, Flughafen Tegel 1, 13405 Berlin

^c Fraunhofer Institute for Building Physics IBP / Project- and business development, Fraunhoferstraße 10, 83626 Valley

This presentation provides a concise overview of the ACCORD Project (<https://accordproject.eu>), focusing on land use permitting at Berlin TXL and the deployment of planning regulations in XPlanung/INSPIRE PLU Notation via OGC-standards as a use case. XPlanung is an XML-based machine-readable standard for spatial planning data, being developed in Germany, that supports a faster exchange of planning data between planners, planning authorities and other stakeholders. In the Use-Case Berlin TXL is collaborating with Fraunhofer IBP, and LGV Hamburg, who are the technical leads and developing the XPlanung/INSPIRE PLU Notation.

Fig. 1: Planning of the development of the Urban Tech Republic.

In the first half of the presentation we are illustrating the advantages of planning regulation compliance facilitated by XPlanung and the regulations' pivotal role in the context of Smart Cities. It delves into the ways in which XPlanung serves as a cornerstone for effective urban planning, fosters intelligent & data-driven decision-making processes and monitors the development of sustainable cities.

The presentation also explores the deployment of planning regulations in XPlanung/INSPIRE PLU Notation, employing cutting-edge OGC web technologies and services (OGC APIs). The integration of these advanced tools enhances the accessibility and usability of planning data,

contributing to more efficient and collaborative urban planning practices. This paper gives an overview of current research results, presenting examples, technical frameworks and key findings.

Overall, the presentation provides a snapshot of how the Accord Project, is developing solutions for the smart cities of tomorrow, by integrating innovative frameworks and state-of-the-art technologies for sustainable urban development.

Fig. 2: Actual intended process and workflow.

The development plans’ regulations are either in force or in the process of being drawn up for the Tegel-Projekt GmbH project area and contain both graphic and textual descriptions. The regulations are encoded in the XPlanung data model in the INSPIRE Planned Land Use (PLU) data model and in the CityGML data model via an Open GIS-compliant Open Api for Features (OAF) web service. The XPlanung data model is legally valid in Germany. In addition to existing GML schema files, JSON-FG schema files were generated based on the UML XPlanung and INSPIRE PLU data models. The graphical and textual regulations can be provided in the three data models in different encodings (GML, JSON-FG, CityJSON) via OAF services.

Checking of Urban Planning Regulations with GeoSPARQL and BIM SPARQL

Vladimir Alexiev^a, Nataliya Keberle^a

^a *Ontotext AD, 79, Nikola Gabrovski Str. Twins Centre, fl.3, Sofia 1700, Bulgaria.*

The former Berlin Tegel airport (TXL) will be the site of a university campus (refurbished airport terminal), startups, production facilities (“tech republic”), a living quarter, stores, smart mobility hubs, park and recreation areas, etc. The Tegel Project company (owned by the City of Berlin) has developed detailed urban planning and regulations covering built area use, height restrictions, noise protection, floor space index (buildup density), greenery requirements (vegetation and habitats), etc.

The regulations are expressed in Xplanung [1] and INSPIRE PLU [2]. These are GML-based UML and XML models for urban planning: Xplanung is Germany-specific and PLU (Planned Land Use) is part of the INSPIRE initiative. Building designs are expressed in IFC and include simple geometries (for residential buildings) and complex geometries (for the university campus).

Compliance checking of urban planning requires accessing two different kinds of data in a harmonized way: BIM (building information) and GIS (also called CIM “city information management” and often represented using GML extension schemas). As part of the Horizon Europe ACCORD project [3], we plan to do this checking using SPARQL in Ontotext GraphDB [4]. GIS data is covered by the existing GeoSPARQL plugin that supports WKT and GML geometries. BIM data can either be converted to GIS/GML using already developed approaches, or accessed through a future Binary Engineering Data connector for GraphDB based on the HDF5 format.

We give an overview of Xplanung, INSPIRE PLU, CityGML and GeoSPARQL 1.0 and 1.1. Then we describe the semantic conversion of Xplanung / INSPIRE PLU data, our approach regarding semantization of BIM data, the overall structure of regulations, the respective geometric and non-geometric checks to be implemented, the use of GeoSPARQL topological relations to leverage planning zone hierarchies and to check which buildings fall in which zones, potential specialized BIM SPARQL functions to be implemented, management of multiple BIM files that need to be checked in concert, and result creation and content.

References

- [1] Xplanung. URL: <https://xleitstelle.de/xplanung> .
- [2] INSPIRE - Infrastructure for Spatial Information in Europe: Planned Land Use. URL: <https://inspire.ec.europa.eu/applicationschema/plu> .
- [3] ACCORD - Automated Compliance Checks for Construction, Renovation or Demolition Works, funded by European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101056973. URL: <https://accordproject.eu>.
- [4] Ontotext GraphDB. URL: <https://www.ontotext.com/products/graphdb/> .

Building Permit Management Data Space

Gonzalo Gil^a, Francisco Javier Diez^a, Ricardo Romero^a, Ignacio Lazaro^a

^a*Tekniker, Basque Research and Technology Alliance (BRTA), C/ Iñaki Goenaga 5, 20600 Eibar, Spain*

Following the path for the digital transformation of the construction industry [1] and considering the DigiPLACE Reference Architecture Framework [2], the DigiChecks Horizon Europe project⁴⁷ designs the DigiChecks Framework, a modular and scalable approach to automate the management of building permits and compliance checks that builds on the DigiChecks Data Space, an open and distributed infrastructure for interoperable, trusted, and sovereign data sharing between the platforms of different stakeholders.

The management of building permits is made up of many processes involving many actors that include companies and public authorities of many different types. To complete these processes, different actors in the role of data providers need to make their data available for others in the role of data consumers for different processing purposes. In this regard, coordination issues should be tackled by combining data stored in different proprietary formats [3]. Also, this data may in many cases contain sensitive data or intellectual property that actors do not wish to make public. In this context, the DigiChecks Data Space offers a framework to not only discover, but also, negotiate and transfer data in an interoperable manner while preserving data sovereignty [4].

Considering the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) and GAIA-X as the reference initiatives currently working on the definition and design of the building blocks required to build a data space [5], Figure 1 represents the DigiChecks Data Space which is based on the GAIA-X Technical Architecture [6] and the IDSA Reference Architecture Model (RAM) [7].

The GAIA-X Technical Architecture, consisting of the GAIA-X Digital Clearing House, the Credential Manager, and the Federated Catalogue, provides a governance framework within the DigiChecks Data Space. This governance framework relies on the novel approach for the self-management of identities denoted as Self-Sovereign Identity (SSI) that is based on the W3C specifications of Decentralized Identifiers⁴⁸ and Verifiable Credentials⁴⁹. The GAIA-X Digital Clearing House exposes a node for the certification of the participants and the services they expose according to European principles of digital sovereignty. For the case of the management of permits, this certification scheme can be enriched with additional certification mechanisms for compliance check services to ensure that those compliance checks services that are deployed within the DigiChecks Data Space are correctly performed and respected. The Credential Manager abstracts end users from the technical complexity that the certification scheme and the management of Verifiable Credentials have. The Federated Catalogue provides a centralized repository of the certified services that the participants within the DigiChecks Data Space provide.

The IDSA RAM, provides the framework for interoperable, trusted, and sovereign data sharing between the platforms of the different stakeholders. IDS Connectors ensure interoperable discovery, negotiation and access of the data based on the Dataspace protocol⁵⁰, trust based on Dynamic Attribute Tokens issued following the SSI approach by the Dynamic Attribute

⁴⁷ [DigiChecks – A European Project to develop a new Digital Framework to manage permits and compliance checks in the construction industry](#)

⁴⁸ [Decentralized Identifiers \(DIDs\) v1.0 \(w3.org\)](#)

⁴⁹ [Verifiable Credentials Data Model v2.0 \(w3.org\)](#)

⁵⁰ [Dataspace Protocol - Working Draft - IDS Knowledge Base \(internationaldataspaces.org\)](#)

Provisioning Service describing security properties related to the IDS Connector and data sovereignty through distributed usage control [8]. The Vocabulary Provider allows the use of a common semantics of the data. The Clearing House allows the traceability of data usage.

Fig. 1: DigiChecks Data Space.

It is worth mentioning that this data space approach is combined with a process execution engine that allows any permission management process to be defined and executed using the federated services within the DigiChecks Data Space. Furthermore, it could be applied to other processes in the construction value chain.

References

- [1] M. Buhler, K. Nübel, T. Jelinek, D. Riechert, T. Bauer, T. Schmid, M. Schneider: *Data cooperatives as catalyst for collaboration, data sharing and the digital transformation of the construction industry*, Buildings (2023) 13(2):442. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13020442>
- [2] A. David, A. Zarli, C. Mirarchi, N. Naville, L. Perisich: *DigiPLACE: Towards a reference architecture framework for digital platforms in the EU construction*, eWork and eBusiness in Architecture, Engineering and Construction (2021) 511-518. <https://doi.org/10.1201/9781003191476-69>.
- [3] Y. Rezgui, J. Miles: *Harvesting and Managing Knowledge in Construction*, Construction Management and Economics (2012) 30(1):95-97. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01446193.2011.651482>.
- [4] M. Jarke, B. Otto, S. Ram: *Data Sovereignty and Data Space Ecosystems*, Business and Information Systems Engineering (2019) 61(5):549-550. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12599-019-00614-2>.
- [5] L. Nagel, D. Lycklama: *Design Principles for Data Spaces – Position Paper (1.0)* (2021). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5105744>.
- [6] International Data Spaces Association: *IDS Reference Architecture Model 4.0* (2023).
- [7] GAIA-X European Association for Data and Cloud: *GAIA-X Architecture Document* (2022).
- [8] G. Gil, A. Arnaiz, M. Higuero, F.J. Diez: *Assessment Framework for the Identification and Evaluation of the Main Features for Distributed Usage Control Solutions*, ACM Transactions on Privacy and

Security (2022) 26(1):1-28. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3561511>.

CYPEURBAN and BIMserver.center: Lessons learned in the digitalization of the Building Permit

Ane Ferreira Sistiaga ^a, Pablo Gilabert Boronat ^a

^a CYPE Software, Av. Loring,5, 03003, Alicante, Spain

Introduction

Tracing the journey from the inception of CYPEURBAN and BIMserver.center in 2016 to its recent involvement in European initiatives, the objective is to highlight lessons learned in the digitalization of building permits from the collaborations with municipalities, architects and real estate developers, including success stories in Rivas Vaciamadrid and Madrid. The discussion encompasses the continuous evolution of the tools, the introduction of new features and its adaptability to diverse urban contexts providing valuable insights for future endeavours.

Urban planning licenses, vital for ensuring the quality and orderly development of cities, undergo a paradigm shift in their acquisition process. The traditional analog review of project documentation, a laborious process known to industry professionals, becomes the focal point for improvement. This session explores the challenges posed by the current manual and paper-based permitting system, emphasizing the need for streamlined processes and efficient management.

Fig. 1: CYPEURBAN

Our Vision for a Digital Urban Permit:

With a rich history of 40 years in software development for architecture, engineering, and construction, CYPE commitment to normative justification, as evidenced by the implementation of over 400 regulations across 52 countries, which positions the company as a key player in aligning with local urban planning requirements.

CYPE proposal involves in its core idea the early project reviews by architects using digital models, ensuring that projects submitted to the public administration comply with regulatory requirements. The comprehensive solution integrates the BIMserver.center platform for project management and visualization, along with CYPEURBAN for normative review. Emphasizing open formats, BIM-GIS integration, and cost-free access for project developers, the proposal aims to facilitate a seamless collaboration between the administration and the industry.

Our Experience in developing DBP solutions:

Following the path from the launch of CYPEURBAN in 2017 to its recent engagement in European projects, the conference emphasizes insights gained through collaborations with municipalities. This includes notable achievements in Rivas Vaciamadrid and Madrid. The conversation covers the ongoing development of the tool, the incorporation of innovative features, and its ability to adjust to various urban settings.

CHEK technology architecture: achieving interoperability for a modular approach

Ane Ferreiro Sistiaga^a, Pablo Gilabert Boronat^a

^a CYPE Software, Av. Loring,5, 03003, Alicante, Spain

Introduction

This presentation introduces a forward-looking software architecture proposed in CHEK project for the Digital Building Permit Process, catering to the needs of its diverse group of stakeholders (designers, municipalities, construction companies...) and strategically crafted to enhance collaboration among software development companies. At the core of this architecture lies the integration of specialized tools for municipalities/public administrations and construction industry professionals. The architecture of the system, rooted in the intricate process maps of the current building permit procedures described by municipalities, not only streamlines urban planning compliance but also nurtures collaboration among developers, fostering innovation, scalability and adaptability, harnessing collaborative software development, open formats, and DBP process mapping. Rooted in the need for scalability and inclusivity, the architecture brings together the expertise of diverse software developers from across Europe to address the complex challenges posed by varied urban licensing procedures.

An architecture for the DBP process maps:

The software architecture of CHEK is designed to align with the process maps of the current building permit procedures as described by our partner municipalities. By mapping and understanding the intricacies of these existing processes, the system wants to ensure the transition to digital workflows.

Fig. 1: Simplified graph of CHEK Technology Architecture.

Software modularity and open formats:

The existence of multiple software developers, each contributing unique perspectives and solutions, is poised to be a driver in achieving scalability and ensuring the widespread adoption of digital urban licensing solutions. The diverse expertise, innovation, and regional insights brought by developers from different parts of Europe create a robust foundation for addressing the intricacies of urban licensing requirements, promoting adaptability to varied regulatory frameworks.

Furthermore, the integration of open formats within the architecture, such as IFC, CityJSON, and OGC standards, plays a pivotal role in enhancing scalability. The system ensures interoperability, data exchange, and integration of tools developed by various contributors. The use of open formats not only promotes transparency but also facilitates the integration of new modules and functionalities, providing a future-proof solution adaptable to evolving urban challenges.

Open collaborative platform – BIMserver.center

A key enabler within the architecture is the integration of the BIMserver.center platform. This open and collaborative platform serves as a hub for software developers, offering an API REST and BIMserver.center Developers module. BIMserver.center will enable the exchange of information between architects/studios and public administration. This exchange will take place through the BIMserver.center Validation module, specially designed for the management of permits by municipal corporations.

Fig. 2: BIMserver.center Developers

Enabling BIM in Building Permitting: The Critical Role of the Permitting Platform

Ilkka Mattila

Cloudpermit, Salomonkatu 17A, 00100 Helsinki, Finland

In the realm of construction and urban planning, Building Information Modeling (BIM) has emerged as a pivotal technology for automating and significantly enhancing productivity in building permitting processes. This technology promises not only swifter processing times but also superior quality in result verification. BIM also fosters improved communication and understanding among various stakeholders by offering interactive 3D plan visualizations.

The introduction of specialized BIM-based tools – such as model checkers, GIS/city model viewers, 4D simulations, and Life-Cycle Assessment (LCA) calculators – into the permitting process is central to realizing these benefits. However, the full potential of BIM cannot be unleashed without addressing certain challenges. A significant hurdle is the need for manual data transfer between systems, reliance on traditional communication methods like emails, and the time-intensive tasks of tracking application statuses and searching the information. To overcome these obstacles, the introduction of the permitting platform is imperative.

Using BIM in permitting does not remove the need for records management and digital archives, but the opposite. As we rely more on data, AI, and automation, the necessity for precise documentation and archiving of each decision grows exponentially. All information collected and generated throughout the permitting process must be systematically and centrally stored and archived in the platform.

The advent of fully digital permitting platforms, such as Cloudpermit, marks a significant advancement. These platforms are not only comprehensive in their information provision for decision-making but also ensure integration with local, regional, and federal information systems and data repositories, including GIS, cadasters, city models, and zoning data. For users, these platforms offer a range of functionalities, including payment processing, circulation, review, communication, inspections. The paperless processes pave the way for step-by-step automation, transforming the application process towards a self-service model with BIM. Permitting platforms are set to revolutionize the application process by enabling applicants to submit plans already checked for zoning and code compliance, thereby reducing the workload on authorities and expediting processing times.

However, for such a digital transformation to be effective, clear definitions and frameworks are essential. The EU ACCORD project is at the forefront of defining the digital permitting process and its components, as well as outlining the interactions and roles within. It is crucial for the further development, adoption of the new process as well as for the procurement to distinguish between the permitting platform, which hosts the permitting processes, and the individual BIM-enabled components responsible for automated steps in the process.

AI-supported, automatic document checking for digital submission and processing of building applications in Germany

Alexandra Nestorowicz^a, Julian Graefenstein^a, Jan Winkels^a, Lisa Lenz^a

^a *Building Information Cloud GLWG GmbH, Fliederweg 1, 92318 Neumarkt*

Introduction

The approval process is crucial for construction projects in Europe, with varying regulations across member states. Efficient navigation through this complexity significantly influences project success. In Germany, the average building permit procedure takes 96 days, due to the limited digitalization in permit authorities, causing delays and inquiries [1]. Our AI-supported approach in Germany aims to automatically check documents for completeness and conformity with local laws, addressing the challenges posed by the intricate application forms.

Status of digitalization for building applications in Germany

On average the building permit procedure in Germany takes 96 days.[2]

One of the inherent reasons for this situation is the lack of digitalization in German building permit authorities. The digitalization of building permit procedures currently leans heavily towards conventional methods, involving manual scrutiny of plans. Consequently, delays and individual inquiries are unavoidable. The lengthy approval procedures are perceived as a deterrent to the swift construction of new housing.[2]

The legal aspects surrounding building permits are encompassed by public building law. Within the German administrative hierarchy, building supervisory authorities are categorized as top, upper, and lower levels. Their primary responsibility lies in ensuring adherence to building regulations. The lower building supervisory authority plays a crucial role in examining building applications and granting building permits. These lower authorities are strategically located within districts and independent cities.[3]

To submit a building application in Germany, a state-specific application form must be completed and submitted by post in paper form or, in exceptional cases, digitally as a pdf file to the relevant building permit authority. The building application form differs in the level of detail and content for each federal state. This is due to the different building regulations of the individual federal states in Germany.

In some cases, the building application forms are overly complex and can only be filled out with the help of numerous legal texts. Not only does the completion of the building application tend to be prone to errors due to the elevated level of complexity, but the project-specific attachments to be included with the building application, such as design drawings, building specifications, expert opinions, etc., are often incorrectly or incompletely prepared and submitted to the building permit authority. As a result, the building application is sent back to the submitting person with subsequent requests for (missing) documents and information and the processing time is extended again.

At the international level, there are many examples of digital solutions in building permits. The successful and phased implementation of computer-assisted verification for all construction projects in Singapore is an example for that. The related advantages are associated with the

standardization of legal interpretation and the corresponding review procedures. This is one of the reasons that shortens the building approval process in Singapore to an average of 14 days.[4] Although there are already some federal states in Germany where a building application can be submitted in electronic form and this is even mandatory in Berlin. This example, only includes the transmission of the data and not its further processing, e.g. the checking of the documents.

Concept of document-based checking rules for building applications in Germany

To limit the errors when submitting building applications in Germany and thus contribute to faster approval of buildings, the Building Information Cloud GLWG GmbH has developed a building application form tool (BAF tool) on its Software-as-a-Service platform.

This ensures guided completion of the building application form with information texts, links to official legal texts and the consistent presentation of the interdependent fields to be filled out. For example, specific information to be provided in the building application depends on the building class of the project. The platform not only provides support in determining the correct building class, but also ensures the associated information, for example on fire protection concepts of the building. In principle, the consistent completion of the building application is enforced depending on the information provided. After completing the building application, users will also be asked to upload the corresponding project-specific attachments such as floor plans, sections, views, expert opinions, building descriptions, cost calculations, etc. These are then automatically checked for completeness on the platform.

The checking of construction project documents is based on the service phases of the HOAI, the German fee structure for architects and engineers, as well as further federal state-specific regulations. The completeness checking of the project documents happens through text and image analysis. At this point, the contents of the construction project documents are checked based on legal requirements, DIN standards and further guidelines.

For the checking rules, all 16 federal states were screened, corresponding systems were identified from the building application forms and the related word pool was determined with the help of literature research of the relevant legal texts of the federal states and comparison with real building project documents. Once the documents have been checked and the corresponding detailed feedback on missing or incorrect information within the documents has been provided, the user has a direct recommendation for action to correct errors before submitting the building application to the building permit authority.

This preliminary check of the building project documents can prevent lengthy subsequent requests for documents and support the time-consuming and error-prone manual checking processes at the building permit authority, making the building approval process both simpler and more efficient. In the following section, the technical implementation of these checking rules will be explained.

Technical Implementation

For the automated checking of planning data provided by the user, a text analysis based on artificial intelligence (AI) is used, among other methods. Such text analysis AI is typically a cloud-based service that processes natural language from unformatted text into machine-readable software. These AIs typically rely on neural networks and offer various functions such as sentiment analysis, keyword recognition, named entity recognition, and language detection. The neural networks, are computational models inspired by the structure and function of the human brain. Neural networks consist of interconnected nodes or neurons organized in layers. Through a process called training, these networks learn to recognize patterns and relationships within the text data. [5, 6]

AI-driven text analysis typically begins with preprocessing steps such as tokenization, where the text is divided into individual words or tokens, and normalization, where variations in spelling or formatting are standardized. Following preprocessing, the AI model utilizes various techniques to extract meaningful information from the text. The Keyword recognition processes any text and returns a list of keywords for each dataset that reflect the content of the text. In the case of named entity recognition, different entities in unstructured text can be identified and categorized, such as automatically identifying individuals or organizations in the text. To achieve this, specific validation rules for each requirement of the application process were designed, which expect certain keywords in specific combinations to assess a requirement as fulfilled. Figure 1 shows the exemplary structure of a test rule in which different logically linked sets of words must be found from different word groups. The rules are structured in a tree-like format, where each requirement is broken down into individual parts and evaluated separately. At each level of the tree, there is a collection of keywords, and a certain number of words from each collection must be present in the document being analyzed for that part of the tree to be accepted. If enough subtrees are fulfilled, the entire requirement is considered fulfilled.

As a result, an automated examination of the planning documents for compliance with HOAI can be conducted. Our checking rules and keyword catalogs are also constantly being refined and further developed. At the current technical level, however, we can check and recognize the completeness of documents of HOAI service phases 1 to 5. This includes the documents for the building permit process (service phase 4). Numerous practice partners are currently evaluating the quality of our audits.

Fig. 1: exemplary structure of a test rule

Conclusion and Outlook

The current tense situation in the construction industry in Germany can be described as challenging. On the one hand, construction projects must be completed as efficiently as possible to be profitable in the current demanding situation in the industry; on the other hand, the approval authorities are increasingly slowing down the process with slow working methods due to a lack of personnel and digital tools to relieve the burden. Digital tools combined with AI methods offer enormous potential to counteract the complexity of regulations and the sluggish building permit process. The approach presented of an already available cloud solution for the automated review of application documents shows a considerable time advantage in the review process.

This approach also offers the potential to function beyond German frameworks and regulations, as the respective specifications can be quickly added as new inspection rule sets. The current direction in the EU is towards a unified standard in the digital building model, which makes it possible to exchange models and information across countries, to plan and work together more

efficiently. The IFC standard suitable for this and our approach are already capable of dealing with these kinds of data as well.

Looking ahead, continued research and development efforts should focus on expanding the scope of document types and service phases covered by the automated checking system, as well as enhancing its adaptability to evolving regulatory frameworks and industry standards. Furthermore, integrating feedback mechanisms to solicit input from end-users and stakeholders will be vital for ensuring the relevance and usability of the system in practice. Overall this concept exemplifies the transformative potential of AI in streamlining regulatory compliance processes within the construction industry, with implications for improved efficiency, accuracy, and transparency in project management.

References

- [1] Der digitale Bauantrag - vom Wunsch zur Wirklichkeit? (o. D.). <https://blog.nemetschek.com/de-de/themen-und-insights/digitaler-bauantrag>, last visited: 06.12.2023.
- [2] Berger (2018): Schnellere Baugenehmigungen mit BIM, v. Fokus, online: <https://www.springer-professional.de/baugenehmigung/building-information-modeling/schnellere-baugenehmigungen-mit-bim/15357120>, last visited: 06.12.2023.
- [3] Fauth (2021): Ein handlungsorientiertes Entscheidungsmodell zur Feststellung der Genehmigungsfähigkeit von Bauvorhaben, S. 53, Weimar.
- [4] Doing Business 2020, p. 12, online: <https://www.doingbusiness.org/content/dam/doingBusiness/country/s/singapore/SGP.pdf>, last visited: 06.12.2023.
- [5] Hegghammer, T. (2022). OCR with Tesseract, Amazon Textract, and Google Document AI: a benchmarking experiment. *Journal of Computational Social Science*, 5(1), 861-882.
- [6] Ustenko, S., & Ostapovych, T. (2023). Amazon Textract and artificial intelligence system at banking document management system. *Artificial intelligence*, (1), 13-28.

AI in compliance for the built environment

Max van Riel

Struck, Ceramiquelaan 361 1031 KG, Amsterdam Netherlands

Background

Compliance and permitting procedures - one of the top three root causes behind project delays, lower than expected financial returns, and consequently fewer new houses built and refurbished.

However, neglecting regulatory compliance leads to even greater risks: financial losses for developers and homeowners, legal liabilities for architects, and reputational risks for municipalities.

STRUCK exists to break this deadlock that slows down the entire EU AEC industry and to help resolving housing, economic and environmental crises.

Problem

Construction compliance in EU requires adherence to extensive regulations across EU, national, regional, and municipal levels, comprising tens of thousands of pages that are regularly updated. Finding the latest versions of these documents is challenging. Additionally, the documents can sometimes contradict or complement each other, making interpretation and cross-referencing complex and often dependent on specific municipal precedents. As a result:

- Developers worry that compliance and permitting procedures will significantly increase project costs and timelines.
- Architects are concerned about legal liabilities for compliance failures, engage various external consultants for assurance, leading to cost increase and delays.
- Municipalities doubt the completeness of submissions, but lack the resources to thoroughly review all projects.
- Homeowners are uncertain about what they can build on their plot and struggle to identify reliable sources of information.

Solution

STRUCK is an AI-assisted compliance platform for the entire AEC industry, designed to help stakeholders reduce costs, time, and risks/uncertainty in preparing and submitting documents for zoning, construction, environmental, and other permits. It offers the following features:

- Searches for the most updated regulatory documents and data sets applicable to a project based on its address.
- Automatically analyzes design drawings for compliance as early as possible without waiting for the detailed design to be complete
- Accumulates knowledge within your company.
- Facilitates collaboration on preparing permit application packages and submitting projects online.

Leading, most complete and updated, EU-wide compliance platform ensuring a 90%+ first-time right submission rate (either in a stand-alone form or as a plug-in for the most popular design tools)

Use of Augmented Reality in the openBIM building authority process

Harald Urban^a, Konstantin Höbart^a, Simon Fischer^a, Christian Schranz^a

^a Research Unit Digital Building Process, TU Wien, 1040 Vienna, Austria

Digital transformation has reached the construction industry and requires consideration of all lifecycle phases. The widespread use of BIM paves the way for Construction 4.0. However, the use of BIM in the approval process of building authorities has been little explored. In the European research project BRISE-Vienna an openBIM approval process was developed for the City of Vienna. This enables model-based submission, checking, and review. The models are also available for other use cases and technologies within the authority. This presentation will focus on augmented reality (AR) and openBIM in the building authority.

In Vienna, the analogous process takes up to 18 months. This long duration hinders progress in the construction industry. One reason for this are objections from non-specialists who have difficulty understanding the project from the 2D plans alone. Therefore, the City of Vienna redesigned the building authority processes in the research project BRISE-Vienna using BIM [1] and augmented reality.

This presentation explores possible applications of openBIM and augmented reality for building authorities. Augmented reality can be used at the interface between public authorities and stakeholders to speed up processes through better communication. For the City of Vienna, 12 augmented reality use cases [2] were developed based on process analyses and expert interviews. In addition to the conception of the augmented reality use cases for public authorities, a study was conducted on their benefits and feasibility. The use cases have the potential to increase the understanding of the project for both experts and non-experts.

The best rated augmented reality use cases, plan checking and hearing during the permission, were developed, implemented, and evaluated in the BRISE-Vienna project [3]. The presentation will show that especially the plan check process and hearings in the approval process can be improved and accelerated by combining BIM and the visualization technology of AR. In the plan check process, AR can support the building authority in checking the compliance with building regulations. Additionally, during the hearing process, AR helps non-experts to visualise and grasp the impact of the planned project [4] and allows for better judgement.

The presentation shows the results of two test groups - plan check process and hearings in the approval process in 2D and with openBIM and augmented reality - and ends with a conclusion and outlook.

References

- [1] Krischmann, T., H. Urban, and C. Schranz (2020). “Entwicklung eines openBIM-Bewilligungsverfahrens”. In: Bauingenieur 95(9), pp. 335–344. doi: 10.37544/0005-6650-2020-09-61
- [2] Gerger, A., Urban, H., & Schranz, C. (2023). Augmented Reality for Building Authorities: A Use Case Study in Austria. Buildings, 13(6), Article 1462. <https://doi.org/10.3390/buildings13061462>
- [3] Schranz, C., H. Urban, and A. Gerger (July 26, 2021). “Potentials of Augmented Reality in a BIM Based Building Submission Process”. In: Journal of Information Technology in Construction 26, pp.

441–457. doi: 10.36680/j.itcon.2021.024.

- [4] Urban, H., G. Pelikan, and C. Schranz (Mar. 22, 2022). “Augmented Reality in AEC Education: A Case Study”. In: Buildings 12.4, p. 391. doi: 10.3390/buildings12040391.

COUNTRY-SPECIFIC EXPERIENCES

Germany's Digital Building Application as a Trailblazing Guarantee for Accelerated Planning and Implementation of Nationwide Construction Projects

Christoph Vollmer^a, Eckhard Riege^b

^a Ministry of the Interior, Building and Digitalisation,

^b Alexandrinenstraße 119055 Schwerin

Within the scope of Germany's federal administration digitization, the state of Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania (MWP) has taken the lead in the field of construction and housing for the entire country. Central to this initiative is the digitization of the building application process, regarded as one of Germany's most politically and economically significant administrative service. The solution is complex, encompassing 42 applications realized within 28 online services. Conceptually holistic, the product is designed as an end-to-end solution and will be rolled out nationwide. A pivotal component of this solution is the collaborative workspace, facilitating real-time efficiency for applicants, processing officials, and further involved public authorities in shaping the administrative process.

To ensure adoption, the services must be adaptable to respective state laws of each federal state without requiring complex programming, achieved through configuration. The successful execution necessitates effective organization of these adaptations through the early establishment of relevant governing bodies. Experience has shown that establishing a task force for the participating federal states was the key in the rollout process, facilitating essential knowledge transfer through on-site best practices. Consequently, MWP's rollout of the Digital Building Application has been highlighted by the federal government and participating states as exemplary in its governance.

Given the project was conceived from an understanding rooted in already existing administrative transformations and prioritizes expertise as well as procedural workflows, the developed collaboration platform serves as a foundation extending beyond the Digital Building Application. From the outset, the solution was designed in an agile approach, open to developments in all directions. Considering ongoing deliberations regarding necessary transformation processes to achieve higher-level political objectives such as accelerating planning, approval, and implementation within the framework of the Deutschland-Pakt, this solution is attributed a key role in the context of other administrative services.

MWP has thus early on developed a Future Roadmap outlining the solution's further development across various domains. Subprojects involving AI-supported data capture and processing of application data commenced as early as September 2023. Specifically, these advancements encompass the implementation of additional communication standards among stakeholders in construction supervisory procedures, the integration of a central citizen mailbox, automated application navigation, and collaborative information and data exchange, for instance, in Building Information Modeling (BIM). BIM implies potentials for accelerating the planning and realization of construction projects and is intended to become a nationwide standard.

At the core of this transformation is the evolution towards a data-driven platform solution. This would enable the comprehensive utilization of construction sector data. Through the vertical and horizontal integration of construction sectors and the availability of respective resulting data, the

solution therefore forms the base for Smart City requirements. Using BIM, future planning, management, and decommissioning with all their facets can be considered. The needs for planning and approval acceleration, resource management, and Smart City infrastructure can be consolidated through this integration. The incorporation of BIM models/platforms will facilitate collaboration among procedure stakeholders based on digital data transmission and data spaces, incorporating interconnected registers. Consequently, they are fundamental prerequisites and the pioneering model for a functionally appropriate digitization, embodying a holistic transformation of administration, economy, and society.

„One-for-All“ – experiences and perspectives of the digital building permit in Germany

Ronny Weinkauff^a, Andreas Fiedler^b

^a University of Applied Sciences Merseburg, Eberhard-Leibnitz-Str. 2, D-06217 Merseburg

^b brain-SCC GmbH, Fritz-Haber-Str. 9, D-06127 Merseburg

The paper-based building application – status quo and challenges

In Germany, around 300,000 building permits are issued every year. Due to the large number of stakeholders involved and the complex requirements, the digital transformation of building permits is a major challenge [1,2]. For example, the building owner, the building owner's representative and the architect work together to prepare the building application. The paper application is then circulated to a large number of parties involved in a circulation process to provide their statement. This creates long processing times.

OZG laboratories and user-centered development

With the German Online Access Act (OZG), 575 administrative services should be digitized for citizens by 2022. The state of Mecklenburg-Western Pomerania has taken over coordination for the topic of “construction and living”. With a strong user focus together with architects and building authority officers, a solution was developed in an OZG laboratory that enables end-to-end digitalization of the building permit process [3].

The process room as collaboration platform

The so-called “process room” is at the heart of the solution. It acts as a central collaboration and communication platform, which serves as both the front end for the applicants and the back end for the public officers and other parties involved. The process room is connected to external basic components such as identity providers for authentication or payment systems. Building applications can be automatically sent to the specialist software in the municipality using a public data standard (XBau). The building owner, its representative and the architect can collaboratively prepare the online building application. Communication between the applicant and the building authority is completely digital. The building authority can now address all parties involved digitally in parallel. Finally, the building permit is sent digitally to the building owner who can pay the fees online [4].

The rollout of digital building permits

The digital building permit went into production in the first municipalities in 2021. Following the “one-for-all” principle, digital building permits are now being used in 10 of Germany's 16 federal states. The online service is quickly adapted to the different state building regulations of the participating states by means of configurations. More than 450 building authorities will use the solution in the future. 28 different online services are offered along the entire value chain. The connection of the specialist software via the XBau standard takes place in close coordination with the software companies. The solution has a high political priority and is intended to simplify and significantly accelerate the approval processes.

Outlook for functional developments

In the near future, applications should also be submitted with additional BIM models [5]. This will allow more data from the building project to be digitally processed. Furthermore, AI should be

used to perform automated preliminary checks and textual summaries of building applications and to support the preparation of the building permit. A digital guide with a chatbot will help the applicant to answer questions. Geodata should increasingly be used and evaluated automatically, for example to simplify neighbourhood participation or to carry out checks of various protected areas [5,6].

References

- [1] F. Noardo, G. Malacarne, S. Mastrolembo Ventura, L. C. Tagliabue, A. L. C. Ciribini, C. Ellul, D. Guler, L. Harrie, L. Senger, A. Waha, and J. Stoter, *Integrating expertises and ambitions for data-driven Digital Building Permits – the EUNET4DBP*, Int. Arch. Photogramm. Remote Sens. Spatial Inf. Sci., XLIV-4/W1-2020, <https://doi.org/10.5194/isprs-archives-XLIV-4-W1-2020-103-2020>, 2020, pp. 103–110.
- [2] F. Noardo, D. Guler, J. Fauth, G. Malacarne, S. Mastrolembo Ventura, M. Azenha, P.-O. Olsson, L. Senger: *Unveiling the actual progress of Digital Building Permit: Getting awareness through a critical state of the art review*, Build. Environ. 213 (2022) 108854. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.buildenv.2022.108854>.
- [3] L. Stasch, A. Steidle, Usability Of Digitized Citizens' Services–A Heuristic Evaluation based on Experiences with Usability Labs within the Implementation of the German Online Access Act, Central and Eastern European eDem and eGov Days, 2020, pp. 103-109.
- [4] A. Fiedler, R. Weinkauff, Digitales Bauantragsverfahren am Beispiel der EfA-Leistung als cokreatives OZG-Projekt zwischen Bundesland und Kommunalverwaltung, Handbuch Digitalisierung der Verwaltung. Bielefeld: transcript Verlag, 1. Aufl., ISBN 978-3-8252-5929-7, 2023.
- [5] R. Weinkauff, A. Fiedler, M. Zehner, S. Scheffler, *OZG-Umsetzung am Beispiel der raumbezogenen, digitalen Baugenehmigung*, GeoForum MV 2022 - Smarte Geoinformation. Tagungsband zum 18. GeoForum MV, Hamburg: tredition Verlag, 2022, pp. 138-144.
- [6] I. Seder, R. Weinkauff, T. Neumann, *Knowledge-based databases and intelligent decision support for environmental management in urban systems*,. Computers, environment and urban systems, 2000, 24. Jg., Nr. 3, pp. 233-250.

Implementing a digital building permit system in Slovenia – current status and aspirations for the future

Jan Brezec^a, Klemen Stropnik^a, Jernej Tekavec^b

^a Ministry of Natural Resources and Spatial Planning,

^b University of Ljubljana, Faculty of Civil and Geodetic Engineering

Slovenian building permit system is currently going through big changes in terms of digitalisation. Two ongoing projects, eConstruction and ePlanning, aim to bring the system to a new level, offering multiple benefits for all involved stakeholders.

Spatial Information System represents a core element of both projects. In short, the overarching goal of a complete Spatial information system is to connect every process that deals with either spatial or building act or permit. Due to the fact that these processes include an enormous number of different users (be it general public – investors, neighbours or specialized users like architects, engineers, various field experts, ...) it is of vital importance that the processes are broken down into a “digestible” and complete subprocesses that encompass only the relevant groups. For example, stakeholders within the processes of building permits have dedicated components that are used to manage communication and documentation exchange between them and investors/experts, when the subprocesses is over, the same component is then used as a segment within the next stages of permit process as a “read-only” section that represents complete documentation for its purpose (stakeholders and opinions). This is the logic that encompasses the whole system, from the adoption of a spatial act (that enacts areas designated for building), to permits for construction and usage, to the eventual decommissions or demolitions. Different components are designed in such a way that they are as reusable as possible (components for data exchange, payments, communication, etc...).

The Spatial Information System aims to bring:

- Implementation of electronic government services in the area of spatial planning (preparation, adoption, enactment of national, regional and local spatial planning documents) and in the processes of obtaining building and usability permits (purely digital documentation, automatization of data gathering, permanent availability of services 24/7),
- single point of entry “one stop shop” for all the relevant parties within processes (investors, technical experts, municipalities, local and government stakeholders and decision makers, inspectorates, public, ...),
- elimination of administrative barriers (unification and standardization of processes),
- reducing costs for investors in the process of obtaining a permit,
- establishment of a common information infrastructure,
- exchange of digital data,
- public access to all adopted spatial and administrative acts.

The implementation of the Spatial Information System will have a beneficial effect for both authorities and citizens.

For authorities:

- Vastly improved transparency and efficiency,
- Alleviating red tape,
- Quality improvements,
- Standardization of processes, services and products,
- Connected systems and underlying data,
- Improved supervision.

For citizens:

- Improved data and information procurement,
- Automatization of processes,
- Tools and guidelines,
- Ease of access,
- Efficient services,
- Faster applications for permits and registry entries,
- Greater transparency.

Future plans for development of Spatial Information System include:

- Inclusion of BIM technology for automatization of individual compliances within processes of building permitting and spatial planning, standardization of documentation,
- Broadening the scope of the information system (additional processes and system interconnectivity, environmental protection, nature conservation, waste management, circular economy, ...)

Developing automated building permitting in Finland

Antero Hirvensalo

Faculty of Management and Business, Tampere University, Kalevantie 4, 33100 Tampere, Finland

The transition to digital building permits requires mutual adaptation of regulation, design guidelines, software and information systems, and permit administration. An effective tool for driving complex change is piloting that involves firms, municipalities, and the government. This paper presents experiences from Finland, where the public-private piloting model has been used for driving industry-wide development.

The model was developed step by step during sequential projects. The projects were partly funded by public bodies like Finnish ministries, but also the participating firms invested their time and resources for the efforts.

The work started in KIRA-Digi projects in 2017, with first attempts to piloting the pre-check of the IFC model before delivery to the permit authority, and the conversion of the IFC model into a part of the CityGML city model.

In 2021, the Finnish association of professional property owners (RAKLI) started a series of pilots, where the developers, architects, permit handlers, software companies and consultants took part into a co-creative model based on trials and learning along real-life building projects and permit applications.

In the RAVA2 project (2021), different use cases for BIM models were identified and the different requirements building control has for them. In the RAVA2 project, it was found important to start with the project's basic data i.e. details of the project stakeholders, area and coordinates of the building, and apartment information, in a machine-readable format.

In the Rava3Pro project (2023), construction projects and their BIM models were used to pilot the export of the project's basic data from the architect to the building control permit processing, and to compare and develop the functionality of different software tools and practices. Parties to the pilots were builders as permit applicants, architects, municipal building control representatives, software suppliers and consultants.

Fig. 1: Stakeholders of the public-private piloting model.

A central factor in the public-private piloting model was the formation of a cross-sector innovation community, that is needed for understanding the complex interrelationships of development on a practical level. Although the legislation will force some changes, an important part is peoples' own enthusiasm and ability to innovate. The Finnish word "talkoohenki" describes the community's ability of working together for a common good.

In Rava3Pro, the piloting was guided by a core group, which included the project manager, officials from the cities, and consultants. The core group mapped out projects where different software tools could be tried, and connected the designers, building controls and software developers, so that they have been able to communicate with each other and develop in collaboration.

The piloting focused on testing the automatic export of permit data to building control. The software firms invited representatives of municipalities to demo meetings, where they showed how the BIM model and data would be transferred to the building controls' customer system. In the demos, files were opened, and observations were made, which were related to, for example, issues in information writing formats. Although the piloting concerned building project data transfer and cooperation with software developers, it also involved contractual issues and information model copyright issues.

It is not possible for the municipalities to turn all their services to new digital processes at once. They must develop new ways in parallel, as the statutory permit operations must remain always running. Therefore, one step at a time is a good progression, as you can gradually introduce new things alongside daily operations. The same principle applies to the software firms' development steps.

Software firms need to understand the data to be transferred to building control, so that they can interpret it correctly in their software. For this, the firms need better cooperation with each other and with architectural designers. To put it bluntly, architects and building inspectors don't know how to code, and software firms don't know how to do the work of architects or building inspectors. Piloting is needed for filling this gap.

The design software firms Archicad and Revit have importers in Finland who took on the development needs found in the piloting. However, global companies are not very willing to consider the needs of building control needs presented in Finland. That's why architectural design offices must come up with their own tailored solutions for meeting the new needs of automated permits.

During the pilots, an idea emerged to ease the work required of architects. The aim was to build an environment where writing the project basic data takes place as easily as possible, and where the designers do not have to learn new rules or coding. The idea was born to develop utility software to enrich the BIM and IFC models. The programs developed in the pilots are Aecmaster and Simplebim.

In terms of legislation, piloting is important to test the degree of digitalization required by the future law. For the preparation of legislation, piloting produces information about what works in practice, so that the law can require things that are possible to implement.

Now that the specs are better known on which basis to act and develop, it would be essential to boost enthusiasm among the builders. It would be necessary to be able to continue introducing digital permits in future building projects, where permitting is done with these new specifications.

Building Permitting process in BRAZIL

Paulo Torreão

TORCH TECNOLOGIAS LTDA

There are more than 5,500 municipalities in Brazil, each with legislative authority over Building Codes and Constructions (BCC) and other urban planning issues. BCCs across the country are highly heterogeneous, featuring distinct content, levels of depth, and varying degrees of requirements. They often overlap with other municipal regulations or Brazilian technical standards. Lack of clarity and legal uncertainty associated with legislation (at the municipal, state, or federal levels), as well as delays or subjectivity in project analyses by public entities, impact the start and completion times of construction projects. This impact can lead to several additional months than necessary, especially when licenses need to be obtained from different competent authorities (Environmental, Traffic, Historical and Cultural Heritage, Fire Prevention and Combat, among other areas).

We have developed a program with the aim of expediting the construction permit issuance, enabling the automation of analysis processes and automatically verifying project compliance with current legislation. It also automates processes and subprocesses related to construction permits, including feasibility and compliance analysis with each municipality's current legislation.

Salvador city has implemented this solution to automate the digital issuance process of Construction Licensing. More than 140 processes were mapped, optimized, and restructured so that over 100 objective urban parameters could be automatically calculated based on the project's location (GeoBIM).

Fig. 1: Legislation/GIS/IFC integration

TECHNOLOGICAL SYSTEM

Through the development of four modules (ENGINE, VIEWER, REGULATOR, WORKFLOW) using programming languages such as C/C++, Assembler, Objective-C, Java, Swift, C#, Dart, Flutter, Python, and Web technologies (HTML5/Javascript/CSS/React), we integrated processes according to local legislation and the project's geolocation.

The urban licensing process flow can be divided into **8 Steps**:

Technical Responsible

- **Step 1** - Exporting IFC File using Building Information Modeling Software.
- **Step 2** - Importing IFC File for Stratification and Automatic Form Filling.
- **Step 3** - IFC File Stratification using Tekto Viewer for Architects.
- **Step 4** - Submitting the Pre-approved Project for Analysis.

Municipality/Regulatory Agency

- **Step 5** - Receipt of the Project for Analysis. The regulatory agency analyst receives the pre-approved process with all forms already filled with project urbanistic information.
- **Step 6** - Distribution of the Project for Collaborative Analysis. The process is distributed to all related departments that will analyze it in coordination.
- **Step 7** - Collaborative and Transparent Analysis.
- **Step 8** - The analyses are completed and the Building Permit is released.

Fig. 2: Building Permitting process flow

Key benefits for this Platform:

- **Efficiency in Analysis and Approval Process:** Automatically verifies project compliance with applicable norms and regulations, significantly reducing the time and resources needed for project analysis and approval.
- **Reduction of Errors and Inconsistencies:** Automatic normative compliance checking minimizes errors and inconsistencies in projects, contributing to building quality and safety.

- **Transparency and Objectivity:** Ensures greater transparency and objectivity in the project analysis and approval process, eliminating possible subjective influences.
- **Adaptability to Regulatory Changes:** Integrates code checking, GIS and a database that can be updated according to changes in norms and regulations, ensuring project compliance with updated legal and technical requirements.
- **Improved Decision-Making:** BIM validation allows for a more precise and detailed analysis of projects, contributing to improved decision-making and risk management associated with urban development.
- **Modernization and Innovation:** BIM implementation with code checking demonstrates a commitment to modernizing and innovating urban management processes, aligning with international trends and industry best practices.
- **Reorganization and Optimization of Technician Activities:** TEKTO Platform implementation allows professionals currently involved in manual project analysis to focus on more relevant and strategic tasks, such as urban planning.

A brief demonstration of the program's functionalities can be viewed at this link: <https://youtu.be/XOGoiGIU-Hs>

LandLogic: Determining Applicable Law Agencies for Digital Building Permitting in Ontario, Canada

Saeid Emamgholian^a, Mark Whitell^a, Arash Shahi^a, Claudia Cozzitorto^a

^a AECO Innovation Lab, 120 East Beaver Creek Rd., Richmond Hill, Ontario, Canada, L4B 4V1

Localities with complex regulatory environments often have multiple agencies with jurisdiction presiding over a given piece of land. There can be many groups outside of a municipal building department that must comment on any given application depending on the size, type, and location of a project. In the Province of Ontario, Canada, the Ontario Building Code outlines approximately forty secondary approvals, which, if required, must be obtained prior to the issuance of a building permit. These secondary approvals are referred to as applicable law, and the organizations that authorize these approvals are referred to as applicable law agencies (ALAs). LandLogic provides an opportunity to simplify the identification of relevant ALAs and subsequent communication.

Applicable law in Ontario takes many forms. Examples of applicable law include obtaining permits from conservation authorities when a property is located in an environmentally sensitive area, obtaining approvals from the Ministry of Transportation when a property is located near a highway corridor, and getting approval from the Ministry of Education for childcare facilities. ALAs, like the applicable law itself, are also quite varied. These ALAs range from other departments within a municipality, provincial ministries, federal departments, crown agencies, conservation authorities, and heritage groups.

The complexity of the applicable law regulation in Ontario and largely manual processes lead to significant delays throughout the building permitting process. Applicants are often not aware of who has jurisdiction over their property; this delays processing as applicants unaware of applicable law requirements are forced to seek additional approvals prior to their permit issuance. Similarly, building permit review staff and administrators are sometimes unsure if certain applicable law approvals are required. In such cases, applications are often sent to ALAs for their review, resulting in further delays.

A second problem arises once an ALA approval is confirmed as a pre-requisite to the building permit. Communication between the municipal building department and the various ALAs involved on a given project is a significant challenge. This work is currently done in siloes that operate independently of each other. This is an inefficient, antiquated method of communication that results in numerous issues such as duplication of work, versioning control, and lack of trackability.

These challenges are solved through the development of a robust GIS platform, called LandLogic, that aggregates necessary GIS datasets that explicitly identify where ALAs have authority and to what degree they have authority. By aggregating thousands of these GIS layers with different coverage in LandLogic, applicants and municipalities across Ontario are informed of the dozens of ALAs that might potentially be involved in their application per the Ontario Building Code. This reduces delays in processing applications and brings transparency to the building permitting process. Integrating LandLogic with municipal electronic permitting software unlocks significant opportunities to automate jurisdictional checks and document circulations based on the size, type, and location of any given application. This further streamlines the permitting process by reducing errors, minimizing duplication, and enabling tracking.

References

- [1] Duong, L., and Amborski, D. (2017). “Modernizing building approvals in Ontario: Catching up with advanced jurisdictions.” Centre for Urban Research and Land Development, Ryerson University, Toronto.
- [2] Evaluation of Tall Building Construction Permitting Process in Toronto. K. Shahi, B. Y. McCabe, A. Shahi, P. De Berardis, R. Lyall, “Evaluation of Tall Building Construction Permitting Process in Toronto,” in 2017 CSCE Annual Conference, Vancouver, British Columbia, Canada. [Online]. Available: https://csce.ca/elf/apps/CONFERENCEVIEWER/conferences/2017/pdfs/CONSPEC/FinalPaper_124.pdf
- [3] Standardizing Ontario’s Permitting Process for E-Permitting Implementation. M. Whittell, Y. Cao, B. Y. McCabe, A. Shahi, M. De Lint, K. Shahi, “Standardizing Ontario’s Permitting Process for E-Permitting Implementation,” in Construction Research Congress 2020, Tempe, Arizona, United States. [Online]. Available: <https://ascelibrary.org/doi/abs/10.1061/9780784482889.143>

Information Model based Urban Planning prototype in Estonia

Christopher-Robin Raitviir^a

^a Head of Digital Construction, Tallinn Strategic Management Office, Tallinn, Estonia, Christopher-robin.raitviir@tallinnlv.ee

Early-Stage Researcher, Tallinn University of Technology, Tallinn, Estonia, Christopher.raitviir@taltech.ee

2D plans are still an integral part of urban spatial planning today and will remain so even when switching to Information Model (IM) based planning. In the norms that have been common so far, the outputs of the plannings have been an explanatory memorandum in text file format and a basic drawing in PDF format. Technologically, for more than 10 years there has been an opportunity to use tools (software) capable of being compatible with both GIS and BIM datasets and transmitting 3D geometry with attribute data attached to them in open data formats as an output. Nevertheless, the possibilities are being ignored and urban planning is still done like it was 20 years ago. As-Is 2D detailed zoning plan drawing [1] is shown on Figure 1 to emphasize where the starting point is.

Fig. 1: Estonian National Broadcast building detailed zoning plan drawing.

Urban planning is the foundation of the building life cycle and starting point of information flow. Before building can be built, it needs a building permit – issued by local municipality. Building permit must be in accordance with detailed zoning plan or design conditions and the latter must be in accordance with comprehensive plans. We are already looking into BIM based building permits and automated rule checking, but at the same time our zoning plans are still in PDF and DOC formats throughout the entire process of planning. Only possible solution for better processes and achieving synchronization of the information flow in the building life cycle is making “the foundation” also digitalized in machine-readable way. Therefore, adapting Urban Planning Information Modeling is a vital process to be achieved in next few years.

This work focuses on observing and testing the software used for IM based planning, with the assumption that the AutoCAD user (so far, the most common software for making plans in Estonia) could move with the simplest effort to create ground models, 3D solids and, most importantly, adding data content and exporting it all to IFC format. Many different software's were used during the work, and the final choice is still left to the discretion of the planner. It is important that urban planners can transmit the geometry they have created with the data content to the National Building Register and its Digital Twin, the Municipal Urban Model (e.g., Esri ArcGIS or Cesium) or other digital twins in open data formats from the selected software. No matter how geometry and data content are generated, it is important to get it into the right coordinates, with a predetermined data content structure (in real-life cases, also with correctly filled data) and standardly, so that it is unambiguous to all those who view it on a 3D public platform. First publicly used information model pilot in planning process, Estonian National Broadcast building detailed zoning plan [2], is shown on figure 2.

Fig. 2: Estonian National Broadcast building detailed zoning plan information model in Tallinn Digital Twin viewer.

IM based urban plans can be used in in very quick and precise analyses, using software that takes IM as input. During the pilot cases direct sunlight, natural daylight, urban heat islands, wind (both 2D and 3D) and noise analyses were performed with the software, that could provide results within few minutes up to one hour, instead of waiting for results of specialists for weeks, even for months. Noise analyse result was compared with the result provided by the acoustical engineering company and it was ~90% accurate. Using this kind of approach enables urban planners to easily change their design based on analyses results in very early stage of their design and analyse multiple options quickly without additional cost of money and time. Result of using AI in finding cracks in street network is shown on Figure 3.

Fig. 3: 3D wind analyses on early-stage IM based urban planning design.

Processing detailed zoning plans is a long process. In Tallinn it takes in average 6-8 years. Detailed zoning plan must be in accordance with comprehensive plans and many checks that are done manually can be easily automated if IM based planning is introduced. Detailed zoning plan is being looked at as bridge between Geographical Information System (GIS) world (comprehensive plans) and Building Information Modeling world (construction design). Using open standards such as Industry Foundation Classes (IFC), CityGML, WMS and WFS, prototype solution is being built to automate simple checks, such as height of buildable area, greenery percentage, distances from cadastral border, compliance of requirements from protection/restriction/flooding areas etc. At the end of the project [3] proof of concept viewer with check results will be introduced in June 2024. After that project developments of actual IM based planning procedural environment software will begin.

References

- [1] National Broadcast Building detailed zoning plan in Tallinn Planning Registry: <https://tpr.tallinn.ee/DetailPlanning/Details/DP045040>. Accessed 23.01.2024
- [2] Information model based planning pilot in participation phase: <https://tallinngis.maps.arcgis.com/apps/webappviewer3d/index.html?id=16a84d6c12d34a41b75be71a06de2f49> Accessed 23.01.2024
- [3] Procurement for analysing and prototyping IM based planning automated checks: <https://eehitus.ee/timeline-post/analysis-and-prototype-of-planning-information-model/>. Accessed 23.01.2024

Transformative Journey: Dubai Municipality's BIM Adoption for Building Permitting and Regulatory Compliance

Ali Ismail^a, Ibrahim Fahdah^a, Maryam Obaid Almheiri^a

^a *Dubai Municipality, Building Regulation and Permit Agency, Dubai - UAE*

The presentation outlines Dubai Municipality's transformative journey in adopting Building Information Modeling (BIM) to enhance building permitting and regulatory compliance processes. Commencing in 2013, the municipality's commitment to improving digital services, enhancing data accuracy, and accelerating decision-making in the construction industry is reflected in its ongoing BIM adoption journey. The Dubai BIM roadmap project is central to this journey, providing a structured framework for successful BIM implementation.

The presentation highlights the significance of BIM technology and the adoption of open BIM standards (IFC, BCF, IDS), explaining their importance for public sector authorities. BIM has been identified as an integral part of the Municipality Digital Strategy for a Happy and Sustainable City. Recognizing this role, BIM services has been integrated with “Build in Dubai” platform, a one-stop shop for all information and services relating to land and real property development and construction in Emirates of Dubai.

Fig. 1: The Build in Dubai platform

In 2017, Dubai took a significant step forward with the establishment of the Committee for Building Permit Procedures Development. And in 2020, within the Municipality, the Dubai's Building Permit Procedures Development Committee launched a project under the supervision of the GIS Centre aimed at designing and implementing the Dubai BIM Roadmap [1] and Dubai BIM standard [2]. Adopting open BIM standards was an integral part in the Dubai BIM Roadmap for the future development of the Municipality digital building services. The Circular 9-1-2

(18/10/2023) made BIM model submissions mandatory from 01/01/2024 for building permits for certain building types.

Fig. 2: BIM Adoption in Dubai Municipality.

The latest BIM mandate by Dubai Municipality issued in the Circular 9-1-2 (18/10/2023) [3] made BIM submissions in IFC format mandatory from 01/01/2024 for building permits for the following building types:

- 1- Buildings exceed a height of 20 floors for architectural designs and 40 floors for structural designs.
- 2- Buildings with an area exceeding 20,000 square meters for architectural designs and 30,000 square meters for structural designs.
- 3- Specialized buildings such as hospitals and universities and the like.
- 4- Government projects, excluding only utility infrastructure projects.

The current implemented BIM services oriented for the building permit use case are primarily aimed at supporting the municipality’s permitting process through automated, BIM-enabled code compliance checking mechanisms. The municipality has developed BIM standard and has implemented a set of tools and workflows to enable the process. Moving from the current 2D CAD submission and the manual review process using closed and non-interoperable formats to a 3D model-based approach based on open standards supporting automating various building permit review tasks, including the automated code compliance checking for the regulation rules of the Dubai building code, is a crucial step in the digital transformation journey to facilitate the next generation of digital buildings and digital twins. BIM adoption and the BIM mandate by the Municipality is a gradual process, which is important in ensuring support for stakeholders throughout this transitional period.

BIM and open BIM standard adoption has the potential to facilitate the automation of many tasks that traditionally carried out manually, particularly when compared to CAD system. Automation can result in a reduction of errors and an enhancement in quality, ultimately leading to the creation of better and more sustainable buildings. In the context of utilising BIM for permitting purpose, it is anticipated that up to 70% of common manual review tasks for building permits can be automated accelerating the permit approval timeline, saving valuable time for both applicants

and regulatory authorities. Also, the BIM models received for building permits would, with time, contribute to the realisation of Dubai’s Digital Twin through enabling various use cases that necessitate building information at the city scale level.

The BIM services are envisioned as a shared and transparent system between permit applicants and permitting engineers that streamlines BIM models submission, validation, and review processes. The services offer a set of tools for permit applicants to submit and self-assess BIM models quality (pre-flight checks) for the purpose of obtaining building permits, and a set of tools for permitting engineers to review and assess the quality of submitted BIM models for the purpose of approving building permits.

Fig. 3: DM BIM Platform & Tools.

The journey towards BIM-enabled building permitting has endured many challenges, and lessons have been learnt during this journey, emphasizing the benefits of incremental implementation,

stakeholder engagement, and comprehensive education and training programs. These lessons underscore the importance of collaboration, technical innovation, and adaptive regulatory frameworks when embracing transformative technologies like BIM in the public sector.

In summary, Dubai Municipality's ongoing journey towards BIM-enabled digital building permitting and automated code compliance checking positions it at the forefront of transforming construction regulatory processes in the UAE (United Arab Emirates). By embracing BIM technology and open BIM standards, the municipality sets a precedent for public sector authorities worldwide, offering valuable insights into the construction industry and urban development [4]. The findings presented in the full presentation highlight the progress made from vision to reality, highlighting the improvements brought about by Dubai Municipality's pioneering approach to BIM adoption.

References

- [1] Dubai BIM Roadmap: <https://api.buildindubai.gov.ae/bim/docs/BIMRoadmap>
- [2] Dubai BIM standard and BIM e-checking service: <https://buildindubai.gov.ae/BIM> .
- [3] Dubai BIM Mandate Circular: <https://www.dm.gov.ae/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/%D8%AA%D8%B9%D9%85%D9%8A%D9%85-BIM-9-1-2.pdf>
- [4] B. Succar, E. Erik: Benchmarking Report: Review of Dubai Municipality BIM adoption report (2023).

[From paper to NOPaper: A 10-year journey of digital transformation for building permits in Vila Nova de Gaia](#)

Carla Pires^a, Ana Baptista^a, Marco Carvalho^a

^a *Gaiurb Urbanismo e Habitação EM*

Abstract

This paper shows the 10-year journey of the digital transformation of building licences in Vila Nova de Gaia, addressed by Gaiurb, the municipal company responsible for analysing and issuing building licences in the city. Its aim is to show the way towards innovation and simplification in verification and permission procedures both for municipal administrations and citizens.

The transformation of our organisational system began in 2012 with the development of a project to simplify the digital presentation of building permits. In 2013, a new digital system called NOPaper was fully implemented and established an electronic procedure for obtaining building licences.

For many years, obtaining a building licence was an extremely time-consuming and complex process that required endless resources, both in human and material terms. Preparing 2D plans on paper with multiple copies meant, among other things, submitting them in person at specific times, manually assembling the files, sending copies by post to external organisations, loading the files onto trolleys up and down the stairs, which caused significant delays and costs.

NOPaper presents a solution that guarantees greater transparency and efficiency by simplifying the interpretation of rules, eliminating unnecessary administrative barriers and providing easily accessible official data. The system interoperates with the municipality's other ERP and GIS technological solutions, creating a single operating environment and ecosystem. Providing an interface between the developer/technician and the municipality, NOPaper prepares and creates all the files for a digital building permit. Two sub-modules 'Constructor' (online, for developers and technicians) and 'Viewer' (for internal viewing by the local administration) are an example of innovation at local and national level, having been recognised with a national award in 2015.

As with many other projects, it was necessary to improve and grow, so 2018 saw the start of BIM integration and the first steps in the transition from 2D to 3D plans with the implementation of BIM-IFC project submission functionalities, in order to pre-test the existing constraints in terms of consultation and IT systems, as well as the current state of BIM implementation in terms of licensing and its integration with geographic information systems.

All this previous experience has given us the opportunity to be part, since 2022, of the international consortium "CHEK: Change toolkit for digital building permit"⁵¹, which will provide a set of innovative tools to support the digitisation of the issuing of building permits and automated compliance checks using the BIM application.

Implementing the adoption of the digital building permit process in municipalities with a BIM application involves different steps and processes that must be validated to guarantee the system's effectiveness and reliability.

⁵¹ 'This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement no. 101058559 CHEK: Change toolkit for digital building permit'.

The aim is to anticipate the impacts on the internal organisational system and to test, in a real scenario with demonstration cases, that it is possible to go further by replacing the "manual" analysis of projects, which still depends on human analysis even when the rules are 100% objective, with automatic verification, achieving time gains and reducing bureaucracy. The ambition is to be considered a true digital company.

Keywords: BIM; Digital Building Permits; Digitization; CHEK Project; Digital Transition

Introduction

Gaiurb, the municipal company established in 2002, has played a crucial role in managing local spatial plans and issuing building permits in Vila Nova de Gaia. As the third most populous municipality in Portugal, Vila Nova de Gaia has experienced significant growth in the real estate sector over the last two decades. In response to the evolving needs of the city, Gaiurb has expanded its scope to include the promotion of key themes such as the circular economy, energy sustainability, and smart city initiatives.

With a workforce of approximately 250 employees organized into small teams, Gaiurb has a dedicated urban planning department of around 125 specialists. The organizational structure is designed to efficiently control and validate urban planning applications, which are inherently complex and involve multiple stakeholders both internally and externally.

Despite being established as a digitalized entity, Gaiurb still relies on software applications from its inception. Recognizing the need to dematerialize urban planning processes, the company embarked on a strategic initiative in 2012 to modernize its systems and workflows. This transformation was not merely seen as a project but as a long-term vision to streamline operations and enhance efficiency.

Urban planning licensing processes are intricate and multifaceted, requiring a comprehensive approach to handle the various challenges. The extensive documentation, multiple stakeholders, lengthy duration, and historical context of each project necessitated a thorough study to develop a digital transformation strategy. Gaiurb's commitment to leveraging digital technologies to streamline licensing procedures is a testament to its dedication to innovation and excellence in urban planning practices.

The project

The NOPaper project was established with the strategic goal of eliminating paper documents from all processes, including urban planning, consultations, internal documents, and applicant delivery.

The project aimed to provide citizens with improved technological solutions and free services, promoting administrative modernization and enhancing digital literacy.

A multidisciplinary team was formed to plan and implement the initiative, focusing on long-term strategy rather than just dematerialization.

Digital transformation was seen as a means to achieve innovation and excellence in urban planning practices, not an end in itself.

The team conducted technical visits to other organizations and collected best practices to map out processes, identify key players, and their needs. It was found that urban planning processes were too complex to simply be treated as document processes, with external and municipal technicians being the primary stakeholders. The main issues identified were complex procedures, excessive paper usage, and time wasted on non-productive tasks.

Due to limited resources, the project prioritized enabling external stakeholders to deliver files digitally first, while only adapting internal systems when necessary to avoid disruption.

The first three products were presented and put into practice in 2013 to facilitate this transition:

- An online tool (digital process builder - Fig 1), in which technicians organise processes in digital format;
- A document management module (Fig 2) for internal use, specially designed and optimised for the documentary complexity of architectural projects;
- A virtual counter for submitting requests via the internet channel, eliminating queues, travelling and time constraints for delivery.

Fig. 1: Gaiurb Digital Process Builder

These 3 products were more widely accepted than expected and within a few years digital delivery had overtaken paper delivery.

Fig. 2: Gaiurb Document Management Builder

In 2019, all private building licence applications were delivered in digital format and the internet channel had overtaken the face-to-face channel (Fig 3). At the very moment when the city saw a rise in property investment and, consequently, an increase in building permit applications.

Fig. 3: Evolution of digital processes in Gaiurb

With the external stakeholders' side resolved, the focus shifted to completing the digitalization process within the organization. Our in-house technicians faced a complex reality, as there were three types of processes to consider: those solely paper-based, those involving both paper and digital documents, and those entirely digital. In all cases, the internal technical information created by Gaiurb remained in paper form, which was the initial challenge of the project.

To address this challenge, a robust document management system was required to replace the traditional paper-based document viewing experience. Additionally, workflows needed to be implemented to facilitate seamless communication between different departments, as physical documents were no longer being transferred between them.

Implementing structured and closed workflows was a daunting task that involved meticulously identifying and mapping out all procedures. This process also allowed for the re-engineering of these procedures to simplify, optimize, and automate various aspects such as:

- Simplifying procedures;
- Facilitating parallel analyses by different teams;
- Decreasing response times by over 20%;
- Providing the ability to monitor all tasks and procedures;

- Automating tasks, including automatic distribution, document creation, sending SMS alerts to customers, and generating records in the ERP system automatically.

The progress made in the project was particularly critical during the challenging years of 2020 and 2021, which were greatly impacted by the constraints of the ongoing pandemic. Thanks to the high level of maturity achieved by the project, the entire team was able to seamlessly transition to remote work within less than 24 hours without any disruption to the processing and analysis of licensing procedures. The digital delivery system was well-established, and the internal digital processing mechanisms were already operational, enabling the organization to maintain uninterrupted operations during this period.

In 2023, a new tool was introduced for citizens and technical planners, available online through Gaiurb's GIS platform. This functionality has been operational within Gaiurb since 2002 but was previously limited to internal use. The tool enables license applications to be spatially compared with the existing urban planning instruments.

By accessing the interactive GIS map on the Plan Consultation portal (<https://sig.gaiurb.pt/geoportal>), citizens can utilize an innovative feature to generate a detailed report on a specific location. This report includes information on the applicable regulations, a description of the regulations, external entities to be consulted, as well as area and percentage metrics corresponding to the zoning regulations. Additionally, users can access information on urbanization plans and allotment permits with free access to approved and publicly available sections (Fig 4).

Fig. 4: GIS and Plan Consultation portal

This new feature has significantly reduced the need for technical consultations as it clearly outlines the conditions and rules pertaining to a licensing site. It serves as a user-friendly and transparent mechanism for accessing relevant information.

Results

The NOPAPER project has yielded significant impacts and results across four core areas:

Resource Savings: The transition to digital processes within the project has resulted in substantial savings in material resources and significantly reduced the need for individuals to physically visit municipal offices. This streamlined approach has enhanced the efficiency and cost-effectiveness of administrative procedures for all parties involved.

Territorial Competitiveness: The success of the project has enhanced transparency, speed, and efficiency in urban licensing processes, positioning the territory as more attractive and

competitive compared to others. This positive differentiation serves as a competitive advantage that is acknowledged by stakeholders within the region.

Decision Intelligence: By dematerializing procedures and incorporating advanced statistical and informational components, the project has improved governance practices. This integration of technology has empowered decision-makers with valuable insights and intelligence to make informed choices.

Transparency and Accessibility: The project has increased the accessibility and transparency of information to citizens through various channels, allowing them to track their administrative procedures from the comfort of their homes. Additionally, urban planning professionals now benefit from a more streamlined relationship with municipal services, leading to cost savings and efficiency improvements in their operations.

The implementation of structured workflows has enabled the systematization of data, facilitating monitoring and follow-up of activities and processes (Fig 5). Teams now have personalized maps showcasing daily activity or performance indicators. All tasks related to analysing an application are quantifiable with specific deadlines. Individual and team indicators provide real-time performance snapshots and overall outcomes (Fig 6), guiding the activities of the entire town planning team.

Fig. 5: Results and outcomes from NOPaper implementation

In terms of measurable outcomes, the NOPAPER project has led to a notable reduction in paper usage, with 99% of applications now submitted digitally. This shift has resulted in over 100,000 applications being submitted, avoiding the use of more than 2 million A4 sheets. The project has also positively impacted water conservation and reduced CO2 emissions, with estimated savings of 4.4 million litres of water and 17 tCO2.

Moreover, the utilization of the internet for 75% of requests has prevented over 42,500 journeys, resulting in an estimated reduction of 60 tCO2, along with financial and time savings. Through the dematerialization of internal procedures, the printing of technical opinions has been eliminated, leading to an annual saving of approximately 150,000 pages. Additionally, the elimination of file transport between buildings has saved time and travel costs, reducing the need for archive furniture investments by around €100,000.

Fig. 6: Monitoring system dashboard

The future

Throughout the years, significant progress and achievements have been made in the evolution of urban planning processes. The journey began in 2002 with the introduction of a new urban planning appraisal model, followed by the integration of GIS as a fundamental tool for urban planning licensing. Subsequent milestones included the implementation of digital processes in 2013 and the acceptance of projects in IFC format based on BIM files in 2018. Looking ahead, the goal is to advance further by automating the integration of IFC-BIM models with geographical information (Fig 7), conducting parametric analyses of models with land uses, extracting data from models automatically, and optimizing response times. These enhancements aim to streamline processes, eliminate manual measurements, and facilitate in-depth analyses of urban impacts.

Fig. 7: Integration of BIM models into the Gaia city model

Building on past experiences, participation in the international consortium "CHEK: Change toolkit for digital building permit" since 2022 presents new opportunities for leveraging innovative tools to digitize building permit issuance and enforce compliance using BIM applications. The implementation of digital building permit processes in municipalities with BIM applications involves multiple validated steps to ensure system effectiveness and reliability.

Recent efforts, driven by the CHEK project, have focused on evaluating optional IFC projects to assess their value, identify limitations, and establish national regulations that effectively address real challenges posed by technological advancements. The adaptation of document management systems, procedural workflows, geographic information, and the integration of control algorithms are noted challenges in this structural transformation.

The overarching aim is to anticipate organizational impacts and test automated verification processes through demonstration cases, seeking to replace manual project analyses with objective automatic checks to save time and streamline bureaucracy. Ultimately, the aspiration is for the entity to be recognized as a leading digital company.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the NOPAPER project undertaken by Gaiurb has resulted in significant advancements in the digital transformation of urban planning processes in Vila Nova de Gaia. The project has not only streamlined operations and enhanced efficiency but has also led to resource savings, improved territorial competitiveness, enhanced decision intelligence, and increased transparency and accessibility for citizens and urban planning professionals. The successful implementation of structured workflows has enabled systematized data and monitoring mechanisms, providing valuable insights for decision-makers and improving overall performance.

Looking towards the future, Gaiurb aims to further automate and optimize urban planning processes by integrating IFC-BIM models with geographical information, conducting parametric analyses, and enhancing compliance using BIM applications. Participation in the CHEK project offers new opportunities to leverage innovative tools for digital building permit issuance and enforcement, with a focus on addressing real challenges posed by technological advancements. By anticipating organizational impacts, testing automated verification processes, and continuously enhancing digital capabilities, Gaiurb is poised to establish itself as a leading digital company in the urban planning sector.

References

Plan Consultation portal <https://sig.gaiurb.pt/geoportal>

Virtual Counter <https://www.gaiurb.pt/p/balcaovirtual>

Digital Process Builder <https://www.gaiurb.pt/p/balcaovirtual>

«GAIA 5.0 Uma melhor experiência no Urbanismo» https://www.gaiurb.pt/pages/936?news_id=687

Secretary of State for Digitalisation and Administrative Modernisation, Mário Campolargo, at the Hannover Messe 2022, 1 July 2022 ["Portugal's ambition is to be considered a true digital nation" - XXIII Government - Portuguese Republic](#)

LICENCIAMENTO 'SEM PAPEL' Marisa Vitorino Figueiredo, Abr 4 2016, Ambiente, Inovação, Notícias <https://smart-cities.pt/ambiente/licenciamento-sem-papel874/>

Concluding remarks: Main uptakes and lessons learnt

Francesca Noardo^a, Judith Fauth^b

^a*Open Geospatial Consortium / Belgium*

^b*Cambridge University / UK*

The International Digital Building Permit Conference 2024 underscored several key insights and future directions for the field of digital building permitting (DBP), highlighting both the progress made and the challenges that lie ahead.

Global Interest and Emerging Research Field

The conference confirmed that there is a growing global interest in DBP, with the importance of the topic widely recognized across various sectors. Although still considered a niche, DBP studies are solidifying as a significant research field, attracting increasing attention from academics and practitioners alike.

Diverse Development Approaches

One notable observation is the variety of approaches to DBP development. Initiatives are being driven both from the bottom-up at the municipal level and top-down by government directives. Additionally, software companies are playing a crucial role in practical implementations as initiators for change. This diverse development landscape reflects the multifaceted nature of DBP and the different contexts in which it operates.

The Role of Technology and Human Involvement

Despite advancements in technology, such as artificial intelligence, the conference highlighted that the human role in DBP processes remains indispensable. This human element is even more pronounced compared to the findings of the EUnet4DBP workshop in 2021, suggesting that the integration of advanced technology must still consider significant human oversight and decision-making as well as how to integrate the human in a digitalized process.

Cross-Sectoral and Interdisciplinary Collaboration

A strong call was made for cross-sectoral and interdisciplinary collaborations to create impactful solutions that address the needs of all stakeholders involved. The complexity and diversity in the field necessitate a collaborative approach to understand and develop comprehensive solutions.

Expanding into New Fields

Future projects should explore new areas such as law and social sciences to address the multifaceted challenges of DBP. Understanding legal implications and the social context of digital building permits can provide deeper insights and more robust solutions.

Education and Training Needs

Education emerged as a critical area needing attention. There is a notable gap in training for professionals and students in the field of DBP. Developing comprehensive educational programs and resources is essential for preparing the next generation of experts.

Addressing Terminology Challenges

The multidisciplinary nature of DBP has led to terminology challenges. Efforts by EUnet4DBP to develop a common glossary should be further pursued to ensure clear and effective communication across disciplines.

Engaging Stakeholders via Social Media

To enhance stakeholder engagement, the conference suggested that EUnet4DBP should become more active on social media platforms. This increased presence can help bring together a wider range of stakeholders, fostering greater collaboration and knowledge sharing.

Learning from New Case Studies

New case studies on infrastructure, despite their differing processes, offer valuable lessons that can be applied to DBP. That might be increased in future even more.

Implementation of Solutions, Adoption of Challenges and Fragmentation

Many technical solutions are available, but there is a pressing need to implement and validate these solutions in real-world scenarios. Although, adoption of DBP is not without its challenges. Differences in historical context, legal frameworks, and infrastructure must be considered. Additionally, digitalization has not eliminated the fragmentation of solutions and applications, suggesting that future studies should focus on creating a cohesive DBP ecosystem.

Emphasizing the Beauty and quality of the Built Environment

Beyond the technical aspects, “*Why*” to digitalise building permits? was one of the most asked and answered questions in the conference presentations, highlighting the benefits in terms of higher quality and beauty of the built environment. The conference definitely emphasized the importance of the built environment's beauty and quality. As acknowledged by the New European Bauhaus, the aesthetic and quality aspects of buildings should not be overlooked in the digitalization process.

Common Challenges and Legal Aspects

Common challenges include regulatory interpretation, regulations formalisation and maintenance through the time, organizational change, and technology use. Solutions often converged on ensuring interoperability, simplifying regulations, providing training, and integrating BIM and GIS. Technology appears to be now mature enough to provide working solutions, although still struggling towards automation and full interoperability, which in any case passes through the use of Open standards, mostly buildingSMART IFC for the building model and OGC CityGML for the city model.

Legal aspects remain an open issue, crucial for the final uptake of digital building permits.

Community Collaboration and Knowledge Sharing

Finally, the conference emphasized the importance of better connecting and learning from each other to avoid reinventing the wheel. The open-minded, enthusiastic, and encouraged community is poised to drive DBP to new levels, benefiting from shared knowledge and collaboration.

Huge strides have been made since the first EUnet4DBP workshop in 2021 (http://www.eurosd.net/sites/default/files/uploaded_files/eurosd_eunet4dbp.pdf), with some

cities now successfully implementing operational digital building permits. We eagerly anticipate witnessing further progress and innovations at the next Digital Building Permit Conference.

Acknowledgements

The event was supported, organised, managed and advertised by the several organisations mentioned in the introduction: OGC, EUnet4DBP, BDTA, EuroSDR, buildingSMART, the EU-BIM task group, ECTP-CEU, CEBC and ISPRS. They supported with in-kind contributions to the organisation and management of the event, and promoted the event through their networks. Rossella Florio has helped with the final editing of proceedings and recording.

The event was sponsored by CYPE, BDTA, FutureInsight, CloudPermit and AEC3.

The work of some members of the Organisational or Scientific Committees was funded by the HORIZON projects: CHEK receiving funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe programme under Grant Agreement No.101058559; ACCORD receiving funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 101056973; DigiChecks receiving funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101058541.

The work of J. Fauth has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement no. No 101034337.

Sponsors

